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Title

Indoor residual spraying for preventing malaria in settings with low or no net coverage: a systematic review

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**Indoor residual spraying for preventing malaria in settings with low or no net coverage:
a systematic review**

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Abstract

Background

Malaria presents a significant public health burden globally. Substantial progress has been made with vector control initiatives such as residual insecticide surface treatment and insecticide treated nets. The objective of this systematic review was to examine the effectiveness of indoor residual spraying (IRS) for preventing malaria in areas with no or low coverage of nets.

Methods

We searched several databases, conference proceedings and organisations for published and unpublished studies investigating the effectiveness of residual insecticide surface treatment for malaria. Studies with moderate or high coverage of nets were excluded. Risk of bias was assessed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias assessment tool for cluster-randomised controlled trials and Risk of Bias In Non-randomised Studies of Intervention (ROBINS-I) tool. The reported outcomes were malaria incidence, malaria prevalence, anaemia prevalence, and all-cause mortality. Pairwise meta-analysis was conducted for the four outcomes and results have been presented for each age group. Results from randomised controlled trials and non-randomised studies were analysed separately. GRADE processes were followed to establish the certainty of the evidence and evidence profiles created.

Results

There was a total of 16 reports included in the systematic review, which represented nine unique studies. Of these, five were cluster-randomised controlled trials, one was a quasi-experimental study, and three were controlled before and after studies.

In clusters that receive IRS, the evidence is very uncertain about the effect of IRS on malaria incidence and malaria prevalence in all ages and children, as well as all-cause mortality

in all ages and in children under five years. In clusters that receive IRS, the evidence suggests that IRS does not reduce malaria prevalence in children under six years. Study settings and follow-up time varied widely between studies and therefore these results may depend on study setting.

Interpretation

There is very low certainty in the evidence for the impact of IRS on malaria outcomes in settings where there is no or very low net coverage. The certainty of this evidence was downgraded due to risk of bias, imprecision and/or inconsistency. Poor reporting of primary evidence was a major obstacle to understanding differences between important subgroups.

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Table 1. IRS compared to no IRS for malaria prevention: GRADE Evidence Profiles

Certainty assessment							Summary of findings				
Participants (studies) Follow-up	Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication bias	Overall certainty of evidence	Study event rates (%)		Relative effect (95% CI)	Anticipated absolute effects	
							With no IRS	With IRS		Risk with no IRS	Risk difference with IRS

Malaria, incidence rate (all ages) (RCT data) (follow-up: range 3 months to 6 months)

4 RCTs	serious ^a	serious ^b	serious ^c	serious ^d	none	⊕○○○ Very low ^{e,f,g,h,i,j,k}	57/1000 (5.7%)	37.58/1000 (3.8%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.90 (0.63 to 1.29)	Study population	
										57 per 1,000	6 fewer per 1,000 (from 21 fewer to 17 more) ^l
										Average global burden (WMR Report 2021)	
										59 per 1,000	6 fewer per 1,000 (from 22 fewer to 17 more) ^m
Average African burden (WMR Report 2021)											

Certainty assessment						Summary of findings					
										233 per 1,000	23 fewer per 1,000 (from 86 fewer to 242 more) ⁿ

Malaria, incidence rate (children under 5 years) (RCT data)

1 RCT ^o	serious ^a	not serious	serious ^c	serious ^p	none	⊕○○○ Very low	138.81/1000 (13.9%) ^o	138.46/1000 (13.8%) ^o	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.90 (0.70 to 1.16)	Study population	
										139 per 1,000 ^o	14 fewer per 1,000 (from 42 fewer to 22 more) ⁱ
										Average global burden (WMR Report 2021)	
										59 per 1,000	6 fewer per 1,000 (from 18 fewer to 9 more) ^m
										Average African burden (WMR Report 2021)	
233 per 1,000	23 fewer per 1,000 (from 70 fewer to 37 more) ⁿ										

Certainty assessment						Summary of findings				
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Malaria, point prevalence (all ages) (nRCT and CBA data) (follow-up: range 1 months to 12 months)

7179 (4 observational studies)	extremely serious ^q	not serious ^r	not serious	not serious ^s	none	⊕○○○ Very low	<p>Gunasekaran tested participants for malaria infection approximately four months post IRS. The risk of malaria infection in the sprayed group was 0.31 (95%CI 0.27 to 0.35) relative to the unsprayed group. Guyatt tested participants for malaria infection at approximately two months after IRS. The risk of malaria infection in the sprayed group relative to the unsprayed group was 0.25 (95%CI 0.15 to 0.42). Mashauri examined participants for malaria infection six months post IRS. The risk of malaria infection was 0.56 (95%CI 0.41 to 0.76) for those in the sprayed group compared with those in the unsprayed group. Ramachandra tested for malaria infection approximately one month post IRS. The risk of malaria infection in the sprayed group was 0.70 (95%CI 0.65 to 0.75) compared with the unsprayed group.</p>				
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Malaria, point prevalence (children under 6) (RCT data) (follow-up: mean 3 months)

423 (1 RCT)	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	serious ^t	none	⊕⊕○○ Low	69.93/259 (27.0%)	41.984/164 (25.6%)	RR 0.95 (0.68 to 1.32)	270 per 1,000	14 fewer per 1,000 (from 86 fewer to 86 more)
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Malaria, point prevalence (children under 5) (nRCT and CBA data) (follow-up: range 6 months to 12 months)

497 (2 observational studies)	extremely serious ^u	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕○○○ Very low	<p>Guyatt tested participants for malaria infection at approximately two months after IRS. The risk of malaria infection in the sprayed group relative to the unsprayed group was 0.28 (95%CI 0.10 to 0.77). Mashauri examined participants for malaria infection six months post IRS. The risk of malaria infection was 0.19 (95%CI 0.07 to 0.48) for those in the sprayed group compared with those in the unsprayed group.</p>				
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Certainty assessment						Summary of findings	
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Malaria, point prevalence (children 5-15 years) (RCT data) (follow-up: range 3 months to 6 months)

2752 (2 RCTs)	serious ^a	serious ^v	not serious	serious ^w	none	⊕○○○ Very low	Curtis examined children over 6 years of age at approximately 3 months post IRS (first quarter of 1996, spraying in December 1995). The risk of malaria infection in the sprayed cohort relative to the unsprayed cohort was 1.10 (95%CI 0.94 to 1.29). Rowland examined children between 5 and 15 years of age 3 months post IRS. The risk of malaria infection in the sprayed cohort relative to the unsprayed cohort was 0.15 (95%CI 0.06 to 0.37).
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Malaria, point prevalence (children aged 5-15 years) (nRCT and CBA data) (follow-up: range 6 months to 12 months)

907 (2 observational studies)	extremely serious ^u	not serious	not serious	serious ^x	none	⊕○○○ Very low	Guyatt tested participants for malaria infection at approximately two months after IRS. The risk of malaria infection in the sprayed group relative to the unsprayed group was 0.32 (95%CI 0.16 to 0.65). Mashauri examined participants for malaria infection six months post IRS. The risk of malaria infection was 0.60 (95%CI 0.42 to 0.87) for those in the sprayed group compared with those in the unsprayed group.
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Malaria, point prevalence (aged 15+ years) (nRCT and CBA data) (follow-up: range 6 months to 12 months)

916 (2 observational studies)	extremely serious ^u	not serious	not serious	serious ^y	none	⊕○○○ Very low	Guyatt tested participants for malaria infection at approximately two months after IRS. The risk of malaria infection in the sprayed group relative to the unsprayed group was 0.17 (95%CI 0.07 to 0.43). Mashauri examined participants for malaria infection six months post IRS. The risk of malaria infection was 1.26 (95%CI 0.57 to 2.76) for those in the sprayed group compared with those in the unsprayed group.
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Deaths, incidence rate (all ages) (RCT data) (follow-up: mean 3 months)

1 RCT ^o	serious ^a	not serious	serious ^c	serious ^z	none					Study population
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Certainty assessment						Summary of findings					
										25 per 100,000 ^o	15 fewer per 100,000 (from 20 fewer to 5 fewer) ^l
										Average global burden (WMR Report 2021)	
										15 per 100,000 ^o	9 fewer per 100,000 (from 12 fewer to 3 fewer) ^m
										Average African burden (WMR Report 2021)	
										62 per 100,000 ^o	37 fewer per 100,000 (from 50 fewer to 12 fewer) ⁿ

Death, incidence rate (children under 5 years) (RCT data) (follow-up: mean 3 months)

1 RCT	serious ^a	not serious	serious ^c	serious ^{aa}	none	⊕○○○ Very low	There were no deaths in children under 5 years in the treated camps within 3 months following IRS. Confidence intervals could not be estimated.
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CI: confidence interval; **RR:** risk ratio

Explanations

- a. Randomisation method unclear and missing outcome data in most studies.
- b. I2 of 59% is moderate. Minimal overlap of confidence intervals between the studies and point estimates vary.
- c. Charlwood data is from refugee camps.
- d. Low event rate and wide CIs around the absolute effect. The optimal information size was 1967.
- e. Subgroup analysis was conducted for insecticide class. For each subgroup the IRR was: organothiophosphates = 1.10 [0.80, 1.51]; pyrethroids = 0.27 (0.02, 3.38); carbamates = 1.03 (0.74, 1.43). Test for differences between subgroups was $p=0.54$ (no differences). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined low credibility: Likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup but uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- f. Subgroup analysis was conducted for background nets. For each subgroup the IRR was: no nets = 0.78 (0.42, 1.45); nets = 1.03 (0.74, 1.43). Test for differences between subgroups was $p=0.44$ (no differences). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined low credibility: Likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup but uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- g. No subgroup analyses for household coverage as all assumed to be full and missing data.
- h. Subgroup analysis was conducted for resistance to IRS compound and contained only one group, with missing data for some studies. For the susceptible groups of studies the IRR was 0.31 (0.02, 5.84). No test for subgroup differences. ICEMAN credibility assessment determined low credibility: Likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup but uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- i. Subgroup analysis was conducted for study setting. For each subgroup the IRR was: rural = 0.99 (0.64, 1.53); mix of rural and urban = 0.71 (0.47, 1.07). Test for differences between subgroups was $p=0.27$ (no differences). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined low credibility: Likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup but uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- j. Subgroup analysis was conducted for transmission level. For each subgroup the IRR was: very low = 0.31 (0.02, 5.84); low = 1.10 (0.80, 1.51); high = 0.71 (0.47, 1.07). Test for differences between subgroups was $p=0.19$ (no differences). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined low credibility: Likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup but uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- k. No subgroup analysis conducted for target sites or mode of action of the intervention as all assumed to be indoor and no other data reported.
- l. Data from the Charlwood study has been digitised using the GetData Graph Digitiser from Figure 2.
- m. Data has been sourced from the World malaria report 2021. Geneva: World Health Organisation; 2021. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO. Figure 3.2
- n. Data has been sourced from the World malaria report 2021. Geneva: World Health Organisation; 2021. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO. Figure 3.3
- o. Data from the Charlwood study has been digitised using the GetData Graph Digitiser from Figure 2. This data was calculated as an average over three months as no summary numbers were provided in the paper. The numbers calculated do not reflect the IRR.
- p. Event rates are low and wide CI. The optimal information size was 1873021 and not met for this study.

- q. Confounding not addressed, deviations from intended interventions, bias due to missing data. As confounding is not addressed AND no randomisation, downgraded 3 levels to extremely serious.
- r. In an exploratory meta-analysis, there was a high I2 and confidence intervals did not overlap - however, all studies favour the intervention meaningfully.
- s. Although no pooled estimate is presented, the optimal information size was 219 and was satisfied for this meta-analysis. In an exploratory meta-analysis there was no concerns regarding imprecision.
- t. The optimal information size was 7701 and was not met for this study. The CI around the absolute effect is wide.
- u. Confounding not addressed. As confounding is not addressed AND no randomisation, downgraded 3 levels to extremely serious.
- v. The two effect estimates have drastically different results on each side of the line of no effect. In an exploratory meta-analysis, the I2 of 94% was considerable.
- w. Event rates are low and wide CIs. Curtis ranges from 0.94-1.29.
- x. Low event rates and wide CIs.
- y. Low event rates and very wide CIs.
- z. Low event rates. The optimal information size for this study was 9955466 and was not met.
- aa. Low event rates. CI could not be calculated.

Introduction

Malaria is a parasitic, mosquito-borne, infectious disease that is highly transmissible, with a significant amount of the world's population at risk.^{1,2} In 2020, there were an estimated 241 million cases of malaria worldwide with 627,000 deaths attributed to the disease.² The World Health Organisation (WHO) designated African region bears the largest burden in terms of malaria morbidity and mortality, with 228 million cases (approximately 95% of the global total) reported in 2020.² Children under five years of age account for 77% of the total deaths.² While malaria remains a significant global public health burden, substantial progress has been made since 2000 when global malaria deaths were estimated at 736,000. Global malaria incidence is estimated to have fallen from 81 cases per 1000 population at risk in 2000 to 59 per 1000 in 2020.² Much of the decline in malaria burden was due to the scale up of malaria prevention and control interventions, particularly vector control strategies such as insecticide treated nets (ITNs) and indoor residual spraying (IRS), which are estimated to have contributed to 68% and 11%, respectively, of the reduction in malaria burden between 2000 and 2015.³

One of the primary measures of prevention and control of malaria includes residual insecticide surface treatment.⁴ This broad intervention involves the spraying (often described as indoor or outdoor residual spraying), painting or application to the surface of walls and ceilings in houses, inside and (sometimes) outside of the home with insecticide to kill mosquitoes, reducing their longevity and population size. This practice, when applied indoors on walls and surfaces, has been used as an effective intervention in the control of malaria, by targeting *Anopheles* mosquitoes at rest, contributing to the significant reduction of malaria cases in multiple at-risk countries.^{3,5-7} A previous Cochrane review studying IRS determined that while the primary evidence was limited in scope to determine efficacy, IRS may be associated with overall health benefits in communities using nets.⁸

While the global burden of malaria has declined since 2000, much of this was achieved between 2000 and 2015. Since 2015, malaria case incidence has declined by less than 2% with 31 countries reporting increased incidence of malaria.¹ There is an urgent need to investigate the efficacy of potential measures for the control of malaria. Previous research on this topic⁸ was limited to randomised controlled trials (RCTs) and concluded that insufficient evidence existed at the time to determine efficacy. New insecticides and interventions now exist that may have a different impact on malaria. Additionally, questions remain regarding the impact of spraying in the absence of nets. Therefore, the current review aims to expand upon this earlier review.

Review question

In areas with ongoing malaria transmission, what are the relative benefits and harms of IRS where all surfaces of interior walls are treated compared with no IRS or other treatments/strategies to prevent malaria in adults and children in areas with no or very low net coverage?

Methods

Eligibility Criteria

Participants

Studies of adults and children who resided in malaria endemic regions for more than one month (excluding travellers) were eligible for this review. Studies that combined residents and travellers were included only if more than 85% of participants were residents for more than one month.

Interventions and comparators

We planned to include all indoor residual surface treatments, with surfaces being sprayed, painted or treated with insecticide, or application of insecticide-treated surface coverings. However, only IRS studies were identified. Non-surface treatments (such as insecticide space sprays) were excluded. Interventions to limit mosquito movement or entry into a dwelling (such as curtains or nets) were excluded. There were no limitations on the type of insecticide that was studied. Studies where additional malaria interventions were considered standard of care were included as long as interventions were balanced between intervention and control arms. Comparators included no residual insecticide surface treatment as a comparator to full residual insecticide surface treatment.

Outcomes

The reported outcomes were malaria incidence, malaria prevalence, anaemia prevalence, and all-cause mortality. Other outcomes considered for inclusion are detailed in the supplementary material and protocol.

Study designs

Randomised studies including cluster randomised controlled trials, crossover trials and stepped wedge designs were included. Quasi-experimental designs and controlled before and after studies were included when there was a comparison/control group present. Studies were excluded if they had only one cluster included in either of the arms. There were no exclusions on buffer period or length of intervention or timing of measurement of outcomes. Entomological studies such as experimental hut, or modelling studies were excluded.

Search strategy

A full search strategy was developed for Ovid MEDLINE using the search refinery tool⁹ with the input of a health librarian. The search strategy was adapted for each included database. The search strategy was peer reviewed based on the Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies (PRESS) 2015 guidelines statement.¹⁰ The full search strategies and results are available in the supplementary materials.

The databases searched included Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), published in The Cochrane Library and included the Cochrane Infectious Diseases Group Specialised Register; MEDLINE (Ovid); EMBASE (Elsevier); CINAHL with full text (EBSCO), US National Institute of Health Ongoing Trials Register (www.ClinicalTrials.gov/); ISRCTN registry (www.isrctn.com/); The WHO's International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO ICTRP) (www.who.int/ictip), the WHO Global Index Medicus (<https://www.globalindexmedicus.net/>), MSF publications and reports (www.msf.org), and Demographics and Health Surveys (DHS) indicator surveys and reports (dhsprogram.com).

Additionally, organisations searched included the Malaria Elimination Initiative at the University of California at San Francisco, the Malaria Eradication Research Agenda Consortium, the Malaria Eradication Scientific Alliance, and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation. Relevant conference proceedings were also reviewed for potential studies. This involved searching the most recent conferences for the Multilateral Initiative on Malaria Pan-African Malaria Conference, American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, and the Malaria in Melbourne event. The reference list of all included studies were screened for additional studies.

Study selection and screening

All identified citations were collated and uploaded into EndNote™ and duplicates removed. The studies were then imported into Covidence for screening, with titles and abstracts screened by three independent reviewers (JCS, THB, ZM) for assessment against the inclusion criteria. Potentially relevant studies were retrieved in full. The full texts of selected citations were assessed in detail against the inclusion criteria by three reviewers (JCS, THB, ZM) in Covidence. Disagreements that arose between reviewers at each stage of the selection process were resolved through discussion. The results of the search and the study inclusion process have been reported in a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA 2020) flow diagram.¹¹

Data extraction

Data was extracted from included studies by two independent reviewers (JCS and THB) using a data extraction tool developed by the reviewers (supplementary material) and piloted on two studies. The data extracted included specific details about the study design, setting, participants, intervention, outcomes, costs, and additional data relevant to the review question. Disagreements that arose between reviewers were resolved through discussion. Authors of primary studies were contacted to request missing or additional data as needed.

Risk of bias assessment

Two review authors (JCS, THB) independently assessed the risk of bias for each study (at the result level) using the Cochrane Risk of Bias 2 tool for cluster randomised controlled trials¹² and the ROBINS-I for non-randomised studies.¹³ Disagreements between reviewers were resolved through discussion or with an additional reviewer.

Data synthesis and meta-analysis

All data were pooled in a meta-analysis, where possible, using Review Manager 5 (RevMan5).¹⁴ A random effects model was used when there were more than two studies and a fixed effect model when there were only two studies. Results from randomised controlled trials and non-randomised studies were analysed separately.

For dichotomous data, effect sizes were calculated as relative risks and presented with 95% confidence intervals (CIs). When there were no events in a treatment arm, RevMan added a fixed value of 0.5 to the empty cell. When incidence rates were reported, incidence rate ratios were calculated. All calculations and data imputations performed as part of the review process have been documented (supplementary material). Decisions regarding which data to select into the analysis was based on guidance from content experts and can be found in the supplementary material.

Heterogeneity

Heterogeneity was assessed by visual inspection of the forest plot and statistically by Cochran's Q (P value 0.05) and I².

Subgroup and sensitivity analyses

Effect modifiers were identified a priori and assessed using subgroup analyses. Sensitivity analyses were conducted using inflated standard errors for trials where cluster designs were not considered and for high or low risk of bias. Sensitivity and subgroup analyses are detailed in the supplementary materials.

GRADE

The Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) approach¹⁵ for grading the certainty of evidence was followed and GRADE Evidence Profiles were created using GRADEpro GDT for each comparison.

Results

Results of screening

Following the removal of duplicate citations, 2692 citations were identified in the initial database and trial registry search. At title and abstract screen 1763 citations were excluded. From this, 929 citations remained for full-text review, 913 of which were excluded based on design, as either editorials, letters, reviews, descriptive (no control group), qualitative or entomological studies with no epidemiological data; no mention of indoor surface spray; topical or spatial spray; and non-malaria outcomes (e.g., Tuberculosis, Dengue etc.). Finally, 16 reports of nine studies remained following the database and registry search.

An indeterminate number of records were additionally screened from websites, organisations, and citation searching as part of a supplementary search process. Of these, 30 were retrieved and assessed for eligibility at full-text screen. Thirty studies were excluded due to incorrect study design, no prevalence data, no surface spray, no control group or were entomological studies.

A total of 16 reports^{16,17 18-31} were included for consideration in the systematic review, which represented nine unique studies^{16,17 18-24} (Figure 1). Reasons for exclusion of studies are detailed in the PRISMA (Figure 1) and supplementary materials.

[Insert Figure 1: PRISMA here]

Study designs and time periods

Of the nine included studies, five were cluster-randomised controlled trials,²⁰⁻²⁴ one was a quasi-experimental study,¹⁷ and three were controlled before and after studies.^{16,18,19} Studies were conducted between 1949¹⁹ and 2016. Study duration ranged from four months²⁰ to two and a half years.²⁴

Population and setting

The sample size ranged from approximately 200 households¹⁷ to 3074 households,²⁴ with six studies not reporting the number of included households.^{16,18-20,23,29} There was a combined sample size of more than approximately 222,541 including two studies that only provided number of participants measured at outcome assessment.^{18,21} One study conducted in Tanzania²³ did not report sample size; however, estimated between 971 and 2445 participants were included from a population census. The countries under study in this review included India,^{16,22} Pakistan,²¹ Afghanistan,¹⁹ Kenya,¹⁷ Tanzania,^{18,23} Ethiopia,²⁴ and Sudan.²⁰ Additional details regarding population, setting, vector characteristics, interventions and comparisons, and outcomes are included in the supplementary materials.

[Insert table 2: characteristics of included studies here]

Risk of bias of included studies

Risk of bias judgments for each included study have been summarised in Figures 2 and 3 with support for every judgment provided in the supplementary material.

[Insert Figure 2: Risk of bias RCTs here]

[Insert Figure 3: Risk of bias non-randomised studies]

Data synthesis and meta-analysis

Incidence of malaria infection, all ages

Randomised controlled trials

When study estimates were pooled, there was no significant reduction in malaria incidence for all ages in clusters that received IRS compared with clusters that received no IRS (IRR = 0.90, 95% CI 0.63 - 1.29, Figure 4). On visual inspection of the forest plot, moderate between-study heterogeneity was found ($\chi^2 = 7.37$, $p = .06$, $I^2 = 59\%$).

[Insert Figure 4]

Incidence of malaria infection, children under 5

Randomised controlled trials

Charlwood et al.²⁰ reported no significant reduction in malaria incidence (IRR = 0.90, 95% CI: 0.70 - 1.16, Figure 5) in clusters that received IRS compared with no IRS in children aged under five years.

[Insert Figure 5]

Prevalence of malaria, all ages

Non-randomised studies of interventions

The reduction in risk ranged from 30% to 69% for malaria in all ages in the IRS cluster compared with the clusters that did not receive IRS (Figure 6).

[Insert Figure 6]

Prevalence of malaria infection, children under 6 years

Randomised controlled trials

Curtis et al.²³ reported no significant difference in risk of malaria infection in children under six years of age in clusters that received IRS compared with no IRS clusters (RR = 0.95, 95% CI: 0.68 – 1.32, Figure 7).

[Insert Figure 7]

Prevalence of malaria, children under 5

Non-randomised studies of interventions

The reduction in risk of malaria ranged from 72% to 81% across two studies for IRS clusters compared with clusters that did not receive IRS for children under five years of age.

[Insert Figure 8]

Prevalence of malaria infection, children aged 5 to 15 years

Randomised controlled trials

Malaria infection for children aged over six years ranged between an 85% reduction in risk to a 10% increase in risk in the clusters receiving IRS compared with those that did not receive IRS.

[Insert Figure 9]

Prevalence of malaria, children aged 5 to 15 years

Non-randomised studies of interventions

Across two studies there was a significant reduction in risk of malaria ranging 35% to 60% in IRS clusters compared with clusters that did not receive IRS for children aged five to 15 years.

[Insert Figure 10]

Prevalence of malaria, aged above 15 years

Non-randomised studies of interventions

There was an 83% reduction to 26% increase in risk for malaria in the IRS clusters compared with clusters that received no IRS.

[Insert Figure 11]

Prevalence of anaemia, all ages

Non-randomised studies of interventions

Mashauri et al.¹⁸ found a reduction in risk of anaemia of 54% in the IRS clusters compared with no IRS clusters (RR = 0.46, 95% CI: 0.34 - 0.62, Figure 12) in all ages.

[Insert Figure 12]

Prevalence of anaemia, children under 6 years

Randomised controlled trials

There was no significant difference in risk of malaria in children aged under 6 years in the clusters that received IRS compared with the clusters that did not (RR = 0.97, 95% CI: 0.83 – 1.13, Figure 13).

[Insert Figure 13]

Prevalence of anaemia, children aged under 5

Non-randomised studies of interventions

There was a 53% reduction in risk of anaemia in children under five years of age in the IRS clusters compared with no IRS clusters (RR = 0.47, 95% CI: 0.31 - 0.69, Figure 14).¹⁸

[Insert Figure 14]

Prevalence of anaemia, children aged 5 to 15 years

Non-randomised studies of interventions

In the IRS clusters compared with the no IRS clusters, there was a 48% reduction in risk of anaemia (RR = 0.52, 95% CI: 0.32 - 0.87; Figure 15) in children aged five to 15 years.¹⁸

[Insert Figure 15]

Prevalence of anaemia, aged 15 and over

Non-randomised studies of interventions

In adults aged over 15 years, there was a reduction in risk of anaemia of 55% (RR = 0.45, 95% CI: 0.22 - 0.92) in the clusters that received IRS compared with those that did not (Figure 16).¹⁸

[Insert Figure 16]

Incidence of all-cause mortality, all ages

Randomised controlled trials

Charlwood et al.²⁰ found no significant difference in incidence between the IRS clusters and those that did not receive IRS in all-cause deaths (IRR = 0.4, 95% CI: 0.2 – 0.8, Figure 17).

[Insert Figure 17]

Incidence of all-cause mortality, children under 5 years

Randomised controlled trials

During the baseline period, Charlwood et al.²⁰ reported 35 child deaths in the camps assigned to be sprayed, and 41 in the control camps. In the three-month post-intervention period, there were no deaths among children in the sprayed camps, compared with six deaths in control camps. The incident rate ratio was 0.0 for all-cause mortality in children under five years of age. Confidence intervals could not be estimated.

Adverse effects

Gunasekaran et al.¹⁶ used Dichlorodiphenyl trichlorethane (DDT) IRS and reported wall decolourisation, bad smell, an increase in bed bug nuisance, and contamination of food grains stored above the false ceiling as adversely impacting participants and were reasons for refusal of the interventions. In addition, negative feelings towards spray personnel due to social caste were reported. Rowland et al.²¹ used 'Fendona' wettable Powder and reported transitory skin irritation and headache were common symptoms in spray personnel and participants shortly after spraying. However, this effect attenuated after a few hours. Similar adverse events were reported for spray personnel in another study by Curtis et al.²³ where, despite wearing goggles and face masks, spray personnel suffered from paraesthesia in their facial skin following use of Microencapsulated lambda-cyhalothrin IRS.

Costs

All costs were reported at the time of the study and therefore, when adjusted for inflation, will likely be much higher than reported. Curtis et al.,²³ over a two-year period between years 1995 and 1996, estimated the cost-effectiveness of IRS in north-east Tanzania. For one year of house spraying for 1000 participants in 258 houses, the annual cost in year one was \$2,304 (USD) and in year two was \$4608. The itemised costs for year one were \$2,064 for insecticide (Icon 10%), labour for 50 person-days in Tanzania \$200, and transport of

personnel \$40. The itemised costs for year two were \$4,128 (Icon 10%), labour for 50 person-days in Tanzania \$400, and transport of personnel \$80. These estimates do not include the costs of the spray pumps and the protective clothing needed by spray teams, since these items are durable.

Misra et al.²⁹ measured the cost of IRS over a two-year study period between years 1997 and 1998 in India. The total cost for IRS over the intervention period was ₹2,331,191 (IRN). The total capital costs were ₹462,113, which made up 20% of all costs. The itemised capital costs were equipment ₹189,582 (8% of total costs), space rental (including project office) ₹66,409 (3% of total costs), vehicles ₹183,372 (8% of total costs), other (development of health education material) ₹22,750 (1% of total costs). The total recurrent costs over the intervention period were ₹1,869,078, which made up 80% of the total costs. The itemised recurrent costs were personnel ₹780,666 (33% of total costs), insecticide (deltamethrin) ₹864,901 (37% of total costs), project office operating expenses ₹41,602 (2% of total costs), vehicle operating expenses ₹93,684 (4% of total costs), hire of IEC items ₹67,662 (3% of total costs), building operating expenditure repairs and anti-termite measures ₹15063 (1% of total costs), and other expenses ₹5500 (0.2% of total costs).

In the year 2000, Guyatt et al.¹⁷ estimated the costs per person of IRS in the highlands of Western Kenya. The financial cost per person protected for providers/ consumers was \$0.86 (USD) and providers only was \$0.86. The economic cost per person protected in year one was \$0.88 and in year two (a hypothetical analysis excluding identification of organised community groups) was \$0.88. Opportunity costs for using existing personnel constituted < 5% of the total costs. Incorporating the estimated reductions in prevalence of infection from sleeping in a sprayed room (9.5%), the cost per infection case prevented in this population in July 2000 was estimated as \$9 for IRS.

One study by Hailu et al.²⁶ (a report using Loha et al.²⁴ data) estimated the cost-effectiveness of IRS in Ethiopia between years 2014 and 2016. The average annual economic cost was \$30,660 (USD) per 10,000 population for standard IRS. The cost of IRS per person year protected was \$3.07. The cost per under-five child year protected was \$20.12 and \$227.67 per pregnant woman year protected. The cost per household covered was \$15.56 (with 1527 total households in the IRS study arm). The itemised cost of malaria prevention per 10,000 population were \$7,883 for personnel, \$17,799 for insecticide (Propoxur), \$2,232 for materials and supplies, \$1,561 for transport, and \$1,186 for training hall.

Discussion

Summary of main findings

This systematic review examined the effectiveness of IRS for preventing malaria. When pooling data for all ages, the evidence from RCTs and non-randomised studies suggests uncertainty about the effect of clusters receiving IRS on malaria versus clusters that do not receive IRS. The reduction in malaria infection for all ages was evident only in non-randomised studies and determining the impact of IRS on malaria infection requires greater consideration of contextual and other factors that could not be achieved in this systematic review. It is unclear whether the differences observed between RCTs and non-randomised studies is due to bias or the limit scale of RCTs or something else. IRS works by achieving high coverage in a given area however, there is also the risk that small clusters allow for high contamination, either due to movement of mosquitoes or movement of people. Cluster RCTs may miss out on the effect of scale as clusters tend to be done at a village level whereas implementation of IRS in practice is often done at province or district level.

There was uncertainty about the effect of IRS on malaria in RCTs conducted in Eastern Sudan and Tanzania for children aged under five and six years of age^{20,23} However, Curtis et

al.²³ suggested a reduction of 31% in quarter three following a second spray round mid-year. The discrepancy between these estimates at different time points remains unexplained.²³ The evidence from two non-randomised studies conducted in North-western Tanzania¹⁸ and western Kenya¹⁷ suggests that in clusters that receive IRS, there is uncertainty in the evidence for a reduction in malaria in children aged under five years compared with clusters that do not receive IRS. Important to note is that Masharui et al.¹⁸ offer an additional follow-up time point not included in the meta-analysis, again six months post IRS, following a second round of spray in 2008 (six months after the first round of spray). In the second cross-sectional survey, malaria prevalence reduction between IRS and non-IRS clusters was not statistically significant. The authors¹⁸ report that low prevalence of malaria in non-IRS villages might have been due to other interventions introduced to the district after the 2006 malaria epidemic, including the distribution of long-lasting insecticidal nets and artemisinin-based combination therapy (ACT) as the first-line treatment of uncomplicated malaria. There was similar uncertainty in the evidence for malaria reduction in children aged five to 15 years and adults aged over 15 years.

17,18,21

Evidence for a reduction in anaemia prevalence in all ages was found in only one non-randomised study conducted in north-western Tanzania. In children aged under six years, evidence for a reduction in anaemia following IRS compared with no IRS was conflicting, with only one non-randomised study from north-western Tanzania¹⁸ showing a significant impact. Loha et al.²⁴ reported that during the first two years of their study (years 2015 and 2016), the study area in Ethiopia was affected by an unexpected severe drought and food shortages leading to an increase in stunting and anaemia prevalence in the first year of the study, which may explain the similarity in anaemia prevalence between IRS and non-IRS trial arms. This may also impact the generalisability of the findings for this RCT and suggests a broader assessment of anaemia causality may be appropriate in similar study settings.²⁴ For children aged five to

15 years, and adults aged 15 years and over, there was evidence from only one non-randomised study for a reduction in anaemia following IRS compared with no IRS. A GRADE certainty of the evidence assessment was not conducted for anaemia outcomes based on guidance from the WHO Guideline Development Group.

All-cause mortality among all ages was considered in one RCT conducted in eastern Sudan.²⁰ Certainty in the evidence from this RCT was very low. Similarly, there was very low certainty in the evidence regarding all-cause mortality incidence in children aged under five years in IRS clusters, compared with clusters that do not receive IRS. Importantly, Charlwood et al.²⁰ reported that while the camps that were sprayed had lower child mortality rates during the three-month sampling period and spraying may be one explanation, the trial had a very small number of units and thus uncertainty remains regarding the cause of any reduction in mortality.

Mosquito species that feed and rest outdoors may continue to transmit malaria even when IRS has been implemented (residual malaria transmission) reducing the expected effect of the intervention if all species predominantly feed and rest indoors. Human behaviour is also key for such an intervention as some people may stay outdoors late where they are less protected from outdoor biting mosquitoes.³² Similarly, where there is resistance to the insecticide used in IRS, mosquito mortality will be low and malaria transmission may continue to occur reducing the expected effect of IRS. We did not see a subgroup effect across insecticide resistant areas nor transmission settings and a large overall effect was not observed.

Overall completeness and applicability of the evidence

Included studies varied widely in their designs and time from implementation of IRS to outcome assessment. Entomological data and modelling were used by the Guideline Development Group to provide indirect evidence for impact against malaria. Included studies also had diverse populations and settings and this warrants consideration when determining the

generalisability of the findings for other populations, especially given the heterogeneity in estimates between studies.

Limitations of the evidence

Five of nine studies were cluster randomised controlled trials with no intervention as the comparator, including no ITNs.^{20,21,23,24,29} Four studies were lower in the hierarchy of evidence and may have greater opportunity for bias in the results.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ The overall certainty in the body of evidence started as high and outcomes were downgraded for risk of bias, inconsistency, and imprecision as appropriate. The certainty of evidence for all outcomes under the one comparison for randomised and non-randomised studies was very low, except the outcome of malaria prevalence for children under six years, which was not downgraded for inconsistency and considered low. Time points for outcome assessment were not consistent across studies and this may be cause for some heterogeneity in the results.

Limitations of the review

While quality assurance measures were in place during the review process, there was still potential for errors and bias in the results of the systematic review. The inclusion criteria for study designs was limited compared with the number of papers available for inclusion that were identified in the initial search. This led to the exclusion of a number of studies that showed an impact of IRS. For example, we are aware of at least two studies^{33,34} that were one-time cross-sectional surveys that showed a significantly lower prevalence of malaria in IRS areas. While these studies employed a lower-level study design, the observed differences were striking compared with those observed in this review.

Publication bias was not assessed as there were five or less studies in each meta-analysis. Studies were eligible if they contained two or more clusters per arm and thus studies with few clusters may be prone to biased results. Poor reporting of the primary evidence led to difficulties with subgrouping, as limited information was available to categorise studies.

Agreements and disagreements with other studies or reviews

Findings in this systematic review vary to those of previous reviews used by the WHO to develop IRS recommendations. There were several differences in the eligibility criteria, including restriction to higher levels of evidence and thus number of studies included. For example, Zhou et al.³⁵ included 25 cross-sectional studies, six cohort studies, five case-control studies, and two RCTs in their systematic review and found a protective effect of IRS on malaria infection. Similarly, in a 2010 systematic review of cluster RCTs, controlled before-and-after studies, and interrupted time series, Pluess et al.³⁶ compared IRS with no IRS intervention and found a marginal and varied effect of IRS in reducing malaria infection in unstable malaria transmission settings but failed to find evidence for this impact in stable transmission settings. There is no clear evidence for support of either of these reviews by this systematic review as the findings are mixed.

Pryce et al.³⁷ examined IRS in communities using nets and included cluster RCTs, interrupted time series, and controlled before-after studies comparing IRS plus ITNs with ITNs alone. Pryce et al.³⁷ found that in communities using ITNs, the addition of IRS with non-pyrethroid-like insecticides was associated with reduced malaria prevalence and a differential effect of IRS in addition to ITNs on malaria incidence based on study setting. The additional benefit of using IRS was not seen when using pyrethroid-like insecticides. Wangdi et al.³⁸ performed a network meta-analysis comparing interventions for malaria prevention in 30 studies published between 1998 and 2016. They found strong support for ITNs and ranked interventions from best to worst in the following order: prophylactic drugs, ITN, IRS and untreated nets, in comparison with no intervention. However, only ITNs showed statistical support for their protective effect with others recommended as important adjunctive treatments.³⁸

Authors' conclusions

Implications for practice

There was heterogeneity in the results of our meta-analyses and the results of individual studies are conflicting, with higher level studies not supporting IRS as a preventive measure for malaria infection. Based on the available evidence, the overall effects of IRS on malaria infection are equivocal and this warrants further investigation regarding the settings and population in which IRS may be of benefit. The cost of IRS in some settings was considered high and thus cheaper alternatives may be sought. Until further research is conducted, the certainty in the evidence remains very low.

Implications for research

Additional high-level and well reported studies would further strengthen the evidence base for IRS as well as better define the specific conditions under which it would remain cost-effective in comparison to other treatments. Evidence from other studies suggests that IRS is less cost-effective than other control measures, such as ITNs, and only useful in specific settings, such as high transmission settings.^{26,36} Further research could tease apart the specific settings in which IRS is most effective. There is a need for recent data using the latest available insecticides, on alternative application methods, outdoor application, and consideration of study designs to determine efficacy of IRS given that it is unethical to have no interventions in the control arm, such as comparing IRS with ITNs.

Disclaimer

The findings and conclusions in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily represent the official position of the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention or the Department of Health and Human Services nor that of the World Health Organisation.

References

1. World Health Organisation. *World malaria report 2020: 20 years of global progress and challenges*. Geneva: World Health Organisation, 2020.
2. World Health Organisation. *World malaria report 2021*. Geneva: World Health Organisation, 2021.
3. Bhatt S, Weiss DJ, Cameron E, et al. The effect of malaria control on *Plasmodium falciparum* in Africa between 2000 and 2015. *Nature* 2015;526(7572):207-211.
4. World Health Organisation. *Preferred product characteristics: indoor residual spraying products for malaria transmission control in areas with insecticide-resistant mosquito populations: draft for public consultation*. Geneva: World Health Organization: 2021. Available from: https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/malaria/ppcs-etc/who-ucn-gmp-2021-02-eng.pdf?sfvrsn=dbd89f86_10.
5. Lengeler C, Sharp B. Indoor residual spraying and insecticide-treated nets. Reducing malaria's burden: evidence of effectiveness for decision makers. *Global Health Council Washington DC* 2003:17-24.
6. Roberts D, Curtis C, Tren R, Sharp B, Shiff C, Bate R. Malaria control and public health. *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 2004;10(6):1170.
7. Shiff C. Integrated approach to malaria control. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews* 2002;15(2):278-293.
8. Pluess B, Tanser FC, Lengeler C, Sharp BL. Indoor residual spraying for preventing malaria. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* 2010(4).
9. Clark J, Glasziou P, Del Mar C, Bannach-Brown A, Stehlik P, Scott AM. A full systematic review was completed in 2 weeks using automation tools: a case study. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 2020;121:81-90.
10. McGowan J, Sampson M, Salzwedel DM, Cogo E, Foerster V, Lefebvre C. PRESS Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Statement. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 2016;75:40-46.
11. Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *British Medical Journal* 2021;372.
12. Sterne JAC, Savović J, Page MJ, et al. RoB 2: a revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials. *British Medical Journal* 2019;366:l4898.
13. Sterne JA, Hernán MA, Reeves BC, et al. ROBINS-I: a tool for assessing risk of bias in non-randomised studies of interventions. *British Medical Journal* 2016;355:i4919.
14. Review Manager (RevMan). 5.3 ed. Copenhagen: The Nordic Cochrane Centre, The Cochrane Collaboration; 2014.
15. Guyatt G, Oxman AD, Akl EA, et al. GRADE guidelines: 1. Introduction—GRADE evidence profiles and summary of findings tables. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 2011;64(4):383-394.
16. Gunasekaran K, Sahu SS, Jambulingam P, Das PK. DDT indoor residual spray, still an effective tool to control *Anopheles fluviatilis*-transmitted *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria in India. *Tropical Medicine and International Health* 2005;10(2):160-8.
17. Guyatt HL, Corlett SK, Robinson TP, Ochola SA, Snow RW. Malaria prevention in highland Kenya: indoor residual house-spraying vs. insecticide-treated bednets. *Tropical Medicine and International Health* 2002;7(4):298-303.
18. Mashauri FM, Kinung'hi SM, Kaatano GM, et al. Impact of indoor residual spraying of lambda-cyhalothrin on malaria prevalence and anemia in an epidemic-prone district of Muleba, north-western Tanzania. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* 2013;88(5):841-9.

19. Ramachandra T. Malaria control using indoor residual sprays in the Eastern Province of Afghanistan. *Bulletin of the World Health Organisation* 1951;3(4):639-61.
20. Charlwood JD, Qassim M, Elmsur EI, et al. The impact of indoor residual spraying with malathion on malaria in refugee camps in eastern Sudan. *Acta Tropica* 2001;80(1):1-8.
21. Rowland M, Mahmood P, Iqbal J, Carneiro I, Chavasse D. Indoor residual spraying with alphacypermethrin controls malaria in Pakistan: a community-randomized trial. *Tropical Medicine and International Health* 2000;5(7):472-81.
22. Bhatia MR, Fox-Rushby J, Mills A. Cost-effectiveness of malaria control interventions when malaria mortality is low: insecticide-treated nets versus in-house residual spraying in India. *Social Science and Medicine* 2004;59(3):525-39.
23. Curtis CF, Maxwell CA, Finch RJ, Njunwa KJ. A comparison of use of a pyrethroid either for house spraying or for bednet treatment against malaria vectors. *Tropical Medicine and International Health* 1998;3(8):619-31.
24. Loha E, Deressa W, Gari T, et al. Long-lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying may not be sufficient to eliminate malaria in a low malaria incidence area: results from a cluster randomized controlled trial in Ethiopia. *Malaria Journal* 2019;18(1):141.
25. Deressa W, Loha E, Balkew M, et al. Combining long-lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying for malaria prevention in Ethiopia: study protocol for a cluster randomized controlled trial. *Trials* 2016;17(1):20.
26. Hailu A, Lindtjørn B, Deressa W, Gari T, Loha E, Robberstad B. Cost-effectiveness of a combined intervention of long lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying compared with each intervention alone for malaria prevention in Ethiopia. *Cost Effectiveness and Resource Allocation* 2018;16:61.
27. Solomon T, Loha E, Deressa W, Gari T, Lindtjørn B. Spatiotemporal clustering of malaria in southern-central Ethiopia: A community-based cohort study. *PLOS ONE* 2019;14(9):e0222986.
28. Gari T, Solomon T, Lindtjørn B. Older children are at increased risk of Plasmodium vivax in south-central Ethiopia: a cohort study. *Malaria Journal* 2021;20(1):251.
29. Misra SP, Webber R, Lines J, Jaffar S, Bradley DJ. Malaria control: bednets or spraying? Spray versus treated nets using deltamethrin--a community randomized trial in India. *Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* 1999;93(5):456-7.
30. Curtis CF. Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene meeting at Manson House, London, 21 January 1999. Malaria control: bednets or spraying? Background and trial in Tanzania. *Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* 1999;93(5):453-4.
31. Guyatt H, Kinnear J, Burini M, Snow R. A comparative cost analysis of insecticide-treated nets and indoor residual spraying in highland Kenya. *Health Policy and Planning* 2002;17(2):144-153.
32. Sherrard-Smith E, Skarp JE, Beale AD, et al. Mosquito feeding behavior and how it influences residual malaria transmission across Africa. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 2019;116(30):15086-15095.
33. Steinhardt LC, Yeka A, Nasr S, et al. The effect of indoor residual spraying on malaria and anemia in a high-transmission area of northern Uganda. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* 2013;88(5):855-61.
34. Skarbinski J, Mwandama D, Wolkon A, et al. Impact of indoor residual spraying with lambda-cyhalothrin on malaria parasitemia and anemia prevalence among children less than five years of age in an area of intense, year-round transmission in Malawi. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* 2012;86(6):997-1004.

35. Zhou Y, Zhang W-X, Tembo E, et al. Effectiveness of indoor residual spraying on malaria control: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Infectious Diseases of Poverty* 2022;11(1):83.
36. Pluess B, Tanser FC, Lengeler C, Sharp BL. Indoor residual spraying for preventing malaria. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* 2010;2010(4):Cd006657.
37. Pryce J, Medley N, Choi L. Indoor residual spraying for preventing malaria in communities using insecticide-treated nets. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* 2022(1).
38. Wangdi K, Furuya-Kanamori L, Clark J, et al. Comparative effectiveness of malaria prevention measures: a systematic review and network meta-analysis. *Parasites and Vectors* 2018;11(1):210.

Tables and Figures

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram of eligible studies.

Study ID	Outcome	D1a	D1b	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall
Loha 2019	Incidence of malaria (all ages)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Loha 2019	Prevalence of anaemia (children under 5 years)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Rowland 2000	Incidence of malaria (all ages)	!	!	-	-	+	!	-
Rowland 2000	Prevalence of malaria (children aged 5-15 years)	!	!	-	-	+	!	-
Curtis 1998	Prevalence of malaria (children under 6 years, active)	!	+	!	+	+	!	!
Curtis 1998	Prevalence of malaria (children under 6 years, passive)	!	+	-	-	!	!	-
Curtis 1998	Prevalence of malaria (children older than 6 years, passive)	!	+	-	-	!	!	-
Curtis 1998	Prevalence of anaemia (children under 6 years, active)	!	+	!	+	+	!	!
Mirsa 1999	Incidence of malaria (all ages)	+	+	-	-	+	!	-
Charlwood 2001	incidence malaria (all ages)	-	!	-	-	!	!	-
Charlwood 2002	incidence malaria (under 5)	-	!	-	-	!	!	-
Charlwood 2001	Incidence all-cause mortality (all ages)	-	!	-	-	!	!	-
Charlwood 2002	Incidence all-cause mortality (under 5)	-	!	-	-	!	!	-

	Low risk
	Some concerns
	High risk
D1a	Randomisation process
D1b	Timing of identification or recruitment of participants
D2	Deviations from the intended interventions
D3	Missing outcome data
D4	Measurement of the outcome
D5	Selection of the reported result

Figure 2. Summary risk of bias assessment results for all outcomes.

	Bias due to confounding	Bias in selection of participants into the study	Bias in classification of interventions	Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Bias due to missing data	Bias in measurement of outcomes	Bias in selection of the reported result	
Gunasekaran 2005	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	High risk
Guyatt 2002	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	
Mashauri 2013	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	
Ramachandra 1951	-	+	+	?	-	+	+	

Figure 3. Risk of bias in non-randomised studies of intervention (same for all outcomes within each study).

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomisation process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants in a cluster-randomized trial
- (C) Deviations from intended intervention
- (D) Missing outcome data: Incidence of malaria
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Incidence of malaria
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Incidence of malaria

Figure 4. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all age, randomised controlled trials

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from incidence rates provided in each study, except Charlwood et al.²⁰ Estimates from Charlwood et al.²⁰ were adjusted for camp and month effects. Other estimates were not adjusted for clustering. Standard errors were inflated in a sensitivity analysis and indicated the pooled findings are robust. Loha et al.²⁴ reported alternative follow-up time points for measurement of malaria incidence. For the meta-analysis we selected the time point of six months following the first round of IRS (weeks 1 to 26). Spraying was conducted three times in September 2014, July 2015, and July 2016. Follow-up data from weeks 26 to 52 (IRR = 0.98, 95% CI: 0.66 - 1.43), weeks 53 to 79 (IRR = 1.00, 95% CI: 0.70 to 1.42), and weeks 79 to 121 (IRR = 1.29, 95% CI: 0.95 - 1.74) suggested no significant reduction in malaria incidence in the clusters that received IRS compared with the clusters that received no IRS. There were no significant subgroup effects and ICEMAN credibility assessments determined low credibility for all subgroups.

Figure 5. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on incidence of malaria in children under 5 years, randomised controlled trials

Footnote: Estimates from Charlwood et al.²⁰ were adjusted for camp and month effects. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the pooled findings are robust.

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Bias due to confounding
- (B) Bias in selection of participants into the study
- (C) Bias in classification of interventions
- (D) Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
- (E) Bias due to missing data
- (F) Bias in measurement of outcomes
- (G) Bias in selection of the reported result

Figure 6. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of malaria in all ages, non-randomised studies.

Footnote: Estimates were not pooled statistically for non-randomised studies due to drastically different time points from implementation of IRS to outcome assessment. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated findings are robust. Mashauri et al.¹⁸ reported a second follow-up time of six months following the second round of IRS (August 2008) and there was a 93% reduction in risk of malaria (RR = 0.07, 95% CI: 0.05 - 0.09) in the IRS clusters relative to the unsprayed clusters. ICEMAN credibility assessments determined low credibility for all subgroups, with likely no effect modification.

Figure 7. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of malaria in children under 6 years, randomised controlled trials

Footnote: Estimates were not adjusted for clustering. Standard errors were inflated in a sensitivity analysis and indicated the pooled findings are robust. Curtis et al.²³ reported quarterly time points for 1996. First time point pooled here There was no significant difference in risk of malaria infection in children under six years of age in clusters that received IRS compared with clusters that did not receive IRS in the second quarter of 1996 (RR = 0.91, 95% CI: 0.70 - 1.18). In the third quarter of 1996, there was 31% reduction in risk of malaria infection for children under six years in the clusters that received IRS compared with those that did not receive IRS (RR = 0.69, 95% CI: 0.52 - 0.91). There was no significant difference in risk of malaria infection for children under six years in clusters that received IRS compared with the clusters that did not receive IRS in the fourth quarter of 1996 (RR = 0.73, 95% CI: 0.52 - 1.03). Curtis et al.²³ also used a system of passive surveillance and report data from combined quarterly time points for children under six years. For the first and second quarters of 1996, there was a 38% reduction in risk of malaria infection in the IRS clusters compared with clusters that received no IRS (RR = 0.62, 95% CI: 0.45 - 0.86). There was no significant difference in risk between the IRS and no IRS clusters during the third and fourth quarters of 1996 (RR = 0.95, 95% CI: 0.59 - 1.51).

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Bias due to confounding
- (B) Bias in selection of participants into the study
- (C) Bias in classification of interventions
- (D) Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
- (E) Bias due to missing data
- (F) Bias in measurement of outcomes
- (G) Bias in selection of the reported result

Figure 8. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of malaria in children aged under 5 years, non-randomised studies.

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from prevalence or raw data provided in each study. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the findings are robust. Mashauri et al.¹⁸ also found no significant difference in risk between the IRS and no IRS clusters six months following the second round of IRS (RR = 0.47, 95% CI: 0.13 - 1.74) in children under five years of age.

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomisation process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants in a cluster-randomized trial
- (C) Deviations from intended intervention
- (D) Missing outcome data: Incidence of malaria
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Incidence of malaria
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Incidence of malaria

Figure 9. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of malaria in children aged 5 to 15 years, randomised controlled trials

Footnote: Estimates were not adjusted for clustering. Standard errors were inflated in a sensitivity analysis and indicated the pooled findings are robust. Curtis et al.²³ report prevalence data from two combined time points across the four quarters of year 1996. First and second quarters combined here. There was no significant difference in risk of malaria infection for children aged over six years in the clusters receiving IRS compared with those that did not receive IRS for the first and second quarters of 1996 combined (RR = 1.10, 95% CI: 0.94 - 1.29) or the third and fourth quarters of 1996 combined (RR = 1.24, 95% CI: 0.74 - 2.06). Rowland et al.²¹ Reported stratified data for *P. falciparum* (reported in this meta-analysis) and *P. vivax* in the clusters that received IRS compared with those that did not receive IRS (RR = 0.15, 95% CI: 0.06 - 0.37). There was a 64% reduction in risk of infection with *P. vivax* in IRS clusters relative to unsprayed clusters (RR = 0.36, 95% CI: 0.23 - 0.57). Because of high heterogeneity these studies were not pooled statistically ($X^2 = 18.49, p < 0.0001, I^2 = 95\%$).

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Bias due to confounding
- (B) Bias in selection of participants into the study
- (C) Bias in classification of interventions
- (D) Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
- (E) Bias due to missing data
- (F) Bias in measurement of outcomes
- (G) Bias in selection of the reported result

Figure 10. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of malaria in children aged 5 to 15 years, non-randomised studies.

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from prevalence or raw data provided in each study. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the findings are robust. Mashauri et al.¹⁸ also found no difference in risk six months following the second round of IRS (RR = 1.0, 95% CI: 0.60 to 1.67) in IRS clusters compared with the no IRS clusters for children aged five to 15 years.

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Bias due to confounding
- (B) Bias in selection of participants into the study
- (C) Bias in classification of interventions
- (D) Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
- (E) Bias due to missing data
- (F) Bias in measurement of outcomes
- (G) Bias in selection of the reported result

Figure 11. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of malaria in participants aged above 15 years, non-randomised studies.

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from prevalence or raw data provided in each study. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the findings are robust. These studies were not pooled statistically due to high heterogeneity ($X^2 = 10.44$, $p < .001$, $I^2 = 90\%$). Mashauri et al.¹⁸ also found no difference in malaria prevalence six months after the second round of IRS (RR = 0.46, 95% CI: 0.18 - 1.18).

Figure 12. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of anaemia in all ages, non-randomised studies.

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from prevalence or raw data provided in each study. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the findings are robust. Mashauri et al.¹⁸ found no significant difference in risk of anaemia six months following the second spray round (RR = 1.60, 95% CI: 1.11 - 2.33).

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomisation process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants in a cluster-randomized trial
- (C) Deviations from intended intervention
- (D) Missing outcome data: Incidence of malaria
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Incidence of malaria
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Incidence of malaria

Figure 13. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of anaemia in children aged under 6 years, randomised controlled trials

Footnote: Estimates were not adjusted for clustering. Standard errors were inflated in a sensitivity analysis and indicated the pooled findings are robust. Curtis et al.²³ reported results quarterly for 1996. First quarter results pooled here. Villages were sprayed in January or February 1996 and re-sprayed in July or August of that year. There was no significant difference in risk for anaemia between the IRS and no IRS cluster in the second quarter of 1996 (RR = 0.78, 95% CI: 0.49 - 1.25). In the IRS clusters, there was a 50% reduction in risk of anaemia in the third quarter of 1996 (RR = 0.50, 95% CI: 0.33 - 0.75) and a 57% reduction in risk for the four quarter of year 1996 (RR = 0.43, 95% CI: 0.25 - 0.73) for children under six years compared with the clusters that did not receive IRS. Loha et al.²⁴ offer anaemia data from three surveys, taken in December of each year. Data from 2014 (first time point) reported here. There was no significant difference between the IRS clusters and no IRS clusters in risk of anaemia for children under 59 months in years 2015 (RR = 1.08, 95% CI: 0.94 - 1.23) or 2016 (RR = 1.09, 95% CI: 0.93 - 1.28). Sensitivity analyses show a difference between high risk of bias and low risk of bias studies (p = 0.04; Supplementary file 2) demonstrating a larger protective effect for Curtis et al.²³ at high risk of bias.

Figure 14. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of anaemia in children aged under 5 years, non-randomised studies.

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from prevalence or raw data provided in each study. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the findings are robust. Mashauri et al.¹⁸ also found no significant difference in risk of anaemia six months following the second round of spray for IRS clusters compared with no IRS clusters (RR = 1.24, 95% CI: 0.74 - 2.25).

Figure 15. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of anaemia in children aged 5 to 15 years, non-randomised studies.

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from prevalence or raw data provided in each study. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the findings are robust. Mashauri et al.¹⁸ also found no significant difference in risk of anaemia six months following the second spray round (RR = 1.14, 95% CI: 0.70 - 1.89 in children aged five to 15 years.

Figure 16. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of anaemia in participants aged 15 years and over, non-randomised studies.

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from prevalence or raw data provided in each study. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the findings are robust. Mashauri et al.¹⁸ also found no significant difference in risk of anaemia six months following the second spray round (RR = 9.7, 95% CI: 1.78 - 54.64) in the clusters that received IRS compared with those that did not.

Figure 17. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on incidence of all-cause mortality in all ages, randomised controlled trials

Footnote: Estimates from Charlwood et al.²⁰ were adjusted for camp and month effects. Other estimates were not adjusted for clustering. Standard errors were inflated in a sensitivity analysis and indicated the pooled findings are robust.

Table 2. *Characteristic of included studies*

Study (location)	Year(s) of study	of IRS characteristics	Indoor residual spray Number of clusters, population details and coverage	Outcomes reported
Loha et al. ²⁴ 2019 RCT (Ethiopia: Adami Tullu district in the East Shewa Zone of the Oromia Regional State)	Sept. 2014 – Dec 2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Propoxur 50 % WP - 2g of active ingredient and packaged in 400 g sachets. • Two sachets mixed with 8L of water. • Indoor residual spraying with propoxur once per year (September 2014, July 2015, and July 2016) prior to the peak transmission season. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: 44 per trial arm. • Population: IRS = 1530 households with 7,753 participants; control = 1544 households with 8,038 participants. • Overall coverage: No household received IRS one year prior to study. Households = 1527. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weeks 1–52 = 97%. • Weeks 53–104 = 92%. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidence of malaria (all ages). • Prevalence of anaemia (children).

· Weeks 105–121 = 94%.

Rowland et al. ²¹ 2000 RCT (Pakistan: Sheikhpura district)	June 1997 – December 1997.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Wettable powder (5% WP) (used in this study).• Suspension concentrate (10% SC) formulations of ‘Fendona’.• Target dose was 25 mg alphacypermethrin per m².• Spraying as completed in June 1997 (peak transmission season: June–November).	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Clusters:<ul style="list-style-type: none">· 60 villages within the study area were included in the trial.· Number of clusters per trial arm not reported.• Population: Two or three sentinel villages totalling 2000 population were selected from each sector for outcome assessment.<ul style="list-style-type: none">· WP sector = 1206 households with 6017 participants.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Incidence of malaria (all ages).• Prevalence of malaria (children aged 5 to 15 years).
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- SC sector = 1124
households
with 5677 participants.
- Control sector = 1328
households with 6567
participants.
- Overall coverage:
 - WP sectors = 96% of
compounds (2665)
sprayed.
 - SC sectors = 97% of
compounds (1991)
sprayed.

Charlwood et al. ²⁰ 2001 RCT (Eastern Sudan: Gedaref and other large towns).	September 1997 – December 1997.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malathion wetttable power. • Applied at 2g/m² over a 5- day period. • Sprayed in the second week of September 1997 during the peak transmission season. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: Refugee camps. • IRS = 9. • Control = 5. • Population: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IRS = 23452. • Control = 25263. • Overall coverage: not reported. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidence of malaria (all ages). • Incidence of malaria (children under 5 years). • Mortality (all cause; all ages). • Mortality (all-cause; children under 5 years).
Misra et al. ²⁹ 1999 RCT (India: Surat, district of Gujarat state).	June 1997- May 1998.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deltamethrin. • The authors then state that the spraying operation in the trial villages was based on the NAMP guidelines. • First year of implementation June 1997-May 1998. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: in total, 3 zones, 42 clusters per arm, and 126 villages • Population: total = 93000 • Overall coverage: not reported. The majority of houses were fully sprayed and refusals were minimal. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidence of malaria (all ages).

Curtis et al. ²³ 1998 RCT (Tanzania: Muheza, Tanga Region, Pangani, and Hale)	December 1995 – 1997.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microencapsulated lambdacyhalothrin (10% Icon CS). • The target dose was 30mg a.i./m². • Diluted 50ml of concentrate in 8 litres. • Villages were sprayed in January/ February 1996 and re-sprayed in July-August of that year (peak transmission season: April to June). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · IRS = 4 villages. · Control = 4 villages. • Population: not reported. Village populations were censused and found to range between 971 and 2445 people, with an average of 17.9% aged less than 6 years. • Overall coverage: not reported. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of malaria (children under 6 years; active and passive surveillance). • Prevalence of malaria (children over 6 years). • Prevalence of anaemia (children under 6 years).
Gunasekaran et al. ¹⁶ 2005 NRCT	August 2001 –	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dichlorodiphenyl trichlorethane (DDT). The 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · IRS – Malkangiri = 26 units, Koraput 28 units. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of malaria (all ages).

<p>(India: Orissa State, Malkangari district and Koraput district).</p>	<p>March 2002.</p>	<p>DDT IRS was done with 1 g active ingredient per m².</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One round of spraying between 29 October and 4 November 2001 (transmission season: July to December). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control – Malkangiri = 6 units, Koraput 4 units. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidence of malaria (all ages; data not reported).
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Population: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IRS - Malkangiri (Khairput) = 5742, Koraput (Boipariguda) = 5886. • Control - Malkangiri (Khairput) = 843, Koraput (Boipariguda) = 1268. 	
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall coverage: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malkangiri District = 74.2% (range: 44.6% - 100%). • Koraput District = 86.2% (range: 68.6 - 100%). 	

<p>Guyatt et al.¹⁷ 2002 NRCT (Western Kenya: Nyamache Division and Gucha District).</p>	<p>November 1999 – May 2000.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Icon 10% WP (lambda-cyhalothrin, 100 g/kg). • February and May 2000 (transmission season: June – August). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · IRS = 3. · Control = 2. • Population: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · IRS = 11928 (290 households). · Control = 9180 (200 households). • Overall coverage: not reported. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · In 200 homesteads, 94% of 600 individuals examined slept in a sprayed room. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of malaria (all ages). • Prevalence of malaria (children under 5 years). • Prevalence of malaria (children 5 – 15 years). • Prevalence of malaria (aged over 15 years).
<p>Mashauri et al.¹⁸ 2013 NRCT (North-Western Tanzania: Muleba district).</p>	<p>May 2007 – August 2008.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lambda-cyhalothrin capsule suspension (ICON 10 CS). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · IRS = 8 sub-villages (4 villages). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of malaria (all ages). • Prevalence of malaria (children under 5 years).

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Following the President's Malaria Initiative (PMI), IRS intervention program. • Two IRS rounds: first round May 2007, second round January–February 2008 (transmission season: May–July and November–January). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control = 4 sub-villages (2 villages). • Population: numbers measured only. • IRS: n=754 (survey 1). • Control: n=405 (survey 1). • Overall coverage: not reported. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of malaria (children 5 – 15 years). • Prevalence of malaria (aged over 15 years). • Prevalence of anaemia (all ages). • Prevalence of anaemia (children under 5 years). • Prevalence of anaemia (children 5 – 15 years). • Prevalence of anaemia (aged over 15 years).
Ramachandra et al. ¹⁹ 1951	Mid-July	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two formulations of DDT,- DDT-Aromex2-soap emulsion and 50% water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IRS n=11. • Control n=13. • Population: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of malaria (all ages).
NRCT (Afghanistan: Laghman District)	1949 - October 1949.			

suspension of wettable

· 14000 (13 villages).

powder.

• Overall coverage: not reported.

- The emulsion was sprayed in two dosages, 200 mg per square foot (2.15 g per m²) and 112m²) mg per square foot (1.21g per and the wettable powder only at the latter dosage.
- The intended final concentration was 5%, but in actual practice it was estimated that the strength was about 4.8%.
- In Pashai-Demalah and Chalmati, the intended

dosage was 112 mg per square foot, but it was estimated that the actual dosages were 61 and 73 mg per square foot (0.66 and 0.79 g per m²).

- 1 spray round for all villages from 23rd July to 15th August (transmission season: August, September, and October).
- 2 villages received a second round from 1st-2nd October.

Contents

Table of Figures	3
List of Tables	4
Extended methods	5
Eligibility Criteria	5
Participants	5
Interventions	5
Comparators	5
Outcomes	5
Setting	6
Study designs	7
Search strategy	8
Study selection and screening	8
Data extraction	9
Assessment of the Risk of Bias	9
Data synthesis and Meta-analysis	10
Meta-analysis	10
Assessment of heterogeneity and publication biases	10
Unit of analysis issues	11
Subgroup and sensitivity analysis	11
Patient and Public Involvement	12
GRADE	12
Extended results	12
Results of screening	12
Excluded studies	13
Study designs and time periods	15
Population, setting and vector characteristics	15
Interventions and comparisons	16
Outcomes	17
Risk of bias of included studies	25
Randomised controlled trials	25
Non-randomised studies	27
Data synthesis and meta-analysis	29
Incidence of malaria infection, all ages (randomised controlled trials)	29
Incidence of malaria infection, children under 5 (randomised controlled trials)	30

Prevalence of malaria, all ages (non-randomised studies)	30
Prevalence of malaria infection, children under 6 years (randomised controlled trials)	31
Prevalence of malaria, children under 5 (non-randomised studies)	32
Prevalence of malaria infection, children aged over 5 years (randomised controlled trials).....	33
Prevalence of malaria, children aged 5 to 15 years (non-randomised studies)	34
Prevalence of malaria, aged above 15 years (non-randomised studies).....	34
Prevalence of anaemia, all ages (non-randomised studies)	35
Prevalence of anaemia, children under 6 years (randomised controlled trials)	35
Prevalence of anaemia, children aged under 5 (non-randomised studies).....	36
Prevalence of anaemia, children aged 5 to 15 years (non-randomised studies)	37
Prevalence of anaemia, aged 15 and over (non-randomised studies)	37
Incidence of all-cause mortality, all ages (randomised controlled trials).....	38
Incidence of all-cause mortality, children under 5 years (randomised controlled trials).....	38
Adverse effects	39
Contextual factors relating to IRS	39

Table of Figures

FIGURE 1. PRISMA FLOW DIAGRAM OF ELIGIBLE STUDIES.	14
FIGURE 2. SUMMARY RISK OF BIAS ASSESSMENT RESULTS FOR ALL OUTCOMES.	27
FIGURE 3. RISK OF BIAS IN NON-RANDOMISED STUDIES OF INTERVENTION (SAME ACROSS ALL OUTCOMES WITHIN EACH STUDY)	29
FIGURE 4. FOREST PLOT OF COMPARISON: IRS VERSUS NO IRS ON INCIDENCE OF MALARIA IN ALL AGE, RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIALS	30
FIGURE 5. FOREST PLOT OF COMPARISON: IRS VS NO IRS ON INCIDENCE OF MALARIA IN CHILDREN UNDER 5 YEARS, RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIALS	30
FIGURE 6. FOREST PLOT OF COMPARISON: IRS VS NO IRS ON PREVALENCE OF MALARIA IN ALL AGES, NON-RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIALS AND CONTROLLED BEFORE AND AFTER STUDIES.	31
FIGURE 7. FOREST PLOT OF COMPARISON: IRS VS NO IRS ON PREVALENCE OF MALARIA IN CHILDREN UNDER 6 YEARS, RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIALS	32
FIGURE 8. FOREST PLOT OF COMPARISON: IRS VS NO IRS ON PREVALENCE OF MALARIA IN CHILDREN AGED UNDER 5 YEARS, NON-RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIALS AND CONTROLLED BEFORE AND AFTER STUDIES.....	33
FIGURE 9. FOREST PLOT OF COMPARISON: IRS VS NO IRS ON PREVALENCE OF MALARIA IN CHILDREN AGED OVER 5 YEARS, RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIALS	33
FIGURE 10. FOREST PLOT OF COMPARISON: IRS VS NO IRS ON PREVALENCE OF MALARIA IN CHILDREN AGED 5 TO 15 YEARS, NON-RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIALS AND CONTROLLED BEFORE AND AFTER STUDIES.	34
FIGURE 11. FOREST PLOT OF COMPARISON: IRS VS NO IRS ON PREVALENCE OF MALARIA IN PARTICIPANTS AGED ABOVE 15 YEARS, NON-RANDOMISED STUDIES.	35
FIGURE 12. FOREST PLOT OF COMPARISON: IRS VS NO IRS ON PREVALENCE OF ANAEMIA IN ALL AGES, NON-RANDOMISED STUDIES.	35
FIGURE 13. FOREST PLOT OF COMPARISON: IRS VS NO IRS ON PREVALENCE OF ANAEMIA IN CHILDREN AGED UNDER 5 YEARS, RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIALS.....	36
FIGURE 14. FOREST PLOT OF COMPARISON: IRS VS NO IRS ON PREVALENCE OF ANAEMIA IN CHILDREN AGED UNDER 5 YEARS, NON-RANDOMISED STUDIES.....	37
FIGURE 15. FOREST PLOT OF COMPARISON: IRS VS NO IRS ON PREVALENCE OF ANAEMIA IN CHILDREN AGED 5 TO 15 YEARS, NON-RANDOMISED STUDIES.....	37
FIGURE 16. FOREST PLOT OF COMPARISON: IRS VS NO IRS ON PREVALENCE OF ANAEMIA IN PARTICIPANTS AGED 15 YEARS AND OVER, NON-RANDOMISED STUDIES.	38
FIGURE 17. FOREST PLOT OF COMPARISON: IRS VS NO IRS ON INCIDENCE OF ALL-CAUSE MORTALITY IN ALL AGES, RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIALS.....	38

List of Tables

TABLE 2. CHARACTERISTIC OF INCLUDED STUDIES	20
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Extended methods

This systematic review was conducted in line with guidance from Cochrane¹ and JBI.² It is reported in line with PRISMA 2020.³ The search methods for the review questions are presented together below. The protocol for the full systematic review has been submitted to PROSPERO, ID: 29314.

Eligibility Criteria

Participants

Studies of adults and children who resided in malaria endemic regions for more than one month (excluding travellers) were eligible for this review. Where studies included travellers, attempts were made to contact the authors regarding residential status or numbers of travellers within the population. Where these attempts were unsuccessful, studies that combined data (residents and travellers) were included only if more than 85% of participants were residents for more than one month.

Interventions

The interventions of interest were indoor residual surface treatments, with surfaces being sprayed, painted or treated with insecticide, or application of insecticide-treated surface coverings such as wallpaper. There were no limitations on the type of insecticide that was studied. Specifically, the interventions of interest for the review question was:

1. Indoor residual insecticide surface treatment of the entirety of all indoor walls and ceilings where applicable.

Different levels of household coverage were to be investigated through subgroup analysis. Where authors did not specify the household coverage, this was presumed to be full surface treatment unless there was information to the contrary.

Non-residual, non-surface treatments (such as insecticide space sprays) were excluded. The target of the interventions were mosquitos at rest, and interventions aiming to limit mosquito movement or entry into a dwelling (such as curtains or nets) were not considered, but interventions such as wall paper and wall linings were relevant.

Background interventions

Background interventions were those other than the interventions under consideration or any other malaria or vector-specific control intervention. Studies conducted where background interventions were present were included as long as interventions (both malaria and non-malaria) were balanced between intervention and control arms. Studies that included nets were excluded if net coverage was moderate or high ($\geq 50\%$)⁴

Comparators

Comparators included no residual insecticide surface treatment as a comparator to full residual insecticide surface treatment. All other comparators, such as nets, were excluded.

Outcomes

The following outcomes were considered for inclusion and were grouped into epidemiological outcomes, entomological outcomes, unintended benefits and harms/ unintended consequences. Entomological outcomes were only extracted from included studies that had also reported epidemiological outcomes.

Epidemiological

- Malaria case incidence (symptomatic infection) in children and adults: defined as malaria symptoms with parasitological confirmation, such as with rapid diagnostic tests, thick/thin blood film for all species, PCR or ELISA, or other methods.
- Malaria infection incidence: active and passive parasitological confirmation with rapid diagnostic tests, thick/thin blood film, PCR or ELISA (both symptomatic and asymptomatic infection).
- Severe clinical malaria incidence: cerebral malaria or malaria with severe anaemia or based on site-specific definition with parasitological confirmation of malaria infection.
- Malaria parasitaemia prevalence, confirmed using rapid diagnostic tests or thick/thin blood film for all species or PCR or other appropriate methods (both symptomatic and asymptomatic infection).
- Mild, moderate or severe anaemia prevalence defined by age- and sex-specific WHO haemoglobin cut-offs.⁵
- Malaria mortality.
- All-cause mortality.

Entomological

- Entomological inoculation rate (EIR), defined as the number of infective bites received by an individual during a season or annually.
- Sporozoite rate, defined as the proportion of mosquitos positive for sporozoites.
- Density of adult female *Anopheles*, including human biting rate (number of mosquitoes caught per person or house per time period) and other measures of adult vector density.
- Mortality of adult female *Anopheles* measured by observation if it is knocked down, immobile or unable to stand or take off for 24 hours after exposure (or as reported in the primary evidence).
- Repellency of vector populations (e.g., anophelines) measured by contact irritancy and toxicity in the laboratory or through field evaluations.
- Parity rate, calculated as the number of parous females multiplied by 100 and divided by the total number of females dissected.

Unintended benefits

- Epidemiological impact on other vector-borne diseases, such as other vector densities.

Harms and/or unintended consequences of interventions

- Adverse effects known to be associated with insecticides, including skin irritation, irritation of upper airways, nausea, and headache.
- Human behaviour changes e.g. proportion of time spent outside the house.
- Any influence on neighbouring houses e.g., increased vector abundance in unsprayed houses
- Environmental impacts such as biodiversity and ecosystem changes.
- Entomological impacts e.g., mosquito behaviour changes such as outdoor biting, biting times, feeding preference, development of insecticide resistance.

Setting

Studies conducted in settings with ongoing human malaria transmission were eligible. The presence of other background interventions did not impact on study eligibility. Studies where additional malaria interventions were considered standard of care were included as long as interventions (both malaria and non-malaria) were balanced between intervention and control arms however, studies that included net use at a low level only (< 50%) were included.⁴

Study designs

Randomised studies including cluster randomised controlled trials (with a minimum of two clusters), crossover trials and stepped wedge designs were included. Quasi-experimental designs (e.g., non-randomised studies of intervention) were included when there was a comparison/ control group present. This included historical controls. There were no exclusions on buffer period or length of intervention or timing of measurement of outcomes.

Entomological studies such as experimental hut studies and modelling studies for which epidemiological outcomes were reported were retrieved and collated for potential future use but excluded from the current systematic review and do not contribute data towards any presented results.

There were no exclusions based on language or publication status (i.e. published, unpublished, in press, in progress, pre-print). There were no date limitations. For studies published in languages other than English, Google Translate was planned to be used to determine whether the study met inclusion criteria. Where studies were published in a language other than English and met inclusion criteria, Google Translate translations were planned to be reviewed by a person fluent in the language.

Due to the large amount of studies identified from the search, screening included a process whereby each article retrieved was categorised based on study methodology and design characteristics. Exclusions were based on study design, such that study designs lower in the evidence hierarchy were excluded. Studies excluded based on study design may be considered by the author team and the Guideline Development Group at a later stage. This was to ensure the best available evidence to answer the research question was used by optimising the signal to noise ratio from the evidence. This allowed the research team to prioritise and balance higher certainty evidence where it existed for a question against very low certainty evidence. For example, the team excluded studies below the level of controlled before and after studies (detailed below) as it was unlikely lower levels would provide higher certainty evidence. Studies were also excluded if they had only one cluster included in either of the arms. Some studies contained elements of multiple study designs and as such the below are not mutually exclusive. Studies were classified using the following hierarchy:

1. Randomised controlled trials
2. Controlled trials
3. Controlled before and after studies
4. Interrupted time series (further split into studies where there are 3 or more data points pre/post the intervention and those where this is not the case)
5. Prospective/retrospective cohort studies (with exposed/non-exposed groups and baseline/post exposure data)
6. Before and after studies with no control group
7. Case control studies
8. Analytical cross-sectional studies at one time point
9. Descriptive cross-sectional studies at one time point
10. Modelling studies

Search strategy

The search strategy located both published and unpublished studies and was developed with the input of a health librarian. The search strategy was peer reviewed based on the Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies (PRESS) 2015 guidelines statement.⁶ An initial limited search of MEDLINE was undertaken to identify relevant articles on this topic. The terminology contained in the titles and abstracts of relevant articles, and the related subject headings and index terms used to describe the articles were used to develop a full search strategy for Ovid MEDLINE. This was also informed by a previous review on reactive indoor residual spraying and by using the search refinery tool.⁷ The search strategy, including all identified keywords and index terms, was adapted for each included database and information source, by using Polyglot and with the aid of a health librarian.⁸ The reference list and citations of all studies undergoing extraction were screened for additional studies using citation chaser⁹ and/ or a related citations search.¹⁰ The full search strategies and results are available in Supplementary file 2.

The databases searched included Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), published in The Cochrane Library and included the Cochrane Infectious Diseases Group Specialized Register; MEDLINE (Ovid); EMBASE (Elsevier); CINAHL with full text (EBSCO), US National Institute of Health Ongoing Trials Register (www.ClinicalTrials.gov/); ISRCTN registry (www.isrctn.com/); The WHO's International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO ICTRP) (www.who.int.ictip), the WHO Global Index Medicus (<https://www.globalindexmedicus.net/>), MSF publications and reports (www.msf.org), and Demographics and Health Surveys (DHS) indicator surveys and reports (dhsprogram.com).

Additionally, experts in the field and relevant organisations were asked whether they knew of any studies (completed or ongoing) that were relevant to this review topic. Organisations included the Malaria Elimination Initiative at the University of California at San Francisco, the Malaria Eradication Research Agenda Consortium, the Malaria Eradication Scientific Alliance, and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation.

Relevant conference proceedings were also reviewed (where accessible) for potential studies. This involved searching the most recent conferences for the Multilateral Initiative on Malaria Pan-African Malaria Conference, American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, and the Malaria in Melbourne event.

Study selection and screening

Following the search, all identified citations were collated and uploaded into EndNote™ and duplicates removed. The studies were then imported into Covidence for screening, with titles and abstracts screened by three independent reviewers (JCS, THB, ZM) for assessment against the inclusion criteria. Potentially relevant studies were retrieved in full. The full texts of selected citations were assessed in detail against the inclusion criteria by three reviewers (JCS, THB, ZM) in Covidence. Reasons for exclusion of studies at full text were recorded and reported. Disagreements that arose between reviewers at each stage of the selection process were resolved through discussion. The results of the search and the study inclusion process have been reported in full in a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA 2020) flow diagram.³ Where relevant systematic reviews were identified in the search, we reviewed the list of included and excluded studies for consideration however, the systematic reviews themselves were not included in this systematic review.

Where members of the review team were named as authors on primary studies identified through the search, these authors were excluded from any decision making regarding the inclusion of the study.

Contextual Factors and Entomological Studies

During the screening process, studies that provided important information regarding the contextual factors required to make a recommendation by a guideline panel were retrieved and collated for future consideration (i.e. for later data extraction and synthesis and potential subsequent or parallel systematic reviews). There were no restrictions based on the study design type for contextual factors. Likewise, entomological studies were retrieved and collated for further consideration.

Data extraction

Data was extracted from papers included in the review by two independent reviewers (JCS and THB) using a tailored data extraction tool developed by the reviewers (Supplementary file 2). The data extracted included specific details about the participants, concept, context, study methods and key findings relevant to the review question. Any disagreements that arose between the reviewers were resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer. Authors of papers were contacted to request missing or additional data when required. The data extraction form for study characteristics and outcome data was piloted on two studies prior to finalisation.

We extracted the following data:

- Study: authors, publication year, trial name, other reports of the study, time period study was conducted, outcomes assessed.
- Design: study design, recruitment method, method of randomisation/ matching or other, unit of allocation, number of units, adjustment for clustering, cluster details including buffer sizes between clusters, other indication of dilution effects.
- Setting: country, sites, peak transmission season, baseline malaria endemicity, study setting, vector species and vector profile details, malaria species.
- Participants: total trial participants in each arm, number of clusters per arm, participants who received the intervention and participants on whom the impact was measured, recruitment rates, eligibility criteria, demographics, frequency of travel in the last month.
- Intervention and comparison: insecticide brand, type, formulation, dose, duration, insecticide application method(s) and strategy, personnel applying the intervention, target area, coverage of household, coverage across cluster, type of dwelling and construction material of surfaces insecticides applied to, time to start intervention after index case, human behaviour, details of comparison, how intervention and comparison was measured, background interventions and cointerventions.
- Outcome: name, definition/ assessment metric, events, total (or unit time), time of outcome assessment, results, effect type.
- Costs: events/ raw costs, results, time of cost assessment, resources needed/ used.
- Additional data: unintended benefits, harms, other contextual information (feasibility, acceptability, preferences/values, impact on equity), entomological outcomes measured, source of funding, possible conflicts of interest.

Assessment of the Risk of Bias

Two review authors (JCS, THB) independently assessed the risk of bias for each study using the Cochrane Risk of Bias 2 tool for cluster randomised controlled trials¹¹ and the ROBINS-I for non-randomised studies,¹² using the templates available at riskofbias.info. Disagreements that arose between the reviewers were resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer. Risk of bias assessment was undertaken at the result level.

Data synthesis and Meta-analysis

Meta-analysis

Randomised controlled trials were pooled in a meta-analysis using Review Manager 5 (RevMan5)¹³ when two or more studies reported the results for the same outcome in a format conducive to meta-analysis. When only one study contributed data to a particular outcome for a comparison, a forest plot was presented for illustrative purposes (without a meta-analytic estimate). A narrative synthesis of the results accompanied one-study meta-analyses. Results from randomised controlled trials and non-randomised studies were analysed separately.

Non-randomised studies were synthesised narratively due to widely different time points from implementation of IRS to outcome assessment. Estimates from studies on children were also analysed narratively due to varying age group cut-offs.

For dichotomous data, effect sizes were calculated as relative risks and presented with 95% confidence intervals (CIs). When there were no events in a treatment arm, RevMan added a fixed value of 0.5 to the empty cell. If there were no events in the study, the study did not contribute to the pooled estimate of effect from the meta-analysis, however results were retained to inform baseline risk for absolute as opposed to relative comparisons and risk difference used. When incidence rates were reported, incidence rate ratios were calculated. Adjusted estimates to control confounding were extracted when given for synthesis of non-randomised study estimates, if reported. Otherwise estimates were calculated from the data provided by study authors. Calculations from raw data were made in StatsDirect. All calculations and data imputations performed as part of the review process have been documented (Supplementary file 2). A random effects model was used when there were more than two studies and a fixed effect model when there were only two studies.

In studies where there was more than one IRS group, decisions were made regarding which insecticide or formulation to select into the analysis based on guidance from content experts. For example, when wettable powder (WP) or suspension concentrate (SC) were reported, WP was selected based on advice from the WHO. In studies where authors split their data by malaria species, we reported data that confirms malaria due to *P. falciparum* parasite. Parasite density was defined by the authors of the individual studies. When more than one measure was available, we selected >4000/ul. Anaemia was defined by authors of individual studies and thus no selections were made. In studies where more than one time point was reported, the time point that most closely aligned with those of other studies was selected for the meta-analysis. Additional time points captured by each study have been narratively synthesised.

Assessment of heterogeneity and publication biases

Heterogeneity was assessed by evaluating the similarities and differences across studies in terms of the population, intervention, and study design. Statistical heterogeneity was assessed visually by inspection of the forest plot and statistically by Cochran's Q (P value 0.05), and by I², a statistic used for quantifying inconsistency in meta-analysis.

The I² was interpreted according to guidance in the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions,¹⁴ bearing in mind the limitations of concrete thresholds for I²:

1. 0% to 40%: might not be important;
2. 30% to 60%: may represent moderate heterogeneity;
3. 50% to 90%: may represent substantial heterogeneity; or

4. 75% to 100%: considerable heterogeneity.

To address publication bias, we sought both published and unpublished literature. We did not create funnel plots or use Egger's test to investigate reporting bias as there were fewer than 10 studies included in each meta-analysis.^{15 16}

Unit of analysis issues

We encountered unit of analysis issues in this systematic review, such that groups of individuals were randomised and assigned together in clusters.¹⁷ We took measures to address unit of analysis issues, such as using the generic inverse variance method in RevMan when studies analysed their data accounting for their cluster design. However, the authors of several studies did not control for clustering and so we contacted authors for the required information to inflate standard errors following the methods in the Cochrane Handbook.¹⁷ When authors did not respond we estimated the ICC to be 0.03 based on the study by Loha et al.¹⁸ Some studies were missing information regarding participant numbers randomised or sprayed. In this instance we performed a meta-analysis including studies that provided the number of participants assessed for the outcome from cross-sectional surveys. We also performed another meta-analysis restricted only to studies that provided initial numbers of participants in each cluster. These were presented as sensitivity analyses.

Subgroup and sensitivity analysis

A number of potential treatment effect modifiers were identified and assessed using subgroup analyses. These were also explored as potential contributors to heterogeneity in the overall analysis. These included:

- Insecticide class of main IRS compound (i.e. organochlorines such as DDT, pyrethroids such as deltamethrin, carbamates such as bendiocarb, organophosphates such as pirimiphos-methyl, neonicotinoids such as clothianidin, and pyrroles such as chlorfenapyr).
- Level of transmission (High: incidence of about 450 cases/1000 persons/year or Plasmodium falciparum (Pf) / Plasmodium vivax (Pv) prevalence of $\geq 35\%$; Moderate: incidence of 250-450 per 1000 persons per year and Pf/Pv prevalence of 10-35%; Low: incidence of 100-250 per 1000 persons per year and Pf/Pv prevalence of 1-10%; Very low: incidence of <100 per 1000 persons per year and Pf/Pv prevalence $<1\%$).⁴
- Vector characteristics (e.g., species, behaviours, insecticide resistance, etc).
- Setting e.g., rural/ urban/ peri-urban.
- Subgroups with/ without ITNs as background intervention (low coverage).

Sensitivity analyses were conducted to determine the following:

- 1) Inflated standard errors for trials where cluster designs were not considered. In this instance we analysed trials as if the individual was the unit of randomisation.
- 2) The impact of risk of bias to compare the differences between studies with high risk of bias against those with low risk of bias.

Subgroups were assessed on their credibility of being a genuine effect modifier using the Instrument for assessing the Credibility of Effect Modification (ICEMAN).¹⁹ The ICEMAN requires reviewers to address eight criteria per identified subgroup and for each outcome, to identify whether the differences between these subgroups are indicative of meaningful effect modification. It is important to note that the ICEMAN assessment is not intended to rule out a true difference between subgroups, and uncertainty can remain, especially with few studies contributing to a meta-analysis.¹⁹ ICEMAN credibility assessment statements are expressed as very low (very likely no effect modification), low

(likely no effect modification), moderate (likely effect modification), and high (very likely effect modification).

Patient and Public Involvement

This systematic review was conducted for the purposes of informing a WHO guideline. Guideline panel members, which include many diverse stakeholders including the public, end users, experts and decision makers have shaped the review question and focus, and guided the interpretation of the results.

GRADE

The Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) approach²⁰ for grading the certainty of evidence was followed and GRADE Evidence Profiles were created using GRADEpro GDT for each comparison. Evidence from RCTs and non-randomised studies started off as high certainty. Historically in the GRADE approach, evidence from non-randomised studies started as low certainty but as the ROBINS-I instrument was used for the assessment of risk of bias²¹ non-randomised studies started off as high. The evidence profile presented the following information where appropriate: absolute risks for the treatment and control, estimates of relative risk, and a rating of the certainty of the evidence based on the risk of bias, indirectness, heterogeneity, imprecision and risk of publication bias of the review results. Assessments from RCTs and non-randomised studies were presented separately. The outcomes reported in the evidence profiles were:

- Malaria incidence
- Malaria prevalence
- Anaemia prevalence
- All-cause mortality

Extended results

Results of screening

Following the removal of duplicate citations, 2692 citations were identified in the initial database (i.e., CENTRAL, MEDLINE, EMBASE, Scopus, CINAHL, WHO Global Index Medicus) and trial registry (i.e., US National Institute of Health Ongoing Trials Register; ISRCTN registry; WHO ICTRP) search. The studies were screened by title and abstract and 1763 citations were excluded based on study exclusion criteria. From this, 929 citations remained for full-text review, 913 of which were excluded based on design, as either editorials, letters, reviews, descriptive (no control group), qualitative or entomological studies with no epidemiological data; no mention of indoor surface spray; topical or spatial spray; and non-malaria populations (e.g., HIV, Tuberculosis, Dengue etc.). Finally, 16 reports of nine studies remained following the database and registry search.

An indeterminate number of records were additionally screened from websites (i.e., MSF publications and reports, Multilateral Initiative on Malaria Pan-African Malaria Conference, American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, and the Malaria in Melbourne event), organisations, and citation searching as part of a supplementary search process. Of these, 30 were retrieved and assessed for eligibility at full-text screen. Thirty studies were excluded due to incorrect study design, no prevalence data, no surface spray, no control group or were entomological studies. No reports were included from the supplementary sources searched.

A total of 16 reports^{22,23 18,24-36} were included for consideration in the systematic review, which represented nine unique studies^{22,23 18,24-29} (Figure 1). Due to the large number of studies identified from the search, each article retrieved was categorised based on study methodology and design

characteristics. Exclusions based on study design, responses from contacted authors, or unusable data may be considered by the author team and the Guideline Development Group for future reviews.

Excluded studies

Nine hundred and forty-three studies were excluded at full-text screen. Of these, eight were previously unidentified duplicates, 62 did not implement indoor surface spray, 93 did not measure malaria prevalence or other malaria outcomes, 81 reported entomological outcomes only, 51 had no control group, and 648 utilised an ineligible study design. Details of excluded studies are included in Supplementary file 2.

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram of eligible studies.

Study designs and time periods

We included a total of nine studies (16 reports) that met our eligibility criteria.^{22,23 18,24-29} Of the nine included studies, five were cluster-randomised controlled trials,^{18,26-29} one was a non-randomised controlled trial,²³ and three were controlled before and after studies.^{22,24,25} The years during which the studies were conducted were 1949,²⁵ 1995 to 1997,²⁹ 1997,^{26,27} 1997 to 1998,³⁴ 1999 to 2000,²³ 2001 to 2002,²² 2007 to 2008,²⁴ and 2014 to 2016.¹⁸ The study duration ranged from four months²⁶ at the shortest to two and a half years¹⁸ at the longest.

Population, setting and vector characteristics

The sample size ranged from approximately 200 households²³ to 3074 households¹⁸ with six studies not reporting number of included households.^{22,24-26,29,34} There was a combined sample size of more than approximately 222,541, including two studies that only provided number of participants measured at outcome assessment.^{24,27} One study conducted in Tanzania²⁹ did not report sample size however, estimated between 971 and 2,445 participants were included from a population census. Eight studies included both adults and children in their design,^{18,22-27,34} however children were considered separately from adults in six studies.^{18,23-27} One study conducted in Tanzania only included children.²⁹ Participants in two studies were subsistence farmers, with a few growing cash crops or depending on livestock rearing and fishing, and living in small houses.^{18,23} In one study conducted in Kenya, participants were mostly of the Wakisii ethnic group.²³ In a study conducted in Ethiopia,¹⁸ participants were of the Oromo ethnic group and the main religion was Islam. In all studies the participants were assumed residents of the villages in which they lived however, only three studies specifically measured this.^{18,23,29} In a study conducted in Kenya, 99.4% of participants had not travelled outside the study area within a last two months,²³ and in two studies, conducted in Ethiopia¹⁸ and Tanzania,²⁹ participants who left the area were excluded from the study as they may have acquired malaria under different conditions from those in their homes.

The countries under study in this review included India,^{22,28} Pakistan,²⁷ Afghanistan,²⁵ Kenya,²³ Tanzania,^{24,29} Ethiopia,¹⁸ and Sudan.²⁶ Most studies were conducted in rural settings^{18,23,24,26,27} or in a mixed rural and urban setting.³⁴ One study was conducted in a refugee camp in Eastern Sudan.²⁹ The type of dwelling material sprayed was mud,^{22,34} or a mixture of mud and brick^{25,27} or mud and concrete,²⁴ with thatched palm,²⁹ leaf,²⁵ or wattle.²⁶ In one study, dwellings were made of a mixture of thatch, corrugated iron and concrete.¹⁸

In most studies peak transmission season followed single periods of rain^{18,26,27,29} or was considered bi-modal following distinct long and short rains.²⁴ In one study conducted in Afghanistan the area was dry and rain did not directly influence mosquito breeding.²⁵ In Tanzania,²⁴ the long rains were between March and May and the short rains between October and December. Single seasons of rain were between August and September in eastern Sudan,²⁶ April to June in Tanzania,²⁹ June to August in Ethiopia and Pakistan.^{18,27} Peak transmission season was from July to December in India,²² June and August in western Kenya,²³ September to December in Ethiopia¹⁸ and June to November in Pakistan.²⁷ In all studies, spray rounds were conducted at the beginning or prior to the peak malaria transmission seasons.

The species of parasite in the studies were *Plasmodium falciparum*,^{18,25-27,34 22-24,29} *Plasmodium vivax*,^{18,25-27,34} *Plasmodium malariae*, and *Plasmodium ovale*.²⁴ Transmission levels varied across the study settings in this review. The levels of transmission were high (Pf/Pv prevalence of $\geq 35\%$) in India (Gujarat state) and north-western Tanzania,^{34 24} moderate (Pf/Pv prevalence of 10-35%) in India (Orissa state), and Afghanistan,^{22,25} low (Pf/Pv prevalence of 1-10%) in eastern Sudan,²⁶ and very low (Pf/Pv prevalence $< 1\%$) in Ethiopia and Pakistan^{18,27} based on the WHO: *a framework for malaria elimination*.⁴ The predominant vector species in the studies were *An. funestus*,^{24,29} *An. arabiensis*,^{18,26,29} *An. gambiae*,²⁹ *An.*

culicifacies,^{22,25,27,34} *An. fluviatilis*,²² *An. stephensi*,^{25,27} *An. pharoensis*,¹⁸ *An. annularis*,²⁷ *An. pulcherrimus*,²⁷ *An. subpictus*,²⁷ while many others were met in the study settings but considered inconsequential.

Interventions and comparisons

All studies compared IRS to a control group that did not receive IRS. The comparators across studies were stable, being no intervention, with or without low coverage of a background intervention, similar across intervention and control groups.^{18,24,26} Four studies^{18,23,28,29} also measured the effects of using bed nets alone and in addition to IRS however, study groups including nets were not investigated in this review.

There were background interventions in three studies.^{18,24,26} The Ethiopian Malaria Control Program¹⁸ involved distribution of LLINs and application of IRS either simultaneously or separately depending on the local setting. LLIN coverage prior to this study was 11% and no IRS was applied the year prior to the study. In eastern Sudan,²⁶ IRS was used to control malaria in the area from 1975 and was coupled with treatment of malaria cases with a variety of medications from 1986. In 1996 (one year prior to the study), sufficient insecticide was only available to spray approximately half the refugee camps.²⁶ In north-western Tanzania,²⁴ following the 2006 malaria epidemics (one year prior to the study) there were ITNs/LLINs distribution campaigns in the district. The Tanzania government introduced ACTs as the first-line treatment of uncomplicated malaria. Coverage of these background interventions was not assessed by the study authors.²⁴

All studies implemented IRS at the household level and four employed trained spraying teams.^{18,23,25,29} Organophosphates were used as IRS intervention in one study.²⁶ Charlwood et al.²⁶ applied Malathion wettable powder (WP; O, O-dimethyl phosphorodithioate of diethyl mercaptosuccinate) at 2g/m² once over a 5-day period to the interior walls of all turkels in the intervention refugee camps.

Two studies used organochlorides as the IRS intervention.^{22,25} Gunasakeran et al.²² applied dichlorodiphenyl-trichloroethane (DDT) applied at 1g of active ingredient per m² directly to mud walls over two months. Spraying was performed by the anti-malaria programme spray personnel. Ramachandra et al.²⁵ sprayed all villages with DDT. Two formulations of DDT,-DDT-Aromex2-soap emulsion and 50% water suspension of WP were used.²⁵ The concentration was approximately 4.8% (target concentration 5%).²⁵ The emulsion was sprayed in two dosages, 2.15g per m² and 1.21g per m², and the WP only at the latter dosage.²⁵ In two villages a second spray was applied, the dosages were 0.66g and 0.79g per m².²⁵ Stirrup pumps fitted with a nozzle was used to produce a fan shaped spray and galeazzi pressure sprayers were used during the second round of IRS.²⁵ All indoor surfaces, including walls, roofs, and all domestic articles, except cooking vessels, were sprayed. Average daily labour employed consisted of 8 havildars (squad foremen) and 40 labourers. Each squad foreman had five labourers with him, four manning pumps and one for supply of materials.²⁵

In five studies pyrethroids were used as the IRS intervention.^{23,24,27,29,34} Rowland et al.²⁷ used WP (5%) Fendona (alphacypermethrin), with a target dose of 25mg alphacypermethrin per m². Hudson X-pert spray pumps were used to spray living quarters, storage rooms and animal shelters.²⁷ Spray personnel sprayed nine to 10 compounds per day and were completed within 24 days.²⁷ Mashauri et al.²⁴ used lambda-cyhalothrin capsule suspension (Icon 10% CS) following the President's Malaria Initiative (PMI), IRS intervention program. Two rounds of IRS per year were organized seven months apart.²⁴ Similarly, Curtis et al.²⁹ applied two rounds of microencapsulated lambda-cyhalothrin (10% Icon CS) seven months apart. The actual dose applied was about 31mg a.i./m² (target was 30mg a.i./m²).²⁹ Spray was applied to the interior walls and ceilings by teams of 10 residents from each of the four villages designated for spraying.²⁹ Guyatt et al.²³ undertook IRS using Icon 10% WP (lambda-cyhalothrin, 100 g/kg). Between February and May 2000, four mobile teams, composed of Merlin and Ministry of Health staff sprayed

houses.²³ Misra et al.³⁴ used deltamethrin (Misra, 1998) according to the NAMP guidelines. Spraying of households was undertaken by the village and the community provided water for spraying.³⁴ Each spray squad covered 60 to 80 houses per day in lowland areas and 50 to 60 houses per day in the hills or foothills. Spray workers were organised into spray squads consisting of field workers and one supervisor.³⁴

Loha et al.¹⁸ used a carbamate, Propoxur (isopropoxy-phenyl methylcarbamate) 50% water-dispersible powder for more than three months at a dosage of 2g. Two 400g sachets were mixed with eight litres of water. Twelve houses were sprayed by each spray operator per day using eight litre Hudson X-pert spray canisters.¹⁸ Spraying was undertaken once a year (September 2014, July 2015 and July 2016) at the beginning, the middle, and before the end of the study, following the national spraying operation guidelines and WHO operation manual guidelines.¹⁸ The spraying teams were organized into squads of four spray personnel and a porter.¹⁸

Coverage of IRS was assessed in five studies presumably through surveys however, measures used to assess coverage were not specifically reported. In one study in India,²² moderate (51-79%) to high coverage ($\geq 80\%$) based on the *WHO: a framework for malaria elimination*⁴ was achieved, with coverage ranging from 74.2% (Malkangiri) to 86.2% (Koraput) across districts. Three studies^{18,23,27} reported to have achieved a high level of coverage, reaching over 90% across households. Misra et al.³⁴ reported coverage in the study was not an issue as the majority of houses were fully sprayed and refusals were minimal. Coverage was not reported in four studies.^{24-26,29} Spray coverage of individual rooms ranged from 48.6% (for Malkangiri District) to 56.6% (for Koraput District) in one study²² and was not reported in all others.

Five studies reported one spray round.^{22,23,26,27,34} Three studies completed two spray rounds^{24,25,29} Two of these were approximately six months apart,^{24,29} and the other re-sprayed only two of the study villages two months after the first round of spray.²⁵ One study applied three rounds of spray, one per year for three years prior to each transmission season.¹⁸

The quality of IRS was assessed using bioassay in five studies.^{18,22,24,27,35} In four studies mortality was found to be high,^{18,24,27,35} and in one study it was mixed depending on species.²² In four studies the quality of IRS was not reported.^{23,25,26,34}

Outcomes

The main outcome measured across all five of the RCTs was incidence of malaria. In the Loha et al.¹⁸ trial, malaria incidence was measured actively and passively in a cohort of approximately 17,360 participants who were followed on a weekly basis for 121 weeks and encouraged to attend health posts for testing and treatment if they had a history of fever within the previous 48 hours. Rowland et al.²⁷ visited 400 houses in each sector every fortnight and took blood smears from any member of a household that reported fever during the previous three days. Similarly, Misra et al.³⁴ actively followed each household in 126 villages twice a week and took blood smears from those reporting a fever. In the Charlwood et al.²⁶ trial however, malaria incidence was measured through passive case detection, with all suspected malaria patients attending clinics at each camp having blood slides taken. Charlwood et al.²⁶ measured malaria incidence in all ages, including children aged under five years. Curtis et al.²⁹ measured malaria incidence in children through both active and passive case detection. An independent cross-section of children aged under six years were surveyed each month for approximately one year. Children participating in each monthly survey were independent, after randomly selecting a new sample each month and excluding children who had been selected in the previous month. A system of passive surveillance was also used to measure malaria incidence in children aged under six years and children aged over six years.²⁹ Within each of the component hamlets (29 hamlets) of the six villages, participants who felt they had a fever

were encouraged to visit a locally appointed assistant who took their axillary temperature and a blood slide.²⁹

Malaria prevalence was measured in all four non-randomised studies. Gunasekaran et al.,²² examined 25% of the population through a blood survey conducted before and four months after IRS in the intervention and control groups, regardless of the presence of malaria symptoms. Likewise, Ramachandra et al.²⁵ conducted blood surveys before and after a small-scale demonstration project for malaria control. Guyatt et al.²³ randomly selected homesteads in IRS and no IRS clusters and residents from homesteads were classified into three age groups (6 months to four years, five to 15 years, and over 15 years). One individual from each age group was chosen at random from each homestead to provide a finger prick blood sample. Similarly, in the Mashauri et al.²⁴ study, randomly selected participants, identified through a census, from randomly selected intervention and control villages undertook parasitological surveys before and after spraying. To represent all age groups in the surveys, selected participants from each sub-village were stratified into three strata of age groups, children aged less than 5 years, children aged five to 14 years, and adults aged above 15 years.²⁴

The other outcomes measured across some of the studies were anaemia prevalence (in three studies^{18,24,29}) and incidence of all-cause mortality.²⁶ Loha et al.¹⁸ measure anaemia prevalence in children aged six to 59 months in the study households at three time points during the study (December 2014 to 2016, at end of each year's main malaria transmission season). Hb concentrations were examined through house-to-house visits, where a single finger-prick sample was taken from each child. Similarly, Mashauri et al.²⁴ surveyed randomly selected participants using parasitological surveys before and after spraying and represented all age groups in the surveys through stratification by age groups (children aged less than 5 years, children aged five to 14 years, and adults aged above 15 years). Similarly, Curtis et al.²⁹ actively measured anaemia prevalence by conducting monthly cross-sectional surveys on samples of children aged under six years in each village. Charlwood et al.²⁶ measured all-cause mortality in all ages, including children aged under five years however, data collection methods were not described.

Time from implementation of IRS to outcome assessment varied widely between the studies. For RCTs, this ranged between three months and one year for different outcome. Charlwood et al.²⁶ conducted one round of spray in mid-September and evaluated malaria and mortality from October to December, three months following IRS. Similarly, Rowland et al.²⁷ also completed a three-month post-IRS follow-up, with one round of spraying completed in June 1997 and cross-sectional surveys conducted in September 1997. Loha et al.¹⁸ reported six monthly follow-up time points for malaria, with a spray round conducted each year for three years, and conducted yearly surveys for anaemia prevalence at the end of the transmission period for each year. Curtis et al.²⁹ provided quarterly (three month) time points for active surveillance of children under six years for both malaria and anaemia prevalence and combined quarterly time points into two time points for passive surveillance of children over six and under six years of age (quarter one and two; quarter three and four). The time between IRS implementation and outcome assessment in the Misra et al.³⁴ trial was difficult to determine. Misra et al.³⁴ reported implementation to be between June 1997 and May 1998 and a mass blood survey conducted in September of 1997.

In the non-randomised studies, follow-up time was drastically different. Gunasekaran et al.²² sprayed between October and November 2001 with blood taken before and four months after spraying in fortnightly intervals. IRS was initiated between February and May 2000 in the Guyatt et al.²³ study, and surveys were conducted in July the same year, indicating a two month follow-up period. Ramachandra et al.²⁵ conducted surveys before IRS in July and August of 1949 and after IRS in October 1949. Spraying was completed in September of 1949 (with a re-spray of two villages in October), providing a one-month follow-up time for outcome assessment. Two follow-up time point were reported by Mashauri et al.,²⁴

both six months post IRS, with two spray rounds being conducted in May 2007 and January to February 2008 and outcome assessment conducted in December 2007 and August 2008.

Summary characteristics of the included studies has been provided in Table 2. The full details of these studies have been included in the characteristics of included studies tables (Supplementary file 2).

Table 2. Characteristic of included studies

Study (location)	Year(s) of study	IRS characteristics	Indoor residual spray	Outcomes reported
			Number of clusters, population details and coverage	
Loha et al. ¹⁸ 2019 (Ethiopia: Adami Tullu district in the East Shewa Zone of the Oromia Regional State)	September 2014 – December 2016.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Propoxur 50 % WP - 2g of active ingredient and packaged in 400 g sachets. • Two sachets mixed with 8L of water. • Indoor residual spraying with propoxur once per year (September 2014, July 2015, and July 2016) prior to the peak transmission season. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: 44 per trial arm. • Population: IRS = 1530 households with 7,753 participants; control = 1544 households with 8,038 participants. • Overall coverage: No household received IRS one year prior to study. Households = 1527. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Weeks 1–52 = 97%. · Weeks 53–104 = 92%. · Weeks 105–121 = 94%. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidence of malaria (all ages). • Prevalence of anaemia (children).
Rowland et al. ²⁷ 2000 (Pakistan: Sheikhpura district)	June 1997 – December 1997.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wettable powder (5% WP) (used in this study). • Suspension concentrate (10% SC) formulations of 'Fendona'. • Target dose was 25 mg alphacypermethrin per m². • Spraying as completed in June 1997 (peak transmission season: June–November). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 60 villages within the study area were included in the trial. · Number of clusters per trial arm not reported. • Population: Two or three sentinel villages totalling 2000 population were selected from each sector for outcome assessment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidence of malaria (all ages). • Prevalence of malaria (children aged 5 to 15 years).

<p>Charlwood et al.²⁶ 2001 (Eastern Sudan: Gedaref and other large towns).</p>	<p>September 1997 – December 1997.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malathion wettable power. • Applied at 2g/m² over a 5-day period. • Sprayed in the second week of September 1997 during the peak transmission season. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP sector = 1206 households with 6017 participants. • SC sector = 1124 households with 5677 participants. • Control sector = 1328 households with 6567 participants. • Overall coverage: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP sectors = 96% of compounds (2665) sprayed. • SC sectors = 97% of compounds (1991) sprayed. • Clusters: Refugee camps. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IRS = 9. • Control = 5. • Population: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IRS = 23452. • Control = 25263. • Overall coverage: not reported. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidence of malaria (all ages). • Incidence of malaria (children under 5 years). • Mortality (all cause; all ages). • Mortality (all-cause; children under 5 years).
<p>Misra et al.³⁴ 1999 (India: Surat, district of Gujarat state).</p>	<p>June 1997- May 1998.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deltamethrin. • The authors then state that the spraying operation in the trial villages was based on the NAMP guidelines. • First year of implementation June 1997-May 1998. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: in total, 3 zones, 42 clusters per arm, and 126 villages • Population: total = 93000 • Overall coverage: not reported. The majority of houses were fully sprayed and refusals were minimal. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidence of malaria (all ages).
<p>Curtis et al.²⁹ 1998 (Tanzania: Muheza, Tanga Region, Pangani, and Hale)</p>	<p>December 1995 – 1997.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microencapsulated lambdacyhalothrin (10% Icon CS). • The target dose was 30mg a.i./m². 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IRS = 4 villages. • Control = 4 villages. • Population: not reported. Village populations were censused and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of malaria (children under 6 years; active and passive surveillance). • Prevalence of malaria (children over 6 years).

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diluted 50ml of concentrate in 8 litres. • Villages were sprayed in January/ February 1996 and re-sprayed in July-August of that year (peak transmission season: April to June). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • found to range between 971 and 2445 people, with an average of 17.9% aged less than 6 years. • Overall coverage: not reported. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of anaemia (children under 6 years).
Gunasekaran et al. ²² 2005 (India: Orissa State, Malkangiri district and Koraput district).	August 2001 – March 2002.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dichlorodiphenyl trichlorethane (DDT). The DDT IRS was done with 1 g active ingredient per m². • One round of spraying between 29 October and 4 November 2001 (transmission season: July to December). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · IRS – Malkangiri = 26 units, Koraput 28 units. · Control – Malkangiri = 6 units, Koraput 4 units. • Population: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · IRS - Malkangiri (Khairput) = 5742, Koraput (Boipariguda) = 5886. · Control - Malkangiri (Khairput) = 843, Koraput (Boipariguda) = 1268. • Overall coverage: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Malkangiri District = 74.2% (range: 44.6% - 100%). · Koraput District = 86.2% (range: 68.6 - 100%). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of malaria (all ages). • Incidence of malaria (all ages; data not reported).
Guyatt et al. ²³ 2002 (Western Kenya: Nyamache Division and Gucha District).	November 1999 – May 2000.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Icon 10% WP (lambda-cyhalothrin, 100 g/kg). • February and May 2000 (transmission season: June – August). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · IRS = 3. · Control = 2. • Population: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · IRS = 11928 (290 households). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of malaria (all ages). • Prevalence of malaria (children under 5 years). • Prevalence of malaria (children 5 – 15 years).

Mashauri et al. ²⁴ 2013 (North-Western Tanzania: Muleba district).	May 2007 – August 2008.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lambda-cyhalothrin capsule suspension (ICON 10 CS). • Following the President's Malaria Initiative (PMI), IRS intervention program. • Two IRS rounds: first round May 2007, second round January–February 2008 (transmission season: May–July and November–January). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · IRS = 8 sub-villages (4 villages). · Control = 4 sub-villages (2 villages). • Population: numbers measured only. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · IRS: n=754 (survey 1). · Control: n=405 (survey 1). • Overall coverage: not reported. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control = 9180 (200 households). • Prevalence of malaria (aged over 15 years). • Overall coverage: not reported. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · In 200 homesteads, 94% of 600 individuals examined slept in a sprayed room. • Prevalence of malaria (all ages). • Prevalence of malaria (children under 5 years). • Prevalence of malaria (children 5–15 years). • Prevalence of malaria (aged over 15 years). • Prevalence of anaemia (all ages). • Prevalence of anaemia (children under 5 years). • Prevalence of anaemia (children 5–15 years). • Prevalence of anaemia (aged over 15 years).
Ramachandra et al. ²⁵ 1951 (Afghanistan: Laghman District)	Mid-July 1949 - October 1949.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two formulations of DDT,-DDT-Aromex2-soap emulsion and 50% water suspension of wettable powder. • The emulsion was sprayed in two dosages, 200 mg per square foot (2.15 g per m²) and 112m²) mg per square foot (1.21g per and the wettable powder only at the latter dosage. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · IRS n=11. · Control n=13. • Population: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 14000 (13 villages). • Overall coverage: not reported. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of malaria (all ages).

- The intended final concentration was 5%, but in actual practice it was estimated that the strength was about 4.8%.
- In Pashai-Demalah and Chalmati, the intended dosage was 112 mg per square foot, but it was estimated that the actual dosages were 61 and 73 mg per square foot (0.66 and 0.79 g per m²).
- 1 spray round for all villages from 23rd July to 15th August (transmission season: August, September, and October).
- 2 villages received a second round from 1st-2nd October.

Risk of bias of included studies

Judgement of the risk of bias in the included studies was based on the revised Cochrane Risk of Bias tool 2 for cluster randomised trials and the ROBINS-I for non-randomised studies of interventions. Judgements for each included study are summarized in Figure 2, with support for judgements provided below and in the risk of bias assessment tables (Supplementary file 2).

Randomised controlled trials

Risk of bias arising from the randomisation process

Two of the five RCTs were at low risk of bias arising from the randomisation process, having specified a clear randomisation process with a concealed allocation sequence until clusters were enrolled and assigned to intervention. Misra et al.³⁴ generated sequences at the time of randomisation through public lottery and Loha et al.¹⁸ through a computer-generated list in another country to the researchers assigning the clusters until the moment of assignment. Loha et al.¹⁸ identified a baseline imbalance in the type of houses between groups however, this was considered due to chance in this cluster RCT in the absence of a substantial excess of other differences between groups. Three RCTs^{26,27,29} reported assignment was randomised however, failed to describe the methods for randomisation and did not report allocation was concealed. Two of these RCTs^{27,29} did not provide a description or table of baseline characteristics warranting some concerns for risk of bias. One RCT²⁶ reported more villages, huts, and participants in the intervention group, which was considered an excess in differences in baseline characteristics and a high risk of bias arising from the randomisation process.

Risk of bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants in a cluster-randomised trial

Two of five RCTs^{26,27} did not report that participants were identified prior to randomisation, and provided no information regarding baseline characteristics or whether selection could have been affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster. There were therefore some concerns for risk of bias in these two RCTs. Three RCTs^{18,29,34} mapped villages and sampling frames, and undertook baseline prevalence surveys of participants prior to assignment. Of these three RCTs, two^{29,34} did not report baseline characteristics and one RCT¹⁸ identified house type as the only baseline difference. These three RCTs were judged to be at low risk of bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants in a cluster-RCT.

Risk of bias due to deviations from the intended interventions (effects of assignment to intervention)

Outcomes in one of five RCTs was considered at low risk of bias due to deviations from the intended interventions. In Loha et al.,¹⁸ participants and carers were aware they were in a trial and had been assigned the intervention as blinding was not possible however, this was unlikely to have impacted the outcomes and intention-to-treat and per-protocol analyses were performed. In Curtis et al.²⁹ the trial was public through meetings however, blinding of participants and carers was not possible in two of the outcomes measured through active case detection (malaria prevalence and anaemia prevalence in children under six years of age). For these outcomes, children were selected at random and measured through cross-sectional surveys. While participants were excluded from the analysis, this was considered a modified intention-to-treat analysis. These outcomes in Curtis et al.²⁹ were considered to have some concerns for risk of bias due to deviations from intended interventions. In two other outcomes reported by Curtis et al.²⁹ (malaria prevalence in children aged under six years and over six years), passive case detection was used. As those attending health facilities may be influenced by knowledge of the intervention assignment and no intention-to-treat analysis was performed, these two outcomes were considered at high risk of bias. Outcomes in two other RCTs^{26,27} were considered at high risk of bias due to deviations from the intended interventions. In these RCTs,

participants were aware they were in a trial and blinding of participants was not possible. Passive case detection was used to assess participants by health workers assigned to clinics. There was no information provided by authors indicating how this may have biased outcomes assessment and no intention-to-treat analyses were performed.

Risk of bias due to missing outcome data

Risk of bias due to missing outcome data was low for outcomes in two RCTs. In Loha et al.,¹⁸ data for all clusters were available and missing data was less than 20% of total participant numbers and balanced across groups. Therefore, there was evidence the outcomes were not biased due to missing outcome data. In Curtis et al.²⁹ data was not available for all participants, only those measured for the outcomes. Two outcomes measured through active case detection (malaria prevalence and anaemia prevalence in children under six years of age) involved cross-sectional surveys of participants selected randomly. These two outcomes were considered at low risk of bias as data was missing at random and therefore missingness was unlikely to depend on the true value of the outcomes. Two other outcomes in Curtis et al.²⁹ were judged to be at high risk of bias. These outcomes (malaria prevalence in children aged under six years and over six years) were measured through passive case detection. As participants attending health facilities were measured, missingness was not considered random. The outcomes from other RCTs were considered at high risk of bias.^{26,27,34} In these RCTs, all clusters were considered in the assessment of outcomes however, not all data for participants were considered. Two RCTs^{27,34} employed active case detection for outcomes assessment and there was no report of participants being selected randomly for this. Therefore, it was difficult to determine whether missing data depended on the true value of the outcome as it was not missing at random. Outcomes from one RCT²⁶ were measured through passive surveillance and while it was possible that missingness could be systematic, it was difficult to determine if it was related to the outcome.

Risk of bias in measurement of the outcome

In all RCTs, measurement of the outcome was considered appropriate, confirmed with objective blood tests, and unlikely to have differed between groups within the trials. Outcomes within four RCTs^{18,27,29,34} were considered to be at low risk of bias in measurement of the outcome. In these RCTs, cross-sectional surveys were used on selected participants and therefore outcome assessors' knowledge of the intervention received was unlikely to influence outcome measurement when confirmed using objective measures. In RCTs that employed passive case detection to measure the outcome,^{26,29} with participants attending health clinics or appointed village assistants, the outcome assessors were both the participants (subjective assessment of wellness) and the clinic assistant who used objective measurements. Knowledge of the intervention received by participants who perform subjective self-assessments prior to attending clinics may prompt more or less visits to clinics for objective measurement and thus outcome measurements have the potential to differ systematically between groups. This warranted some concern for risk of bias in measurement of the outcomes for these two RCTs.

Risk of bias in selection of the reported result

One of five RCTs was considered at low risk of bias in selection of the reported result.¹⁸ This study provided a protocol and all subgroup analyses were justified. There were some concerns in four of five RCTs,^{26,27,29,34} which were unable to be checked against a published protocol. Data dredging was considered absent in all of the RCTs, with minimal subgroup analyses justified by the background and objectives of the RCTs.

Overall bias

Overall, the risk of bias was low for all outcomes in one RCT (for the outcomes, incidence of malaria in all ages and prevalence of anaemia in children under 5 years),¹⁸ there were some concerns for two

outcomes in one RCT (prevalence of malaria and prevalence of anaemia in children under six years),²⁹ and high for all outcomes within three RCTs (incidence of malaria in all ages,²⁷ incidence of malaria in children aged five to 15 years,²⁷ incidence of malaria in children under five years,²⁶ all-cause mortality in all ages and children under five years²⁶) and two outcomes (prevalence of malaria in children over six years and children under six years) in one RCT.²⁹ The main concerns were with the lack of details provided by study authors on the randomisation process and allocation concealment, missing outcome data and measurement of the outcome. Risk of bias judgments for each included study have been summarised in Figure 2 with support for every judgment provided in Supplementary file 2.

Study ID	Outcome	D1a	D1b	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall
Loha 2019	Incidence of malaria (all ages)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Loha 2019	Prevalence of anaemia (children under 5 years)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Rowland 2000	Incidence of malaria (all ages)	!	!	-	-	+	!	-
Rowland 2000	Prevalence of malaria (children aged 5-15 years)	!	!	-	-	+	!	-
Curtis 1998	Prevalence of malaria (children under 6 years, active)	!	+	!	+	+	!	!
Curtis 1998	Prevalence of malaria (children under 6 years, passive)	!	+	-	-	!	!	-
Curtis 1998	Prevalence of malaria (children older than 6 years, passive)	!	+	-	-	!	!	-
Curtis 1998	Prevalence of anaemia (children under 6 years, active)	!	+	!	+	+	!	!
Mirsa 1999	Incidence of malaria (all ages)	+	+	-	-	+	!	-
Charlwood 2001	incidence malaria (all ages)	-	!	-	-	!	!	-
Charlwood 2002	incidence malaria (under 5)	-	!	-	-	!	!	-
Charlwood 2001	Incidence all-cause mortality (all ages)	-	!	-	-	!	!	-
Charlwood 2002	Incidence all-cause mortality (under 5)	-	!	-	-	!	!	-

+

!

-

Low risk

Some concerns

High risk

D1a Randomisation process

D1b Timing of identification or recruitment of participants

D2 Deviations from the intended interventions

D3 Missing outcome data

D4 Measurement of the outcome

D5 Selection of the reported result

Figure 2. Summary risk of bias assessment results for all outcomes.

Non-randomised studies

Bias due to confounding

Confounding was not addressed in our results and all studies were deemed to be at serious risk of bias due to confounding.

Bias in selection of participants into the study

Three studies were considered at low risk of bias for selection of participants into the study. In these three studies,^{22,23} baseline measurements were conducted at the start of the study and thus follow-up was deemed to coincide with the start of the intervention. Selection was based on characteristics determined after the start of the study, being age, in one study²³ however, this was not considered associated with the intervention. In one non-randomised study there was a serious risk of bias in selection of participants into the study.²⁴ In this study IRS villages were selected from an area affected by a malaria epidemic while no IRS villages selected from an area not affected by the epidemic. This selection characteristic was considered associated with the intervention and the outcome.

Bias in classification of interventions

All four studies were considered at low risk of bias in classification of the intervention. In all studies, intervention groups were clearly identified, with information used to define the intervention recorded at the start of the study. Classification of the intervention status was unlikely to have been affected by knowledge or risk of the outcome in any study.

Bias due to deviations from intended interventions

Risk of bias due to deviations from the intended interventions was considered serious in one non-randomised study.²² In Gunasekaran et al.²² many participants re-plastered their walls following application of IRS thus reducing the effectiveness of IRS. In one study,²⁵ only two villages received a second round of IRS after the first round was insufficient.²⁵ Two studies^{23,24} did not report deviations

from the intended interventions and were considered at low risk of bias due to deviations from intended interventions.

Bias due to missing data

Two studies were considered to be at serious risk of bias due to missing data. In one study the outcome data were a cross-section under active surveillance.²² In the latter study, epidemiological outcomes were monitored in less than 30% of participants within selected index villages under study and selection characteristics were unclear. In one study,²⁵ the methods for collection of data were unclear however, the number of smears was different from the number of participants sprayed and thus data was considered missing. There was no evidence of robustness of the results to missing data in these studies. In two of five studies, participants were selected randomly from households to have outcomes measured and thus missingness was considered random and therefore results were considered robust to the presence of missing data.²³

Bias in measurement of outcomes

In three studies,²²⁻²⁵ the risk of bias in measurement of the outcomes was considered low. Outcome assessors used objective measures, such as body temperature, light microscopy, and blood measures to survey selected participants. While these outcome assessors were aware of the intervention received by study participants, this was considered a low risk of bias as objective outcome measures were unlikely to be influenced by knowledge of the intervention received.

Bias in selection of the reported result

All five studies were considered at low risk of bias in selection of the reported result. While a protocol was not always available, the analyses were justified by the objectives of the study and no data-dredging was identified. There was a deviation from the protocol in one study²² where the planned result was malaria parasite incidence defined as the number of positive malaria cases per 100 population however, an odds ratio was used instead for malaria prevalence. This was not considered a problem of selection of reported result rather an issue of data type and appropriate analyses.

Overall bias

Overall, the risk of bias was serious in all non-randomised studies. In all studies, there was risk of bias due to confounding. There were some concerns in deviations from the interventions when houses were replastered.²² The main concerns besides confounding were with the lack of details provided by study authors on flow of participants warranting high risk of bias in missing outcome data as well as concerns in measurement of the outcome. Risk of bias judgments for each included study have been summarised in Figure 3 with support for every judgment provided in Supplementary file 2.

	Bias due to confounding	Bias in selection of participants into the study	Bias in classification of interventions	Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Bias due to missing data	Bias in measurement of outcomes	Bias in selection of the reported result	
Gunasekaran 2005	High risk	Low risk	Low risk	High risk	High risk	Low risk	Low risk	
Guyatt 2002	High risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	
Mashauri 2013	High risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	
Ramachandra 1951	High risk	Low risk	Low risk	Some concerns	High risk	Low risk	Low risk	

+ Low risk
? Some concerns
- High risk

Figure 3. Risk of bias in non-randomised studies of intervention (same across all outcomes within each study)

Data synthesis and meta-analysis

Incidence of malaria infection, all ages (randomised controlled trials)

Malaria control, as determined by the reduction of malaria incidence, was reported to occur in approximately 50% of the RCTs pertaining to IRS for all ages.^{27,34} When study estimates were pooled, there was no significant reduction in malaria incidence for all ages in clusters that received IRS compared with clusters that received no IRS (IRR = 0.90, 95% CI 0.63 - 1.29, Figure 4). On visual inspection of the forest plot, moderate between-study heterogeneity was found ($\chi^2 = 7.37, p = .06, I^2 = 59\%$).

Loha et al.¹⁸ reported alternative follow-up time points for measurement of malaria incidence. For the meta-analysis in Figure 4 we selected the time point of six months following the first round of IRS (weeks 1 to 26). Spraying was conducted three times in September 2014, July 2015, and July 2016. Follow-up data from weeks 26 to 52 (IRR = 0.98, 95% CI: 0.66 - 1.43), weeks 53 to 79 (IRR = 1.00, 95% CI: 0.70 to 1.42), and weeks 79 to 121 (IRR = 1.29, 95% CI: 0.95 - 1.74) suggested no significant reduction in malaria incidence in the clusters that received IRS compared with the clusters that received no IRS.

RCTs were categorised into subgroups based on available data, including background intervention of nets, resistance to IRS insecticide status, urban or rural setting, insecticide class, and transmission setting. Subgroups with unknown data were removed based on guidance by WHO content experts. There were no significant subgroup effects and ICEMAN credibility assessments determined low credibility for all subgroups. Subgroups analyses and corresponding ICEMAN assessments have been presented in Supplementary file 2. All sensitivity analyses are presented in Supplementary file 2.

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomisation process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants in a cluster-randomized trial
- (C) Deviations from intended intervention
- (D) Missing outcome data: Incidence of malaria
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Incidence of malaria
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Incidence of malaria

Figure 4. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all age, randomised controlled trials

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from incidence rates provided in each study, except Charlwood et al.²⁶ Estimates from Charlwood et al.²⁶ were adjusted for camp and month effects. Other estimates were not adjusted for clustering. Standard errors were inflated in a sensitivity analysis and indicated the pooled findings are robust.

Incidence of malaria infection, children under 5 (randomised controlled trials)

Charlwood et al.²⁶ measured malaria incidence in children under five years of age with suspected malaria attending health facilities in 1997. There was no significant reduction in malaria incidence (IRR = 0.90, 95% CI: 0.70 - 1.16, Figure 5).

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomisation process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants in a cluster-randomized trial
- (C) Deviations from intended intervention
- (D) Missing outcome data: Incidence of malaria
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Incidence of malaria
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Incidence of malaria

Figure 5. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on incidence of malaria in children under 5 years, randomised controlled trials

Footnote: Estimates from Charlwood et al.²⁶ were adjusted for camp and month effects. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the pooled finding are robust.

Prevalence of malaria, all ages (non-randomised studies)

The prevalence of malaria in all ages was measured between one month and 12 months across studies and thus due to the variability in time from implementation of IRS to measurement of malaria

prevalence, the results were not pooled statistically. There was a 30% to 75% reduction in risk of malaria across studies (Figure 6). Gunasekaran et al.²² measured malaria prevalence approximately four months after IRS implementation. There was a 69% reduction in risk of malaria in IRS clusters compared with clusters that did not receive IRS (RR = 0.31, 95%CI 0.27 - 0.35). Guyatt et al.²³ measured malaria infection approximately two months after IRS implementation. There was a 75% reduction in risk of malaria infection in the IRS clusters relative to the unsprayed clusters. (RR = 0.25, 95%CI 0.15 - 0.41). Mashauri et al.²⁴ examined participants for malaria infection six months following IRS. There was a 44% reduction in risk of malaria infection in the IRS clusters compared with no IRS clusters (RR = 0.56, 95% CI: 0.41 - 0.77) following the first round of spraying (December 2007). Mashauri et al.²⁴ reported a second follow-up time of six months following the second round of IRS (August 2008) and there was a 93% reduction in risk of malaria (RR = 0.07, 95% CI: 0.05 - 0.09) in the IRS clusters relative to the unsprayed clusters. Ramachandra et al.²⁵ measured malaria infection one month after IRS implementation and there was a 30% reduction in risk of malaria in the IRS clusters compared with the no IRS clusters (RR = 0.70, 95% CI: 0.65 - 0.75).

Non-randomised studies were split into subgroups based on available data, including background intervention of nets, resistance to IRS insecticide status, urban or rural setting, insecticide class, and transmission setting. Exploratory subgroup meta-analyses were conducted, and subgroups with unknown data were removed based on guidance by content experts at WHO. ICEMAN credibility assessments determined low credibility for all other subgroups, with likely no effect modification.

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Bias due to confounding
- (B) Bias in selection of participants into the study
- (C) Bias in classification of interventions
- (D) Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
- (E) Bias due to missing data
- (F) Bias in measurement of outcomes
- (G) Bias in selection of the reported result

Figure 6. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of malaria in all ages, non-randomised controlled trials and controlled before and after studies.

Footnote: Estimates were not pooled statistically for non-randomised studies due to drastically different time points from implementation of IRS to outcome assessment. Estimates were calculated from prevalence or raw data provided in each study. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated findings are robust.

Prevalence of malaria infection, children under 6 years (randomised controlled trials)

Curtis et al.²⁹ measured malaria prevalence in children under six years of age using cross-sectional surveys from the latter part of 1995 until the end of 1996 in each study village, reported as quarterly time points for 1996. Villages were sprayed in January or February of 1996 and re-sprayed in July or August of that year. There was no significant difference in risk of malaria infection in children under six years of age in clusters that received IRS compared with clusters that did not receive IRS in the first

quarter (RR = 0.95, 95% CI: 0.68 – 1.32, Figure 7) or the second quarter of 1996 (RR = 0.91, 95% CI: 0.70 - 1.18). In the third quarter of 1996, there was 31% reduction in risk of malaria infection for children under six years in the clusters that received IRS compared with those that did not receive IRS (RR = 0.69, 95% CI: 0.52 - 0.91). There was no significant difference in risk of malaria infection for children under six years in clusters that received IRS compared with the clusters that did not receive IRS in the fourth quarter of 1996 (RR = 0.73, 95% CI: 0.52 - 1.03).

Curtis et al.²⁹ also used a system of passive surveillance to measure test positivity rates in children under six years of age. Curtis et al.²⁹ report data from combined quarterly time points for passive surveillance of children under six years. For the first and second quarters of 1996, there was a 38% reduction in risk of malaria infection in the IRS clusters compared with clusters that received no IRS (RR = 0.62, 95% CI: 0.45 - 0.86). There was no significant difference in risk between the IRS and no IRS clusters during the third and fourth quarters of 1996 (RR = 0.95, 95% CI: 0.59 - 1.51).

Figure 7. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of malaria in children under 6 years, randomised controlled trials

Footnote: Estimates were not adjusted for clustering. Standard errors were inflated in a sensitivity analysis and indicated the pooled findings are robust.

Prevalence of malaria, children under 5 (non-randomised studies)

Prevalence of malaria infection was measured in children under five years of age. Time from IRS implementation to measurement of malaria was six months to 12 months. The reduction in risk of malaria ranged from 72% to 81% across two studies (Figure 8). Guyatt et al.²³ measured malaria infection approximately two months after IRS implementation. There was a 72% reduction in risk of malaria in the IRS clusters compared with the no IRS clusters for children under five years of age (RR = 0.28, 95%CI 0.10 - 0.77). Mashauri et al.²⁴ measured malaria infection six months post IRS at two time points (2007 and 2008). There was a reduction in risk of 81% in the IRS clusters compared with no IRS clusters (RR = 0.19, 95% CI: 0.07 - 0.48) and no significant difference in risk between the IRS and no IRS clusters six months following the second round of IRS (RR = 0.47, 95% CI: 0.13 - 1.74) in children under five years of age.

Prevalence of malaria, children aged 5 to 15 years (non-randomised studies)

Prevalence of malaria infection was measured in children aged five to 15 years in two studies. Time from IRS implementation to measurement of malaria was six months to 12 months. There was a significant reduction in risk of malaria from 35% to 60% (Figure 10). Guyatt et al.²³ measured malaria infection approximately two months after IRS implementation. There was a 68% reduction in risk of malaria in the IRS clusters compared with clusters that did not receive IRS (RR = 0.32, 95% CI: 0.16 - 0.65) in children aged five to 15 years. Mashauri et al.²⁴ measured participants six months post IRS implementation. There was a 40% reduction in risk of malaria infection six months following the first round of IRS (RR = 0.60, 95%CI 0.42 - 0.87) and a no difference in risk six months following the second round of IRS (RR = 1.0, 95% CI: 0.60 to 1.67) in IRS clusters compared with the no IRS clusters for children aged five to 15 years.

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Bias due to confounding
- (B) Bias in selection of participants into the study
- (C) Bias in classification of interventions
- (D) Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
- (E) Bias due to missing data
- (F) Bias in measurement of outcomes
- (G) Bias in selection of the reported result

Figure 10. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of malaria in children aged 5 to 15 years, non-randomised controlled trials and controlled before and after studies.

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from prevalence or raw data provided in each study. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the findings are robust.

Prevalence of malaria, aged above 15 years (non-randomised studies)

Prevalence of malaria was measured in participants aged 15 years and over. Time from IRS implementation to measurement of malaria was six months to 12 months. The risk of malaria was 26% higher in one study (*n.s.*) and reduced to 83% (*sig.*) in another study for clusters that received IRS compared with those that did not receive IRS (Figure 11). Guyatt et al.²³ measured malaria infection approximately two months after IRS. There was an 83% reduction in risk of malaria in the sprayed clusters compared with unsprayed clusters (RR = 0.17, 95% CI: 0.07 - 0.43). Mashauri et al.²⁴ measured malaria infection six months post IRS implementation. There was no significant difference in risk between sprayed and unsprayed clusters six months after the first round of IRS (RR = 1.26, 95% CI: 0.57 - 2.76) or six months after the second round of IRS (RR = 0.46, 95% CI: 0.18 - 1.18).

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Bias due to confounding
- (B) Bias in selection of participants into the study
- (C) Bias in classification of interventions
- (D) Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
- (E) Bias due to missing data
- (F) Bias in measurement of outcomes
- (G) Bias in selection of the reported result

Figure 11. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of malaria in participants aged above 15 years, non-randomised studies.

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from prevalence or raw data provided in each study. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the findings are robust.

Prevalence of anaemia, all ages (non-randomised studies)

Mashauri et al.²⁴ measured the prevalence of anaemia in all ages through active case detection using cross-sectional surveys. Two rounds of IRS per year were organized, the first IRS round was carried out in May 2007 and the second round was carried out in January to February 2008. Two surveys were undertaken, both six months following IRS. The first survey was undertaken in December 2007 and the second in August 2008. There was a reduction in risk of anaemia of 54% in the IRS clusters compared with no IRS clusters six months following the first spray round (RR = 0.46, 95% CI: 0.34 - 0.62, Figure 12) and no significant difference in risk of anaemia six months following the second spray round (RR = 1.60, 95% CI: 1.11 - 2.33).

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Bias due to confounding
- (B) Bias in selection of participants into the study
- (C) Bias in classification of interventions
- (D) Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
- (E) Bias due to missing data
- (F) Bias in measurement of outcomes
- (G) Bias in selection of the reported result

Figure 12. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of anaemia in all ages, non-randomised studies.

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from prevalence or raw data provided in each study. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the findings are robust.

Prevalence of anaemia, children under 6 years (randomised controlled trials)

Curtis et al.²⁹ measured anaemia in children under six years of age using active case detection. Cross-sectional surveys were carried out monthly from the latter part of 1995 until the end of 1996 in each

village, and data was reported quarterly for 1996. Villages were sprayed in January or February 1996 and re-sprayed in July or August of that year. There was a 36% reduction in risk of anaemia in children aged under six years in the clusters that received IRS compared with the clusters that did not (RR = 0.64, 95% CI: 0.42 - 0.97, Figure 13) in the first quarter of 1996. There was no significant difference in risk for anaemia between the IRS and no IRS cluster in the second quarter of 1996 (RR = 0.78, 95% CI: 0.49 - 1.25). In the IRS clusters, there was a 50% reduction in risk of anaemia in the third quarter of 1996 (RR = 0.50, 95% CI: 0.33 - 0.75) and a 57% reduction in risk for the four quarter of year 1996 (RR = 0.43, 95% CI: 0.25 - 0.73) for children under six years compared with the clusters that did not receive IRS.

Loha et al.¹⁸ measured anaemia in children aged 6 months to 59 through active case detection. Indoor residual spraying was carried out three times in September of 2014, July 2015, and July 2016. Loha et al.¹⁸ offer anaemia data from three surveys, taken in December of each year. There was no significant difference between the IRS clusters and no IRS clusters in risk of anaemia for children under 59 months in years 2014 (RR = 1.03, 95% CI: 0.87 - 1.21, Figure 14), 2015 (RR = 1.08, 95% CI: 0.94 - 1.23), or 2016 (RR = 1.09, 95% CI: 0.93 - 1.28).

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomisation process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants in a cluster-randomized trial
- (C) Deviations from intended intervention
- (D) Missing outcome data: Incidence of malaria
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Incidence of malaria
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Incidence of malaria

Figure 13. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of anaemia in children aged under 5 years, randomised controlled trials

Footnote: Estimates were not adjusted for clustering. Standard errors were inflated in a sensitivity analysis and indicated the pooled findings are robust.

Prevalence of anaemia, children aged under 5 (non-randomised studies)

Mashauri et al.²⁴ also present anaemia prevalence for different age categories for two time points, both six months following IRS, in December 2007 and August 2008. There was a 53% reduction in risk of anaemia in children under five years of age in the IRS clusters compared with no IRS clusters six months following the first round of spray (RR = 0.47, 95% CI: 0.31 - 0.69, Figure 14) and no significant difference in risk of anaemia six months following the second round of spray for IRS clusters compared with no IRS clusters (RR = 1.24, 95% CI: 0.74 - 2.25).

Figure 14. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of anaemia in children aged under 5 years, non-randomised studies.

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from prevalence or raw data provided in each study. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the findings are robust.

Prevalence of anaemia, children aged 5 to 15 years (non-randomised studies)

The prevalence of anaemia in children aged five to 15 years was reported for two time points in the one study by Mashauri et al.²⁴ In the IRS clusters compared with the no IRS clusters, there was a 48% reduction in risk of anaemia six months following the first spray round (RR = 0.52, 95% CI: 0.32 - 0.87) and no significant difference in risk of anaemia six months following the second spray round (RR = 1.14, 95% CI: 0.70 - 1.89, Figure 15) in children aged five to 15 years.

Figure 15. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of anaemia in children aged 5 to 15 years, non-randomised studies.

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from prevalence or raw data provided in each study. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the findings are robust.

Prevalence of anaemia, aged 15 and over (non-randomised studies)

In adults aged over 15 years, there was a reduction in risk of anaemia of 55% six months following the first spray round (RR = 0.45, 95% CI: 0.22 - 0.92) and no significant difference in risk of anaemia six months following the second spray round (RR = 9.7, 95% CI: 1.78 - 54.64) in the clusters that received IRS compared with those that did not in the Mashauri et al.²⁴ study (Figure 16).

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Bias due to confounding
- (B) Bias in selection of participants into the study
- (C) Bias in classification of interventions
- (D) Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
- (E) Bias due to missing data
- (F) Bias in measurement of outcomes
- (G) Bias in selection of the reported result

Figure 16. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on prevalence of anaemia in participants aged 15 years and over, non-randomised studies.

Footnote: Estimates were calculated from prevalence or raw data provided in each study. Estimates were adjusted for clustering in a sensitivity analysis by inflating standard errors and indicated the findings are robust.

Incidence of all-cause mortality, all ages (randomised controlled trials)

Charlwood et al.²⁶ examined all-cause deaths in all ages from the months of October to December, up to three months after spraying in September 1997. There was no significant difference in incidence between the IRS clusters and those that did not receive IRS in all-cause deaths (IRR = 0.4, 95% CI: 0.2 - 1.2, Figure 17).

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomisation process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants in a cluster-randomized trial
- (C) Deviations from intended intervention
- (D) Missing outcome data: Incidence of malaria
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Incidence of malaria
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Incidence of malaria

Figure 17. Forest plot of comparison: IRS vs no IRS on incidence of all-cause mortality in all ages, randomised controlled trials

Footnote: Estimates from Charlwood et al.²⁶ were adjusted for camp and month effects. Other estimates were not adjusted for clustering. Standard errors were inflated in a sensitivity analysis and indicated the pooled findings are robust.

Incidence of all-cause mortality, children under 5 years (randomised controlled trials)

Charlwood et al.²⁶ examined all deaths from the months of October to December, up to three months after spraying in September. In the period up to September (pre-intervention), there were 35 child deaths in the camps assigned to be sprayed, and 41 in the control camps. In the three-month post-intervention period, there were no deaths among children in the sprayed camps, compared with six deaths in control camps. The incident rate ratio was 0.0 for all-cause mortality in children under five years of age. Confidence intervals could not be estimated because there were no reported deaths among children under five years of age in the treated camps after IRS was introduced.

Adverse effects

Gunasekaran et al.²² used Dichlorodiphenyl trichlorethane (DDT) IRS and reported wall decolourization, bad smell, an increase in bed bug nuisance, and contamination of food grains stored above the false ceiling as adversely impacting participants and were reasons for refusal of the interventions. In addition, negative feelings towards spray personnel due to social caste were reported. Rowland et al.²⁷ used 'Fendona' wettable Powder and reported transitory skin irritation and headache were common symptoms in spray personnel and participants shortly after spraying. However, this effect attenuated after a few hours. Similar adverse events were reported for spray personnel in another study by Curtis et al.²⁹ where, despite wearing goggles and face masks, spray personnel suffered from paraesthesia in their facial skin following use of Microencapsulated lambda-cyhalothrin IRS.

Contextual factors relating to IRS

In one RCT conducted in Pakistan,²⁷ participants expressed appreciation for the spray used (Fendona WP) as there was no persistent odour or residue left after spraying. In addition, both nuisance and vector mosquitoes were controlled. In another RCT conducted in north-east Tanzania,²⁹ questionnaires administered to participants indicated general satisfaction with house spraying and there were no refusals for spraying.

All costs were reported at the time of the study and therefore, when adjusted for inflation, will likely be much higher than reported. Curtis et al.,²⁹ over a two-year period between years 1995 and 1996, estimated the cost-effectiveness of IRS in north-east Tanzania. For one year of house spraying for 1000 participants in 258 houses, the annual cost in year one was \$2,304 (USD) and in year two was \$4608. The itemised costs for year one were \$2,064 for insecticide (Icon 10%), labour for 50 person-days in Tanzania \$200, and transport of personnel \$40. The itemised costs for year two were \$4,128 (Icon 10%), labour for 50 person-days in Tanzania \$400, and transport of personnel \$80. These estimates do not include the costs of the spray pumps and the protective clothing needed by spray teams, since these items are durable.

Misra et al.³⁴ measured the cost of IRS over a two-year study period between years 1997 and 1998 in India. The total cost for IRS over the intervention period was ₹2,331,191 (IRN). The total capital costs were ₹462,113, which made up 20% of all costs. The itemised capital costs were equipment ₹189,582 (8% of total costs), space rental (including project office) ₹66,409 (3% of total costs), vehicles ₹183,372 (8% of total costs), other (development of health education material) ₹22,750 (1% of total costs). The total recurrent costs over the intervention period were ₹1,869,078, which made up 80% of the total costs. The itemised recurrent costs were personnel ₹780,666 (33% of total costs), insecticide (deltamethrin) ₹864,901 (37% of total costs), project office operating expenses ₹41,602 (2% of total costs), vehicle operating expenses ₹93,684 (4% of total costs), hire of IEC items ₹67,662 (3% of total costs), building operating expenditure repairs and anti-termite measures ₹15063 (1% of total costs), and other expenses ₹5500 (0.2% of total costs).

In the year 2000, Guyatt et al.²³ estimated the costs per person of IRS in the highlands of Western Kenya. The financial cost per person protected for providers/ consumers was \$0.86 (USD) and providers only was \$0.86. The economic cost per person protected in year one was \$0.88 and in year two (a hypothetical analysis excluding identification of organised community groups) was \$0.88. Opportunity costs for using existing personnel constituted < 5% of the total costs. Incorporating the estimated reductions in prevalence of infection from sleeping in a sprayed room (9.5%), the cost per infection case prevented in this population in July 2000 was estimated as \$9 for IRS.

One study by Hailu et al.³¹ (a report using Loha et al.¹⁸ data) estimated the cost-effectiveness of IRS in Ethiopia between years 2014 and 2016. The average annual economic cost was \$30,660 (USD) per 10,000 population for standard IRS. The cost of IRS per person year protected was \$3.07. The cost per under-five child year protected was \$20.12 and \$227.67 per pregnant woman year protected. The cost per household covered was \$15.56 (with 1527 total households in the IRS study arm). The itemised cost of malaria prevention per 10,000 population were \$7,883 for personnel, \$17,799 for insecticide (Propoxur), \$2,232 for materials and supplies, \$1,561 for transport, and \$1,186 for training hall.

References

1. Higgins JP, Thomas J, Chandler J, et al. *Cochrane handbook for systematic reviews of interventions*. John Wiley & Sons, 2019.
2. Aromataris E, Munn Z. *JBI manual for evidence synthesis*. Adelaide: JBI 2020.
3. Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *British Medical Journal* 2021;372.
4. World Health Organisation. *A framework for malaria elimination: World Health Organisation*, 2017.
5. World Health Organisation. *Haemoglobin concentrations for the diagnosis of anaemia and assessment of severity*. World Health Organization, 2011.
6. McGowan J, Sampson M, Salzwedel DM, Cogo E, Foerster V, Lefebvre C. PRESS Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Statement. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 2016;75:40-46.
7. Clark J, Glasziou P, Del Mar C, Bannach-Brown A, Stehlik P, Scott AM. A full systematic review was completed in 2 weeks using automation tools: a case study. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 2020;121:81-90.
8. Clark JM, Sanders S, Carter M, et al. Improving the translation of search strategies using the Polyglot Search Translator: a randomized controlled trial. *Journal of the Medical Library Association* 2020;108(2):195-207.
9. Haddaway N, Grainger M, Gray C. *Citationchaser: An R package and Shiny app for forward and backward citations chasing in academic searching*. 2021.
10. Waffenschmidt S, Janzen T, Hausner E, Kaiser T. Simple search techniques in PubMed are potentially suitable for evaluating the completeness of systematic reviews. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 2013;66(6):660-665.
11. Sterne JAC, Savović J, Page MJ, et al. RoB 2: a revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials. *British Medical Journal* 2019;366:l4898.
12. Sterne JA, Hernán MA, Reeves BC, et al. ROBINS-I: a tool for assessing risk of bias in non-randomised studies of interventions. *British Medical Journal* 2016;355:i4919.
13. Review Manager (RevMan). 5.3 ed. Copenhagen: The Nordic Cochrane Centre, *The Cochrane Collaboration*; 2014.
14. Deeks JJ, Higgins J, Altman DG, Green S. *Cochrane handbook for systematic reviews of interventions version 5.1.0* (updated March 2011). The cochrane collaboration 2011;2.
15. Sterne JA, Sutton AJ, Ioannidis JP, et al. Recommendations for examining and interpreting funnel plot asymmetry in meta-analyses of randomised controlled trials. *British Medical Journal* 2011;343.
16. Egger M, Smith GD, Schneider M, Minder C. Bias in meta-analysis detected by a simple, graphical test. *British Medical Journal* 1997;315(7109):629-634.
17. Higgins JP, Eldridge S, Li T. Including variants on randomized trials. *Cochrane handbook for systematic reviews of interventions* 2019:569-593.
18. Loha E, Deressa W, Gari T, et al. Long-lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying may not be sufficient to eliminate malaria in a low malaria incidence area: results from a cluster randomized controlled trial in Ethiopia. *Malaria Journal* 2019;18(1):141.
19. Schandelmaier S, Briel M, Varadhan R, et al. Development of the Instrument to assess the Credibility of Effect Modification Analyses (ICEMAN) in randomized controlled trials and meta-analyses. *Canadian Medical Association Journal* 2020;192(32):E901-E906.
20. Guyatt G, Oxman AD, Akl EA, et al. GRADE guidelines: 1. Introduction—GRADE evidence profiles and summary of findings tables. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 2011;64(4):383-394.
21. Schünemann HJ, Cuello C, Akl EA, et al. GRADE guidelines: 18. How ROBINS-I and other tools to assess risk of bias in nonrandomized studies should be used to rate the certainty of a body of evidence. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 2019;111:105-114.

22. Gunasekaran K, Sahu SS, Jambulingam P, Das PK. DDT indoor residual spray, still an effective tool to control *Anopheles fluviatilis*-transmitted *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria in India. *Tropical Medicine and International Health* 2005;10(2):160-8.
23. Guyatt HL, Corlett SK, Robinson TP, Ochola SA, Snow RW. Malaria prevention in highland Kenya: indoor residual house-spraying vs. insecticide-treated bednets. *Tropical Medicine and International Health* 2002;7(4):298-303.
24. Mashauri FM, Kinung'hi SM, Kaatano GM, et al. Impact of indoor residual spraying of lambda-cyhalothrin on malaria prevalence and anemia in an epidemic-prone district of Muleba, north-western Tanzania. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* 2013;88(5):841-9.
25. Ramachandra T. Malaria control using indoor residual sprays in the Eastern Province of Afghanistan. *Bulletin of the World Health Organisation* 1951;3(4):639-61.
26. Charlwood JD, Qassim M, Elsur EI, et al. The impact of indoor residual spraying with malathion on malaria in refugee camps in eastern Sudan. *Acta Tropica* 2001;80(1):1-8.
27. Rowland M, Mahmood P, Iqbal J, Carneiro I, Chavasse D. Indoor residual spraying with alphacypermethrin controls malaria in Pakistan: a community-randomized trial. *Tropical Medicine and International Health* 2000;5(7):472-81.
28. Bhatia MR, Fox-Rushby J, Mills A. Cost-effectiveness of malaria control interventions when malaria mortality is low: insecticide-treated nets versus in-house residual spraying in India. *Social Science and Medicine* 2004;59(3):525-39.
29. Curtis CF, Maxwell CA, Finch RJ, Njunwa KJ. A comparison of use of a pyrethroid either for house spraying or for bednet treatment against malaria vectors. *Tropical Medicine and International Health* 1998;3(8):619-31.
30. Deressa W, Loha E, Balkew M, et al. Combining long-lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying for malaria prevention in Ethiopia: study protocol for a cluster randomized controlled trial. *Trials* 2016;17(1):20.
31. Hailu A, Lindtjørn B, Deressa W, Gari T, Loha E, Robberstad B. Cost-effectiveness of a combined intervention of long lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying compared with each intervention alone for malaria prevention in Ethiopia. *Cost Effectiveness and Resource Allocation* 2018;16:61.
32. Solomon T, Loha E, Deressa W, Gari T, Lindtjørn B. Spatiotemporal clustering of malaria in southern-central Ethiopia: A community-based cohort study. *PLOS ONE* 2019;14(9):e0222986.
33. Gari T, Solomon T, Lindtjørn B. Older children are at increased risk of *Plasmodium vivax* in south-central Ethiopia: a cohort study. *Malaria Journal* 2021;20(1):251.
34. Misra SP, Webber R, Lines J, Jaffar S, Bradley DJ. Malaria control: bednets or spraying? Spray versus treated nets using deltamethrin--a community randomized trial in India. *Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* 1999;93(5):456-7.
35. Curtis CF. Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene meeting at Manson House, London, 21 January 1999. Malaria control: bednets or spraying? Background and trial in Tanzania. *Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* 1999;93(5):453-4.
36. Guyatt H, Kinnear J, Burini M, Snow R. A comparative cost analysis of insecticide-treated nets and indoor residual spraying in highland Kenya. *Health Policy and Planning* 2002;17(2):144-153.

Contents

Supplementary item 1 – Deviations from protocol.....	4
Supplementary item 2 – Search strategies.....	6
Supplementary item 3 – Data extraction tool.....	11
Supplementary item 4 – Calculations and data imputations	14
Charlwood et al. 2001	14
Malaria incidence (all ages and children under 5 years).....	14
All-cause mortality.....	14
Loha et al. 2019	14
Malaria incidence	14
Anaemia prevalence.....	14
Misra et al. 1999.....	14
Malaria incidence	14
Rowland et al. 2000.....	14
Malaria incidence	14
Malaria prevalence (children 5-15 years).....	15
Curtis et al. 1998.....	15
Malaria prevalence (children under 6 years; active case detection)	15
Malaria prevalence (children over 6 years; passive case detection).....	15
Anaemia prevalence (children under 6 years; active case detection)	15
Gunasekaran et al. 2005.....	15
Malaria prevalence (all ages).....	15
Guyatt et al. 2005	16
Malaria prevalence (all ages).....	16
Malaria prevalence (children under 5 years, 5-15 years, and adults aged 15+ years).....	16
Mashauri et al. 2013.....	16
Malaria prevalence (all ages).....	16
Malaria prevalence (children under 5 years, 5-15 years, and adults aged 15+ years).....	16
Anaemia prevalence (all ages).....	16
Anaemia prevalence (children under 5 years, 5-15 years, and adults aged 15+ years).....	16
Ramachandra 1951.....	17
Malaria prevalence (all ages).....	17
Supplementary item 5 – Studies excluded at full-text screen.....	18
Supplementary item 6 – Characteristics of included studies	161
Charlwood et al.	161

Curtis et al.....	165
Loha et al.	172
Misra et al.....	181
Rowland et al.....	186
Gunasekaran et al.....	193
Guyatt et al.....	198
Mashauri et al.....	203
Ramachandra.....	210
Supplementary item 7 – Support for risk of bias judgments	215
Randomised controlled trials	215
Risk of Bias Non-randomised Studies	256
Supplementary item 8 – Subgroup analyses.....	280
Incidence of malaria (all ages; RCTs) – subgrouped by background nets (low coverage)	280
Incidence of malaria (all ages; RCTs) – subgrouped by susceptibility to IRS compound	280
Incidence of malaria (all ages; RCTs) – subgrouped by setting	281
Incidence of malaria (all ages; RCTs) – subgrouped by insecticide class.....	281
Incidence of malaria (all ages; RCTs) – subgrouped by transmission setting.....	282
Prevalence of malaria (all ages; non-randomised studies) – subgrouped by susceptibility to IRS compound	282
Prevalence of malaria (all ages; non-randomised studies) – subgrouped by transmission setting....	283
Prevalence of malaria (all ages; non-randomised studies) – subgrouped by insecticide class.....	283
Supplementary item 9 – ICEMAN assessments for subgroup analyses	284
Randomised controlled trials	284
ICEMAN: Insecticide class.....	284
ICEMAN: Background nets.....	287
ICEMAN: Susceptibility	290
ICEMAN: Setting	293
ICEMAN: Transmission setting	296
Non-randomised studies	299
ICEMAN: Insecticide class.....	299
ICEMAN: Susceptibility to IRS.....	302
ICEMAN: Transmission level.....	305
Supplementary item 10 – Sensitivity analyses.....	308
Inflated standard error	308
Incidence of malaria (all ages).....	308
Prevalence of malaria (all ages).....	311

Prevalence of anaemia (children under 5 years).....	313
Risk of bias.....	314
Incidence of malaria (all ages).....	314
Prevalence of anaemia (children under 5 years).....	314

Supplementary item 1 – Deviations from protocol

1. Review question 2: In areas with ongoing malaria transmission, what are the relative benefits and harms of selective (or partial) residual insecticide surface treatment (such as where surfaces of interior walls are partially treated) compared with no residual insecticide surface treatment, full residual insecticide surface treatment, or other treatments/strategies to prevent malaria in adults and children? This was not addressed as no studies identified during screening.
2. Review question 3: In areas with ongoing malaria transmission, what are the relative benefits and harms of outdoor residual surface treatment (either stand alone or with concomitant treatment) compared with no outdoor residual surface treatment or other treatments/strategies to prevent malaria in adults and children? This was not addressed as no studies identified during screening.
3. The following subgroups were specified in the protocol but were not conducted for the stated reasons:
 - a. Deployment strategy of intervention applied e.g. number of rounds of spraying/treatment per year/season. This was not addressed as this was too varied.
 - b. Coverage of intervention (Low coverage ($\leq 50\%$) v. Moderate coverage (51-79%) v. High coverage ($\geq 80\%$)). This was not reported in many studies and all that were reported had high coverage.
 - c. Target sites, mode of action, and duration required to produce such effect(s). This was not addressed as too varied and underreported.
 - d. Dwelling material and/or type (e.g., fixed versus temporary/ humanitarian structures). This was not assessed as too varied.
 - e. Level of household coverage (i.e. different amounts of 'partial' treatment or label indications given by the manufacturer (bedrooms only vs all house; 1 metre from the floor vs full, 10cm from the ceiling vs full)). This was not assessed as only reported in one study.
 - f. Coverage of other background interventions (Low coverage v. Moderate coverage v. High coverage). If net coverage assessed as house-holds with ≥ 1 net: (low $\leq 50\%$; moderate 51%-79%; high $\geq 80\%$); If net coverage assessed as house-holds with ≥ 1 net per two people: (low $\leq 20\%$, moderate 21- 49%, high $\geq 50\%$). If net coverage assessed as population access: (low $\leq 40\%$; moderate 41%-59%; high $\geq 60\%$). This was only reported in one study.
 - g. Vector species. This was not assessed as too varied.
 - h. Human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, re-plastering of houses). This was not assessed as underreported.
 - i. Time from implementation. This was not assessed as too varied.
 - j. Population demographics e.g., sex or social-economic status or ethnicity. This was not assessed as underreported.
4. Sensitivity analyses was originally planned conducted to analyse the following (below). However, as all the included studies were at high risk of bias (RCTs) or serious risk of bias (non-randomised studies) it was unnecessary.
5. The following outcomes were not included in the GRADE evidence profiles as this would require greater than seven outcomes and is thus not recommended.
 - a. Prevalence of anaemia

6. The following outcomes were not included in the GRADE evidence profiles and systematic review due to a lack of available data.
 - a. Malaria mortality
7. A meta-analysis was planned for non-randomised studies however, these were narratively synthesised due to drastically varied time points for follow-up.
8. ICEMAN was used to assess credibility of subgroup analyses. This was not specified in the protocol.

Supplementary item 2 – Search strategies

Databases	Cochrane Library, MEDLINE (Ovid), Embase (Elsevier), CINAHL with Full Text (EBSCO), Scopus, WHO Global Index Medicus
Registries	ClinicalTrials.gov, ISRCTN Registry, WHO ICTRP
Date Run	14th October 2021
Total Results	6233
Duplicates Removed	3254
Unique Results	2979
Searcher(s)	Carrie Price, MLS, Health Professions Librarian, Towson University, Towson, Maryland, USA Jennifer Stone, JBI Research Fellow

Line	Ovid MEDLINE	Results
1	exp malaria/	
2	(black water fever OR black water fevers OR blackwater fever OR blackwater fevers OR malaria* OR marsh fever OR marsh fevers OR paludism OR plasmodia OR plasmodiosis OR plasmodium OR plasmodiums OR remittent fever OR remittent fevers OR swamp fever OR swamp fevers).mp.	
3	1 OR 2	
4	(indoor OR in door OR outdoor OR out door OR indoors OR outdoors OR in doors OR out doors OR interior OR exterior OR interiors OR exteriors OR inside OR outside OR insides OR outsides).mp.	
5	(chair OR chairs OR counter* OR door OR doorknob* OR doors OR dwelling OR dwellings OR furniture* OR home OR homes OR homestead OR homesteads OR house OR houses OR household OR households OR hut OR huts OR residence OR residences OR paint OR paints OR plaster* OR shelf OR shelves OR surface OR surfaces OR table OR tables OR tabletop OR tabletops OR wall OR walls OR residual*).mp.	
6	(additive OR additives OR aerosol* OR fumigant* OR fumigat* OR IRS OR spray* OR treatment OR treatments).mp.	
7	4 AND 5 AND 6	
8	3 AND 7	1443

Line	Embase	Results
1	'malaria'/exp	
2	('black water fever' OR 'black water fevers' OR 'blackwater fever' OR 'blackwater fevers' OR malaria* OR 'marsh fever' OR 'marsh fevers' OR 'paludism' OR 'plasmodia' OR 'plasmodiosis' OR 'plasmodium' OR 'plasmodiums' OR 'remittent fever' OR 'remittent fevers' OR 'swamp fever' OR 'swamp fevers'):ti,ab,kw	
3	1 OR 2	
4	('indoor' OR 'in door' OR 'outdoor OR 'out door' OR 'indoors' OR 'outdoors' OR 'in doors' OR 'out doors' OR 'interior' OR 'exterior' OR 'interiors' OR 'exteriors' OR 'inside' OR 'outside' OR 'insides' OR 'outsides'):ti,ab,kw	
5	('chair' OR 'chairs' OR counter* OR 'door' OR doorknob* OR 'doors' OR 'dwelling' OR 'dwellings' OR furniture* OR 'home' OR 'homes' OR 'homestead' OR 'homesteads' OR 'house' OR 'houses' OR 'household' OR 'households' OR 'hut' OR 'huts' OR 'residence' OR 'residences' OR 'paint' OR 'paints' OR 'plaster*' OR 'shelf' OR 'shelves' OR 'surface' OR 'surfaces' OR 'table' OR 'tables' OR 'tabletop' OR 'tabletops' OR 'wall' OR 'walls' OR residual*):ti,ab,kw	
6	(additive' OR 'additives' OR aerosol* OR fumigant* OR fumigat* OR 'IRS' OR spray* OR 'treatment' OR 'treatments'):ti,ab,kw	
7	4 AND 5 AND 6	
8	'indoor residual spraying'/exp	
9	7 OR 8	
10	3 AND 9	2288

Line	Cochrane Library	Results
1	[mh "malaria"]	
2	("black water fever" OR "black water fevers" OR "blackwater fever" OR "blackwater fevers" OR "malaria*" OR "marsh fever" OR "marsh fevers" OR "paludism" OR "plasmodia" OR "plasmodiosis" OR "plasmodium" OR "plasmodiums" OR "remittent fever" OR "remittent fevers" OR "swamp fever" OR "swamp fevers"):ti,ab,kw	
3	#1 OR #2	
4	("indoor" OR "in door" OR "outdoor" OR "out door" OR "indoors" OR "outdoors" OR "in doors" OR "out doors" OR "interior" OR "exterior" OR "interiors" OR "exteriors" OR "inside" OR "outside" OR "insides" OR "outsides"):ti,ab,kw	

5	("chair" OR "chairs" OR counter* OR "door" OR doorknob* OR "doors" OR "dwelling" OR "dwellings" OR furniture* OR "home" OR "homes" OR "homestead" OR "homesteads" OR "house" OR "houses" OR "household" OR "households" OR "hut" OR "huts" OR "residence" OR "residences" OR "paint" OR "paints" OR plaster* OR "shelf" OR "shelves" OR "surface" OR "surfaces" OR "table" OR "tables" OR "tabletop" OR "tabletops" OR "wall" OR "walls" OR residual*):ti,ab,kw	
6	("additive" OR "additives" OR aerosol* OR fumigant* OR fumigat* OR "IRS" OR spray* OR "treatment" OR "treatments"):ti,ab,kw	
7	#4 AND #5 AND #6	
8	#3 AND #7	205

Line	Scopus (use advanced document search)	Results
1	TITLE-ABS-KEY({black water fever} OR {black water fevers} OR {blackwater fever} OR {blackwater fevers} OR malaria* OR {marsh fever} OR {marsh fevers} OR {paludism} OR {plasmodia} OR {plasmodiosis} OR {plasmodium} OR {plasmodiums} OR {remittent fever} OR {remittent fevers} OR {swamp fever} OR {swamp fevers})	
2	TITLE-ABS-KEY ({indoor} OR {in door} OR {outdoor} OR {out door} OR {indoors} OR {outdoors} OR {in doors} OR {out doors} OR {interior} OR {exterior} OR {interiors} OR {exteriors} OR {inside} OR {outside} OR {insides} OR {outsides})	
3	TITLE-ABS-KEY ({chair} OR {chairs} OR counter* OR {door} OR doorknob* OR ⁵¹ OR {dwelling} OR {dwellings} OR furniture* OR ³⁹ OR {homes} OR {homestead} OR {homesteads} OR {house} OR {houses} OR {household} OR {households} OR {hut} OR ⁵² OR {residence} OR {residences} OR {paint} OR {paints} OR plaster* OR {shelf} OR {shelves} OR {surface} OR {surfaces} OR {table} OR {tables} OR {tabletop} OR {tabletops} OR ¹⁶ OR {walls} OR residual*)	
4	TITLE-ABS-KEY ({additive} OR {additives} OR aerosol* OR fumigant* OR fumigat* OR {IRS} OR spray* OR {treatment} OR {treatments})	
5	#2 AND #3 AND #4	
6	#1 AND #5	1774

Line	CINAHL with full text	Results
1	MH "malaria"	
2	("black water fever" OR "black water fevers" OR "blackwater fever" OR "blackwater fevers" OR malaria* OR "marsh fever" OR "marsh fevers" OR "paludism" OR "plasmodia" OR "plasmodiosis" OR "plasmodium" OR	

	"plasmodiums" OR "remittent fever" OR "remittent fevers" OR "swamp fever" OR "swamp fevers")	
3	1 OR 2	
4	("indoor" OR "in door" OR "outdoor" OR "out door" OR "indoors" OR "outdoors" OR "in doors" OR "out doors" OR "interior" OR "exterior" OR "interiors" OR "exteriors" OR "inside" OR "outside" OR "insides" OR "outsides")	
5	("chair" OR "chairs" OR counter* OR "door" OR doorknob* OR "doors" OR "dwelling" OR "dwellings" OR furniture* OR "home" OR "homes" OR "homestead" OR "homesteads" OR "house" OR "houses" OR "household" OR "households" OR "hut" OR "huts" OR "residence" OR "residences" OR "paint" OR "paints" OR plaster* OR "shelf" OR "shelves" OR "surface" OR "surfaces" OR "table" OR "tables" OR "tabletop" OR "tabletops" OR "wall" OR "walls" OR residual*)	
6	("additive" OR "additives" OR aerosol* OR fumigant* OR fumigat* OR "IRS" OR spray* OR "treatment" OR "treatments")	
7	4 AND 5 AND 6	
8	3 AND 7	118

Line	WHO Global Index Medicus (use advanced search) https://pesquisa.bvsalud.org/gim/advanced/?lang=en	Results
1	(tw:(("black water fever" OR "black water fevers" OR "blackwater fever" OR "blackwater fevers" OR malaria* OR "marsh fever" OR "marsh fevers" OR "paludism" OR "plasmodia" OR "plasmodiosis" OR "plasmodium" OR "plasmodiums" OR "remittent fever" OR "remittent fevers" OR "swamp fever" OR "swamp fevers"))) AND (tw:("indoor" OR "in door" OR "outdoor" OR "out door" OR "indoors" OR "outdoors" OR "in doors" OR "out doors" OR "interior" OR "exterior" OR "interiors" OR "exteriors" OR "inside" OR "outside" OR "insides" OR "outsides") AND ("chair" OR "chairs" OR counter* OR "door" OR doorknob* OR "doors" OR "dwelling" OR "dwellings" OR furniture* OR "home" OR "homes" OR "homestead" OR "homesteads" OR "house" OR "houses" OR "household" OR "households" OR "hut" OR "huts" OR "residence" OR "residences" OR "paint" OR "paints" OR plaster* OR "shelf" OR "shelves" OR "surface" OR "surfaces" OR "table" OR "tables" OR "tabletop" OR "tabletops" OR "wall" OR "walls" OR residual*) AND ("additive" OR "additives" OR aerosol* OR fumigant* OR fumigat* OR "IRS" OR spray* OR "treatment" OR "treatments"))))	79

Other Terms: spraying

Condition or disease: Malaria

Other Terms: IRS

Condition or disease: Malaria

Other terms: residual

TOTAL 64

ISRCTN registry Results

Malaria 244

WHO ICTRP Results

<https://trialssearch.who.int/Default.aspx>

Malaria AND spraying

Malaria AND IRS

Malaria AND residual

TOTAL 37

Supplementary item 3 – Data extraction tool

Study:
DESIGN
Lead Author
Publication year
Trial name
Other reports of this study (i.e., author, year, title, doi)
Time period study was conducted
Design
Eligibility criteria of participants
Recruitment methods and rate
Unit of allocation
Number of units
Method of Randomization/ matching or other
Number of clusters per arm
Adjustment for clustering
Cluster details (including buffer sizes between clusters, other indication of dilution effects)
Total trial participants per group/arm (including number of exclusions and reasons)
Outcomes assessed
SETTING
Country
Site/s (town/settlements/region)
Peak transmission season
Baseline malaria endemicity/ level of transmission
Study site (e.g., rural/ urban/ peri-urban/ level of urbanicity)
Vector species and vector profile details (i.e., behaviours, resistance profile/ susceptibility tests, parity, sporozoite rates and all other reported information)
Malaria species
PARTICIPANTS (those who received the intervention and on whom impact was measured)
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants who received the intervention
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants

on whom the impact was measured.
Frequency of travel in the last month
INTERVENTION (Repeat if multiple arms)
Insecticide brand, type, formulation (including active ingredient), dose, duration (this includes timing and frequency of application)
Insecticide application method(s) and strategy (e.g., spray, paint, treated materials, wallpaper)
Personnel applying the intervention
Target area (inside/outside)
How the coverage of the intervention was measured
Coverage of household (full, selective/partial)
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction
Length of intervention, including number of rounds of spraying/application per year/season
Type of dwelling (e.g., fixed or temporary) and construction material of surfaces insecticides applied to (e.g., cement, brick or mud walls, canvas etc)
Time to start intervention after index case
Human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, re-plastering of houses)
COMPARISON
Details of Comparison
How the coverage of the comparison was measured
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction for the comparison
Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period and other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)
OUTCOME 1

Name
Definition/ assessment metric
Events
Total (or unit time)
Time of outcome assessment
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)
Effect type
COSTS
Event/raw costs
Results
Time of cost assessment
Resources needed/ used
ADDITIONAL DATA
Unintended benefits
Harms
Other contextual information present/measured/reported) (feasibility, acceptability, preferences/values, impact on equity)
Entomological outcomes measured (list)
Other
Source of funding
Possible conflicts of interest

Supplementary item 4 – Calculations and data imputations

Charlwood et al. 2001

Malaria incidence (all ages and children under 5 years)

- No person years reported just number of cases and IRR.
- IRR from report used for this analysis.

All-cause mortality

- No person years reported just number of cases and IRR.
- IRR from report used for this analysis.
- There were 35 child deaths in IRS camp, 41 in control camps. There were no deaths among children in the IRS camps, compared with 6 deaths in control camps.
- Zero deaths under 5 years and therefore confidence intervals could not be computed.

Loha et al. 2019

Malaria incidence

- Authors have reported the number of malaria cases and person years.
- IRR was calculated using malaria cases and person years, entered into StatsDirect.
- Data reported for 4 different time points. We selected weeks 1-26.
 - Weeks: 1-26
 - Weeks, 27-52
 - Weeks 53-79
 - Weeks 79-121

Anaemia prevalence

- Authors have reported the number of anaemia cases and expressed this as a prevalence percentage. Have not provided total N.
 - Total N was back calculated, based on the values reported. For each group.
 - (e.g. 29.1% = 199 [as reported], therefore 199 is 29.1% of 683.8487973. This is rounded to the nearest whole number of 684 – IRS)
 - (e.g. 28.3% = 223 [as reported], therefore 223 is 28.3% of 787.98586. This is rounded to the nearest whole number of 788 – Control). This was entered into StatsDirect.
- Data reported the data for 3 different time points (December 2014, 2015 and 2016 surveys). We selected the first year, 2014.

Misra et al. 1999

Malaria incidence

- Authors reported cases over 1000 person-years.
- IRR was calculated using malaria cases and person years, entered into Stats Direct.

Rowland et al. 2000

Malaria incidence

- Authors reported cases per 1000 person-years.
- IRR was calculated using malaria cases and person years, entered into Stats Direct

- Data reported for IRS (with WP) and IRS (with SC) against the same untreated group. For the analysis we selected the data for IRS (with WP) based on guidance by WHO.
- Data reported for *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax*. For the analysis we have selected the data for *P. falciparum* based on guidance by WHO.

Malaria prevalence (children 5-15 years)

- Authors reported prevalence data against the total slides examined.
- Daw data was imputed as below and entered into StatsDirect.
 - 3.9% of 831 = 1.95 = 32.409 = 32 (rounded to nearest whole number) (control group)
 - 0.6% of 891 = 3.051 = 5.346 = 5 (rounded to nearest whole number) (treatment group)
- Data reported for IRS (with WP) and IRS (with SC) against the same untreated group. For the analysis we selected the data for IRS (with WP) based on guidance by WHO.
- Data reported for *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax*. For the analysis we have selected the data for *P. falciparum* based on guidance by WHO.

Curtis et al. 1998

Malaria prevalence (children under 6 years; active case detection)

- Data reported as percentages of total that responded with a parasite density of >4000/ul. This was imputed as below and entered into StatsDirect.
 - 25.6% of 164 = 41.984 = 42 (rounded to nearest full number) (Spray)
 - 27% of 259 = 69.93 = 70 (rounded to nearest full number) (Control)
- Data also reported for parasite density >16000/ul and >4000/ul + febrile symptoms. For the analysis we have selected data for parasites >4000/ul.
- The authors have reported the data for 4 different time points at each quarter of 1996 (Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4). We have selected Q1 for the analysis.

Malaria prevalence (children over 6 years; passive case detection)

- Data reported as percentages of total that responded with a parasite density of >4000/ul. This was imputed as below and entered into StatsDirect.
 - 39.6% of 527 = 208.692 = 209 (rounded to nearest full number) (Spray)
 - 40.6% of 503 = 181.1187 = 181 (rounded to nearest full number) (Control)
- Data reported for parasite density >16000/ul and >4000/ul + febrile symptoms. For the analysis we have selected data for parasites >4000/ul.
- Data reported for 2 different time points, the first and last quarter of 1996 combined (Q1 + Q2, Q3 + Q4). We have selected Q1+Q2 for the analysis.

Anaemia prevalence (children under 6 years; active case detection)

- The Authors reported their data as percentages of total that responded with Hb concentrations of <8g/dl. This was imputed as below and entered into StatsDirect.
 - 15.2% of 164 = 24.928 = 25 (rounded to nearest full number) (Spray)
 - 23.6% of 259 = 61.123 = 62 (rounded to nearest full number) (Control)
- The authors have reported the data for 4 different time points at each quarter of 1996 (Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4). We have selected Q1 for the analysis.

Gunasekaran et al. 2005

Malaria prevalence (all ages)

- Smears and prevalence reported for IRS and control in each village.

- Prevalence was back calculated to get the denominator. Villages were combined. Data entered into StatsDirect to produce RR.
 - Malkangiri: Intervention: 1540 (smears collected) with SPR of 12.5%=192.5 positive; Control: 265 (smears collected) with SPR of 54.7% = 145 positive
 - Boipariguda: Intervention: 1525 (smears collected) with SPR of 14.4% = 220 positive; Control: 343 (smears collected) with SPR of 35.3% = 122 positive

Guyatt et al. 2005

Malaria prevalence (all ages)

- Prevalence, events, and total numbers were reported (for all ages).
- RR was calculated using the events and total numbers, entered into StatsDirect

Malaria prevalence (children under 5 years, 5-15 years, and adults aged 15+ years)

- Prevalence, events, and total numbers were reported (stratified by age).
- RR was calculated using the events and total numbers, entered into StatsDirect

Mashauri et al. 2013

Malaria prevalence (all ages)

- Prevalence and totals were provided for overall population (not stratified by age).
- RR was calculated by back calculating the numbers from prevalence. There were entered into StatsDirect.
- Data reported for 2 different time points:
 - 1: December 2007 - 6-months post first IRS round
 - 2: August 2008 - 2 years post second IRS round. We selected time point 1, December 2007 for the analysis.

Malaria prevalence (children under 5 years, 5-15 years, and adults aged 15+ years)

- Prevalence and totals were provided for overall population (stratified by age).
- RR was calculated by back calculating the numbers from prevalence. There were entered into StatsDirect.
- Data reported for 2 different time points:
 - 1: December 2007 - 6-months post first IRS round
 - 2: August 2008 - 2 years post second IRS round. We selected time point 1, December 2007 for the analysis.

Anaemia prevalence (all ages)

- Anemia was defined as Hb levels < 8 g/dL.
- Prevalence and totals were provided for overall population (not stratified by age).
- RR was calculated by back calculating the numbers from prevalence. There were entered into StatsDirect.
- Data reported for 2 different time points:
 - 1: December 2007 - 6-months post first IRS round
 - 2: August 2008 - 2 years post second IRS round. We selected time point 1, December 2007 for the analysis.

Anaemia prevalence (children under 5 years, 5-15 years, and adults aged 15+ years)

- Anemia was defined as Hb levels < 8 g/dL.
- Prevalence and totals were provided for overall population (stratified by age).

- RR was calculated by back calculating the numbers from prevalence. There were entered into StatsDirect.
- Data reported for 2 different time points:
 - 1: December 2007 - 6-months post first IRS round
 - 2: August 2008 - 2 years post second IRS round. We selected time point 1, December 2007 for the analysis.

Ramachandra 1951

Malaria prevalence (all ages)

- Prevalence, events, and total were provided.
- RR was calculated using events and total, entered into StatsDirect for this analysis.

Supplementary item 5 – Studies excluded at full-text screen

Study ID	Authors	Published Year	Title	Journal	Notes
1	{GlaxoSmithKline, 2013 #30}	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
2	{Path, 2019 #9}	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
3	{Path, 2019 #9} Duplicated reference in covidence - not picked up till FT	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
4	{Path, 2019 #9} Duplicated reference in covidence - not picked up till FT	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
5	{Path, 2022 #7}	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
6	{Path, 2022 #7} (duplicated from covidence)	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
7	{Radboud, 2012 #21}	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
8	A cluster randomized trial to compare bendiocarb and deltamethrin for indoor residual spraying on bioko island, equatorial guinea	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
9	A, Raeisi; M.R, Abai; K, Akbarzadeh; M, Nateghpour; M, Sartipi; A, Hassanzehi; N, Shahbakhsh; L, Faraji;	2010	Residual effects of deltamethrin WG 25% as a new formulation on different surfaces against anopheles stephensi, in Southeastern Iran	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only

	F, Nikpour; M, Mashayekhi				
10	AÃƒkpon, R.	2014	Malaria vector control	International journal of infectious diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
11	AÃƒkpon, R. Y.; Padonou, G.; Dagnon, F.; OssÃƒ, R.; Ogouyemi Hounto, A.; Tokponon, F.; AÃƒkpon, G.; Lyikirenga, L.; AkogbÃƒto, M.	2020	Upsurge of malaria transmission after indoor residual spraying withdrawal in Atacora region in Benin, West Africa	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
12	AÃƒkpon, R.; Padonou, G.; Dagnon, F.; OssÃƒ, R.; Kouletio, M.; Akogbeto, M. C.	2018	Lessons learned from monitoring indoor residual spraying (IRS) in atacora district, benin, 2011-2016	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
13	AÃƒkpon, R.; SÃƒzonlin, M.; Tokponon, F.; OkÃƒ, M.; Oussou, O.; OkÃƒ-Agbo, F.; Beach, R.; AkogbÃƒto, M.	2014	Good performances but short lasting efficacy of Actellic 50 EC Indoor Residual Spraying (IRS) on malaria transmission in Benin, West Africa	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
14	Abai, M. R.; Vatandoost, H.; Dorzadeh, H.; Shayeghi, M.; Hanafi-Bojd, A. A.; Raeisi, A.	2021	Bioefficacy of bendiocarb WP80 in vector-borne and zoonotic diseases areas in borderline of Iran and Pakistan	Toxicology Research	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
15	Abate, A.; Degarege, A.; Erko, B.	2013	Community knowledge, attitude and practice about malaria in a low endemic setting of Shewa Robit Town, northeastern Ethiopia	BMC Public Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
16	Abdalla, H.; Wilding, C. S.; Nardini, L.; Pignatelli, P.; Koekemoer, L. L.; Ranson, H.; Coetzee, M.	2014	Insecticide resistance in Anopheles arabiensis in Sudan: Temporal trends and underlying mechanisms	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only

17	Abeku, T. A.; Helinski, M. E. H.; Kirby, M. J.; Kefyalew, T.; Awano, T.; Batisso, E.; Tesfaye, G.; Ssekitooleko, J.; Nicholas, S.; Erdmanis, L.; Nalwoga, A.; Bass, C.; Cose, S.; Assefa, A.; Kebede, Z.; Habte, T.; Katamba, V.; Nuwa, A.; Bakeera-Ssali, S.; Akiror, S. C.; Kyomuhagi, I.; Tekalegne, A.; Magumba, G.; Meek, S. R.	2015	Monitoring changes in malaria epidemiology and effectiveness of interventions in Ethiopia and Uganda: Beyond Garki Project baseline survey	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
18	Abeku, T. A.; Helinski, M. E. H.; Kirby, M. J.; Ssekitooleko, J.; Bass, C.; Kyomuhangi, I.; Okia, M.; Magumba, G.; Meek, S. R.	2017	Insecticide resistance patterns in Uganda and the effect of indoor residual spraying with bendiocarb on kdr L1014S frequencies in Anopheles gambiae s.s	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
19	Abeku, T. A.; Helinski, M. E.; Kyomuhangi, I.; Ssekitooleko, J.; Magumba, G.; Bass, C.; Meek, S. R.	2016	Indoor residual spraying for malaria control using bendiocarb reduces KDR l1014S homozygote frequency in anopheles gambiae S.S	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
20	Abeku, T. A.; Helinski, M.; Ssekitooleko, J.; Kirby, M. J.; Kyomuhangi, I.; Magumba, G.; Meek, S. R.	2014	Variations in malaria epidemiology in relation to vector control coverage in nine districts of Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
21	Abilio, Ana P.; Kleinschmidt, Immo; Rehman, Andrea M.; Cuamba, Nelson; Ramdeen, Varsha; Mthembu, David S.; Coetzer, Sarel; Maharaj, Rajendra; Wilding, Craig S.; Steven, Andrew; Coleman, Marlize; Hemingway, Janet; Coleman, Michael	2011	The emergence of insecticide resistance in central Mozambique and potential threat to the successful indoor residual spraying malaria control programme	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

22	Abogan, A.	2017	Data-driven approaches for finer temporal and spatial resolution coverage and progress estimates for indoor residual spraying (IRS) campaigns in Chobe district, Botswana	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
23	Abogan, A.; Berlin, E.; Shirreff, G.; Senyatso, R.; Jamu, S.; Mosweunyane, T.	2018	Defining the boundaries of local malaria transmission to inform targeted response strategies in the remaining hotspots in Okavango, NGAMI and Chobe malaria endemic districts of Botswana	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
24	Abong'o, B. O.; Bayoh, N. M.; Ouma, C.; Walker, E. D.; Ombok, M.; Vulule, J.; Gimnig, J.	2011	Impacts of insecticide-treated bednets (ITNS) and indoor residual spraying (IRS) on host selection pattern by <i>Anopheles gambiae</i> S.S., <i>An. arabiensis</i> and <i>An. funestus</i> in Western Kenya	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
25	Abong'o, B.; Gimnig, J. E.; Torr, S. J.; Longman, B.; Omoke, D.; Muchoki, M.; Ter Kuile, F.; Ochomo, E.; Munga, S.; Samuels, A. M.; Njagi, K.; Maas, J.; Perry, R. T.; Fornadel, C.; Donnelly, M. J.; Oxborough, R. M.	2020	Impact of indoor residual spraying with pirimiphos-methyl (Actellic 300CS) on entomological indicators of transmission and malaria case burden in Migori County, western Kenya	Scientific reports	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
26	Abong'o, B.; Omoke, D.; Ochomo, E.; Bayoh, N.; Njangi, K.; Karuki, S.; Ejersa, W.; Perry, R.; Norris, L.; Longman, B.; Gimnig, J.; Oxborough, R.	2017	The impact of indoor residual spraying (IRS) with pirimiphos-methyl on entomological indices in a malaria hyperendemic region of western Kenya	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
27	Aboobakar, S.; Tatarsky, A.; Cohen, J. M.; Bheecarry, A.; Boolaky, P.; Gopee, N.; Moonasar, D.; Phillips, A. A.; Kahn, J.	2012	Eliminating malaria and preventing its reintroduction: The Mauritius case study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

	G.; Moonen, B.; Smith, D. L.; Sabot, O.				
28	Abraham, M.; Massebo, F.; LindtjÄ, rn, B.	2017	High entomological inoculation rate of malaria vectors in area of high coverage of interventions in southwest Ethiopia: Implication for residual malaria transmission	Parasite Epidemiology and Control	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
29	Abu, O.; Ignatius Ayogu, I.	2021	An Optimal Control Strategy for a Malaria Model	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
30	Abuaku, B.; Ahorlu, C.; Psychas, P.; Ricks, P.; Oppong, S.; Mensah, S.; Sackey, W.; Koram, K. A.	2018	Impact of indoor residual spraying on malaria parasitaemia in the Bunkpurugu-Yunyoo District in northern Ghana 11 Medical and Health Sciences 1117 Public Health and Health Services	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
31	Abuaku, B.; Ahorlu, C.; Ricks, P.; Psychas, P.; Mumba, P.; Mensah, D.; Mensah, S.; Sackey, W.; Bhattarai, A.; Koram, K.	2014	Longitudinal impact of indoor residual spraying (IRS) on malaria parasitaemia in northern Ghana	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
32	Abuaku, B.; Psychas, P.; Ricks, P.; Ahorlu, C.; Mumba, P.; Mensah, D.; Mensah, S.; Sackey, W.; Oppong, S.; Koram, K.	2015	Impact of one vs. Two rounds of annual indoor residual spraying (IRS) on malaria parasitaemia in children in Northern Ghana	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
33	Abuaku, B.; Yaw Peprah, N.; Ahorlu, C.; Mohammed, W.; Quashie, N.; Asamoah, A.; Addo, C.; Amoako, E. O.; Malm, K.; Bart-Plange, C.; Koram, K.	2017	Tracking malaria slide positivity rates in 30 sentinel sites across Ghana	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
34	Abuaku, Benjamin; Ahorlu, Collins; Psychas, Paul; Ricks, Philip; Oppong, Samuel; Mensah, Sedzro; Sackey,	2018	Impact of indoor residual spraying on malaria parasitaemia in the Bunkpurugu-Yunyoo District in northern Ghana	Parasites & vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	William; Koram, Kwadwo A.				
35	Acheson, E. S.; Kerr, J. T.	2018	Nets versus spraying: A spatial modelling approach reveals indoor residual spraying targets Anopheles mosquito habitats better than mosquito nets in Tanzania	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
36	Adeniji, E.; Asante, K. P.; Boahen, O.; CompaorÃ©, G.; Coulibaly, B.; Kaali, S.; Kabore, Y.; Lamy, M.; Lusingu, J.; Malabeja, A.; Mens, P.; Orsini, M.; Otieno, L.; Otieno, W.; Owusu-Agyei, S.; Oyieko, J.; PirÃ§on, J. Y.; Praet, N.; Roman, F.; Sie, A.; Sing'oei, V.; Sirima, S. B.; Sylla, K.; Tine, R.; Tiono, A. B.; Tivura, M.; Usuf, E.; WÃ©ry, S.	2020	Estimating annual fluctuations in malaria transmission intensity and in the use of malaria control interventions in five sub-saharan African countries	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
37	Adeniran, T. T.; Brown, C. A.; Rogers, W.; Wilson, M. D.; Appawu, M. A.; Boakye, D. A.	2009	Susceptibility status of Anopheles gambiae sensu stricto (Diptera: Culicidae) to pyrethroid and carbamate insecticides in the Greater Accra region of Ghana, West Africa	International Journal of Tropical Insect Science	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
38	Adhikari, S. R.; Sapkota, V. P.; Thapa, A. K.; Acharya, Y.	2019	Understanding challenges to malaria elimination in Nepal: A qualitative study with an embedded capacity-building exercise	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
39	Admasu, K.; Jima, D.; Assefa, A.; Solomon, H.; Yeshiwondim, A.; Kebede, Z.; Dissanayake, G.; Teka, H.; Chibsa, S.; Florey, L.; Taylor, C.; Hwang, J.; Malone, J.; Hershey, C.; Nielsen,	2013	The impact of malaria control interventions in Ethiopia, 2000-2012	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	C.; Berhane, Y.; Kebede, A.				
40	Afoakwah, Clifford; Deng, Xin; Onur, Ilke	2018	Malaria infection among children under-five: the use of large-scale interventions in Ghana	BMC Public Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
41	Afonne, C.; Ajayi, I. O.; Hannah, D. A.; Falade, C. O.	2015	Household characteristics associated with malaria-intestinal helminths co-infections among rural dwellers the Southwest, Nigeria	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
42	Agaba, B. B.; Opigo, J.; Kassahun, B.; Sebikari, G.; Katureebe, C.; Mbaka, P.; Kagwire, F.; Rubahika, D.; Okullo, A.; Rutazaana, D.; Walusimbi, D.; Gasasira, A.	2016	Malaria upsurge following withdrawal of indoor residual spraying in northern Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
43	Agossa, F. R.; AÃkpon, R.; AzondÃkon, R.; Govoetchan, R.; Padonnou, G. G.; Oussou, O.; OkÃ-Agbo, F.; AkogbÃto, M. C.	2014	Efficacy of various insecticides recommended for indoor residual spraying: Pirimiphos methyl, potential alternative to bendiocarb for pyrethroid resistance management in Benin, West Africa	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
44	Agossa, F. R.; Gnanguenon, V.; Anagonou, R.; Azondekon, R.; AÃzoun, N.; Sovi, A.; OkÃ-Agbo, F.; SÃzonlin, M.; AkogbÃto, M. C.	2015	Impact of insecticide resistance on the effectiveness of pyrethroid-based malaria vectors control tools in Benin: Decreased toxicity and repellent effect	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
45	Agossa, F. R.; Padonou, G. G.; Fassinou, A. J. Y. H.; Odjo, E. M.; Akuoko, O. K.; Salako, A.; Koukpo, Z. C.; Nwangwu, U. C.; Akinro, B.; Sezonlin, M.; Akogbeto, M. C.	2018	Small-scale field evaluation of the efficacy and residual effect of Fludora® Fusion (mixture of clothianidin and deltamethrin) against susceptible and resistant Anopheles gambiae populations from Benin, West Africa	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only

46	Agossa, F. R.; Padonou, G. G.; Koukpo, C. Z.; Zola-Sahossi, J.; Azondekon, R.; Akuoko, O. K.; Ahoga, J.; N'Dombidje, B.; Akinro, B.; Fassinou, A. J. Y. H.; Sezonlin, M.; Akogbeto, M. C.	2018	Efficacy of a novel mode of action of an indoor residual spraying product, SumiShield® 50WG against susceptible and resistant populations of <i>Anopheles gambiae</i> (s.l.) in Benin, West Africa	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
47	Agossa, Fiacre R.; Padonou, Gil G.; Fassinou, Arsene Jacques Y. H.; Odjo, Esdras M.; Akuoko, Osei K.; Salako, Albert; Koukpo, Zinsou C.; Nwangwu, Udoka C.; Akinro, Bruno; Sezonlin, Michel; Akogbeto, Martin C.	2018	Small-scale field evaluation of the efficacy and residual effect of Fludora R Fusion (mixture of clothianidin and deltamethrin) against susceptible and resistant <i>Anopheles gambiae</i> populations from Benin, West Africa	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
48	Agossa, Fiacre R.; Padonou, Gil G.; Koukpo, Come Z.; Zola-Sahossi, Jacques; Azondekon, Roseric; Akuoko, Osei K.; Ahoga, Juniace; N'Dombidje, Boris; Akinro, Bruno; Fassinou, Arsene Jacques Y. H.; Sezonlin, Michel; Akogbeto, Martin C.	2018	Efficacy of a novel mode of action of an indoor residual spraying product, SumiShield R 50WG against susceptible and resistant populations of <i>Anopheles gambiae</i> (s.l.) in Benin, West Africa	Parasites & vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
49	Agumba, S. O.	2019	Diagnostic dose determination and efficacy of chlorfenapyr and clothianidin insecticides against <i>Anopheles malaria</i> vector populations of western Kenya	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
50	Agumba, S.; Gimnig, J. E.; Ogonda, L.; Ombok, M.; Kosgei, J.; Munga, S.; Guyah, B.; Omondi, S.; Ochomo, E.	2019	Diagnostic dose determination and efficacy of chlorfenapyr and clothianidin insecticides against <i>Anopheles malaria</i> vector populations of western Kenya	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only

51	Agusto, F. B.; Elmojtaba, I. M.	2017	Optimal control and cost-effective analysis of malaria/visceral leishmaniasis co-infection	PloS one	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
52	Aju-Ameh, O. C.; Awolola, T. S.; Mwansat, G. S.; Mafuyai, H. B.	2018	Determining malaria situation through linelist hospital attendance records in selected communities in Benue state, North-Central Nigeria	Nigerian Journal of Parasitology	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
53	Akachi, Y.; Atun, R.	2011	Effect of investment in Malaria control on child mortality in Sub-Saharan Africa in 2002-2008	PloS one	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
54	Akogbeto, M. C.; Akanke, R. Y.; Azondakon, R.; Padonou, G. G.; Ossian, R. A.; Agossa, F. R.; Beach, R.; Sezonlin, M.	2015	Six years of experience in entomological surveillance of indoor residual spraying against malaria transmission in Benin: Lessons learned, challenges and outlooks	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
55	Akogbeto, M. C.; Dagnon, F.; Akanke, R.; Ossian, R.; Salako, A. S.; Ahogni, I.; Akinro, B.; Sominahouin, A.; Sidick, A.; Tokponnon, F.; Padonou, G. G.	2020	Lessons learned, challenges and outlooks for decision-making after a decade of experience monitoring the impact of indoor residual spraying in Benin, West Africa	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
56	Akogbeto, M. C.; Salako, A. S.; Dagnon, F.; Akanke, R.; Kouletio, M.; Sovi, A.; Sezonlin, M.	2018	Blood feeding behaviour comparison and contribution of Anopheles coluzzii and Anopheles gambiae, two sibling species living in sympatry, to malaria transmission in Alibori and Donga region, northern Benin, West Africa	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
57	Akogbeto, M.	2019	Lessons learned, challenges and implications for decision-making after a decade of experience monitoring the impact of indoor residual spraying in Benin, West Africa	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

58	Akogbeto, M. C.; N'Tcha, L. K.; AÃkpon, R.; Salako, A.; Dagnon, F.; Patton, M. E.; Kouletio, M.; Humes, M.; Beach, R.	2018	Socio-behavioral surveillance on outdoor sleeping and other outdoor nighttime behaviors in Northern Benin for indoor residual spraying decision-making	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
59	Akogbeto, M. C.; Salako, A.; Dagnon, F.; Sezonlin, M.; Agossa, F. R.; Ahokposs, H.; Kouletio, M.; Beach, R.	2017	Contribution of two sympatric sibling species, anopheles coluzzii and An. gambiae, to malaria transmission in North Benin	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
60	Akogbeto, M.; AÃkpon, R.; Padonou, G.; Osse, R.; Agossa, F. R.; YadoulÃ©ton, A.	2015	Lessons learned, challenges and prospects after six years of experience in the implementation of indoor residual spraying in Benin, West Africa	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
61	Akogbeto, M.; Aikpon, R.; Sezonlin, M.; Tokponnon, F.; Ahokposs, H.; Beach, R. F.; Thomas, P.	2016	Dry season malaria transmission reduces the impact of seasonal indoor residual spraying in Benin	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
62	Akogbeto, M.; Padonou, G. G.; Bankole, H. S.; Gazard, D. K.; Gbedjissi, G. L.	2011	Dramatic decrease in malaria transmission after large-scale indoor residual spraying with bendiocarb in Benin, an area of high resistance of Anopheles gambiae to pyrethroids	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
63	Alam, M. Z.; Niaz Arifin, S. M.; Al-Amin, H. M.; Alam, M. S.; Rahman, M. S.	2017	A spatial agent-based model of Anopheles vagus for malaria epidemiology: Examining the impact of vector control interventions	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
64	Al-Arydah, M.; Smith, R.	2011	Controlling malaria with indoor residual spraying in spatially heterogeneous environments	Mathematical Biosciences and Engineering	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
65	Al-Arydah, Mo'tassem; Smith, Robert	2011	Controlling malaria with indoor residual spraying in spatially heterogeneous environments	Mathematical biosciences and engineering : MBE	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

66	Alava, F.; Saavedra, M.; Moreno, M.; Gamboa, D.; Conn, J.	2017	Biting behavior of anopheles darlingi in four communities in the mazan district of the peruvian amazon	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
67	Alegana, V. A.; Kigozi, S. P.; Nankabirwa, J.; Arinaitwe, E.; Kigozi, R.; Mawejje, H.; Kilama, M.; Ruktanonchai, N. W.; Ruktanonchai, C. W.; Drakeley, C.; Lindsay, S. W.; Greenhouse, B.; Kanya, M. R.; Smith, D. L.; Atkinson, P. M.; Dorsey, G.; Tatem, A. J.	2016	Spatio-temporal analysis of malaria vector density from baseline through intervention in a high transmission setting	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
68	Alegana, V. A.; Suiyanka, L.; Macharia, P. M.; Ikahu-Muchangi, G.; Snow, R. W.	2021	Malaria micro-stratification using routine surveillance data in Western Kenya	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
69	Al-Eryani, S. M. A.; Kelly-Hope, L.; Harbach, R. E.; Briscoe, A. G.; Barnish, G.; Azazy, A.; McCall, P. J.	2016	Entomological aspects and the role of human behaviour in malaria transmission in a highland region of the Republic of Yemen	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
70	Ali, M. H.	2019	Existence of malaria hotspots in Zanzibar: Potential contribution to ongoing malaria transmission	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
71	Alidina, Z.; Colaco, R.; Ali, A. S.; Mcha, J. H.; Mwalimu, C. D.; Thawer, N. G.; Lalji, S.; Mutagahywa, J.; Ramsan, M. M.; Kafuko, J. M.; Kaspar, N.; Magesa, S. M.; Reithinger, R.; Ngondi, J. M.	2016	Taking local ownership: Government and household contribution to indoor residual spraying in Zanzibar and mainland Tanzania	International Health	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
72	Alidina, Z.; Lalji, S.; Mutagahywa, J.; Ramsan, M.; Kafuko, J. M.; Ekenna, U.; Magesa, S.; Ngondi, J.; Colaco, R.	2013	Taking local ownership: Government and household contributions to indoor residual spraying for malaria	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

			control in Zanzibar and Mainland Tanzania		
73	Al-Koleeby, Z.; El Aboudi, A.; Assada, M.; Al-Hadi, M.; Abdalr Ahman, M.; Awash, A.; Ahmed, A. S.; Mohamedi, H.; Al Jarbany, J.; Faraj, C.	2020	The Current Insecticide Resistance in Main Malaria Vector Anopheles arabiensis in Yemen	Journal of Tropical Medicine	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
74	Allcock, S. H.; Young, E. H.; Sandhu, M. S.	2018	A cross-sectional analysis of ITN and IRS coverage in Namibia in 2013	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
75	Al-Mafazy, A. W.; McElroy, P.; Msellem, M.; Molteni, F.; Ramsan, M.; Kafuko, J.; Murugasampillay, S.; Jiddawi, M.; Suleiman, A.	2012	Examination of surveillance data milestones as zanzibar transitions to the pre-elimination of malaria 2008-2011	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
76	Alonso, S.; Chaccour, C. J.; Wagman, J.; Candrinho, B.; Muthoni, R.; Saifodine, A.; Saute, F.; Robertson, M.; Zulliger, R.	2021	Cost and cost-effectiveness of indoor residual spraying with pirimiphos-methyl in a high malaria transmission district of Mozambique with high access to standard insecticide-treated nets	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
77	Alyko Chaffa, E. S.; Fiekowsky, E.; Sodjinou, J.; Johns, B.; Belemvire, A.; George, K.; Fornadel, C.	2014	Can health management information system (HMIS) data be used to make indoor residual spray policy decisions in Benin?	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
78	Amajoh, C. N.; Umar, A.; Inyama, P. U.; Ordu, D. A.; Kabir, B. G. J.; Barde, A. A.; Misau, A. A.	2011	Susceptibility test of female Anopheles mosquitoes to ten insecticides for indoor residual spraying (IRS) baseline data collection in northeastern Nigeria	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
79	Anderegg, C.; Chacky, F.; Green, E.; Mandike, R.; McElroy, P.; Molteni, F.	2010	Establishment of population malaria surveillance in Kagera region, Tanzania, by routine testing for parasitemia at time of measles vaccination and first antenatal care	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

			attendance to evaluate impact of malaria intervention		
80	Animut, A.; Balkew, M.	2019	Efficacy of a new indoor residual insecticidal combination containing clothianidin and deltamethrin (â€œfludora® fusionâ€œ) in simple hut trials against anopheles arabiensis	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
81	Animut, A.; LindtjÄ, rn, B.	2018	Use of epidemiological and entomological tools in the control and elimination of malaria in Ethiopia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
82	Animut, A.; Negash, Y.; Kebede, N.	2014	Distribution and utilization of vector control strategies in a malarious village of Jabi Tehnan District, north-western Ethiopia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
83	Ansari, M. A.; Razdan, R. K.	2004	Impact of residual spraying of bendiocarb against the malaria vector Anopheles culicifacies in selected villages of the Ghaziabad District, Uttar Pradesh, India	Journal of the american mosquito control association	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
84	Ansari, M. A.; Razdan, R. K.	2004	Impact of residual spraying of Reldan against Anopheles culicifacies in selected villages of District Ghaziabad (Uttar Pradesh), India	Journal of Vector Borne Diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
85	Ansari, M. A.; Razdan, R. K.	2004	Impact of residual spraying of Reldan against Anopheles culicifacies in selected villages of District Ghaziabad (Uttar Pradesh), India	Journal of Vector Borne Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
86	Ansari, M. A.; Razdan, R. K.	2004	Follow-up studies after withdrawal of deltamethrin spraying against Anopheles	Journal of the american mosquito	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

			culicifacies and malaria incidence	control association	
87	Ansari, M. A.; Razdan, R. K.	2004	Impact of residual spraying of bendiocarb against the malaria vector Anopheles culicifacies in selected villages of the Ghaziabad District, Uttar Pradesh, India	Journal of the american mosquito control association	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
88	Aregawi, Maru W.; Ali, Abdullah S.; Al-mafazy, Abdul-wahiyd; Molteni, Fabrizio; Katikiti, Samson; Warsame, Marian; Njau, Ritha J. A.; Komatsu, Ryuichi; Korenromp, Eline; Hosseini, Mehran; Low-Beer, Daniel; Bjorkman, Anders; D'Alessandro, Umberto; Coosemans, Marc; Otten, Mac	2011	Reductions in malaria and anaemia case and death burden at hospitals following scale-up of malaria control in Zanzibar, 1999-2008	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
89	Aregawi, Maru; Malm, Keziah L.; Wahjib, Mohammed; Kofi, Osae; Allotey, Naa-Korkor; Yaw, Peprah Nana; Abba-Baffoe, Wilmot; Segbaya, Sylvester; Owusu-Antwi, Felicia; Kharchi, Abderahmane T.; Williams, Ryan O.; Saalfeld, Mark; Workneh, Nibretie; Shargie, Estifanos Biru; Noor, Abdisalan M.; Bart-Plange, Constance	2017	Effect of anti-malarial interventions on trends of malaria cases, hospital admissions and deaths, 2005-2015, Ghana	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
90	Argaw, M. D.; Woldegiorgis, A. G.; Workineh, H. A.; Akelom, B. A.; Abebe, M. E.; Abate, D. T.; Ashenafi, E. G.	2021	Access to malaria prevention and control interventions among seasonal migrant workers: A multi-region formative assessment in Ethiopia	PloS one	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

91	Argyropoulos, D. C.; Ruybal-Pesántez, S.; Deed, S. L.; Oduro, A. R.; Dadzie, S. K.; Appawu, M. A.; Asoala, V.; Pascual, M.; Koram, K. A.; Day, K. P.; Tiedje, K. E.	2021	The impact of indoor residual spraying on Plasmodium falciparum microsatellite variation in an area of high seasonal malaria transmission in Ghana, West Africa	Molecular ecology	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
92	Arifin, S. M. N.	2012	Examining the impact of combining multiple interventions for malaria control by using a spatial agent-based model	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
93	Arinaitwe, E.; Greenhouse, B.; Kamya, M. R.; Rosenthal, P. J.; Drakeley, C.; Dorsey, G.; Staedke, S. G.	2017	Overnight travel and the risk of malaria: prospective cohort studies at 3 sites in Uganda of varying malaria transmission intensity	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene. Conference: 66th annual meeting of the american society of tropical medicine and hygiene, ASTMH 2017. United states	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
94	Arinaitwe, E.; Mpimbaza, A.; Nankabirwa, J. I.; Kamya, V.; Asimwe, A.; Kuule, J. K.; Kamya, M. R.; Drakeley, C.; Dorsey, G.; Rosenthal, P. J.; Staedke, S. G.	2020	Malaria diagnosed in an urban setting strongly associated with recent overnight travel: A case-control study from Kampala, Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
95	Arinaitwe, E.; Nankabirwa, J. I.; Krezanoski, P.; Rek, J.; Kamya, V.; Epstein, A.; Rosenthal, P. J.; Drakeley, C.; Kamya, M. R.; Dorsey, G.; Staedke, S. G.	2020	Association between recent overnight travel and use of long-lasting insecticidal nets in rural Uganda: a prospective cohort study in Tororo	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
96	Armand, A.; Carneiro, P.; Locatelli, A.; Mihreteab, S.; Keating, J.	2017	Do public health interventions crowd out private health investments? Malaria control policies in Eritrea	Labour Economics	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

97	Armel, D.	2009	Indoor use of carbamate treated plastic sheeting in combination with long lasting insecticidal nets to control pyrethroid resistant malaria vectors in West Africa	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
98	Arredondo-Jiménez, J. I.; Rodríguez, M. H.; Bown, D. N.; Loyola, E. G.	1993	Indoor low-volume insecticide spray for the control of Anopheles albimanus in southern Mexico. Village-scale trials of bendiocarb, deltamethrin and cyfluthrin	Journal of the american mosquito control association	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
99	Arredondo-Jimanez	1993	Indoor low-volume insecticide spray for the control of Anopheles albimanus in southern Mexico. Village-scale trials of bendiocarb, deltamethrin and cyfluthrin	Journal of the american mosquito control association	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
100	Arredondo-Jimenez, J. I.; Bown, D. N.; Rodriguez, M. H.; Loyola, E. G.	1995	Control of Anopheles albimanus mosquitos in southern Mexico by spraying their preferred indoor resting sites	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
101	Arredondo-Jimenez, J. I.; Bown, D. N.; Rodriguez, M. H.; Loyola, E. G.	1996	Control of Anopheles albimanus mosquitos in southern Mexico by spraying their preferred indoor resting sites	Boletin de la Oficina Sanitaria Panamericana	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
102	Asale, A.; Getachew, Y.; Hailesilassie, W.; Speybroeck, N.; Duchateau, L.; Yewhalaw, D.	2014	Evaluation of the efficacy of DDT indoor residual spraying and long-lasting insecticidal nets against insecticide resistant populations of Anopheles arabiensis Patton (Diptera: Culicidae) from Ethiopia using experimental huts	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
103	Asante, K. P.; Dery, D. B.; Dosoo, D. K.; Kayan, K.; Segbaya, S.; Asoala, V.; Tchum, K.; Amoyaw, F.; Amoako, N.; Oduro, A.; Owusu-Agyei, S.	2014	Baseline studies on AngloGold ashantis' indoor residual spraying program (IRS) for malaria control in Ghana	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

104	Ashton, R.; Bennett, A.; Al-Mafazy, A. W.; Abass, A.; Msellem, M.; Salgado, S. R.; McElroy, P.; Greer, G.; Paxton, L.; Kachur, S. P.; Yoon, S.; Ali, A. S.; Yukich, J.; Eisele, T. P.; Bhattarai, A.	2017	Use of routine health information system data to evaluate impact of malaria interventions in Zanzibar during the period 2000-2015	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
105	Ashton, Ruth A.; Bennett, Adam; Al-Mafazy, Abdul-Wahid; Abass, Ali K.; Msellem, Mwinyi I.; McElroy, Peter; Kachur, S. Patrick; Ali, Abdullah S.; Yukich, Joshua; Eisele, Thomas P.; Bhattarai, Achuyt	2019	Use of Routine Health Information System Data to Evaluate Impact of Malaria Control Interventions in Zanzibar, Tanzania from 2000 to 2015	EclinicalMedicine	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
106	Asinas, C. Y.; Hugo, C. T.; Boase, C. J.; Evans, R. G.	1994	Evaluation of selective spraying of bendiocarb (Ficam VC) for the control of Anopheles flavirostris in the Philippines	Journal of the american mosquito control association	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
107	Asingizwe, D.; Poortvliet, P. M.; Koenraadt, C. J. M.; Van Vliet, A. J. H.; Ingabire, C. M.; Mutesa, L.; Leeuwis, C.	2019	Role of individual perceptions in the consistent use of malaria preventive measures: Mixed methods evidence from rural Rwanda	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
108	Assebe, L. F.; Kwete, X. J.; Wang, D.; Liu, L.; Norheim, O. F.; Jbaily, A.; Verguet, S.; Johansson, K. A.; Tolla, M. T.	2020	Health gains and financial risk protection afforded by public financing of selected malaria interventions in Ethiopia: An extended cost-effectiveness analysis	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
109	Asua, V.; Tukwasibwe, S.; Conrad, M.; Walakira, A.; Nankabirwa, J. I.; Mugenyi, L.; Kanya, M. R.; Nsobya, S. L.; Rosenthal, P. J.	2017	Plasmodium species infecting children presenting with malaria in Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
110	Asua, V.; Tukwasibwe, S.; Conrad, M.; Walakira, A.; Nankabirwa, J.	2017	Prevalence of mixed-species malaria infections in uganda	American journal of tropical	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	Mugenyi, L.; San, J.; Arinaitwe, E.; Yeka, A.; Kanya, M. R.; Nsobya, S. L.; Rosenthal, P. J.			medicine and hygiene	
11 1	Athrey, G.; Hodges, T. K.; Reddy, M. R.; Arnez, A. M.; Overgaard, H. J.; Atue, M.; Abaga, S.; Caccone, A.; Slotman, M.	2011	The impact of anti-vector interventions on the effective population size of malaria mosquitoes	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
11 2	Athrey, G.; Hodges, T. K.; Reddy, M. R.; Overgaard, H. J.; Matias, A.; Ridl, F. C.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Caccone, A.; Slotman, M. A.	2012	The Effective Population Size of Malaria Mosquitoes: Large Impact of Vector Control	PLoS Genetics	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
11 3	Athrey, G.; Hodges, T.; Deitz, K.; Reddy, M.; Overgaard, H. J.; Matias, A.; Ridl, F.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Caccone, A.; Slotman, M. A.	2013	The impacts of vector control on the effective population sizes of malaria mosquitoes	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
11 4	Awine, T.; Silal, S. P.	2020	Accounting for regional transmission variability and the impact of malaria control interventions in Ghana: a population level mathematical modelling approach	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
11 5	Ayalew, S.; Mamo, H.; Animut, A.; Erko, B.	2016	Assessment of current malaria status in light of the ongoing control interventions, socio-demographic and environmental variables in Jiga area, northwest Ethiopia	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
11 6	Ayele, Dawit G.; Zewotir, Temesgen T.; Mwambi, Henry G.	2014	Semiparametric models for malaria rapid diagnosis test result	BMC Public Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
11 7	Ayieko, C.; Maue, A. C.; Jura, W. G. Z. O.; Noland, G. S.; Ayodo, G.; Rochford, R.; John, C. C.	2013	Changes in B Cell Populations and Merozoite Surface Protein-1-Specific Memory B Cell Responses after Prolonged Absence	PloS one	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

			of Detectable P. falciparum Infection		
11 8	Baber, I.; Williams, C.; Gweh, G.; Nador, A.; Dehnue, G.; Lama, J.; Nyansaiye, P. K.; Pratt, O.; Jose, R.; Reed, C.; Seyoum, A.; Fornadel, C.	2016	Distribution and frequency of insecticide resistance in anopheles gambiae s.l. population in liberia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
11 9	Baeza, A.; Bouma, M. J.; Dhiman, R.; Pascual, M.	2014	Malaria control under unstable dynamics: Reactive vs. climate-based strategies	Acta tropica	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
12 0	Baidjoe, A. Y.; Stevenson, J.; Stresman, G.; Stone, W.; Owaga, C.; Makori, E.; China, P.; Odongo, W.; Oduor, A.; Drakeley, C.; Bousema, T.; Cox, J.	2012	Identification of hotspots of malaria transmission in western Kenyan Highlands; paving the road to targeted and effective intervention strategies	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
12 1	Bajunirwe, Francis	2020	Pyrethroid resistance in sub-Saharan Africa	Lancet	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
12 2	Bakare, E. A.; Hoskova-Mayerova, S.	2021	Numerical treatment of optimal control theory applied to malaria transmission dynamic model	Quality and Quantity	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
12 3	Bakare, E. A.; Onasanya, B. O.; Hoskova-Mayerova, S.; Olubosedo, O.	2021	Analysis of Control Interventions against Malaria in communities with Limited Resources	Analele Stiintifice ale Universitatii Ovidius Constanta, Seria Matematica	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
12 4	Balogh, B.; Hutton, D. W.; Anupindi, R. M.; Arney, L.; Liu, M.; Wu, H.; Larson, P. S.; Yadav, P.; Wilson, M. L.	2014	Optimal coverage at minimal cost: A dynamic modeling approach to simultaneous allocation of multiple anti-malaria interventions	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
12 5	Bamaga, O. A.; Mahdy, M. A.; Mahmud, R.; Lim, Y. A.	2014	Malaria in Hadhramout, a southeast province of Yemen: Prevalence, risk factors, knowledge, attitude and practices (KAPs)	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

12 6	Bang, F. B.; Hairston, N. G.	1947	DDT spraying inside houses as a means of malaria control in New Guinea	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
12 7	Bang, F. B.; Hairston, N. G.	1947	DDT spraying inside houses as a means of malaria control in New Guinea	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
12 8	Barbosa, S.; Kay, K.; Chitnis, N.; Hastings, I. M.	2018	Modelling the impact of insecticide-based control interventions on the evolution of insecticide resistance and disease transmission	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
12 9	Basilua Kanza, Jean Pierre; El Fahime, Elmostafa; Alaoui, Sanaa; Essassi, El Mokhtar; Brooke, Basil; Nkebolo Malafu, Andre; Watsenga Tezzo, Francis	2013	Pyrethroid, DDT and malathion resistance in the malaria vector Anopheles gambiae from the Democratic Republic of Congo	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
13 0	Bath, D.; Cook, J.; Govere, J.; Mathebula, P.; Morris, N.; Hlongwana, K.; Raman, J.; Seocharan, I.; Zitha, A.; Zitha, M.; et al.,	2021	Effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of reactive, targeted indoor residual spraying for malaria control in low-transmission settings: a cluster-randomised, non-inferiority trial in South Africa	Lancet	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
13 1	Baume, C. A.; Reithinger, R.; Woldehanna, S.	2009	Factors associated with use and non-use of mosquito nets owned in Oromia and Amhara Regional States, Ethiopia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
13 2	Baxi, S. M.; Gasasira, A.; Kigozi, R.; Sserwanga, A.; Kakeeto, S.; Nasr, S.; Kamyra, M. R.; Filler, S.; Dorsey, G.	2011	Effect of indoor residual spraying of insecticides on the malaria slide positivity rate in an area of high transmission intensity in Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
13 3	Bayoh, N.; Marube, E.; Ombok, M.; Ouma, P.; Kariuki, S.; Kiptui, R.; Hershey,	2016	Facility-based enhanced malaria surveillance to measure vector-control intervention impact in	American journal of tropical	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	C.; Butts, J.; Desai, M.; Fiore, A.; Gimnig, J.; Williamson, J.; Buff, A. M.		western kenya, 2012-2015	medicine and hygiene	
134	Beer, Netta; Ali, Abdullah S.; Shakely, Deler; Elfving, Kristina; Al-Mafazy, Abdul-Wahiyd H.; Msellem, Mwinyi; Petzold, Max; Bjorkman, Anders; Kallander, Karin	2013	High effective coverage of vector control interventions in children after achieving low malaria transmission in Zanzibar, Tanzania	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
135	Bekele, D.; Belyhun, Y.; Petros, B.; Deressa, W.	2012	Assessment of the effect of insecticide-treated nets and indoor residual spraying for malaria control in three rural kebeles of Adami Tulu District, South Central Ethiopia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
136	Belay, B.; Gelana, T.; Gebresilassie, A.	2021	Malaria prevalence, knowledge, attitude, and practice among febrile patients attending Chagni health center, Northwest Ethiopia: a cross-sectional study	Tropical Diseases, Travel Medicine and Vaccines	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
137	Bell, C. E.; Slutsker, L.; Beach, R. F.; Foster, S. O.; Jimenez, G.; Sarmiento, M. E.	2009	Malaria control in the municipality of San Esteban, Honduras	Revista Panamericana de Salud Pblica	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
138	Bellai, G. L.; Mouhamadou, C. S.; Adja, A. M.; N'Goran, K. E.	2015	Pyrethroid and DDT resistance in Anopheles gambiae from Taabo, south-central Cote d'Ivoire	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
139	Benavente, L.; Linder, B.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2008	Reduction of malaria incidence among workers on Bioko Island, equatorial guinea	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
140	Bennett, A. F.; Miller, J.; Hawela, M.; Hamainza, B.; Vounatsou, P.; Kamuliwo, M.; Steketee, R.; Eisele, T. P.	2011	Association between vector control coverage, climate variability and the spatial distribution of malaria at three time points in Zambia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

14 1	Bennett, A.; Bhattarai, A.; Al-Mafazy, A. W.; Abass, A. K.; Msellem, M. I.; Kachur, S. P.; Yoon, S. S.; Ali, A. S.; Eisele, T. P.	2015	Modeled counterfactual of predicted malaria case incidence using a difference-in-difference analysis, unguja and pemba islands, Zanzibar, 1999-2010	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
14 2	Bennett, A.; Miller, J.; Ingwe, M. M.; Moonga, H. B.; Hamainza, B.; Kamuliwo, M.; Yukich, J.; Smith, T. A.; Steketee, R. W.; Eisele, T. P.	2012	Using health management information system data on parasitologically-confirmed malaria cases to evaluate the effect of vector control coverage	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
14 3	Bennett, A.; Yukich, J.; Miller, J. M.; Keating, J.; Moonga, H.; Hamainza, B.; Kamuliwo, M.; Andrade-Pacheco, R.; Vounatsou, P.; Steketee, R. W.; Eisele, T. P.	2016	The relative contribution of climate variability and vector control coverage to changes in malaria parasite prevalence in Zambia 2006-2012	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
14 4	Bennett, A.; Yukich, J.; Robertson, M.; Hamainza, B.; Stuck, L.; Rerolle, F.; Porter, T.; Conner, R. O.; Steketee, R. W.; Miller, J. M.; Eisele, T. P.	2017	Impact of indoor residual spraying with pirimiphosmethyl in the context of a comprehensive malaria elimination strategy in Southern Province Zambia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
14 5	Beretta, E.; Capasso, V.; Garao, D. G.	2018	A mathematical model for malaria transmission with asymptomatic carriers and two age groups in the human population	Mathematical Biosciences	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
14 6	Berger, Franck; Flamand, Claude; Musset, Lise; Djossou, Felix; Rosine, Jacques; Sanquer, Marie-Anne; Dusfour, Isabelle; Legrand, Eric; Ardillon, Vanessa; Rabarison, Patrick; Grenier, Claire; Girod, Romain	2012	Investigation of a sudden malaria outbreak in the isolated Amazonian village of Saul, French Guiana, January-April 2009	The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

147	Berhane, A.; Mihreteab, S.; Ahmed, H.; Zehaie, A.; Abdulmumini, U.; Chanda, E.	2015	Gains attained in malaria control coverage within settings earmarked for pre-elimination: Malaria indicator and prevalence surveys 2012, Eritrea	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
148	Berti, J.; Zimmerman, R.; Amarista, J.	1993	Adult abundance, biting behavior and parity of <i>Anopheles aquasalis</i> , Curry 1932 in two malarious areas of Sucre State, Venezuela	Memorias do Instituto Oswaldo Cruz	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
149	Betson, M.; Jawara, M.; Awolola, T. S.	2009	Status of insecticide susceptibility in <i>Anopheles gambiae</i> s.l. from malaria surveillance sites in the Gambia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
150	Bever, C. A.; Gerardin, J.; Hamainza, B.; Conner, R.; Miller, J.; Eckhoff, P. A.; Earle, D.; Wenger, E. A.	2016	Epidemiological and operational lessons learned from a malaria elimination campaign in zambia's lake kariba region	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
151	Bhatt, R. M.; Srivastava, H. C.; Rajnikant,; Yadav, R. S.	2008	Dynamics of <i>Anopheles culicifacies</i> -transmitted malaria in the absence of effective zooprophylaxis in a riverine settlement in Gujarat, India	Current Science	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
152	Bhattarai, A.; Ali, A. S.; Roberts, J.; Shakely, D.; MaËšrtensson, A.; Eng, J. V.; Abbas, A. K.; Abdul-Wahiyd, A. M.; Kachur, S. P.; Hightower, A.; BjÄ¶rkman, A.	2012	All cause under-five mortality declines in north a and micheweni districts of zanzibar archipelago, 1999-2008	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
153	Bhavnani, D.; Trejo, B.; Perez, L. M.; Cohen, J. M.; Le Menach, A.; Banegas, E.	2015	Predictive malaria risk modeling using aggregate case data for improved intervention targeting in honduras	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
154	Biggs, J.; Raman, J.; Cook, J.; Hlongwana, K.; Drakeley, C.; Morris, N.; Serocharan, I.; Agubuzo, E.; Kruger, P.; Mabuza, A.; et al.,	2017	Serology reveals heterogeneity of <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> transmission in northeastern South Africa: implications for malaria elimination	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

15 5	Bigoga, J. D.; Ndangoh, D. N.; Awono-Ambene, P. H.; Patchoke, S.; Fondjo, E.; Leke, R. G. F.	2012	Pyrethroid resistance in Anopheles gambiae from the rubber cultivated area of Niete, South Region of Cameroon	Acta tropica	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
15 6	Birhanu, Zewdie; Abebe, Lakew; Sudhakar, Morankar; Dissanayake, Gunawardena; Yihdego, Yemane Ye- Ebiyo; Alemayehu, Guda; Yewhalaw, Delenasaw	2016	Malaria Related Perceptions, Care Seeking after Onset of Fever and Anti-Malarial Drug Use in Malaria Endemic Settings of Southwest Ethiopia	PloS one	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
15 7	Bisong, C. E.; Dongmo, C. M.	2013	Utilization of malaria prevention methods by pregnant women in Yaounde	Pan African Medical Journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
15 8	Bjorkman, A.; Shakely, D.; Ali, A. S.; Abbas, A. K.; Msellem, M.; Bhattarai, A.; Beer, N.; Al-Mafazy, A. W.; Elfving, K.; Hassan, J.; Majambere, S.; Petzold, M.; Omar, R. S.; McElroy, P.; Maertensson, A.	2011	Zanzibar - Towards elimination?	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
15 9	Blumberg, L.; Frean, J.	2007	Malaria control in South Africa - Challenges and successes	South African Medical Journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
16 0	Blumberg, L.; Frean, J.	2017	Malaria reduces globally but rebounds across Southern Africa	Southern African Journal of Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
16 1	Boene, H.; Gonzales, R.; Vali, A.; Ruperez, M.; Velasco, C.; Machevo, S.; Saco, C.; Sevane, E.; Macete, E.; Menendez, C.; Munguambe, K.	2014	Perceptions of malaria in pregnancy and acceptability of preventive interventions among Mozambican pregnant women: Implications for effectiveness of malaria control in pregnancy	PloS one	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
16 2	Bornman, M.; Delport, R.; Faras, P.; Aneck-Hahn, N.;	2018	Alterations in male reproductive hormones in relation to environmental DDT exposure	Environment International	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

	Patrick, S.; Millar, R. P.; de Jager, C.				
163	Bornman, M.; Kylin, H.; Bouwman, H.	2012	Household behavioural responses following successful IRS malaria control: Challenges for health education and intervention strategies	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
164	Bornman, R.	2016	Dichlorodiphenyltrichloro ethane (DDT) exposure and male reproductive health	Toxicology Letters	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
165	Bornman, R.; De Jager, C.; Worku, Z.; Farias, P.; Reif, S.	2010	DDT and urogenital malformations in newborn boys in a malarial area	BJU International	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
166	Bousema, T.; Griffin, J. T.; Sauerwein, R. W.; Smith, D. L.; Churcher, T. S.; Takken, W.; Ghani, A.; Drakeley, C.; Gosling, R.	2012	Hitting hotspots: Spatial targeting of malaria for control and elimination	PLoS Medicine	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
167	Bousema, T.; Stevenson, J.; Baidjoe, A.; Stresman, G.; Bayoh, N.; Vulule, J.; Fillinger, U.; Drakeley, C.; Cox, J.	2012	A cluster-randomized trial to determine the impact of hotspot-targeted interventions on malaria transmission	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
168	Bousema, Teun; Stevenson, Jennifer; Baidjoe, Amrish; Stresman, Gillian; Griffin, Jamie T.; Kleinschmidt, Immo; Remarque, Edmond J.; Vulule, John; Bayoh, Nabie; Laserson, Kayla; Desai, Meghna; Sauerwein, Robert; Drakeley, Chris; Cox, Jonathan	2013	The impact of hotspot-targeted interventions on malaria transmission: study protocol for a cluster-randomized controlled trial	Trials	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
169	Bousema, Teun; Stevenson, Jennifer; Baidjoe, Amrish; Stresman, Gillian; Griffin, Jamie T.; Kleinschmidt, Immo;	2013	The impact of hotspot-targeted interventions on malaria transmission: study protocol for a cluster-randomized controlled trial	Trials	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

	Remarque, Edmond J.; Vulule, John; Bayoh, Nabie; Laserson, Kayla; Desai, Meghna; Sauerwein, Robert; Drakeley, Chris; Cox, Jonathan				
170	Bousema, Teun; Stresman, Gillian; Baidjoe, Amrish Y.; Bradley, John; Knight, Philip; Stone, William; Osoiti, Victor; Makori, Euniah; Owaga, Chrispin; Odongo, Wycliffe; China, Pauline; Shagari, Shehu; Doumbo, Ogobara K.; Sauerwein, Robert W.; Kariuki, Simon; Drakeley, Chris; Stevenson, Jennifer; Cox, Jonathan	2016	The Impact of Hotspot-Targeted Interventions on Malaria Transmission in Rachuonyo South District in the Western Kenyan Highlands: A Cluster-Randomized Controlled Trial	PLoS Medicine	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
171	Bousema, Teun; Stresman, Gillian; Baidjoe, Amrish Y.; Bradley, John; Knight, Philip; Stone, William; Osoiti, Victor; Makori, Euniah; Owaga, Chrispin; Odongo, Wycliffe; China, Pauline; Shagari, Shehu; Doumbo, Ogobara K.; Sauerwein, Robert W.; Kariuki, Simon; Drakeley, Chris; Stevenson, Jennifer; Cox, Jonathan	2016	The Impact of Hotspot-Targeted Interventions on Malaria Transmission in Rachuonyo South District in the Western Kenyan Highlands: A Cluster-Randomized Controlled Trial	PLoS Medicine	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
172	Bouwman, Hindrik; van den Berg, Henk; Kylin, Henrik	2011	DDT and Malaria Prevention: Addressing the Paradox	Environmental Health Perspectives	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
173	Bradley, J.; Hergott, D.; Garcia, G.; Lines, J.; Cook, J.; Slotman, M. A.; Phiri, W. P.; Schwabe, C.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2016	A cluster randomized trial comparing deltamethrin and bendiocarb as insecticides for indoor residual spraying to	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

			control malaria on Bioko Island, Equatorial Guinea		
17 4	Bradley, J.; Hergott, D.; Garcia, G.; Lines, J.; Cook, J.; Slotman, M.; Phiri, W.; Schwabe, C.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2016	A cluster randomized trial to compare bendiocarb and deltamethrin for indoor residual spraying on bioko island, equatorial guinea	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
17 5	Bradley, J.; Matias, A.; Schwabe, C.; Vargas, D.; Monti, F.; Nseng, G.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2012	Increased risks of malaria due to limited residual life of insecticide and outdoor biting versus protection by combined use of nets and indoor residual spraying on Bioko Island, Equatorial Guinea	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
17 6	Bradley, J.; Matias, A.; Schwabe, C.; Vargas, D.; Monti, F.; Nseng, G.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2012	The effect of limited residual life of insecticide and outdoor biting on malaria infection in children on bioko Island, equatorial guinea: An examination of two key assumptions of indoor residual spraying	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
17 7	Brennan, B. A.; Johns, B.; Masendu, H.; Sande, S.; Tangwena, A.	2015	The rise of vector resistance and insecticide costs: An assessment of insecticide change for indoor residual spraying and malaria burden in Zimbabwe	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
17 8	Brennan, B.; Belemvire, A.; Sande, S.; Muchenje, T.; Johns, B.	2015	Beneficiary satisfaction assessment to guide health program communication and increase acceptance of indoor residual spraying	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
17 9	Brenyah, R. C.	2014	Insecticide susceptibility, characterization of breeding sites and community perceptions on malaria vector control interventions on knust campus	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only

180	BriÅ«t, O. J. T.; Impoinvil, D. E.; Chitnis, N.; Pothin, E.; Lemoine, J. F.; Frederic, J.; Smith, T. A.	2019	Models of effectiveness of interventions against malaria transmitted by Anopheles albimanus	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
181	Briet, O. J. T.; Angluben, R.; Torno, M.; Navarro, M. A. H.; Deray, R.; Schapira, A.	2017	Modelling to support the planning of malaria elimination in southern Palawan, the Philippines	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
182	Briggs, J.; Nankabirwa, J.; Rek, J.; Arinaitwe, E.; Dorsey, G.; Rodriguez-Barraquer, I.; Kanya, M.; Greenhouse, B.	2018	Using amplicon deep-sequencing to determine the etiology of residual asymptomatic parasitemia following highly effective indoor residual spraying in a previously high transmission setting in Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
183	Brosseau, Laura; Drame, Papa Makhtar; Besnard, Patrick; Toto, Jean-Claude; Foumane, Vincent; Le Mire, Jacques; Mouchet, Francois; Remoue, Franck; Allan, Richard; Fortes, Filomeno; Carnevale, Pierre; Manguin, Sylvie	2012	Human antibody response to Anopheles saliva for comparing the efficacy of three malaria vector control methods in Balombo, Angola	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
184	Brown, Z. S.; Kramer, R. A.	2018	Preference Heterogeneity in the Structural Estimation of Efficient Pigovian Incentives for Insecticide Spraying to Reduce Malaria	Environmental and Resource Economics	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
185	Brown, Z. S.; Kramer, R. A.; Ocan, D.; Oryema, C.	2016	Household perceptions and subjective valuations of indoor residual spraying programmes to control malaria in northern Uganda	Infectious diseases of poverty	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
186	Brutus, L.; Le Goff, G.; Rasoloniaina, L. G.; Rajaonarivelo, V.; Raveloson, A.; Cot, M.	2001	Comparison of lambda-cyhalothrin and DDT house-spraying for malaria control on the western slopes of	Parasite	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only

			Madagascar highlands. I - Entomological study		
187	Brutus, L.; Le Goff, G.; Rasoloniaina, L. G.; Rajaonarivelo, V.; Raveloson, A.; Cot, M.	2001	The campaign against malaria in central western Madagascar: comparison of the efficacy of lambda-cyhalothrin and DDT house spraying. I-- Entomological study	Parasite (paris, france)	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
188	Bugoro, Hugo; Cooper, Robert D.; Butafa, Charles; Iro'ofa, Charles; Mackenzie, Donna O.; Chen, Cheng-Chen; Russell, Tanya L.	2011	Bionomics of the malaria vector Anopheles farauti in Temotu Province, Solomon Islands: issues for malaria elimination	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
189	Bukirwa, H.; Yau, V.; Kigozi, R.; Filler, S.; Quick, L.; Lugemwa, M.; Dissanayake, G.; Kanya, M.; Wabwire-Mangen, F.; Dorsey, G.	2009	Short report: Assessing the impact of indoor residual spraying on malaria morbidity using a sentinel site surveillance system in Western Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
190	Bukirwa, Hasifa; Yau, Vincent; Kigozi, Ruth; Filler, Scott; Quick, Linda; Lugemwa, Myers; Dissanayake, Gunawardena; Kanya, Moses; Wabwire-Mangen, Fred; Dorsey, Grant	2009	Assessing the impact of indoor residual spraying on malaria morbidity using a sentinel site surveillance system in Western Uganda	The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
191	Burch, Jane; Tort, Sera	2020	What are the effects of indoor residual spraying for preventing malaria?	Cochrane Clinical Answers	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
192	Burkot, T.; Russell, T. L.; Myo, M.; Mnzava, A.; Espino, E.; Farlow, R.	2018	Malaria vector surveillance-can vector data guide country policy and programmatic malaria control decisions?	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

19 3	Cameron, Ewan; Young, Alyssa J.; Twohig, Katherine A.; Pothin, Emilie; Bhavnani, Darlene; Dismer, Amber; Merilien, Jean Baptiste; Hamre, Karen; Meyer, Phoebe; Le Menach, Arnaud; Cohen, Justin M.; Marseille, Samson; Lemoine, Jean Frantz; Telfort, Marc-Aurele; Chang, Michelle A.; Won, Kimberly; Knipes, Alaine; Rogier, Eric; Amratia, Punam; Weiss, Daniel J.; Gething, Peter W.; Battle, Katherine E.	2021	Mapping the endemicity and seasonality of clinical malaria for intervention targeting in Haiti using routine case data	eLife	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
19 4	Cameron, J. A.	2010	Malaria vector control using indoor residual spraying with DDT in Arusha Region, Tanzania: A comparison of community and governmental views on the perceived barriers preventing a high level of community uptake and wider implementation	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
19 5	Campodonico, Joanna; Sevilla- Martir, Javier; Arrizabalaga, Gustavo; Kochhar, Komal	2015	Assessing Knowledge and Perceptions Related to Preventive Methods and Treatment of Malaria in the Local Endemic Area of Trujillo, Honduras	Hispanic Health Care International (Springer Publishing Company, Inc.)	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
19 6	Canana, N.	2021	A cost analysis to address issues of budget constraints on the implementation of the indoor residual spray programme in two districts of Maputo Province, Mozambique	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

197	Canavati, Sara E.; Kelly, Gerard C.; Quintero, Cesia E.; Vo, Thuan Huu; Tran, Long Khanh; Ngo, Thang Duc; Tran, Duong Thanh; Edgel, Kimberly A.; Martin, Nicholas J.	2020	Targeting high risk forest goers for malaria elimination: a novel approach for investigating forest malaria to inform program intervention in Vietnam	BMC Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
198	Cano, J.; Aguilar, R.; Moreno, M.; Manaca, M. N.; Gonzlez, V.; Sanz, S.; Aponte, J. J.; Nhacolo, A.; Benito, A.; Alonso, P. L.	2011	Impact of control activities in malaria transmission by <i>Anopheles funestus</i> in Southern Mozambique (Manhia district)	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
199	Cassin, J. W.; Jacob, C. G.; Thesing, P. C.; Nyirenda, O. M.; Masonga, R.; Taylor, T. E.; Plowe, C. V.; Laufer, M. K.	2013	Malaria transmission in households in Blantyre, Malawi	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
200	Cavanzos, T.; Rossheim, M.; Donfack, O. T.; Phiri, W. P.; Garcia, G. A.; Von Fricken, M. E.	2019	Hearing to understand: Associations between hearing malaria health messaging and malaria knowledge, awareness and practice of preventative measures in the 2018 malaria indicator survey for bioko island, equatorial	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
201	Cern, V.	2009	Epidemiology and first approach to estimate vulnerability to malaria outbreaks: Steps to implement a malaria early warning system (MEWS) as adaptation measure for climate change in Colombia (INAP project)	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
202	Chabot-Couture, G.; Eckhoff, P. A.	2012	Balancing interventions within fixed-budget malaria control programs in africa	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
203	Chaccour	2021	Incremental impact on malaria incidence following indoor residual spraying in a highly endemic area with high	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

			standard ITN access in Mozambique: results from a cluster-randomized study		
204	Chaccour, C. J.; Alonso, S.; Zulliger, R.; Wagman, J.; Saifodine, A.; Candrinho, B.	2018	Combination of indoor residual spraying with long-lasting insecticide-treated nets for malaria control in Zambezia, Mozambique: a cluster randomised trial and cost-effectiveness study protocol	BMJ global health	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
205	Chaccour, C. J.; Alonso, S.; Zulliger, R.; Wagman, J.; Saifodine, A.; Candrinho, B.	2018	Combination of indoor residual spraying with long-lasting insecticide-treated nets for malaria control in Zambezia, Mozambique: a cluster randomised trial and cost-effectiveness study protocol	BMJ global health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
206	Chaccour, C.; Zulliger, R.; Wagman, J.; Casellas, A.; Nacima, A.; Elobolobo, E.; Savaio, B.; Saifodine, A.; Fornadel, C.; Richardson, J.; Candrinho, B.; Robertson, M.; Saute, F.	2021	Incremental impact on malaria incidence following indoor residual spraying in a highly endemic area with high standard ITN access in Mozambique: results from a cluster-randomized study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
207	Chaccour, C.; Zulliger, R.; Wagman, J.; Casellas, A.; Saifodine, A.; Candrinho, B.; Richardson, J.; Robertson, M.; Saute, F.	2019	Combining long-lasting insecticidal nets (LLINs) with third generation-indoor residual spraying (IRS) provides significant added protection compared to LLINs alone in children under five years of age in a high-transmission area of mozambique	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
208	Chanda, E.; Arshad, M.; Khaloua, A.; Zhang, W.; Namboze, J.; Uusiku, P.; Angula, A. H.; Gausi, K.; Tiruneh, D.; Islam, Q.	2018	An investigation of the Plasmodium falciparum malaria epidemic in Kavango and Zambezi regions of Namibia in 2016	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	M.; Kolivras, K.; Haque, U.				
209	Chanda, E.; Coleman, M.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Hemingway, J.; Hamainza, B.; Masaninga, F.; Chanda-Kapata, P.; Baboo, K. S.; DÄ¼rrheim, D. N.	2012	Impact assessment of malaria vector control using routine surveillance data in Zambia: Implications for monitoring and evaluation	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
210	Chanda, E.; Hemingway, J.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Rehman, A. M.; Ramdeen, V.; Phiri, F. N.; Coetzer, S.; Mthembu, D.; Shinondo, C. J.; Chizema-Kawesha, E.; Kamuliwo, M.; Mukonka, V.; Baboo, K. S.; Coleman, M.	2011	Insecticide resistance and the future of malaria control in Zambia	PloS one	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
211	Chanda, E.; Mzilahowa, T.; Chipwanya, J.; Ali, D.; Troell, P.; Dodoli, W.; Mnzava, A. P.; Ameneshewa, B.; Gimnig, J.	2016	Scale-up of integrated malaria vector control: Lessons from Malawi	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
212	Chanda, E.; Mzilahowa, T.; Chipwanya, J.; Mulenga, S.; Ali, D.; Troell, P.; Dodoli, W.; Govere, J. M.; Gimnig, J.	2015	Preventing malaria transmission by indoor residual spraying in Malawi: Grappling with the challenge of uncertain sustainability	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
213	Chanda, P.; Hamainza, B.; Mulenga, S.; Chalwe, V.; Msiska, C.; Chizema-Kawesha, E.	2009	Early results of integrated malaria control and implications for the management of fever in under-five children at a peripheral health facility: A case study of Chongwe rural health centre in Zambia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
214	Chandre, Fabrice; Dabire, Roch K.; Hougard, Jean-Marc; Djogbenou, Luc S.; Irish, Seth R.;	2010	Field efficacy of pyrethroid treated plastic sheeting (durable lining) in combination with long	Parasites & vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only

	Rowland, Mark; N'Guessan, Raphael		lasting insecticidal nets against malaria vectors		
21 5	Chang, M. A.; Impoinvil, D.; Hamre, K. E.; Javel, A.; Dalexis, P. E.; MÃ©riliën, J. B.; Dismer, A. M.; FouchÃ©, B.; Pothin, E.; Battle, K.; Cameron, E.; Holmes, K.; Desir, L.; Noland, G.; Young, A.; Cohen, J.; Lafortune, W.; Van Den Hoogen, L.; Stresman, G.; Drakeley, C.; Rogier, E.; Ashton, R.; Druetz, T.; Eisele, T. P.; Lemoine, J. F.	2019	Results of a pilot of targeted mass drug administration with sulfadoxine- pyrimethamine and primaquine as a component of a malaria elimination package in Haiti	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
21 6	Chang, Mei-Chun; Teng, Hwa-Jen; Chen, Chen-Fu; Chen, Yung- Chen; Jeng, Chian- Ren	2008	The resting sites and blood-meal sources of Anopheles minimus in Taiwan	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
21 7	Channa, K.; RÃ©llin, H. B.; NÃ©st, T. H.; Odland, J. Ã~; Sandanger, T. M.	2012	Prenatal exposure to DDT in malaria endemic region following indoor residual spraying and in non- malaria coastal regions of South Africa	Science of the Total Environment	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
21 8	Chareonviriyaphap, T.; Bangs, M. J.; Ratanatham, S.	2000	Status of malaria in Thailand	The Southeast Asian journal of tropical medicine and public health	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
21 9	Charlwood, J. D.; Alecrim, W. D.; Fe, N.; Mangabeira, J.; Martins, V. J.	1995	A field trial with lambda- cyhalothrin (ICON) for the intradomiciliary control of malaria transmitted by Anopheles darlingi root in Rondonia, Brazil	Acta tropica	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
22 0	Charlwood, J. D.; Qassim, M.; Elnsur, E. I.; Donnelly, M.; Petrarca, V.; Billingsley, P. F.; Pinto, J.; Smith, T.	2001	The impact of indoor residual spraying with malathion on malaria in refugee camps in eastern Sudan	Acta tropica	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

22 1	Chaumeau, V.; Kajeechiwa, L.; Kulabkeeree, T.; Vishwakarma, R. K.; Wasisakun, P.; Hsel, S. N.; Oo, K.; Dah, T.; Sawasdichai, S.; Trakoolchengkaew, M.; Phanaphadungtham, M.; Inta, A.; Akararungrot, Y.; Lee, N. Y.; Kankew, P.; Wiladphaingern, J.; Mukaka, M.; Delmas, G.; Nosten, F.	2020	Impact of outdoor residual spraying on the biting rate of malaria vectors: A pilot study in four villages in Kayin state, Myanmar	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
22 2	Chen, H. H.; Chen, A. L.; O'Shaughnessy, P. T.	2009	Indoor residual spraying of DDT for malaria control...O'Shaughnessy PT. Parachuting cats and crushed eggs: the controversy over the use of DDT to control malaria. Am J Public Health. 2008;98:1940-1948	American Journal of Public Health	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
22 3	Chen, Hsi Hsuan; Chen, Anthony L. T.	2009	Indoor residual spraying of DDT for malaria control	American Journal of Public Health	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
22 4	Chen, Ying-An; Lien, Jih-Ching; Tseng, Lien-Fen; Cheng, Chien-Fu; Lin, Wan- Yu; Wang, Hurng-Yi; Tsai, Kun-Hsien	2019	Effects of indoor residual spraying and outdoor larval control on Anopheles coluzzii from Sao Tome and Principe, two islands with pre- eliminated malaria	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
22 5	Cheng, F. Y.	1968	Responses of Anopheles balabacensis to various patterns of DDT-spraying of shelters in Sabah, East Malaysia	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
22 6	Chevrier, J.; Gunier, R. B.; Harley, K. G.; Kogut, K.; Bradman, A.; Eskenazi, B.	2012	Prenatal exposure to ddt and behavior in 7-year old children participating in the chamacos study	Epidemiology	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
22 7	Chevrier, J.; Rauch, S.; Obida, M.; Crause, M.; Bornman, R.; Eskenazi, B.	2019	Sex and poverty modify associations between maternal peripartum concentrations of DDT/E and pyrethroid metabolites and thyroid hormone levels in	Environment International	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

			neonates participating in the VHEMBE study, South Africa		
228	Chevrier, Jonathan; Rauch, Stephen; Crause, Madelein; Obida, Muvhulawa; Gaspar, Fraser; Bornman, Riana; Eskenazi, Brenda	2019	Associations of Maternal Exposure to Dichlorodiphenyltrichloro ethane and Pyrethroids With Birth Outcomes Among Participants in the Venda Health Examination of Mothers, Babies and Their Environment Residing in an Area Sprayed for Malaria Control	American Journal of Epidemiology	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
229	Chimberengwa, P. T.; Masuka, N.; Gombe, N. T.; Tshimanga, M.; Takundwa, L.; Bangure, D.	2015	Indoor household residual spraying program performance in Matabeleland South Province, Zimbabwe: 2011 to 2012; A Descriptive cross-sectional study	Pan African Medical Journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
230	Chinula, D.; Hamainza, B.; Chizema, E.; Kavishe, D. R.; Sikaala, C. H.; Killeen, G. F.	2018	Proportional decline of Anopheles quadriannulatus and increased contribution of An. arabiensis to the An. gambiae complex following introduction of indoor residual spraying with pirimiphos-methyl: An observational, retrospective secondary analysis of pre-	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
231	Chitnis, N.; Briet, O.; Smith, T.	2012	Modeling the effects of vector control interventions in reducing malaria transmission and disease burden	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
232	Chitnis, N.; Hardy, D.; Smith, T.	2012	A Periodically-Forced Mathematical Model for the Seasonal Dynamics of Malaria in Mosquitoes	Bulletin of Mathematical Biology	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
233	Chitnis, N.; Hyman, J. M.; Cushing, J. M.	2008	Determining important parameters in the spread of malaria through the	Bulletin of Mathematical Biology	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

			sensitivity analysis of a mathematical model		
23 4	Chitnis, N.; Schapira, A.; Smith, T.; Steketee, R.	2010	Comparing the effectiveness of malaria vector-control interventions through a mathematical model	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
23 5	Choi, L.; Pryce, J.; Garner, P.	2019	Indoor residual spraying for preventing malaria in communities using insecticide-treated nets	Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
23 6	Chritz, S.; Yeshiwondim, A. K.; Bansil, P.; Workie, W. M.; Agmas, A. A.; Zeleke, M. T.; Guesses, G. S.; Serda, B. A.; Tesfay, B. H.; Kidanemariam, T. G.; Salisbury, N.; Earle, D.; Steketee, R. W.; Guinovart, C.; Getachew, A.	2017	Malaria control in migrant laborers working in agricultural farms in Metema region, Ethiopia: Current practices, feasibility and acceptability of new malaria interventions	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
23 7	Chukwuocha, A. N.; Chukwuocha, U. M.	2011	The continued relevance of home management of malaria strategy in the effective and sustainable control of malaria in endemic areas	Scientific Research and Essays	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
23 8	Chunga, C.; Kumwenda, S.	2014	Community satisfaction with indoor residual spraying for malaria control in Karonga, Northern Malawi	Malawi Medical Journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
23 9	Chunga, C.; Kumwenda, S.	2014	Community satisfaction with indoor residue spraying for Malaria control in Karonga, Northern Malawi	Malawi medical journal : the journal of Medical Association of Malawi	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
24 0	Church, K. E. M.; Smith, R. J.	2016	Comparing malaria surveillance with periodic spraying in the presence of insecticide-resistant mosquitoes: Should we spray regularly or based on human infections?	Mathematical Biosciences	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

24 1	Cirera, L.; Galatas, B.; Alonso, S.; Paaajmans, K.; Mamuquele, M.; MartÃ-Soler, H.; Guinovart, C.; Munguambe, H.; Luis, F.; Nhantumbo, H.; MontaÃ±Ã , J.; Bassat, Q.; Candrinho, B.; Rabinovich, R.; Macete, E.; Aide, P.; Alonso, P.; SaÃete, F.; Sicuri, E.	2020	Moving towards malaria elimination in southern Mozambique: Cost and cost-effectiveness of mass drug administration combined with intensified malaria control	PloS one	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
24 2	Cisse, M. B.; Dengela, D.; Oxborough, R.; Lucas, B.; Dicko, A.; Mihigo, J.; Sadou, A.; George, K.; Fornadel, C.; Norris, L.; Belemvire, A.; Powell, S.; Beach, R. F.	2016	Dynamics of entomological inoculation rates following indoor residual spraying in Mali	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
24 3	Cisse, M.; Ndiop, M.	2018	Impact of antimalarial interventions on malaria morbidly and mortality in hospitals from 2001 to 2017, Senegal	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
24 4	Coker, E.; Chevrier, J.; Rauch, S.; Bradman, A.; Obida, M.; Crause, M.; Bornman, R.; Eskenazi, B.	2018	Association between prenatal exposure to multiple insecticides and child body weight and body composition in the VHEMBE South African birth cohort	Environment International	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
24 5	Colborn, J. M.; Yava, R.; De Leon, G. P.; Chan, A.; Hershey, C.; Fortes, F.	2013	Sub-national evaluation of the impact of malaria control programs in huambo province, Angola	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
24 6	Colborn, J.; Colborn, K.; Wenger, E.; Mathe, G.; Matsinhe, G.	2014	Identifying factors associated with malaria parasitemia in mozambique using a geostatistical model	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
24 7	Coleman, M.; Al- Zahrani, M. H.; Hemingway, J.; Omar, A.; Stanton, M. C.; Thomsen, E. K.; Alsheikh, A. A.; Alhakeem, R. F.;	2014	A country on the verge of malaria elimination - The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia	PloS one	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

	McCall, P. J.; Al Rabeeah, A. A.; Memish, Z. A.				
248	Coleman, M.; Mabuza, A. M.; Kok, G.; Coetzee, M.; Durrheim, D. N.	2009	Using the SaTScan method to detect local malaria clusters for guiding malaria control programmes	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
249	Coleman, S.; Dadzie, S. K.; Seyoum, A.; Yihdego, Y.; Mumba, P.; Dengela, D.; Ricks, P.; George, K.; Fornadel, C.; Szumlas, D.; Psychas, P.; Williams, J.; Appawu, M. A.; Boakye, D. A.	2017	A reduction in malaria transmission intensity in Northern Ghana after 7 years of indoor residual spraying	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
250	Coleman, S.; Dadzie, S. K.; Yihdego, Y.; Gyamfi, F.; Kolyada, L.; Dengela, D.; Seyoum, A.; Tongren, J. E.; Zigirumugabe, S.; Dery, D.; George, K.; Armistead, J.; Appawu, M.; Badu, K.; Obiri-Danso, K.; Boakye, D.; Szumlas, D.	2019	Feeding and resting behavior of anopheles gambiae s.l. in areas getting indoor residual spraying for malaria vector control and areas not sprayed in Northern Ghana	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
251	Coleman, S.; Dadzie, S.; Seyoum, A.; Yihdego, Y.; Fletcher, E. A.; Dengela, D.; George, K.; Appawu, M.; Boakye, D.	2016	Entomological indicators of malaria transmission after IRS was discontinued: Findings from savelugu nanton district and its implications for malaria control in Ghana	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
252	Coleman, S.; Yihdego, Y.; Gyamfi, F.; Obum, E. K.; Kolyada, L.; Tongren, J. E.; George, K.; Armistead, J.; Zigirumugabe, S.; Dery, D.; Dadzie, S.; Appawu, M.; Boakye, D.; Szumlas, D.; Dengela, D.	2019	Efficacy of Sumishield® 50wg for indoor residual spraying and susceptibility of anopheles Gambiae s.l. to clothianidin in Northern Ghana	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only

25 3	Coleman, S.; Yihdego, Y.; Sherrard-Smith, E.; Thomas, C. S.; Dengela, D.; Oxborough, R. M.; Dadzie, S. K.; Boakye, D.; Gyamfi, F.; Obiri-Danso, K.; Johns, B.; Siems, L. V.; Lucas, B.; Tongren, J. E.; Zigirumugabe, S.; Dery, D.; Fornadel, C.; George, K.; Belemvire, A.; Carlson, J.; Irish, S. R.; Armistead, J. S.; Seyoum, A.	2021	Partial indoor residual spraying with pirimiphos-methyl as an effective and cost-saving measure for the control of <i>Anopheles gambiae</i> s.l. in northern Ghana	Scientific reports	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
25 4	Colson, K. E.; Dwyer-Lindgren, L.; Fullman, N.; Achoki, T.; Schneider, M.; Hangoma, P.; Ng, M.; Masiye, F.; Gakidou, E.	2014	Assessing the contribution of malaria control interventions on reductions in all-cause under-5 mortality in Zambia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
25 5	Coluzzi, M.	2000	Malaria eradication in Calabria, residual anopheles and transmission risk	Parassitologia	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
25 6	Combination interventions for controlling malaria transmitted by pyrethroid resistant mosquitoes: A novel bed net with synergist and IRS formulation	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
25 7	Comfort, A.; Leegwater, A.; Nakhimovsky, S.; Kansembe, H.; Hamainza, B.; Bwalya, B.; Alilio, M.; Johns, B.; Olsho, L.	2017	Exploring the use of routinely-available, retrospective data to study the association between malaria control scale-up and micro-economic outcomes in Zambia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
25 8	Conner, R. O.; Kamuliwo, M.; Mudenda, M.; Ingwe, M. M.; Moonga, H.; Hamainza, B.; Lungu, C.; Silumbe, K.; Earle,	2016	Results and recommendations from the 2015 malaria indicators survey (MIS) in Zambia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	D.; Kawesha, E. C.; Miller, J. M.				
259	Conteh, L.; Sharp, B. L.; Streat, E.; Barreto, A.; Konar, S.	2004	The cost and cost-effectiveness of malaria vector control by residual insecticide house-spraying in southern Mozambique: A rural and urban analysis	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
260	Conteh, Lesong; Shuford, Kathryn; Agboraw, Efundem; Kont, Mara; Kolaczinski, Jan; Patouillard, Edith	2021	Costs and Cost-Effectiveness of Malaria Control Interventions: A Systematic Literature Review	Value in Health	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
261	Cook, J.; Biggs, J.; Mair, C.; Hergott, D.; Akum, A.; Herman, L.; De Carvalho, J. N.; Garcia, G.; Schwabe, C.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Drakeley, C. J.	2017	Longitudinal serological evaluation of malaria transmission patterns in Bioko Island, Equatorial Guinea	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
262	Cook, J.; Garcia, G.; Smith, J.; Hergott, D.; Akum, A.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Phiri, W. P.; Schwabe, C.; De Carvalho, J. N.	2017	Impact of stratification methods used to target indoor residual spraying in Bioko Island, Equatorial Guinea	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
263	Cook, J.; Hergott, D.; Phiri, W.; Rivas, M. R.; Bradley, J.; Segura, L.; Garcia, G.; Schwabe, C.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2018	Trends in parasite prevalence following 13 years of malaria interventions on Bioko island, Equatorial Guinea: 2004-2016	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
264	Coosemans, M.	1978	Control of malaria vectors in tropical Africa	Medecine Tropicale	Exclusion reason: duplicate
265	Coosemans, M.	1978	[Control of malaria vectors in tropical Africa (author's transl)]	Lutte contre les vecteurs du paludisme en Afrique tropicale.	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
266	Coosemans, M.; Barutwanayo, M.	1989	Papers based on posters selected for awards Malaria control by antivectorial measures in a zone of chloroquine-resistant malaria: A successful programme in a rice growing area of the Rusizi valley, Burundi	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

267	Coosemans, M.; Barutwanayo, M.	1989	Malaria control by antivectorial measures in a zone of chloroquine-resistant malaria: A successful programme in a rice growing area of the Rusizi valley Burundi	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
268	Coosemans, M.; Barutwanyo, M.	1989	Malaria control by antivectorial measures in a zone of chloroquine-resistant malaria: a successful programme in a rice growing area of the Rusizi valley	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: duplicate
269	Corbel	2012	Combination of malaria vector control interventions in pyrethroid resistance area in Benin: a cluster randomised controlled trial	The lancet. Infectious diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
270	Cost-effectiveness evaluation of vector control strategies in Mozambique (COST)	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
271	Cost-effectiveness evaluation of vector control strategies in Mozambique (COST)	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
272	Cot, M.; Brutus, L.; Le Goff, G.; Rajaonarivelo, V.; Raveloson, A.	2001	Comparison of lambda-cyhalothrin and DDT house-spraying for malaria control on the western slopes of Madagascar Highlands. II - Parasitological and clinical study	Parasite	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
273	Cot, M.; Brutus, L.; Le Goff, G.; Rajaonarivelo, V.; Raveloson, A.	2001	The campaign against malaria in central western Madagascar: comparison of lambda-cyhalothrin and DDT house spraying. II-- Parasitological and clinical study	Parasite (paris, france)	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
274	Cot, M.; Brutus, L.; Pinell, V.; Ramaroson, H.; Raveloson, A.; Rabeson, D.; Rakotonjanabelo, A. L.	2002	Malaria prevention during pregnancy in unstable transmission areas: The highlands of Madagascar	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data

27 5	Coulibaly, Drissa; Guindo, Boureima; Niangaly, Amadou; Maiga, Faycal; Konate, Salimata; Kodio, Aly; Diallo, Astou; Antar, Abdou Tahirou Mohamed; Kone, Abdoulaye K.; Traore, Karim; Travassos, Mark A.; Sagara, Issaka; Dumbo, Ogobara K.; Thera, Mahamadou A.	2021	A Decline and Age Shift in Malaria Incidence in Rural Mali following Implementation of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention and Indoor Residual Spraying	The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
27 6	Cupul-Uicab, L. A.; Bornman, R.; Archer, J. I.; Kudumu, M. O.; Travlos, G. S.; Wilson, R. E.; Whitworth, K. W.	2020	Exposure to DDT from indoor residual spraying and biomarkers of inflammation among reproductive-aged women from South Africa	Environmenta l Research	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
27 7	Curtis, C. F.	2002	Should the use of DDT be revived for malaria vector control?	Biomédica : revista del Instituto Nacional de Salud	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
27 8	Curtis, Chris F.	2002	Debe regresar el uso del DDT para el control de vectores de la malaria	Biomédica (Bogotá)	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
27 9	Custodio, Estefania; Descalzo, Miguel Angel; Villamor, Eduardo; Molina, Laura; Sanchez, Ignacio; Lwanga, Magdalena; Bernis, Cristina; Benito, Agustin; Roche, Jesus	2009	Nutritional and socio- economic factors associated with Plasmodium falciparum infection in children from Equatorial Guinea: results from a nationally representative survey	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
28 0	Daba Hamusse, Shallo; Balcha, Taye T.; Belachew, Tefera	2012	The impact of indoor residual spraying on malaria incidence in East Shoa Zone, Ethiopia	Global Health Action	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
28 1	Dacuma, M. G. B.; Hallett, R.; Dimalibot, J.; Ugaddan, G.; Yadao, F.; Notario, W.	2011	Asymptomatic Plasmodium vivax infections in southern Mindanao, Philippines: A challenge to malaria elimination	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray

28 2	Dadzie, S.; Coleman, S.; Mumba, P.; Seyoum, A.; Ricks, P.; Szumlas, D.; Psychas, P.; Williams, J.; Appawu, M.; Boakye, D.	2014	Impact of indoor residual spraying on entomological indices of malaria transmission in the Bunkpurugu-Yunyoo District in the Northern Savannah zone of Ghana	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
28 3	Das, M.; Srivastava, B. N.; Rao, C. K.; Thapar, B. R.; Sharma, G. K.	1987	Field trial of the effectiveness of indoor-spraying with pirimiphos-methyl emulsion for malaria control in a tribal area of Phulbani district, Orissa State, India	Medical and veterinary entomology	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
28 4	Dattani, Mamta; Prajapati, Pb; Raval, Dinkar	2009	Impact of indoor residual spray with synthetic pyrethroid in gandhinagar district, gujarat	Indian journal of community medicine : official publication of Indian Association of Preventive & Social Medicine	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
28 5	Daygena, T. Y.; Massebo, F.; LindtjÄ, rn, B.	2017	Variation in species composition and infection rates of Anopheles mosquitoes at different altitudinal transects, and the risk of malaria in the highland of Dirashe Woreda, south Ethiopia	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
28 6	De Jager, C.; Aneck-Hahn, N. H.; Bornman, M. S.; Farias, P.; SpanÄ², M.	2012	DDT exposure levels and semen quality of young men from a malaria area in South Africa	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
28 7	De Jager, C.; Patrick, S.; Cronje, T.; Aneck-Hahn, N.	2019	The impact of changes in malaria control strategies in South Africa on DDT exposure and seminal parameters	Andrology	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
28 8	Deguenon, Jean M.; Azondekon, Roseric; Agossa, Fiacre R.; Padonou, Gil G.; Anagonou, Rodrigue; Ahoga, Juniace; N'Dombidje, Boris; Akinro, Bruno; Stewart, David A.;	2020	ImergardTMWP: A Non-Chemical Alternative for an Indoor Residual Spray, Effective against Pyrethroid-Resistant Anopheles gambiae (s.l.) in Africa	Insects	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only

	Wang, Bo; Gittins, David; Tihomirov, Larissa; Apperson, Charles S.; McCord, Marian G.; Akogbeto, Martin C.; Roe, R. Michael				
289	Dengela, D.; Seyoum, A.; Lucas, B.; Johns, B.; George, K.; Belemvire, A.; Caranci, A.; Norris, L. C.; Fornadel, C. M.	2018	Multi-country assessment of residual bio-efficacy of insecticides used for indoor residual spraying in malaria control on different surface types: Results from program monitoring in 17 PMI/USAID-supported IRS countries	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
290	Deressa, W.; Loha, E.; Balkew, M.; Desalegne, A.; Gari, T.; Gebremichael, T.; Kenea, O.; Jima, D.; Robberstad, B.; Overgaard, H. J.; et al.,	2014	Combining long-lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying for malaria prevention in Ethiopia: study protocol for a cluster randomized controlled trial	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
291	Dhiman, R. C.; Shahi, B.; Sharma, S. N.; Nanda, N.; Khargiwarkar, V. N.; Subbarao, S. K.	2005	Persistence of malaria transmission in a tribal area in Maharashtra, India	Current Science	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
292	Dhiman, R. C.; Sharna, S. K.; Pillai, C. R.; Subbarao, S. K.	2001	Investigation of outbreak of malaria in tribal area of Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh	Current Science	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
293	Diallo, A.; Cisse, B.; Tairou, F.; Ba, E. H.; Sy, O.; Gomis, J.; Sokhna, C.; Gaudart, J.; Flach, C.; Gaye, O.; et al.,	2014	A cluster-randomized trial of targeted control to eliminate malaria in central Senegal: study design and acceptability of the interventions	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene.	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
294	Diallo, A.; Cisse, B.; Tairou, F.; Ba, E. H.; Sy, O.; Gomis, J.; Sokhna, C.; Gaudart, J.; Flach, C.; Gaye, O.; et al.,	2014	A cluster-randomized trial of targeted control to eliminate malaria in central Senegal: study design and acceptability of the interventions	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene.	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
295	Diallo, A.; Cisse, B.; Tairou, F.; Ba, E.; Gomis, J.; Sy, O.; Sokhna, C.; Gaudart,	2015	A cluster-randomized trial of targeted control to eliminate malaria in central Senegal: main results in year 2	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	J.; Flach, C.; Faye, O.; et al.,				
29 6	Diboulo, E.; SiÃ©, A.; Vounatsou, P.	2016	Assessing the effects of malaria interventions on the geographical distribution of parasitaemia risk in Burkina Faso	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
29 7	Dimas, H. J.; Sambo, N. M.; Ibrahim, M. S.; Ajayi, I. O. O.; Nguku, P. M.; Ajumobi, O. O.	2019	Coverage of indoor residual spraying for malaria control and factors associated with its acceptability in Nasarawa state, north-central Nigeria	Pan African Medical Journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
29 8	DjÃ©nontin, A.; Chandre, F.; DabirÃ©, K. R.; Chabi, J.; N'Guessan, R.; Baldet, T.; AkogbÃ©to, M.; Corbel, V.	2010	Indoor use of plastic sheeting impregnated with carbamate combined with long-lasting insecticidal mosquito nets for the control of pyrethroid-resistant malaria vectors	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
29 9	Donfack, O. T.; Eribo, C. O.; Nze, L. O.; Motobe, L.; Smith, J.; Phiri, W. P.; Falla, C. C.; Tam, L.; Schwabe, C.; Garcia, G.	2018	Factors associated with refusal and reluctance to indoor residual spraying on bioko island, Equatorial Guinea	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
30 0	Donfack, O. T.; Garcia, G. A.; Smith, J. M.; Smith, D. L.; Guerra, C. A.	2019	Improving the spatial granularity for targeting indoor residual spraying on bioko island	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
30 1	Druetz, T.; Stresman, G.; Ashton, R. A.; Joseph, V.; van den Hoogen, L.; Worges, M.; Hamre, K. E. S.; Fayette, C.; Monestime, F.; Impoinvil, D.; Rogier, E.; Chang, M. A.; Lemoine, J. F.; Drakeley, C.; Eisele, T. P.	2021	The Immediate Effects of a Combined Mass Drug Administration and Indoor Residual Spraying Campaign to Accelerate Progress towards Malaria Elimination in Grande-Anse, Haiti	The Journal of infectious diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

30 2	Druetz, T.; Stresman, G.; Joseph, V.; Ashton, R.; Worges, M.; Van Den Hoogen, L.; Fouche, B.; Rogier, E.; Chang, M. A.; Lemoine, J. F.; Drakeley, C.; Eisele, T. P.	2019	Reduction in malaria prevalence in sentinel populations following introduction of a package of interventions for malaria elimination: Results from easy access group surveys in 2017 and 2018, Grande-Anse (Haiti)	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
30 3	Dube, B.; Mberikunashe, J.; Dhliwayo, P.; Tangwena, A.; Shambira, G.; Chimusoro, A.; Madinga, M.; Gambia, B.	2019	How far is the journey before malaria is knocked out in Zimbabwe: Results of the malaria indicator survey 2016	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
30 4	Dunn, C. E.; Le Mare, A.; Makungu, C.	2011	Malaria risk behaviours, socio-cultural practices and rural livelihoods in southern Tanzania: Implications for bednet usage	Social Science & Medicine	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
30 5	Echodu, D. C.; Colborn, K.; Wanzirah, H.; Mulebeke, R.; Elliott, R.; Odude, W.; Bukonya, F.; Eganyu, T.; Maiteki-Sebuguzi, C.; Gonahasa, S.; Kyohere, M.; Yeka, A.	2018	Mass drug administration combined with indoor residual spraying for accelerated reduction of malaria in a high transmission setting in northeastern Uganda: Preliminary results	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
30 6	Echodu, D.; Colborn, K.; Mulebeke, R.; Eganyu, T.; Wanzira, H.; Bukonya, F.; Elliott, R.; Nankabirwa, J.; Opigo, J.; Yeka, A.	2019	Comparative effectiveness trial of two community case management techniques following withdrawal of indoor residual spraying in NE Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
30 7	Eckert, E.; Florey, L. S.; Tongren, J. E.; Salgado, S. R.; Rukundo, A.; Habimana, J. P.; Hakizimana, E.; Munguti, K.; Umulisa, N.; Mulindahabi, M.; Karema, C.	2017	Impact evaluation of malaria control interventions on morbidity and all-cause child mortality in Rwanda, 2000-2010	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

308	Eckhoff, P.	2011	Modeling for malaria elimination in a variety of transmission settings	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
309	Eckhoff, P. A.; Burkot, T. R.; Collins, F. H.; Gentile, J.; Lobo, N. F.; Raybaud, B.; Russell, T. L.; Wenger, E. A.	2013	The roles of vector control in enabling malaria elimination campaigns in varying transmission settings	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
310	Ediau, M.; Babirye, J. N.; Tumwesigye, N. M.; Matovu, J. K.; MacHingaidze, S.; Okui, O.; Wanyenze, R. K.; Waiswa, P.	2013	Community knowledge and perceptions about indoor residual spraying for malaria prevention in Soroti district, Uganda: A cross-sectional study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
311	Edwards, H. M.; Sriwichai, P.; Kirabittir, K.; Prachumsri, J.; Chavez, I. F.; Hii, J.	2019	Transmission risk beyond the village: Entomological and human factors contributing to residual malaria transmission in an area approaching malaria elimination on the Thailand-Myanmar border	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
312	Eisele, T. P.; Larsen, D.; Steketee, R. W.	2010	Protective efficacy of interventions for preventing malaria mortality in children in Plasmodium falciparum endemic areas	International Journal of Epidemiology	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
313	Elliott, R. C.; Smith, D. L.; Echodu, D.	2018	Medical and entomological malarial interventions, a comparison and synergy of two control measures using a Ross/Macdonald model variant and openmalaria simulation	Mathematical Biosciences	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
314	Elliott, R. C.; Smith, D. L.; Echodu, D. C.	2019	Synergy and timing: A concurrent mass medical campaign predicted to augment indoor residual spraying for malaria	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
315	Emerson, P. M.; Ngondi, J.; Biru, E.; Graves, P. M.; Ejigsemahu, Y.; Gebre, T.; Endeshaw, T.; Genet, A.;	2008	Integrating an NTD with one of "the big three" Combined malaria and trachoma survey in Amhara region of Ethiopia	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

	Mosher, A. W.; Zerihum, M.; Messele, A.; Richards Jr, F. O.				
31 6	Emerson, Paul M.; Ngondi, Jeremiah; Biru, Estifanos; Graves, Patricia M.; Ejigsemahu, Yeshewamebrat; Gebre, Teshome; Endeshaw, Tekola; Genet, Asrat; Mosher, Ayc W.; Zerihun, Mulat; Messele, Ayennew; Richards, Frank O.	2008	Integrating an NTD with one of "The big three": combined malaria and trachoma survey in Amhara Region of Ethiopia	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
31 7	Entomological research, training and prevention strategies for malaria in Africa	Year not provi ded	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
31 8	Ernst, K. C.; Lindblade, K. A.; Koech, D.; Sumba, P. O.; Kuwuor, D. O.; John, C. C.; Wilson, M. L.	2009	Environmental, socio- demographic and behavioural determinants of malaria risk in the western Kenyan highlands: A case-control study	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
31 9	Esayas, E.; Tufa, A.; Massebo, F.; Ahemed, A.; Ibrahim, I.; Dillu, D.; Bogale, E. A.; Yared, S.; Deribe, K.	2020	Malaria epidemiology and stratification of incidence in the malaria elimination setting in Harari Region, Eastern Ethiopia	Infectious diseases of poverty	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
32 0	Estimating the Malaria Prevention Impact of New Nets: Observational Analyses to Evaluate the Evidence Generated During Piloted New Net Distributions in Rwanda	Year not provi ded	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
32 1	Evaluating the feasibility and effectiveness of Reactive Targeted Parasite Elimination vs. Reactive Case Detection as a	Year not provi ded	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	community level intervention in response to a passively identified index case: a cluster randomised controlled trial in Namibia				
32 2	Eyobo, M. B.; Awur, A. C.; Wani, G.; Julla, A. I.; Remijo, C. D.; Sebit, B.; Azairwe, R.; Thabo, O.; Bepo, E.; Lako, R. L.; Riek, L.; Chanda, E.	2014	Malaria indicator survey 2009, South Sudan: Baseline results at household level	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
32 3	Faye, S.; Cico, A.; Baruwa, E.	2017	Cost and effectiveness analysis of malaria control in Senegal: "theoretical" single interventions vs. "actual" packages of interventions	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
32 4	Faye, S.; Cico, A.; Gueye, A. B.; Baruwa, E.; Johns, B.; Ndiop, M.; Alilio, M.	2018	Scaling up malaria intervention "packages" in Senegal: Using cost effectiveness data for improving allocative efficiency and programmatic decision-making	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
32 5	Fekadu, A.; Dobo, B.; Birmeka, M.	2021	Prevalence of, and risk factors for, malaria infection among patients visiting Goljota Health Center, Heben Arsi District, West Arsi Zone, Oromia Regional State, Ethiopia: A retrospective and an institution-based cross-sectional study	Ethiopian Journal of Health Development	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
32 6	Feltrer, A. R.; Sesay, S.; Lalloo, D.; Phiri, K.; Terlouw, D. J.	2012	Assessment of malaria control progress over a two-year period using a continuous 'rolling' malaria indicator survey across age groups in chikhwawa district, malawi	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

327	Feufack-Donfack, Lionel Brice; Sarah-Matio, Elangwe Milo; Abate, Luc Marcel; Bouopda Tuedom, Aline Gaelle; Ngano Bayibeki, Albert; Maffo Ngou, Christelle; Toto, Jean-Claude; Sandeu, Maurice Marcel; Eboumbou Moukoko, Carole Else; Ayong, Lawrence; Awono-Ambene, Parfait; Morlais, Isabelle; Nsango, Sandrine Eveline	2021	Epidemiological and entomological studies of malaria transmission in Tibati, Adamawa region of Cameroon 6 years following the introduction of long-lasting insecticide nets	Parasites & vectors	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
328	Fletcher, I. K.; Stewart-Ibarra, A. M.; Sippy, R.; Carrasco-Escobar, G.; Silva, M.; Beltran-Ayala, E.; Ordoñez, T.; Adrian, J.; Sáenz, F. E.; Drakeley, C.; Jones, K. E.; Lowe, R.	2020	The Relative Role of Climate Variation and Control Interventions on Malaria Elimination Efforts in El Oro, Ecuador: A Modeling Study	Frontiers in Environmental Science	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
329	Fontaine, R. E.; Pull, J. H.; Payne, D.	1978	Evaluation of fenitrothion for the control of malaria	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
330	Fontaine, R. E.; Pull, J. H.; Payne, D.	1978	Evaluation of fenitrothion for the control of malaria	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
331	Forero, D. A.; Chaparro, P. E.; Vallejo, A. F.; Benavides, Y.; Gutiérrez, J. B.; Arvalo-Herrera, M.; Herrera, S.	2014	Knowledge, attitudes and practices of malaria in Colombia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
332	Fouque, Florence; Knox, Tessa	2021	Special Programme for Research and Training in Tropical Diseases-coordinated Multicountry Study to Determine the Burden and Causes of Residual Malaria Across Different Regions	Journal of Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
333	From Malaria Control to Sustainable Elimination: Cluster	Year not	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	randomised trial comparing targeted versus generalised vector control in South Africa (Targeted Indoor Residual Spraying Against Malaria (TIRS))	provided			
334	Fullman, N.; Burstein, R.; Lim, S. S.; Medlin, C.; Gakidou, E.	2013	Nets, spray or both? the effectiveness of insecticide-treated nets and indoor residual spraying in reducing malaria morbidity and child mortality in sub-Saharan Africa	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
335	Fuseini, G.; Nguema, R. N.; Phiri, W. P.; Donfack, O. T.; Cortes, C.; Von Fricken, M. E.; Meyers, J. I.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Garcia, G. A.; Maas, C.; Schwabe, C.; Slotman, M. A.	2019	Increased biting rate of insecticide-resistant culex mosquitoes and community adherence to IRS for malaria control in urban Malabo, Bioko Island, Equatorial Guinea	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
336	Galappaththy, G. N. L.; Gueye, C. S.; Abeyasinghe, R. R.; Kahn, J. G.; Feachem, R. G. A.	2012	Progress towards elimination: A case study of Sri Lanka	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
337	Galatas, B.; Marti-Soler, H.; Guinovart, C.; Nhamussua, L.; Simone, W.; Munguambe, H.; Chidimatembue, A.; Montañez, J.; Luis, F.; Paaijmans, K.; Bassat, Q.; Mayor, A.; Menéndez, C.; Candrinho, B.; Rabinovich, R.; Alonso, P.; Saete, F.; Aide, P.	2019	The magude project: Drastic reduction of malaria burden and sustained gains after a malaria elimination project in Southern Mozambique	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
338	Galatas, B.; Nhacolo, A.; Marti, H.; Munguambe, H.; Jamise, E.; Guinovart, C.; Cirera, L.; Amone,	2020	Demographic and health community-based surveys to inform a malaria elimination project in Magude	BMJ open	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

	F.; MacEte, E.; Bassat, Q.; Rabinovich, R.; Alonso, P.; Aide, P.; Saute, F.; Sacoor, C.		district, southern Mozambique		
339	Galatas, Beatriz; Sañte, Francisco; Martñ-Soler, Helena; Guinovart, Caterina; Nhamussua, Lidia; Simone, Wilson; Munguambe, Humberto; Hamido, Camilo; Monta±ñ , Jñlia; Muguande, Olinda; Maartens, Francois; Luis, Fabiño; Paaijmans, Krijn; Mayor, Alfredo; Bassat, Quique; Menñndez, Clara; Macete, Eusebio; Rabinovich, Regina; Alonso, Pedro L.; Candrinho, Baltazar	2020	A multiphase program for malaria elimination in southern Mozambique (the Magude project): Añ before-after study	PLoS Medicine	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
340	Gandahusada, S.; Fleming, G. A.; Sukamto,	1984	Malaria control with residual fenitrothion in Central Java, Indonesia: An operational-scale trial using both full and selective coverage treatments	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
341	Gandahusada, S.; Fleming, G. A.; Sukamto,	1984	Malaria control with residual fenitrothion in Central Java, Indonesia: An operational-scale trial using both full and selective coverage treatments	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
342	Garcia Contreras, G. A.; Hergott, D.; Schwabe, C.; Phiri, W.; Perry, M.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Bradley, J.; Segura, J. L.; Smith, J.	2016	Evaluating stratified malaria control interventions in bioko island: Different approaches to focalized intensified malaria control interventions through spatial clustering and risk maps	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

34 3	Gari, T.; Kenea, O.; Loha, E.; Deressa, W.; Hailu, A.; Balkew, M.; Gebre-Michael, T.; Robberstad, B.; Overgaard, H. J.; Lindtjorn, B.	2016	Malaria incidence and entomological findings in an area targeted for a cluster-randomized controlled trial to prevent malaria in Ethiopia: results from a pilot study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
34 4	Gari, T.; Solomon, T.; Lindtjorn, B.	2021	Older children are at increased risk of Plasmodium vivax in south-central Ethiopia: a cohort study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
34 5	Gaspar, Fraser W.; Chevrier, Jonathan; QuirÃ³s-AlcalÃ¡, Lesliam; Lipsitt, Jonah M.; Barr, Dana Boyd; Holland, Nina; Bornman, Riana; Eskenazi, Brenda	2017	Levels and Determinants of DDT and DDE Exposure in the VHEMBE Cohort	Environmental Health Perspectives	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
34 6	Gavi, S.; Tapera, O.; Mberikun Ashe, J.; Kanyangarara, M.	2021	Malaria incidence and mortality in Zimbabwe during the COVID-19 pandemic: analysis of routine surveillance data	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
34 7	Georgia, D.; Aguemon, B.; Remoue, F.; Rogier, C.	2017	Effectiveness of vectors control intervention on malaria infection and clinical cases, Benin, West Africa	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
34 8	Gething, P.; Savory, D.; Midekisa, A.; Andrade-Pacheco, R.; Holl, F.; Tatarsky, A.; Killeen, G.; Bennett, A.; Sturrock, H.	2016	Exploring environmental factors mediating spatiotemporal variation in vector control impact in Sub-Saharan Africa 2000-2015	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
34 9	Gharakhanlou, N. M.; Hooshangi, N.; Helbich, M.	2020	A spatial agent-based model to assess the spread of malaria in relation to anti-malaria interventions in southeast Iran	ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
35 0	Giardina, F.; Kasasa, S.; SiÃ©, A.; Utzinger, J.; Tanner, M.; Vounatsou, P.	2014	Effects of vector-control interventions on changes in risk of malaria parasitaemia in sub-Saharan Africa: A spatial and temporal analysis	The Lancet Global Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

35 1	Gillies, M. T.; Smith, A.	1960	The effect of a residual house-spraying campaign in east africa on species balance in the anopheles funestus group. the replacement of a. funestus giles by a. rivulorum leeson	Bulletin of Entomological Research	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
35 2	Gimnig, J. E.; Otieno, P.; Were, V.; Marwanga, D.; Abong'o, D.; Wiegand, R.	2016	The Effect of Indoor Residual Spraying on the Prevalence of Malaria Parasite Infection, Clinical Malaria and Anemia in an Area of Perennial Transmission and Moderate Coverage of Insecticide Treated Nets in Western Kenya	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
35 3	Githeko, A. K.; Ototo, E. N.; Guiyun, Y.	2012	Progress towards understanding the ecology and epidemiology of malaria in the western Kenya highlands: Opportunities and challenges for control under climate change risk	Acta tropica	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
35 4	Gnanguenon, V.; Govoetchan, R.; Agossa, F. R.; OssÃ", R.; Oke-Agbo, F.; Azondekon, R.; Sovi, A.; Attolou, R.; Badirou, K.; Tokponnon, F. T.; Padonou, G. G.; Akogbeto, M. C.	2014	Transmission patterns of Plasmodium falciparum by Anopheles gambiae in Benin	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
35 5	Gobena, T.; Berhane, Y.; Worku, A.	2013	Women's knowledge and perceptions of malaria and use of malaria vector control interventions in Kersa, Eastern Ethiopia	Global Health Action	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
35 6	Gogue, C.; Wagman, J.; Tynuv, K.; Richardson, J.; Saibu, A.; Yihdego, Y.; Coleman, S.; Bart-Plange, C.; Mohamed, W.; Ofosu, A.; Steketee, R.; Robertson, M.	2017	Evaluating the epidemiological impact of shifting IRS products from 2011-2014 in Northern Ghana	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

357	Gogue, C.; Wagman, J.; Tynuv, K.; Richardson, J.; Saibu, A.; Yihdego, Y.; Coleman, S.; Bart-Plange, C.; Mohamed, W.; Ofori, A.; Steketee, R.; Robertson, M.	2017	An observational analysis of the impact of indoor residual spraying in the Northern, upper east and upper West regions of Ghana: 2011-2016	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
358	Gogue, C.; Wagman, J.; Tynuv, K.; Richardson, J.; Saibu, A.; Yihdego, Y.; Coleman, S.; Bart-Plange, C.; Mohamed, W.; Ofori, A.; Steketee, R.; Robertson, M.	2017	Analyses of the impact of shifting IRS operations on malaria transmission rates in the northern, upper east and upper west regions of Ghana: 2014-2015	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
359	Gogue, C.; Wagman, J.; Tynuv, K.; Saibu, A.; Yihdego, Y.; Malm, K.; Mohamed, W.; Akplu, W.; Tagoe, T.; Ofori, A.; Williams, I.; Asiedu, S.; Richardson, J.; Fornadel, C.; Slutsker, L.; Robertson, M.	2020	An observational analysis of the impact of indoor residual spraying in Northern, Upper East, and Upper West Regions of Ghana: 2014 through 2017	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
360	Govere, J.; Durrheim, D.; La Grange, K.; Mabuza, A.; Booman, M.	2000	Community knowledge and perceptions about malaria and practices influencing malaria control in Mpumalanga Province, South Africa	South African Medical Journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
361	Graves, P. M.; Osgood, D. E.; Thomson, M. C.; Sereke, K.; Araia, A.; Zerom, M.; Ceccato, P.; Bell, M.; Corral, J. D.; Ghebreselassie, S.; Brantly, E. P.; Ghebremeskel, T.	2008	Effectiveness of malaria control during changing climate conditions in Eritrea, 1998-2003	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
362	Griffin, J. T.	2015	The Interaction between Seasonality and Pulsed Interventions against Malaria in Their Effects on the Reproduction Number	PLoS Computational Biology	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

36 3	Griffin, J. T.; Hollingsworth, D.; Okell, L. C.; Churcher, T. S.; White, M.; Hinsley, W.; Bousema, T.; Drakeley, C. J.; Ferguson, N. M.; Basanez, M. G.; Ghani, A. C.	2010	Strategies towards plasmodium falciparum malaria elimination in Africa using currently available tools	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
36 4	Griffin, Jamie T.; Hollingsworth, T. Deirdre; Okell, Lucy C.; Churcher, Thomas S.; White, Michael; Hinsley, Wes; Bousema, Teun; Drakeley, Chris J.; Ferguson, Neil M.; Basanez, Maria- Gloria; Ghani, Azra C.	2010	Reducing Plasmodium falciparum malaria transmission in Africa: a model-based evaluation of intervention strategies	PLoS Medicine	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
36 5	Grigg, M. J.; Cox, J.; William, T.; Jelip, J.; Fornace, K. M.; Brock, P. M.; von Seidlein, L.; Barber, B. E.; Anstey, N. M.; Yeo, T. W.; Drakeley, C. J.	2017	Individual-level factors associated with the risk of acquiring human Plasmodium knowlesi malaria in Malaysia: a case-control study	The lancet planetary health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
36 6	Gryseels, C.; Durnez, L.; Gerrets, R.; Uk, S.; Suon, S.; Set, S.; Phoeuk, P.; Sluydts, V.; Heng, S.; Sochantha, T.; Coosemans, M.; Peeters Grietens, K.	2015	Re-imagining malaria: Heterogeneity of human and mosquito behaviour in relation to residual malaria transmission in Cambodia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrongstudy design - other
36 7	Guerra, C. A.; Fuseini, G.; Donfack, O. T.; Smith, J. M.; Ondo Mifumu, T. A.; Akadiri, G.; Eyang, D. E. M.; Eburu, C. O.; Motobe Vaz, L.; Micha, V. M.; Okenve, L. A.; Janes, C. R.; Andeme, R. M.; Rivas, M. R.; Phiri, W. P.; Slotman, M. A.; Smith, D. L.; Garca, G. A.	2020	Malaria outbreak in Riaba district, Bioko Island: Lessons learned	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data

368	Guerra, M.; De Sousa, B.; Ndong-Mabale, N.; Berzosa, P.; Arez, A. P.	2018	Malaria determining risk factors at the household level in two rural villages of mainland Equatorial Guinea	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
369	Gueye, Cara Smith; Gerigk, Michelle; Newby, Gretchen; Lourenco, Chris; Uusiku, Petrina; Liu, Jenny	2014	Namibia's path toward malaria elimination: a case study of malaria strategies and costs along the northern border	BMC Public Health	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
370	Guhey, A.; Sekaran, V. C.; Monteiro, A. D.; Motwani, N.	2019	An epidemiological study to assess the environmental and socio-cultural determinants of malaria in coastal Karnataka	Journal of Communicable Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
371	Gul, D.; Rodríguez-Rodríguez, D.; Nate, E.; Auwan, A.; Salib, M.; Lorry, L.; Keven, J. B.; Katusele, M.; Rosado, J.; Hofmann, N.; Ome-Kaius, M.; Koepfli, C.; Felger, I.; Kazura, J. W.; Hetzel, M. W.; Mueller, I.; Karl, S.; Clements, A. C. A.; Fowkes, F. J. I.; Laman, M.; Robinson, L. J.	2021	Investigating differences in village-level heterogeneity of malaria infection and household risk factors in Papua New Guinea	Scientific reports	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
372	Gunasekaran, K.; Sahu, S. S.; Jambulingam, P.; Das, P. K.	2005	DDT indoor residual spray, still an effective tool to control Anopheles fluviatilis-transmitted Plasmodium falciparum malaria in India	Tropical Medicine & International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
373	Guyatt, H. L.; Corlett, S. K.; Robinson, T. P.; Ochola, S. A.; Snow, R. W.	2002	Malaria prevention in highland Kenya: Indoor residual house-spraying vs. insecticide-treated bednets	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
374	Guyatt, H. L.; Kinnear, J.; Burini, M.; Snow, R. W.	2002	A comparative cost analysis of insecticide-treated nets and indoor residual spraying in highland Kenya	Health Policy & Planning	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

37 5	Habyarimana, F.; Ramroop, S.	2020	Prevalence and risk factors associated with malaria among children aged six months to 14 years old in Rwanda: Evidence from 2017 Rwanda malaria indicator survey	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
37 6	Hailu, A.; Lindtjrn, B.; Deressa, W.; Gari, T.; Loha, E.; Robberstad, B.	2016	Equity in long-lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying for malaria prevention in a rural South Central Ethiopia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
37 7	Haindongo, E. H.; Mumbengegwi, D. R.; Bock, R.; Sturrock, H.; Gosling, R.	2015	An investigation into the risk factors of malaria in a pre-elimination rural and peri-urban setting of Northern Namibia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
37 8	Hakizimana, E.; Iranzi, G.; Munyakanage, D.; Muthoni, R.; Karema, C.	2014	Insecticide resistance status in Anopheles Gambiae s.l. following the scale up of malaria control interventions in Rwanda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
37 9	Hakizimana, E.; Munyakanage, D.; Piercefield, E.; Murindahabi, M.; Uwimana, A.; Uyizeye, D.; Eckert, E.; Munguti, K.; Obenauer, P.; Mbituyumuremyi, A.	2018	Impact of indoor residual spraying in reducing malaria cases in Rwanda, 2013-2017	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
38 0	Hamainza, B.; Fraser, M.; Chizema-Kawasha, E.; Silumbe, K.; Mwanza-Ingwe, M.; Moonga, H.; Yeta, A.; Mudenda, M.; Masaninga, F.; Miller, J. M.	2019	Zambia malaria indicator survey 2018: Continued progress toward national coverage and burden reduction targets	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
38 1	Hamainza, B.; Sikaala, C. H.; Moonga, H. B.; Chanda, J.; Chinula, D.; Mwenda, M.	2016	Incremental impact upon malaria transmission of supplementing pyrethroid-impregnated long-lasting insecticidal nets with indoor residual spraying using pyrethroids or the	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

			organophosphate, pirimiphos methyl		
38 2	Hamel, M. J.; Otieno, P.; Bayoh, N.; Kariuki, S.; Laserson, K.; Akhwale, W.; Williamson, J.; Slutsker, L.; Gimnig, J.	2009	Does indoor residual spraying provide added protection to insecticide treated nets in preventing malaria - Preliminary results of an incidence cohort	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
38 3	Hamel, M. J.; Otieno, P.; Bayoh, N.; Kariuki, S.; Were, V.; Marwanga, D.; Laserson, K. F.; Williamson, J.; Slutsker, L.; Gimnig, J.	2011	The combination of indoor residual spraying and insecticide-treated nets provides added protection against malaria compared with insecticide-treated nets alone	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
38 4	Hamer, D. H.; Singh, M. P.; Wylie, B. J.; Yeboah-Antwi, K.; Tuchman, J.; Desai, M.; Udhayakumar, V.; Gupta, P.; Brooks, M. I.; Shukla, M. M.; Awasthy, K.; Sabin, L.; MacLeod, W. B.; Dash, A. P.; Singh, N.	2009	Burden of malaria in pregnancy in Jharkhand State, India	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
38 5	Hamilton, M.; Mahian, G.; Werst, E.; Bri, O.; Cibulskis, R.; Cameron, E.; Bhatt, S.; Pretorius, C.; Korenromp, E. L.	2016	Spectrum-malaria: A user-friendly projection tool for health impact assessment and strategic planning for malaria programs in sub-saharan Africa	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
38 6	Hamilton, M.; Mahiane, G.; Werst, E.; Sanders, R.; Bri, O.; Smith, T.; Cibulskis, R.; Cameron, E.; Bhatt, S.; Weiss, D. J.; Gething, P. W.; Pretorius, C.; Korenromp, E. L.	2017	Spectrum-Malaria: A user-friendly projection tool for health impact assessment and strategic planning by malaria control programmes in sub-Saharan Africa	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

387	Hamre, K. E. S.; Ayodo, G.; Hodges, J. S.; John, C. C.	2020	Amass insecticide-treated bed net distribution campaign reduced malaria risk on an individual but not population level in a highland epidemic-prone area of Kenya	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
388	Hamre, K. E. S.; Hodges, J. S.; Ayodo, G.; John, C. C.	2020	Lack of consistent malaria incidence hotspots in a highland Kenyan area during a 10-year period of very low and unstable transmission	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
389	Hassen, H. Y.; Ali, J. H.	2016	The association between chronic undernutrition and malaria among Ethiopian children aged 6 - 59 months: A facility-based case-control study	SAJCH South African Journal of Child Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
390	Hast, M. A.; Chaponda, M.; Bridges, D. J.; Larsen, D.; Searle, K. M.; Lupiya, J.; Kobayashi, T.; Shields, T. M.; Mulenga, M.; Curriero, F. C.; Moss, W. J.	2015	The effectiveness of a targeted indoor residual spray campaign with pirimiphos-methyl in Nchelenge district, Northern Zambia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
391	Hast, M. A.; Chaponda, M.; Searle, K. M.; Lupiya, J.; Lubinda, J.; Kobayashi, T.; Shields, T. M.; Mulenga, M.; Curriero, F. C.; Moss, W. J.	2015	The use of GPS data loggers to describe spatiotemporal movement patterns and correlations with malaria risk in an area of hyperendemic malaria in Northern Zambia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
392	Hast, M. A.; Stevenson, J. C.; Muleba, M.; Chaponda, M.; Kabuya, J. B.; Mulenga, M.; Jones, C. M.; Lessler, J.; Shields, T.; Moss, W. J.; Norris, D.	2016	Characterizing the impact of dynamic vector abundance on individual malaria prevalence in a high transmission area of Northern Zambia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
393	Hast, M.; Chaponda, M.; Lupiya, J.; Muleba, M.; Kabuya, J. B.; Kobayashi, T.;	2017	Evaluating three years of a targeted indoor residual spraying (IRS) campaign	American journal of tropical	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	Shields, T. M.; Curriero, F. C.; Lessler, J.; Mulenga, M.; Stevenson, J. C.; Norris, D. E.; Moss, W. J.		in a high transmission area of Northern Zambia	medicine and hygiene	
39 4	Hast, M.; Searle, K. M.; Chononda, M.; Lupiya, J.; Lubinda, J.; Sikalima, J.; Kobayashi, T.; Shields, T.; Mulenga, M.; Lessler, J.; Moss, W. J.	2019	The use of GPS data loggers to describe the impact of spatio- temporal movement patterns on malaria control in a high- transmission area of northern Zambia	International journal of health geographics	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
39 5	Hast, Marisa A.; Chononda, Mike; Muleba, Mbangi; Kabuya, Jean-Bertin; Lupiya, James; Kobayashi, Tamaki; Shields, Timothy; Lessler, Justin; Mulenga, Modest; Stevenson, Jennifer C.; Norris, Douglas E.; Moss, William J.	2019	The Impact of 3 Years of Targeted Indoor Residual Spraying With Pirmiphos- Methyl on Malaria Parasite Prevalence in a High-Transmission Area of Northern Zambia	American Journal of Epidemiology	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
39 6	Hategeka, Celestin; Tuyisenge, Germaine; Bayingana, Christian; Tuyisenge, Lisine	2019	Effects of scaling up various community-level interventions on child mortality in Burundi, Kenya, Rwanda, Uganda and Tanzania: a modeling study	Global health research and policy	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
39 7	Herdiana, H.	2012	Progress toward malaria elimination in sabang, aceh, indonesia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
39 8	Hergott, D. B.; Schwabe, C.; Garcia, G.; Phiri, W. P.; Perry, M.; Segura, J. L.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Cook, J.	2016	Stratification of indoor residual spraying (IRS) in Bioko Island: Methodology and impact	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
39 9	Hetzl, M. W.; Pulford, J.; Timbi, D.; Koimbu, G.; Barnadas, C.; Siba, P. M.; Mueller, I.	2015	Dynamic changes in prevalence and incidence of malaria after intensifying control across Papua New Guinea	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

400	Hetzel, M. W.; Saweri, O. P.; Kuadima, J. J.; Smith, I.; Lorry, L.; Tandrapah, A.; Jamea-Maiasa, S.; Robinson, L. J.; Siba, P. M.; Pulford, J.	2018	Major resurgence of malaria follows previously unprecedented decline in Papua New Guinea	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
401	Heukelbach, Jorg; Kweka, Eliningaya J.; Manyiri, Paulina; Mauka, Wilhelmus; Mazigo, Humphrey D.; Mnyone, Ladslaus L.; Obasy, Emmanuel; Zinga, Maria	2011	Knowledge; Attitudes; and Practices about Malaria and its Control in Rural Northwest Tanzania	Malaria Research and Treatment	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
402	Hiwat, H.	2011	Novel strategies lead to near elimination of malaria in previously high-risk areas in suriname, South America	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
403	Hiwat, H.; Hardjopawiro, L. S.; Takken, W.; Villegas, L.	2012	Novel strategies lead to pre-elimination of malaria in previously high-risk areas in Suriname, South America	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
404	Hlongwana, K. W.; Mabaso, M. L. H.; Kunene, S.; Govender, D.; Maharaj, R.	2009	Community knowledge, attitudes and practices (KAP) on malaria in Swaziland: A country earmarked for malaria elimination	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
405	Hlongwana, K. W.; Zitha, A.; Mabuza, A. M.; Maharaj, R.	2011	Knowledge and practices towards malaria amongst residents of Bushbuckridge, Mpumalanga, South Africa	African Journal of Primary Health Care and Family Medicine	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
406	Ho, D. T.; Van Bortel, W.; Sochantha, T.; Keokenchanh, K.; BriÅ«t, O. J. T.; Coosemans, M.	2005	Behavioural heterogeneity of Anopheles species in ecologically different localities in Southeast Asia: A challenge for vector control	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
407	Hoek Spaans, R.; Stanton, M. C.; Jones, C. M.	2019	Spatio-temporal malaria case distribution in the presence of indoor residual spraying (IRS) at a plantation in southern Malawi	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

408	Homan, T.; Hiscox, A.; Smith, T.; Takken, W.	2015	A geographically heterogeneous context and spatially varying risk factors for malaria at Lake Victoria	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
409	Hosseini, M.; Korenromp, E.; Cibulskis, R.; Viisainen, K.; Atun, R.	2011	Progress toward millennium development goal 6 and roll back malaria targets in global fund-supported malaria programs	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
410	Howard, N.; Guinness, L.; Rowland, M.; Durrani, N.; Hansen, K. S.	2017	Cost-effectiveness of adding indoor residual spraying to case management in Afghan refugee settlements in Northwest Pakistan during a prolonged malaria epidemic	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
411	Hsiang, Michelle S.; Mumbengegwi, Davis; Chimumbwa, John	2021	Mini-outbreak response for malaria using indoor residual spraying	Lancet	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
412	Hsiang, Michelle S.; Ntuku, Henry; Roberts, Kathryn W.; Dufour, Mi-Suk Kang; Whittemore, Brooke; Tambo, Munyaradzi; McCreesh, Patrick; Medzihradsky, Oliver F.; Prach, Lisa M.; Siloka, Griffith; Siame, Noel; Gueye, Cara Smith; Schrubbe, Leah; Wu, Lindsey; Scott, Valerie; Tessema, Sofonias; Greenhouse, Bryan; Erlank, Erica; Koekemoer, Lizette L.; Sturrock, Hugh J. W.	2020	Effectiveness of reactive focal mass drug administration and reactive focal vector control to reduce malaria transmission in the low malaria-endemic setting of Namibia: a cluster-randomised controlled, open-label, two-by-two factorial design trial	Lancet	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
413	Hutton, R.; Loveridge, R.; Welton, R.; Weeden, D.; Woods, P.; Kayani, G.; Manube, G.; Paiva, D.; Tomo, C.; Lorry, K.; Aliabe, N.	2007	Community malaria control within a petroleum project impact area in Papua New Guinea	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	Bisibister, L.; Rozendaal, J.				
41 4	Impact of Insecticide Resistance on Vector Control	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
41 5	Impact of resistance in mosquitoes on the efficacy of long-lasting insecticidal nets alone and in combination with indoor residual spraying on malaria transmission in insecticide resistant areas in India	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
41 6	Impoinvil, D.; Anagonou, R.; Patel, F.; Jacob, D.; Dismer, A. M.; Merilien, J. B.; Hamre, K. E.; Holmes, K.; Lafortune, W.; Lemoine, J. F.; Chang, M. A.	2019	Coverage of indoor residual spraying (IRS) and impact of IRS in anopheles populations in sites of elevated malaria transmission in Grande anse, Haiti	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
41 7	Increased risks of malaria due to limited residual life of insecticide and outdoor biting versus protection by combined use of nets and indoor residual spraying on Bioko Island, Equatorial Guinea	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
41 8	Ingabire, C. M.; Hakizimana, E.; Kateera, F.; Rulisa, A.; Van Den Borne, B.; Nieuwold, I.; Muvunyi, C.; Koenraadt, C. J. M.; Van Vugt, M.; Mutesa, L.; Alaii, J.	2016	Using an intervention mapping approach for planning, implementing and assessing a community-led project towards malaria elimination in the Eastern Province of Rwanda	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
41 9	Ingabire, C. M.; Rulisa, A.; Alaii, J.; Hakizimana, E.; Kateera, F.; Muvunyi,	2014	Community perceptions and practices towards malaria control measures in Rwanda: A descriptive qualitative study	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

	C.; Mutesa, L.; Van Den Borne, B.				
420	Ingabire, C. M.; Rulisa, A.; Van Kempen, L.; Muvunyi, C.; Koenraadt, C. J. M.; Van Vugt, M.; Mutesa, L.; Van Den Borne, B.; Alaii, J.	2015	Factors impeding the acceptability and use of malaria preventive measures: Implications for malaria elimination in eastern Rwanda	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
421	Ippolito, M. M.; Searle, K. M.; Hamapumbu, H.; Shields, T. M.; Stevenson, J. C.; Thuma, P. E.; Moss, W. J.	2017	House structure is associated with Plasmodium falciparum infection in a low-transmission setting in southern Zambia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
422	Island, B.; Maluku, N.	2000	The human behavioral and socioeconomic determinants of malaria in	Journal of epidemiology	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
423	Ismail, I. A.; Notananda, V.; Schepens, J.	1975	Studies on malaria and responses of Anopheles balabacensis balabacensis and Anopheles minimus to DDT residual spraying in Thailand	Acta tropica	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
424	Isrctn,	2010	Effect of malaria prevention on in-hospital mortality among severely ill tuberculosis patients	http://www.who.int/trialsearch/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=ISRCTN83944306	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
425	ISRCTN01738840	Year not provided	Spraying And Nets Towards malaria Elimination	.	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
426	ISRCTN07404145	Year not provided	Entomological research, training and prevention strategies for malaria in Africa	.	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
427	Iwuafor, Anthony Achizie; Egwuatu, Chukwudi Charles; Nnachi, Agwu Ulu; Ita Okokon, Ita; Ogban, Godwin Ibitham; Akujobi, Comfort Nneka; Egwuatu, Tenny Obiageli; Ita, Ita Okokon	2016	Malaria Parasitaemia and the use of insecticide-treated nets (INTs) for malaria control amongst under-5 year old children in Calabar, Nigeria	BMC Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray

428	Izadi, Shahrokh	2016	The effects of electricity network development besides routine malaria control measures in an underdeveloped region in the pre-elimination phase	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
429	Jakubowski, A.; Stearns, S. C.; Thirumurthy, H.	2016	Impact of President's Malaria Initiative on all-cause child mortality from 1996 to 2014: A difference-in-differences analysis	Annals of Global Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
430	Jakubowski, Aleksandra; Stearns, Sally C.; Kruk, Margaret E.; Angeles, Gustavo; Thirumurthy, Harsha	2017	The US President's Malaria Initiative and under-5 child mortality in sub-Saharan Africa: A difference-in-differences analysis	PLoS Medicine	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
431	Jambou, R.; Ranaivo, L.; Raharimalala, L.; Randrianaivo, J.; Rakotomanana, F.; Modiano, D.; Pietra, V.; Boisier, P.; Rabarijaona, L.; Rabe, T.; Raveloson, N.; De Giorgi, F.	2001	Malaria in the highlands of Madagascar after five years of indoor house spraying of DDT	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
432	Jawara, M.; Mwesigwa, J.; Daitta, M.; Adiamoh, M. H.; Affara, M.; Worwui, A.; Di Tanna, G. L.; Achan, J.; D'Alessandro, U.	2015	Changing vector population dynamics with an emerging population of anopheles funestus in a setting of high malaria control interventions in the Gambia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
433	Jima, D.; Getachew, A.; Bilak, H.; Steketee, R. W.; Emerson, P. M.; Graves, P. M.; Gebre, T.; Reithinger, R.; Hwang, J.	2010	Malaria indicator survey 2007, Ethiopia: Coverage and use of major malaria prevention and control interventions	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
434	John, C. C.; Riedesel, M. A.; Magak, N. G.; Lindblade, K. A.; Menge, D. M.; Hodges, J. S.; Vulule, J. M.; Akhwale, W.	2009	Possible interruption of malaria transmission, highland Kenya, 2007-2008	Emerging Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
435	John, C. C.; Riedesel, M. A.; Magak, N. G.; Menge, D. M.; Lindblade, K. A.	2009	Possible interruption of malaria transmission in two highland areas of Kenya	American journal of tropical	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	Vulule, J. M.; Hodges, J. A.; Akhwale, W.			medicine and hygiene	
436	Jumbam, D. T.; Stevenson, J. S.; Grieco, J. P.; Ahern, L.; Hamainza, B.; Sikaala, C. H.; Chanda-Kapata, P.; Matoba, J.; Achee, N. L.	2016	Knowledge, attitudes and practices (KAP) assessment of malaria interventions in zambia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
437	Jumbam, Desmond T.; Stevenson, Jennifer C.; Matoba, Japhet; Grieco, John P.; Ahern, Lacey N.; Hamainza, Busiku; Sikaala, Chadwick H.; Chanda-Kapata, Pascalina; Cardol, Esther I.; Munachoonga, Passwell; Achee, Nicole L.	2020	Knowledge, attitudes and practices assessment of malaria interventions in rural Zambia	BMC Public Health	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
438	Kabunga, N.; Duggan, C.; Bashaasha, B.; Agaba, E.; Webb, P.; Ghosh, S.; Griffiths, J.	2017	Cattle ownership, childhood malaria and anemia in Uganda	Annals of Nutrition and Metabolism	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
439	Kafy	2017	Impact of insecticide resistance in Anopheles arabiensis on malaria incidence and prevalence in Sudan and the costs of mitigation	Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
440	Kagaya, W.; Konishi, A.; Kurihara, K.; Chan, C.; Gitaka, J.; Kongere, J.; Uchihashi, K.; Okomo, G.; Kaneko, A.	2019	The impact of indoor residual spraying for malaria prevalence in homa bay county, Kenya: An observational study	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
441	Kambarami, R.; Mandisarisa, J.; Chikhata, F.; Nyadundu, S.; Mashizha, S.; Mafaune, P.; Mberikunashe, J.; Mutseyekwa, F.;	2017	A situational assessment of the drivers of malaria in communities along the Zimbabwe-Mozambique border of Manicaland province	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	Mandigo, R. G.; Gilroy, K.				
44 2	Kamuliwo, M.; Chanda, E.; Haque, U.; Mwanza-Ingwe, M.; Sikaala, C.; Katebe-Sakala, C.; Mukonka, V. M.; Norris, D. E.; Smith, D. L.; Glass, G. E.; Moss, W. J.	2013	The changing burden of malaria and association with vector control interventions in Zambia using district-level surveillance data, 2006- 2011	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
44 3	Kamuliwo, M.; Kirk, K. E.; Chanda, E.; Elbadry, M. A.; Lubinda, J.; Weppelmann, T. A.; Mukonka, V. M.; Zhang, W.; Mushinge, G.; Mwanza-Ingwe, M.; Haque, U.	2015	Spatial patterns and determinants of malaria infection during pregnancy in Zambia	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
44 4	Kamya, M. R.; Kakuru, A.; Muhindo, M.; Arinaitwe, E.; Nankabirwa, J. I.; Rek, J.; Bigira, V.; Kapisi, J.; Wanzira, H.; Achan, J.; Natureeba, P.; Gasasira, A.; Havlir, D.; Jagannathan, P.; Rosenthal, P. J.; Rodriguez-Barraquer, I.; Dorsey, G.	2020	The impact of control interventions on malaria burden in young children in a historically high- transmission district of Uganda: A pooled analysis of cohort studies from 2007 to 2018	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
44 5	KanÃ©, F.; KeÃ©ta, M.; TraorÃ©, B.; Diawara, S. I.; Bane, S.; Diarra, S.; Sogoba, N.; Doumbia, S.	2020	Performance of IRS on malaria prevalence and incidence using pirimiphos-methyl in the context of pyrethroid resistance in Koulikoro region, Mali	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
44 6	Kanyangarara, M.; Mamini, E.; Mharakurwa, S.; Munyati, S.; Gwanzura, L.; Kobayashi, T.; Shields, T.; Mullany, L. C.; Mutambu, S.; Mason, P. R.;	2016	Reduction in malaria incidence following indoor residual spraying with actellic 300 CS in a setting with pyrethroid resistance: Mutasa District, Zimbabwe	PloS one	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

	Curriero, F. C.; Moss, W. J.				
44 7	Karunajeewa, H.; Berman, J.	2020	Is the Epidemiology of Plasmodium knowlesi Changing, and What Does This Mean for Malaria Control in Southeast Asia?	Clinical Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
44 8	Kassa, A. W.; Tamiru, M. A.; Yeshanew, A. G.	2015	Assessment of control measures and trends of malaria in Burie-Zuria district, west Gojjam zone, Amhara region, north west Ethiopia	Malaria Research and Treatment	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
44 9	Katrak, S.; Nayebare, P.; Rek, J.; Arinaitwe, E.; Nankabirwa, J. I.; Kanya, M.; Dorsey, G.; Rosenthal, P.; Greenhouse, B.	2017	Clinical consequences of submicroscopic malaria parasitemia in Ugandan children	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
45 0	Katureebe, Agaba; Zinszer, Kate; Arinaitwe, Emmanuel; Rek, John; Kakande, Elijah; Charland, Katia; Kigozi, Ruth; Kilama, Maxwell; Nankabirwa, Joaniter; Yeka, Adoke; Mawejje, Henry; Mpimbaza, Arthur; Katamba, Henry; Donnelly, Martin J.; Rosenthal, Philip J.; Drakeley, Chris; Lindsay, Steve W.; Staedke, Sarah G.; Smith, David L.; Greenhouse, Bryan	2016	Measures of Malaria Burden after Long-Lasting Insecticidal Net Distribution and Indoor Residual Spraying at Three Sites in Uganda: A Prospective Observational Study	PLoS Medicine	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
45 1	Katureebe, Agaba; Zinszer, Kate; Arinaitwe, Emmanuel; Rek, John; Kakande, Elijah; Charland, Katia; Kigozi, Ruth; Kilama, Maxwell; Nankabirwa, Joaniter;	2016	Measures of Malaria Burden after Long-Lasting Insecticidal Net Distribution and Indoor Residual Spraying at Three Sites in Uganda: A Prospective Observational Study	PLoS Medicine	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

	Yeka, Adoke; Mawejje, Henry; Mpimbaza, Arthur; Katamba, Henry; Donnelly, Martin J.; Rosenthal, Philip J.; Drakeley, Chris; Lindsay, Steve W.; Staedke, Sarah G.; Smith, David L.; Greenhouse, Bryan				
45 2	Kaufman, M. R.; Rweyemamu, D.; Koenker, H.; MacHa, J.	2012	My children and i will no longer suffer from malaria: A qualitative study of the acceptance and rejection of indoor residual spraying to prevent malaria in Tanzania	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
45 3	Kayentao, K.; Florey, L. S.; Mihigo, J.; Doumbia, A.; Diallo, A.; KonÃ©, D.; Doumbo, O.; Eckert, E.	2018	Impact evaluation of malaria control interventions on morbidity and all-cause child mortality in Mali, 2000-2012	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
45 4	Keating	2011	Evaluating indoor residual spray for reducing malaria infection prevalence in Eritrea: results from a community randomized control trial	Acta tropica	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
45 5	Keating, J.; Yukich, J. O.; Miller, J. M.; Scates, S.; Hamainza, B.; Eisele, T. P.; Bennett, A.	2021	Retrospective evaluation of the effectiveness of indoor residual spray with pirimiphosâ€methyl (Actellic) on malaria transmission in Zambia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
45 6	Kelly, G. C.; Nguyen, T. X.; Ngo, T. D.; Lover, A. A.; Pham, H. Q.; Martin, N.; Nguyen, X. X.; Nguyen, A. Q.; Tran, D. T.; Ohrt, C.	2015	Implementing enhanced high-resolution surveillance using spatial decision support systems (SDSS) to guide targeted rapid response in multidrug resistant areas of vietnam	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
45 7	Keno, T. D.; Makinde, O. D.; Obsu, L. L.	2021	Optimal control and cost effectiveness analysis of SIRS malaria disease model with temperature variability factor	Journal of Mathematical and Fundamental Sciences	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

458	Kern, S. E.; Tiono, A. B.; Makanga, M.; GbadoÃ©, A.; Premji, Z.; Gaye, O.; Sagara, I.; Ubben, D.; Cousin, M.; Oladiran, F.; Sander, O.; Ogotu, B.	2011	Community screening and treatment of asymptomatic carriers of Plasmodium falciparum with artemether-lumefantrine to reduce malaria disease burden: A modelling and simulation analysis	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
459	Kesteman, T.; Randrianariveლოსია, M.; Mattern, C.; Raboanary, E.; Pourette, D.; Girond, F.; Raharimanga, V.; Randrianasolo, L.; Piola, P.; Rogier, C.	2014	Nationwide evaluation of malaria infections, morbidity, mortality, and coverage of malaria control interventions in Madagascar	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
460	Kesteman, T.; Randrianariveლოსია, M.; Piola, P.; Rogier, C.	2014	Evaluation of the effectiveness of malaria control activities by simultaneous nationwide cross-sectional and case-control surveys in Madagascar	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
461	Kesteman, T.; Randrianariveლოსია, M.; Piola, P.; Rogier, C.	2014	Assessing the impact of vector control interventions by measuring their effectiveness-what has been done in Madagascar	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
462	Kesteman, T.; Randrianariveლოსია, M.; Raharimanga, V.; Randrianasolo, L.; Piola, P.; Rogier, C.	2016	Effectiveness of malaria control interventions in Madagascar: A nationwide case-control survey	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
463	Keys, H. M.; Noland, G. S.; De Rochars, M. B.; Blount, S.; Gonzales, M.	2019	Prevalence of malaria and lymphatic filariasis in bateyes of the Dominican Republic	Infectious diseases of poverty	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
464	Khairy, S.; Al-Surimi, K.; Ali, A.; Shubily, H. M.; Al Walaan, N.; Househ, M.; El-Metwally, A.	2017	Knowledge, attitude and practice about malaria in south-western Saudi Arabia: A household-based cross-sectional survey	Journal of Infection and Public Health	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
465	Kheang, S. T.	2014	Addressing artemisinin-resistant malaria by identifying malaria hotspots in Cambodia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

46 6	Kheang, Soy T.; Por, Ir; Sovannaroeth, Siv; Dysoley, Lek; Chea, Huch; Po, Ly; AlMossawi, Hala J.; Imran, Abu Al; Kak, Neeraj	2021	Cambodia malaria indicator survey 2020: Implications for malaria elimination	MalariaWorld journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
46 7	Khosa, E.; Kuonza, L. R.; Kruger, P.; Maimela, E.	2013	Towards the elimination of malaria in South Africa: A review of surveillance data in Mutale Municipality, Limpopo Province, 2005 to 2010	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
46 8	Kigozi, R.; Baxi, S. M.; Gasasira, A.; Sserwanga, A.; Kakeeto, S.; Nasr, S.; Rubahika, D.; Dissanayake, G.; Kanya, M. R.; Filler, S.; Dorsey, G.	2012	Indoor residual spraying of insecticide and malaria morbidity in a high transmission intensity area of Uganda	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
46 9	Kigozi, S. P.; Kigozi, R. N.; Epstein, A.; Mpimbaza, A.; Sserwanga, A.; Yeka, A.; Nankabirwa, J. I.; Halliday, K.; Pullan, R. L.; Rutazaana, D.; Sebuguzi, C. M.; Opigo, J.; Kanya, M. R.; Staedke, S. G.; Dorsey, G.; Greenhouse, B.; Rodriguez-Barraquer, I.	2020	Rapid shifts in the age-specific burden of malaria following successful control interventions in four regions of Uganda	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
47 0	Kim, D.; Fedak, K.; Kramer, R.	2012	Reduction of malaria prevalence by indoor residual spraying: A meta-regression analysis	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
47 1	Kishimba, R. S.; Mghamba, J.; Sheuya, S.	2014	High under-five case fatality rate in the recent malaria upsurge in Muleba, Tanzania	International journal of infectious diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
47 2	Kitidamrongsuk, P.; Jareinpituk, S.; Pattanasin, S.; Viwatwongkasem, C.; Soontornpipit, P.; Silabuttra, J.; Satitvipawee, P.	2016	Determinants of Impregnated Net Ownership and Utilization in Rural Community on the Thai-Myanmar Border in Prachuab Khiri Khan, Thailand	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray

47 3	Kleinschmidt, I.; Govere, J.; Cook, J.; Matebula, P.; Hlongwana, K.; Morris, N.; Raman, J.; Agubuzo, E.; Serocharan, I.; Bath, D.; Biggs, J.; Zitha, A.; Machaba, E.; Mabuza, A.; Kruger, P.; Drakeley, C.; Coetzee, M.	2017	Is targeted reactive vector control a noninferior substitute for generalized indoor residual spraying in areas of very low malaria transmission-results from a cluster randomized trial	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
47 4	Kleinschmidt, I.; Mnzava, A. P.; Kafy, H. T.; Mbogo, C.; Bashir, A. I.; Bigoga, J.; Adechoubou, A.; Raghavendra, K.; Knox, T. B.; Malik, E. M.; et al.,	2015	Design of a study to determine the impact of insecticide resistance on malaria vector control: a multi-country investigation	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
47 5	Kleinschmidt, I.; Schwabe, C.; Shiva, M.; Segura, J. L.; Sima, V.; Mabunda, S. J.; Coleman, M.	2009	Combining Indoor Residual Spraying and insecticide treated net interventions	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
47 6	Kleinschmidt, I.; Sharp, B.; Benavente, L. E.; Schwabe, C.; Torrez, M.; Kuklinski, J.; Morris, N.; Raman, J.; Carter, J.	2006	Reduction in infection with Plasmodium falciparum one year after the introduction of malaria control interventions on Bioko island, Equatorial Guinea	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
47 7	Kleinschmidt, I.; Torrez, M.; Schwabe, C.; Benavente, L.; Seocharan, I.; Jituboh, D.; Nseng, G.; Sharp, B.	2007	Factors influencing the effectiveness of malaria control in Bioko Island, Equatorial Guinea	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
47 8	Kleinschmidt, Immo; Bradley, John; Knox, Tessa Bellamy; Mnzava, Abraham Peter; Kafy, Hmooda Toto; Mbogo, Charles; Ismail, Bashir Adam; Bigoga, Jude D.; Adechoubou, Alioun; Raghavendra, Kamaraju; Cook, Jackie; Malik, Elfatih M.; Nkuni, Zinga	2018	Implications of insecticide resistance for malaria vector control with long- lasting insecticidal nets: a WHO-coordinated, prospective, international, observational cohort study	Lancet Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	JosÃ©; Macdonald, Michael; Bayoh, Nabie; Ochomo, Eric; Fondjo, Etienne; Awono-Ambene, Herman Parfait; Etang, Josiane; Akogbeto, Martin				
479	Kobayashi, T.; Ippolito, M. M.; Sikalima, J.; Lupiya, J. S.; Chaponda, M.; Moss, W. J.	2019	Subclinical plasmodium falciparum infection among children and adults residing in a high malaria transmission community	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
480	Kolawole, O. T.; Stephen, A. O.	2016	Mothersâ€™ Socioeconomic Differentials and Management of Malaria in Nigeria	SAGE Open	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
481	Korenromp, E.; MahianÃ©, G.; Hamilton, M.; Pretorius, C.; Cibulskis, R.; Lauer, J.; Smith, T. A.; BriÃ©t, O. J. T.	2016	Malaria intervention scale-up in Africa: Effectiveness predictions for health programme planning tools, based on dynamic transmission modelling	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
482	Kroeger, Axel; Ayala, C; Lara, A Medina	2002	Unit costs for house spraying and bednet impregnation with residual insecticides in Colombia: a management tool for the control of vector-borne disease	Annals of Tropical Medicine & Parasitology	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
483	Kunene, S.	2006	Impact of Indoor Residual House Spraying on Malaria in Swaziland	Afr. health monit. (Online)	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
484	Lalji, S.; Mwaipape, O.; Lusinde, R.; Mutafungwa, A.; Colaco, R.; Mandike, R.; Ngondi, J.	2014	Examination of 2006-2013 malaria incidences in relation to the scaling of preventative control interventions in Muleba district in Northwest Tanzania	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
485	Lalji, S.; Salum, A. R.; Suleiman, A. A.; Abdulwahid, H. A. M.; Lusinde, R.; McElroy, P.; Ramsan, M.; Ekenna, U.; Kafuko, J. M.; Molteni, F.	2012	Shifting from blanket to targeted indoor residual spraying for malaria control in zanzibar: A novel approach for integrated management of malaria vectors	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

48 6	Larsen, D. A.; Martin, A.; Pollard, D.; Nielsen, C. F.; Hamainza, B.; Burns, M.; Stevenson, J.; Winters, A.	2020	Leveraging risk maps of malaria vector abundance to guide control efforts reduces malaria incidence in Eastern Province, Zambia	Scientific reports	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
48 7	Lee, B. Y.; Bartsch, S. M.; Stone, N. T. B.; Zhang, S.; Brown, S. T.; Chatterjee, C.; DePasse, J. V.; Zenkov, E.; Briñón, O. J. T.; Mendis, C.; Viisainen, K.; Candrinho, B.; Colborn, J.	2017	The economic value of long-lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying implementation in Mozambique	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
48 8	Lee, M. C.; Dixit, A.; Yan, G.	2018	Modeling the added benefits of supplemental intervention tools on malaria transmission in endemic settings in western kenya highland	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
48 9	Lee, P. W.; Liu, C. T.; Do Rosario, V. E.; De Sousa, B.; Rampao, H. S.; Shaio, M. F.	2010	Potential threat of malaria epidemics in a low transmission area, as exemplified by so Tomã and Prãncipe	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
49 0	Lee, Pei-Wen; Liu, Chia-Tai; do Rosario, Virgilio E.; de Sousa, Bruno; Rampao, Herodes Sacramento; Shaio, Men-Fang	2010	Potential threat of malaria epidemics in a low transmission area, as exemplified by Sao Tome and Principe	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: duplicate
49 1	Lee, Pei-Wen; Liu, Chia-Tai; Rampao, Herodes Sacramento; do Rosario, Virgilio E.; Shaio, Men-Fang	2010	Pre-elimination of malaria on the island of Principe	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
49 2	Lien, F. T.; Wen, C. C.; Ferreira, M. C.; Cheng, H. W.; Rampão, H. S.; Jih, C. L.	2008	Short report: Rapid control of malaria by means of indoor residual spraying of alphacypermethrin in the democratic republic of São Tomã and prãncipe	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
49 3	Liu, Hui; Xu, Jian-Wei; Yang, Heng-Lin; Li, Mei; Sun, Cheng-De; Yin, Yi-Jie; Zheng, Zhi-Liang; Zhang, Guang-	2016	Investigation and control of a Plasmodium falciparum malaria outbreak in Shan Special Region II of Myanmar	Infectious diseases of poverty	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data

	Yun; Yu, Ai-Shui; Yang, Yong-Hui; Li, Chun-Hui; Ai, Shui		along the China-Myanmar Border from June to December 2014		
49 4	Liu, J. X.; Bousema, T.; Zelman, B.; Gesase, S.; Hashim, R.; Maxwell, C.; Chandramohan, D.; Gosling, R.	2014	Is housing quality associated with malaria incidence among young children and mosquito vector numbers? Evidence from Korogwe, Tanzania	PloS one	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
49 5	Loha, E.; Deressa, W.; Gari, T.; Balkew, M.; Kenea, O.; Solomon, T.; Hailu, A.; Robberstad, B.; Assegid, M.; Overgaard, H. J.; et al.,	2017	Combining long-lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying for malaria prevention in Ethiopia: a cluster randomized controlled trial	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
49 6	Loha, E.; LindtjÄrn, B.	2012	Eff ect of bednets and indoor residual spraying on spatio-temporal clustering of malaria in a village in South Ethiopia: A longitudinal study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
49 7	Loha, E.; Lunde, T. M.; LindtjÄrn, B.	2012	Effect of Bednets and Indoor Residual Spraying on Spatio-Temporal Clustering of Malaria in a Village in South Ethiopia: A Longitudinal Study	PloS one	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
49 8	Lopez, J. M.; Galatas, B.; Munguambe, H.; MartÄ, H.; Nhamussua, L.; Simone, W.; Saute, F.; Aide, P.	2018	Risk factors associated with malaria cases observed via passive and reactive case detection after two years of interventions aiming at elimination in Southern Mozambique	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
49 9	Lopez, J. M.; Simone, W.; Galatas, B.; Guinovart, C.; Laice, F.; Chidimatembue, A.; Rabinovich, R.; Candrinho, B.; Saute, F.; Aide, P.	2019	Risk factors of malaria infection in a low endemic district with intensified vector control in Maputo Province, South of Mozambique	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
50 0	Lourenco, C.; Tatem, A. J.; Kandula, D.; Cohen, J. M.; Le Menach, A.	2015	Overview of malaria surveillance systems in elimination settings: Lessons from the past,	American journal of tropical	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

			and assessing critical program needs	medicine and hygiene	
50 1	Lubinda, M.; Katowa, B.; Sing'anga, C.; Matoba, J.; Stevenson, J. C.; Shields, T.; Shiff, C.; Thuma, P. E.; Moss, B. J.	2017	Longitudinal survey of malaria burden to assess the effects of malaria control interventions in a low transmission setting in Southern Zambia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
50 2	MacDonald, E.; Rakotonirina, A.; Rakotoson, J. D.; Gandaho, T.; Kiti, E.; Belemvire, A.; Kapesa, L.; Razafindrakoto, J.; Nambinisoa, M. A.; Rakotorahalahy, A. J.; Johns, B.; Jacob, D.	2018	Impact of indoor residual spraying (IRS) interventions on malaria incidence trends in the east coast of Madagascar	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
50 3	Mace, K. E.; Chalwe, V.; Craig, A. S.; Katalenich, B. L.; Nambozi, M.; Mubikayi, L.; Mulele, C.; Kamuliwo, M.; Filler, S. J.; Tan, K. R.	2011	Evaluation of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine for intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy--- Mansa, Zambia, 2010	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
50 4	Mace, K. E.; Chalwe, V.; Katalenich, B. L.; Nambozi, M.; Mubikayi, L.; Mulele, C. K.; Wiegand, R. E.; Filler, S. J.; Kamuliwo, M.; Craig, A. S.; Tan, K. R.	2015	Evaluation of sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine for intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy: A retrospective birth outcomes study in Mansa, Zambia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
50 5	Madani, A.; Soleimani-Ahmadi, M.; Davoodi, S. H.; Sanei-Dehkordi, A.; Jaberhashemi, S. A.; Zare, M.; Aghamolaei, T.	2017	Household knowledge and practices concerning malaria and indoor residual spraying in an endemic area earmarked for malaria elimination in Iran	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
50 6	MagaÃo, A.; BotÃo, C.; Nhassengo, P.; Saide, M.; Ubisse, A.; Chicumbe, S.; Zulliger, R.	2019	Community knowledge and acceptance of indoor residual spraying for malaria prevention in Mozambique: A qualitative study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

507	Maharaj, R.; Morris, N.	2015	When sustainability fails: The impact on elimination	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
508	Maharaj, R.; Qwabe, B.; Mkhabela, M.; Seocharan, I.	2018	Changing malaria epidemiology in Kwazulu-Natal, a province in South Africa targeting elimination by 2020	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
509	Maharaj, R.; Raman, J.; Morris, N.; Moonasar, D.; Durrheim, D. N.; Seocharan, I.; Kruger, P.; Shandukani, B.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2013	Epidemiology of malaria in South Africa: From control to elimination	South African Medical Journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
510	Maharaj, R.; Seocharan, I.; Qwabe, B.; Mkhabela, M.; Kissoon, S.; Lakan, V.	2019	Decadal epidemiology of malaria in KwaZulu-Natal, a province in South Africa targeting elimination	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
511	MahianÃ©, G.; Korenromp, E. L.; Pretorius, C.; Smith, T.; BriÃ©t, O.	2016	Malaria intervention scale-up in Africa: Statistical effectiveness predictions for health program planning tools, based on dynamic transmission modelling	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
512	Makadzange, K.; Dlamini, N.; Zulu, Z.; Dlamini, S.; Kunene, S.; Sikhondze, W.; Owiti, P.; Geoffroy, E.; Zachariah, R.; Mengestu, T. K.	2018	Low uptake of preventive interventions among malaria cases in Swaziland: Towards malaria elimination	Public Health Action	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
513	MakoutodÃ©, C. P.; Audibert, M.; Massougbodji, A.	2014	Analysis of the cost-effectiveness of the implementation of Indoor Residual Spraying and distribution of Long-Lasting Insecticidal Nets in the municipality of KouandÃ© and municipality of Copargo in Benin	Cost effectiveness and resource allocation	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

51 4	Malaria, M.	2017	Evaluating the feasibility and effectiveness of Reactive Targeted Parasite Elimination vs. Reactive Case Detection as a community level intervention in response to a passively identified index case: a cluster randomised controlled trial in Namibia.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
51 5	Malaria, M.	2017	From Malaria Control to Sustainable Elimination: Cluster randomised trial comparing targeted versus generalised vector control in South Africa (Targeted Indoor Residual Spraying Against Malaria (TIRS))	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
51 6	Malaria, M.	2019	Combination interventions for controlling malaria transmitted by pyrethroid resistant mosquitoes: A novel bed net with synergist and IRS formulation.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
51 7	Malaria, M.	2019	Cost-effectiveness evaluation of vector control strategies in Mozambique (COST).	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
51 8	Malaria, M.	2022	Impact of malaria control interventions on the infectious reservoir, host immunity, and drug resistance in Uganda.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
51 9	Malaria, M.	2022	Impact of PBO ITN and IRS co-deployment in Sierra Leone.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrongstudy design - other
52 0	Malaria, M.	2022	Impact of PBO ITN and IRS co-deployment in Sierra Leone.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
52 1	Malaria, M.	2024	Environmental Modifications in Sub-Saharan Africa: Changing Epidemiology, Transmission and Pathogenesis of Plasmodium Falciparum and P. Vivax Malaria.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

52 2	Maltrials	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
52 3	Mammadov, S.; Gasimov, E.; Kurdova-Mintcheva, R.; Wongsrichanalai, C.	2016	Elimination of Plasmodium vivax malaria in Azerbaijan	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
52 4	Manana, Pinky N.; Kuonza, Lazarus; Musekiwa, Alfred; Mpangane, Hluphi D.; Koekemoer, Lizette L.	2017	Knowledge, attitudes and practices on malaria transmission in Mamfene, KwaZulu-Natal Province, South Africa 2015	BMC Public Health	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
52 5	Mancuso, B.; Porter, T.; Fraser, M.; Silumbe, K.; Hamainza, B.; Moonga, H.; Bennett, A.; Yukich, J.; Guinovart, C.; Schneider, K.; Miller, J. M.; Eisele, T. P.	2019	Ongoing assessment of plasmodium falciparum parasite prevalence in southern province Zambia: Results from a 2019 parasite survey three years after a mass drug administration trial	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
52 6	Manrique-Saide, P.; Dean, N. E.; Halloran, M. E.; Longini, I. M.; Collins, M. H.; Waller, L. A.; Gomez-Dantes, H.; Lenhart, A.; Hladish, T. J.; Che-Mendoza, A.; et al.,	2020	The TIRS trial: protocol for a cluster randomized controlled trial assessing the efficacy of preventive targeted indoor residual spraying to reduce Aedes-borne viral illnesses in Merida, Mexico	Trials	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
52 7	Manyangadze, T.; Chimbari, M. J.; Macherera, M.; Mukaratirwa, S.	2017	Micro-spatial distribution of malaria cases and control strategies at ward level in Gwanda district, Matabeleland South, Zimbabwe	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
52 8	Martin, A. C.	2013	Experiences of benin regarding indoor residual spraying (IRS) implementation: performances and limits	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
52 9	Martin, A. C.; Gil, P.; Anges, Y.; EugÃne, K.	2010	Drastic reduction of malaria transmission and severe cases in departement of ouÃmÃ after protection of communities against pyrethroid resistant anophelines with ficamr	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

			m (bendiocarb 800g/kg) in indoor residual spraying (IRS) in Republic of Benin		
530	Martins-Campos, K. M.; Pinheiro, W. D.; VÃtor-Silva, S.; Siqueira, A. M.; Melo, G. C.; Rodrigues, I. C.; FÃ©, N. F.; Barbosa, M.; Tadei, W. P.; Guinovart, C.; Bassat, Q.; Alonso, P. L.; Lacerda, M. V.; Monteiro, W. M.	2012	Integrated vector management targeting Anopheles darlingi populations decreases malaria incidence in an unstable transmission area, in the rural Brazilian Amazon	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
531	Mashauri, F. M.; Kinung'Hi, S. M.; Kaatano, G. M.; Magesa, S. M.; Kishamawe, C.; Mwangi, J. R.; Nnko, S. E.; Malima, R. C.; Mero, C. N.; Mboera, L. E. G.	2013	Impact of indoor residual spraying of lambda-cyhalothrin on malaria prevalence and anemia in an epidemic-prone District of Muleba, North-western Tanzania	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
532	Mathanga, D. P.; Walker, E. D.; Wilson, M. L.; Ali, D.; Taylor, T. E.; Laufer, M. K.	2012	Malaria control in Malawi: Current status and directions for the future	Acta tropica	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
533	Matthews, G. A.; Dobson, H. M.; Nkot, P. B.; Wiles, T. L.; Birchmore, M.	2009	Preliminary examination of integrated vector management in a tropical rainforest area of Cameroon	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
534	Mauny, F.; Viel, J. F.; Handschumacher, P.; Sellin, B.	2004	Multilevel modelling and malaria: A new method for an old disease	International Journal of Epidemiology	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
535	Maziarz, M.; Kinyera, T.; Otim, I.; Kagwa, P.; Nabalende, H.; Legason, I. D.; Ogwang, M. D.; Kirimunda, S.; Emmanuel, B.; Reynolds, S. J.; Kerchan, P.; Joloba, M. M.; Bergen, A. W.; Bhatia, K.; Talisuna,	2017	Age and geographic patterns of Plasmodium falciparum malaria infection in a representative sample of children living in Burkitt lymphoma-endemic areas of northern Uganda	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	A. O.; Biggar, R. J.; Goedert, J. J.; Pfeiffer, R. M.; Mbulaiteye, S. M.				
53 6	Maziarz, M.; Nabalende, H.; Otim, I.; Legason, I. D.; Kinyera, T.; Ogwang, M. D.; Talisuna, A. O.; Reynolds, S. J.; Kerchan, P.; Bhatia, K.; Biggar, R. J.; Goedert, J. J.; Pfeiffer, R. M.; Mbulaiteye, S. M.	2018	A cross-sectional study of asymptomatic Plasmodium falciparum infection burden and risk factors in general population children in 12 villages in northern Uganda	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
53 7	Mazigo, Humphrey D.; Obasy, Emmanuel; Mauka, Wilhellmus; Manyiri, Paulina; Zinga, Maria; Kweka, Eliningaya J.; Mnyone, Ladslaus L.; Heukelbach, Jorg	2010	Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices about Malaria and Its Control in Rural Northwest Tanzania	Malaria Research and Treatment	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
53 8	Mbaka, P.; Kyabayinze, D. J.; Rutaazana, D.; Opigo, J.	2018	Early detection of malaria upsurges at subnational levels in Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
53 9	Mbonye, A. K.; Bygbjerg, I. C.; Magnussen, P.	2008	Prevention and treatment practices and implications for malaria control in mukono district Uganda	Journal of Biosocial Science	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
54 0	Mbunge, Elliot; Millham, Richard; Sibiya, Nokuthula; Takavarasha, Sam, Jr.	2021	Is malaria elimination a distant dream? Reconsidering malaria elimination strategies in Zimbabwe	Public health in practice (Oxford, England)	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
54 1	McCann, R. S.; van den Berg, H.; Diggle, P. J.; van Vugt, M.; Terlouw, D. J.; Phiri, K. S.; Di Pasquale, A.; Maire, N.; Gowelo, S.; Mburu, M. M.; et al.,	2017	Assessment of the effect of larval source management and house improvement on malaria transmission when added to standard malaria control strategies in southern Malawi: study protocol for a cluster- randomised controlled trial	BMC Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray

54 2	McCord, G. C.; Anttila-Hughes, J. K.	2017	A malaria ecology index predicted spatial and temporal variation of malaria burden and efficacy of antimalarial interventions based on African serological data	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
54 3	McCreesh, P.; Mumbengegwi, D.; Roberts, K.; Tambo, M.; Smith, J.; Whittemore, B.; Kelly, G.; Moe, C.; Murphy, M.; Chisenga, M.; Greenhouse, B.; Ntuku, H.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Sturrock, H.; Uusiku, P.; Gosling, R.; Bennett, A.; Hsiang, M. S.	2018	Subpatent malaria in a low transmission African setting: A cross-sectional study using rapid diagnostic testing (RDT) and loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) from Zambezi region, Namibia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
54 4	McHa, J. H.; Khatib, B. O.; Haji, K. A.; Majambere, S.; Devine, G. J.	2011	Barriers to malaria elimination on the islands of Zanzibar	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
54 5	Medzihradsky, Oliver F.; Kleinschmidt, Immo; Mumbengegwi, Davis; Roberts, Kathryn W.; McCreesh, Patrick; Dufour, Mi-Suk Kang; Uusiku, Petrina; Katokele, Stark; Bennett, Adam; Smith, Jennifer; Sturrock, Hugh; Prach, Lisa M.; Ntuku, Henry; Tambo, Munyaradzi; Didier, Bradley; Greenhouse, Bryan; Gani, Zaahira; Aerts, Ann; Gosling, Roly; Hsiang, Michelle S.	2018	Study protocol for a cluster randomised controlled factorial design trial to assess the effectiveness and feasibility of reactive focal mass drug administration and vector control to reduce malaria transmission in the low endemic setting of Namibia	BMJ open	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

54 6	Medzihradsky, Oliver F.; Kleinschmidt, Immo; Mumbengegwi, Davis; Roberts, Kathryn W.; McCreesh, Patrick; Dufour, Mi-Suk Kang; Uusiku, Petrina; Katokele, Stark; Bennett, Adam; Smith, Jennifer; Sturrock, Hugh; Prach, Lisa M.; Ntuku, Henry; Tambo, Munyaradzi; Didier, Bradley; Greenhouse, Bryan; Gani, Zaahira; Aerts, Ann; Gosling, Roly; Hsiang, Michelle S.	2018	Study protocol for a cluster randomised controlled factorial design trial to assess the effectiveness and feasibility of reactive focal mass drug administration and vector control to reduce malaria transmission in the low endemic setting of Namibia	BMJ open	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
54 7	Menjetta, T.	2021	Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice towards Prevention and Control of Malaria in Halaba Town, Southern Ethiopia, 2017	Journal of Tropical Medicine	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
54 8	Messenger, L. A.; Matias Arnez, A.; Stiles- Ocran, J. B.; Coulibaly, M. B.; Miller, N.; Awolola, A.; Mulder, C. E. G.; Khoa, P. T.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Rowland, M.	2012	Multicentre studies of insecticide-treated durable lining in africa and southeast asia: Entomological efficacy and household acceptability during one year of field use	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
54 9	Messenger, L. A.; Miller, N. P.; Adeogun, A. O.; Awolola, T. S.; Rowland, M.	2012	The development of insecticide-treated durable wall lining for malaria control: Insights from rural and urban populations in Angola and Nigeria	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
55 0	Messenger, L. A.; Rowland, M.	2017	Insecticide-treated durable wall lining (ITWL): future prospects for control of malaria and other vector-borne diseases	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

55 1	Messenger, Louisa A.; Matias, Abrahan; Manana, Antonio Nkulu; Stiles-Ocran, Joseph B.; Knowles, Steve; Boakye, Daniel A.; Coulibaly, Mamadou B.; Larsen, Marie-Louise; Traore, Amadou S.; Diallo, Brehima; Konate, Mamadou; Guindo, Amadou; Traore, Sekou F.; Mulder, Chris Eg; Le, Hoan; Kleinschmidt, Immo; Rowland, Mark	2012	Multicentre studies of insecticide-treated durable wall lining in Africa and South-East Asia: entomological efficacy and household acceptability during one year of field use	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
55 2	Mharakurwa, S.; Mutambu, S. L.; Mberikunashe, J.; Thuma, P. E.; Moss, W. J.; Mason, P. R.	2013	Changes in the burden of malaria following scale up of malaria control interventions in Mutasa District, Zimbabwe	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
55 3	Mihreteab, S.; Lubinda, J.; Zhao, B.; Rodriguez-Morales, A. J.; Karamehic- Muratovic, A.; Goitom, A.; Shad, M. Y.; Haque, U.	2020	Retrospective data analyses of social and environmental determinants of malaria control for elimination prospects in Eritrea	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
55 4	Minja, E. G.; Swai, J. K.; Mrimi, E.; Ngowo, H.; Okumu, F.	2019	Prevalence and drivers of plasmodium infection across villages in Southeastern Tanzania	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
55 5	Mohammadi, M.; Ansari-Moghaddam, A.; Raiesi, A.; Rakhshani, F.; Nikpour, F.; Haghdost, A.; Ranjbar, M.; Taghizadeh-Asl, R.; Sakeni, M.; Safari, R.; Saffari, M.	2011	Baseline results of the first malaria indicator survey in Iran at household level	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
55 6	Mohammed, M. A.; Hong, T.	2021	Role of vector control in fighting against malaria: Evidence from Ethiopian health-related indicators	Journal of Infection and Public Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

55 7	Mohammed-Awel, J.; Gumel, A. B.	2019	Mathematics of an epidemiology-genetics model for assessing the role of insecticides resistance on malaria transmission dynamics	Mathematical Biosciences	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
55 8	Mohammed-Awel, J.; Iboi, E. A.; Gumel, A. B.	2020	Insecticide resistance and malaria control: A genetics-epidemiology modeling approach	Mathematical Biosciences	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
55 9	Molineaux, L.; Dietz, K.; Thomas, A.	1978	Further epidemiological evaluation of a malaria model	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
56 0	Molteni, F.; Kahitsi, W.; Mugalura, F.; Lalji, S.; Mandike, R.; Mwita, A.	2012	Shrinking the malaria map in muleba district, northwestern tanzania: Monitoring the impact of malaria prevention interventions scale-up through Hospital admissions	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
56 1	Monitoring the effects of an indoor residual spraying intervention on the reservoir of Plasmodium falciparum in an area characterized by seasonal transmission in Ghana (2019) Kathryn E. Tiedje - School of BioSciences, The University of Melbourne, Bio21 Molecular Science and Biotechnology Institute; Department of Microbiology and Immunology, The University of Melbourne, Bio21 Molecular Science and Biotechnology Institute, Melbourne, Australia	Year not provi ded	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

56 2	Monroe, A.; Asamoah, O.; Lam, Y.; Koenker, H.; Psychas, P.; Lynch, M.; Ricotta, E.; Hornston, S.; Berman, A.; Harvey, S. A.	2015	Outdoor-sleeping and other night-time activities in northern Ghana: Implications for residual transmission and malaria prevention	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
56 3	Monroe, A.; Asamoah, O.; Lam, Y.; Lynch, M.; Koenker, H.; Psychas, P.; Hornston, S. E.; Akuoku, J.; Harvey, S.	2014	Potential implications of outdoor-sleeping behaviors and nighttime activities for malaria control in the upper west and northern regions of Ghana	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
56 4	Montanari, R. M.; Pyakalyia, T. R.; Ake, I. N.	1992	The malaria control program in Papua New Guinea: epidemiological surveillance and a look into the future	Papua and New Guinea Medical Journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
56 5	Mora-Ruiz, M.; Penilla, R. P.; Ordóñez, J. G.; López, A. D.; Solis, F.; Torres-Estrada, J. L.; Rodríguez, A. D.	2014	Socioeconomic factors, attitudes and practices associated with malaria prevention in the coastal plain of Chiapas, Mexico	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
56 6	Mouchet, J.; Manguin, S.	1999	Global warming and malaria expansion	Annales de la Societe Entomologiqu e de France	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
56 7	Mpangala, Kihomo Robert; Halasa- Rappel, Yara A.; Mohamed, Mohamed Seif; Mnzava, Ruth C.; Mkuza, Kaseem J.; Mangesho, Peter E.; Kisinja, William N.; Mugasa, Joseph P.; Messenger, Louisa A.; Mtove, George; Kihombo, Aggrey R.; Shepard, Donald S.	2021	On the cost-effectiveness of insecticide-treated wall liner and indoor residual spraying as additions to insecticide treated bed nets to prevent malaria: findings from cluster randomized trials in Tanzania	BMC Public Health	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
56 8	Mpimbaza, A.; Kigozi, R.; Sserwanga, A.; Wanzira, H.; Rubahika, D.; Yoon, S. S.; Chang, M. A.; Yeka, A.; Belay, K. A.; Staedke, S. S.; Kanya, M.; Dorsey, G.; Kapella, B. K.	2015	Malaria test positivity rates among patients at five outpatient health centers located in an endemic region in Uganda: IRS versus non- IRS districts	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

569	Mpimbaza, A.; Sserwanga, A.; Rutazaana, D.; Kapisi, J.; Walemwa, R.; Suiyanka, L.; Kyalo, D.; Kanya, M.; Opigo, J.; Snow, R. W.	2020	Changing malaria fever test positivity among paediatric admissions to Tororo district hospital, Uganda 2012–2019	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
570	Msaky, D. S.; Musiba, R.; Shubis, G.; Chila, G.; Mihayo, K.; McHa, J.; Khaji, K.; Tarimo, B.; Kiware, S.	2018	The implementation and the impact of adapting technologies to support residual malaria transmission: A case study in Unguja, Zanzibar	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
571	Msellemu, D.; Shemdoe, A.; Makungu, C.; Mlacha, Y.; Kannady, K.; Dongus, S.; Killeen, G. F.; Dillip, A.	2017	The underlying reasons for very high levels of bed net use, and higher malaria infection prevalence among bed net users than non-users in the Tanzanian city of Dar es Salaam: A qualitative study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
572	Mtove, George; Mugasa, Joseph P.; Messenger, Louisa A.; Malima, Robert C.; Mangesho, Peter; Magogo, Franklin; Plucinski, Mateusz; Hashimu, Ramadhan; Matowo, Johnson; Shepard, Donald; Batengana, Bernard; Cook, Jackie; Emidi, Basiliana; Halasa, Yara; Kaaya, Robert; Kihombo, Aggrey; Lindblade, Kimberly A.; Makenga, Geoffrey; Mpangala, Robert; Mwambuli, Abraham	2016	The effectiveness of non-pyrethroid insecticide-treated durable wall lining to control malaria in rural Tanzania: study protocol for a two-armed cluster randomized trial	BMC Public Health	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
573	Muchena, G.; Dube, B.; Chikodzore, R.; Pasipamire, J.; Murugasampillay, S.; Mberikunashe, J.	2018	A review of progress towards sub-national malaria elimination in Matabeleland South Province, Zimbabwe (2011-2015): A qualitative study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data

57 4	Muchena, G.; Gombe, N.; Takundwa, L.; Tshimanga, M.; Bangure, D.; Masuka, N.; Juru, T.	2017	Factors associated with contracting malaria in ward 29 of Shamva district, Zimbabwe, 2014	South African Medical Journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
57 5	Mufunda, J.; Nyarango, P.; Usman, A.; Gebremeskel, T.; Mebrahtu, G.; Ogbamariam, A.; Kosia, A.; Ghebrat, Y.; Gebresillosie, S.; Goitom, S.; Araya, E.; Andemichael, G.; Gebremichael, A.	2007	Roll back malaria - An African success story in Eritrea	South African Medical Journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
57 6	Mugasa, J.; Malima, R.; Mtove, G.; Tenu, F.; Mangesho, P.; Magogo, S.; Shepard, D.; Samuels, A.; Gimnig, J.; Rowland, M.; et al.,	2014	Next generation durable wall liners, a new strategy for malaria control: baseline results from a cluster randomized trial	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
57 7	Mugenyi, L.; Nankabirwa, J. I.; Arinaitwe, E.; Rek, J.; Hens, N.; Kanya, M.; Dorsey, G.	2020	Estimating the optimal interval between rounds of indoor residual spraying of insecticide using malaria incidence data from cohort studies	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
57 8	Mugwagwa, N.; Mberikunasho, J.; Gombe, N. T.; Tshimanga, M.; Bangure, D.; Mungati, M.	2015	Factors associated with malaria infection in Honde valley, Mutasa district, Zimbabwe, 2014: a case control study	BMC research notes	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
57 9	Muhindo, M. K.; Kakuru, A.; Awori, P.; Natureeba, P.; Opira, B.; Amailuk, M.; Olwoch, P.; Nalugo, N.; Okiring, J.; Opiro, L.; et al.,	2018	Intermittent preventive treatment with dihydroartemisinin piperaquine in young Ugandan children in the setting of indoor residual spraying of insecticide	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
58 0	Muhindo, M. K.; Kakuru, A.; Awori, P.; Natureeba, P.; Opira, B.; Amailuk, M.; Olwoch, P.; Nalugo, N.; Okiring, J.; Opiro, L.; et al.,	2017	Intermittent preventive treatment with dihydroartemisinin- piperaquine in young Ugandan children in the setting of indoor residual spraying of insecticide	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data

58 1	Muhindo, M. K.; Kakuru, A.; Natureeba, P.; Awori, P.; Olwoch, P.; Ategeka, J.; Nayebare, P.; Clark, T. D.; Muehlenbachs, A.; Roh, M.; Mpeka, B.; Greenhouse, B.; Havlir, D. V.; Kamya, M. R.; Dorsey, G.; Jagannathan, P.	2016	Reductions in malaria in pregnancy and adverse birth outcomes following indoor residual spraying of insecticide in Uganda	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
58 2	Mukhopadhyay, A. K.; Patnaik, S. K.	2014	Evaluation of ongoing indoor residual spray programme in some malaria endemic districts of Andhra Pradesh, India	Indian journal of public health research and development	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
58 3	Mukonka, V. M.; Chanda, E.; Haque, U.; Kamuliwo, M.; Mushinge, G.; Chileshe, J.; Chibwe, K. A.; Norris, D. E.; Mulenga, M.; Chaponda, M.; Muleba, M.; Glass, G. E.; Moss, W. J.	2014	High burden of malaria following scale-up of control interventions in Nchelenge District, Luapula Province, Zambia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
58 4	Mulamba, M.; Mash, B.	2010	Evaluation of malaria prevention strategies during pregnancy in Ndola, Zambia	African Journal of Primary Health Care and Family Medicine	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
58 5	Mulamba, S. M.	2010	Evaluation of malaria prevention strategy during pregnancy in Ndola, Zambia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
58 6	Mulebeke, R.; Bukenya, F.; Collborn, K.; Elliot, R.; Eganyu, T.; Odude, W.; Wnazirah, H.; Gonahasa, S.; Kyohere, M.; Maiteki, C.; Van geertruyden, J. P.; Echodu, D.; Yeka, A.	2018	Implementing malaria mass drug administration: Experience from a high transmission setting in northeastern uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
58 7	Mumbengegwi, D. R.; Sturrock, H.; Hsiang, M.; Roberts, K.;	2018	Is there a correlation between malaria incidence and IRS	Public Health Action	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	Kleinschmidt, I.; Nghipumbwa, M.; Uusiku, P.; Smith, J.; Bennet, A.; Kizito, W.; Takarinda, K.; Ade, S.; Gosling, R.		coverage in western Zambezi region, Namibia?		
588	Munajat, M. B.; Rahim, M. A. F. A.; Wahid, W.; Seri Rakna, M. I. M.; Divis, P. C. S.; Chuangchaiya, S.; Lubis, I. N. D.; Osman, E.; Mohd Kasri, M. R.; Idris, Z. M.	2021	Perceptions and prevention practices on malaria among the indigenous Orang Asli community in Kelantan, Peninsular Malaysia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
589	Munga, S.; Kimwetich, Z.; Atieli, F.; Vulule, J.; Kweka, E. J.	2017	Knowledge and perceptions about indoor residual spray for malaria prevention in numberes division, Nandi county in central province of Kenya	Tanzania Journal of Health Research	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
590	Munguambe, K.; Pool, R.; Boene, H.; Gonzalez, R.; Macete, E.; Menendez, C.; Alonso, P.	2011	Understanding health behaviours through social science research: Experiences from two malaria control interventions in Mozambique	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
591	Munguambe, K.; Pool, R.; Montgomery, C.; Bavo, C.; Nhacolo, A.; Fiosse, L.; Sacoor, C.; Nhalungo, D.; Mabunda, S.; Macete, E.; Alonso, P.	2011	What drives community adherence to indoor residual spraying (IRS) against malaria in Manhica district, rural Mozambique: A qualitative study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
592	Mutegeki, E.; Chimbari, M. J.; Mukaratirwa, S.	2017	Assessment of individual and household malaria risk factors among women in a South African village	Acta tropica	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
593	Mutombo, B.; Littrell, M.; Dieye, Y.; Dieng Sow, G.; Ba, M.; Ngom, A.; Cisse, M.; Mboup, B. M.; Earle, D.; Steketee, R. W.	2013	Case investigation and reactive infection detection for malaria elimination in northern Senegal	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
594	Mwamtobe, P. M.; Abelman, S.; Tchuente, J. M.; Kasambara, A.	2014	Optimal (control of) intervention strategies for malaria epidemic in karonga District, Malawi	Abstract and Applied Analysis	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

59 5	Mwanga, G. G.; Haario, H.	2014	Optimal control of two age structured malaria model with model parameter uncertainty	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
59 6	Mwanga, G. G.; Haario, H.; Capasso, V.	2015	Optimal control problems of epidemic systems with parameter uncertainties: Application to a malaria two-age-classes transmission model with asymptomatic carriers	Mathematical Biosciences	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
59 7	Mwesigwa, J.; Okebe, J.; Affara, M.; Di Tanna, G. L.; Nwakanma, D.; Janha, O.; Ngwa, A. A.; D'Alessandro, U.	2014	A countrywide cross- sectional survey of the prevalence of asymptomatic plasmodium falciparum infection in the Gambia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
59 8	Mwesigwa, Julia; Achan, Jane; Di Tanna, Gian Luca; Affara, Muna; Jawara, Musa; Worwui, Archibald; Hamid-Adiamoh, Majidah; Kanuteh, Fatoumatta; Ceesay, Sainey; Bousema, Teun; Drakeley, Chris; Grietens, Koen Peeters; Lindsay, Steve W.; Van Geertruyden, Jean- Pierre; D'Alessandro, Umberto	2017	Residual malaria transmission dynamics varies across The Gambia despite high coverage of control interventions	PloS one	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
59 9	Myers-Hansen, J. L.; Abuaku, B.; Oyebola, M. K.; Mensah, B. A.; Ahorlu, C.; Wilson, M. D.; Awandare, G.; Koram, K. A.; Ngwa, A. A.; Ghansah, A.	2020	Assessment of antimalarial drug resistant markers in asymptomatic Plasmodium falciparum infections after 4 years of indoor residual spraying in Northern Ghana	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
60 0	Nahum, A.; Erhart, A.; MayÃ©, A.; Ahounou, D.; Van Overmeir, C.; Menten, J.; Van Loen, H.; Akogbeto, M.; Coosemans, M.; Massougbojji, A.; D'Alessandro, U.	2011	Malaria incidence and prevalence among children living in peri- urban area on the coast of Benin, West Africa: Longitudinal study	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray

60 1	Nahum, A.; Erhart, A.; MayÃ©, A.; Ahounou, D.; Van Overmeir, C.; Menten, J.; Van Loen, H.; Akogbeto, M.; Coosemans, M.; Massougboji, A.; D'Alessandro, U.	2010	Malaria incidence and prevalence among children living in a Peri- Urban area on the Coast of Benin, West Africa: A longitudinal study	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
60 2	Nalim, S.; Barodji,; Widiarti,; Widiyastuti, U.	1997	A field trial with etofenprox (OMS 3002) as a residual insecticide against malaria vectors, in Tanjung Bunga district, east Flores, Indonesia	The Southeast Asian journal of tropical medicine and public health	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
60 3	Nalim, S.; Barodji,; Widiarti,; Widiyastuti, U.	1997	A field trial with etofenprox (OMS 3002) as a residual insecticide against malaria vectors, in Tanjung Bunga district, east Flores, Indonesia	The Southeast Asian journal of tropical medicine and public health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
60 4	Nambozi, M.; Malunga, P.; Van Geertruyden, J. P.; Mulenga, M.; D'Alessandro, U.	2012	Defining the malaria burden in nchelenge district using the who malaria indicators survey	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
60 5	Nambuusi, B. B.; Ssempiira, J.; Makumbi, F. E.; Kasasa, S.; Vounatsou, P.	2019	The effects and contribution of childhood diseases on the geographical distribution of all-cause under-five mortality in Uganda	Parasite Epidemiology and Control	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
60 6	Namuganga, J. F.; Epstein, A.; Nankabirwa, J. I.; Mpimbaza, A.; Kiggundu, M.; Sserwanga, A.; Kapisi, J.; Arinaitwe, E.; Gonahasa, S.; Opigo, J.; Ebong, C.; Staedke, S. G.; Shililu, J.; Okia, M.; Rutazaana, D.; Maiteki-Sebuguzi, C.; Belay, K.; Kanya, M. R.; Dorsey, G.; Rodriguez-Barraquer, I.	2021	The impact of stopping and starting indoor residual spraying on malaria burden in Uganda	Nature communicatio ns	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

607	Nankabirwa, J. I.; Arinaitwe, E.; Rek, J.; Kilama, M.; Kizza, T.; Staedke, S. G.; Rosenthal, P. J.; Rodriguez-Barraquer, I.; Briggs, J.; Greenhouse, B.; Bousema, T.; Drakeley, C.; Roos, D. S.; Tomko, S. S.; Smith, D. L.; Kanya, M. R.; Dorsey, G.	2020	Malaria transmission, infection, and disease following sustained indoor residual spraying of insecticide in Tororo, Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
608	Nankabirwa, J. I.; Briggs, J.; Rek, J.; Arinaitwe, E.; Staedke, S. G.; Rosenthal, P. J.; Kanya, M. R.; Dorsey, G.; Rodriguez-Barraquer, I.; Greenhouse, B.	2019	Quantifying the potential impact of mass drug administration on the parasite reservoir in an area of declining malaria transmission in Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
609	Nankabirwa, J. I.; Rek, J.; Arinaitwe, E.; Nayebare, P.; Katrak, S.; Staedke, S.; Kanya, M.; Rosenthal, P.; Rodriguez, I. B.; Greenhouse, B.; Dorsey, G.	2017	Differential impacts of indoor residual spraying on the characteristics of malaria infections in a high transmission setting in Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
610	Nankabirwa, Joaniter I.; Briggs, Jessica; Rek, John; Arinaitwe, Emmanuel; Nayebare, Patience; Katrak, Shereen; Staedke, Sarah G.; Rosenthal, Philip J.; Rodriguez-Barraquer, Isabel; Kanya, Moses R.; Dorsey, Grant; Greenhouse, Bryan	2018	Persistent Parasitemia Despite Dramatic Reduction in Malaria Incidence After 3 Rounds of Indoor Residual Spraying in Tororo, Uganda	Journal of Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
611	Natureeba, P.; Kakuru, A.; Muhindo, M.; Ochieng, T.; Ategeka, J.; Koss, C. A.; Plenty, A.; Charlebois, E. D.; Clark, T. D.; Nzarubara, B.; et al.,	2017	Intermittent Preventive Treatment With Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine for the Prevention of Malaria Among HIV-Infected Pregnant Women	Journal of Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray

61 2	Nawa, M.; Halwindi, H.; Hangoma, P.	2020	Modelling malaria reduction in a highly endemic country: Evidence from household survey, climate, and programme data in Zambia	Journal of Public Health in Africa	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
61 3	Nawa, M.; Hangoma, P.; Morse, A. P.; Michelo, C.	2019	Investigating the upsurge of malaria prevalence in Zambia between 2010 and 2015: A decomposition of determinants	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
61 4	Nawa, Mukumbuta; Halwindi, Hikabasa; Hangoma, Peter	2020	Modelling malaria reduction in a highly endemic country: Evidence from household survey, climate, and program data in Zambia	Journal of Public Health in Africa	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
61 5	Author details not provided	Year not provided	valuation of Insecticide Treated Nets and Wall Liners for the Prevention of Malaria.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
61 6	Author details not provided	Year not provided	The Combined Use of Indoor Residual Spraying (IRS) and Long-lasting Insecticidal Nets (LLINs) for Malaria Prevention	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
61 7	Author details not provided	Year not provided	Evaluation of a Novel Long Lasting Insecticidal Net and Indoor Residual Spray Product.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
61 8	Author details not provided	Year not provided	Evaluation of Targeted Parasite Elimination (TPE) in Namibia.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
61 9	Author details not provided	Year not provided	Evaluation of Targeted Parasite Elimination (TPE) in Namibia.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
62 0	Author details not provided	Year not provided	The Effectiveness of Non-Pyrethroid Insecticide-Treated Durable Wall Liners as a Method for Malaria Control in Endemic Rural Tanzania.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

62 1	Author details not provided	Year not provided	The Effectiveness of Non-Pyrethroid Insecticide-Treated Durable Wall Liners as a Method for Malaria Control in Endemic Rural Tanzania.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
62 2	Nct (2015). "Trial to Compare Effectiveness of 2 Insecticides in Preventing Malaria." https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT02458066 .	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
62 3	Nct (2015). "Trial to Compare Effectiveness of 2 Insecticides in Preventing Malaria." https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT02458066 . (Duplicated from Covidence)	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
62 4	Author details not provided	Year not provided	Cost-effectiveness Evaluation of Vector Control Strategies in Mozambique	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
62 5	Author details not provided	Year not provided	Adaptive Interventions for Optimizing Malaria Control: a Cluster-Randomized SMART Trial.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
62 6	Author details not provided	Year not provided	Malaria High-Risk Populations in Namibia.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
62 7	Nct,	2015	Evaluation of Long-Lasting Microbial Larvicides in Reducing Malaria Transmission and Clinical Malaria Incidence	https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT02392832	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
62 8	Nct,	2005	Preventing Malaria During Pregnancy in Epidemic-prone Areas	https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT00142207	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
62 9	Nct,	2016	Prevention of Malaria in HIV-uninfected Pregnant Women and Infants	https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT02392832	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray

				w/NCT02793622	outdoor surface spray
630	NCT02556242	2020	Targeted Indoor Residual Spraying Against Malaria.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
631	NCT03689036	2021	Transmission Dynamics of Residual and Re-emerging Malaria in the Amazon: Defining a Roadmap to Malaria Elimination.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
632	NCT04230161	2021	Estimating the Malaria Prevention Impact of New Nets: Observational Analyses to Evaluate the Evidence Generated During Piloted New Net Distributions in Rwanda.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
633	NCT04419766	2021	Evaluation of IR3535 as a Spatial Repellent for Malaria Control.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
634	Ndiop, M.; Gueye, A. B.; Diallo, I.; Cisse, M.; Diouf, M. L.	2016	Impact of antimalarial interventions on malaria morbidity and mortality in hospitals from 2001-2015, Senegal	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
635	Ndong, Ignatius Cheng; Okyere, Daniel; Enos, Juliana Yartey; Mensah, Benedicta A.; Nyarko, Alexander; Abuaku, Benjamin; Amambua-Ngwa, Alfred; Merle, Corinne Simone C.; Koram, Kwadwo Ansah; Ahorlu, Collins Stephen	2019	Prevalence of asymptomatic malaria parasitaemia following mass testing and treatment in Pakro sub-district of Ghana	BMC Public Health	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
636	Nejati, J.; Moosa-Kazemi, S. H.; Saghafipour, A.; Soofi, K.	2018	Knowledge, attitude and practice (KAP) on malaria, from high malaria burden rural communities, southeastern Iran	Journal of Parasitic Diseases	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
637	Nejati, J.; Tabatabaei, S. M.; Salehi, M.; Saghafipour, A.; Mozafari, E.	2017	Some probable factors affecting the malaria situation before and at the beginning of a pre-elimination program in southeastern Iran	Journal of Parasitic Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
638	Newman, R. D.	2011	Progress in malaria control and advances towards elimination	Tropical Medicine and	Exclusion reason: No indoor or

				International Health	outdoor surface spray
639	Ngatu, N. R.; Kanbara, S.; Renzaho, A.; Wumba, R.; Mbelambela, E. P.; Muchanga, S. M. J.; Muzembo, B. A.; Leon-Kabamba, N.; Nattadech, C.; Suzuki, T.; Oscar-Luboya, N.; Wada, K.; Ikeda, M.; Nojima, S.; Sugishita, T.; Ikeda, S.	2019	Environmental and sociodemographic factors associated with household malaria burden in the Congo	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
640	Ngomane, L.; de Jager, C.	2012	Changes in malaria morbidity and mortality in Mpumalanga Province, South Africa (2001-2009): A retrospective study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
641	Ngondi, J. M.; Graves, P. M.; Gebre, T.; Mosher, A. W.; Shargie, E. B.; Emerson, P. M.; Richards, F. O.	2011	Which nets are being used: Factors associated with mosquito net use in Amhara, Oromia and Southern Nations, Nationalities and Peoples' Regions of Ethiopia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
642	Nguitragool, W.; Karl, S.; White, M.; Koepfli, C.; Felger, I.; Singhasivanon, P.; Mueller, I.; Sattabongkot, J.	2019	Highly heterogeneous residual malaria risk in western Thailand	International Journal for Parasitology	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
643	Nkya, T. E.; Fillinger, U.; Dlamini, M.; Sangoro, O. P.; Marubu, R.; Zulu, Z.; Chanda, E.; Mutero, C. M.; Dlamini, Q.	2021	Malaria in Eswatini, 2012–2019: a case study of the elimination effort	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
644	Noland, G. S.; Ayodo, G.; Abuya, J.; Hodges, J. S.; Rolfes, M. A. R.; John, C. C.	2012	Decreased prevalence of anemia in highland areas of low malaria transmission after a 1-year interruption of transmission	Clinical Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
645	Noland, G. S.; Ayodo, G.; Hodges, J. S.; Vulule, J. M.; John, C. C.	2010	Significant decrease in anemia in areas of very low malaria transmission after interruption of transmission	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

64 6	Noland, G. S.; Graves, P. M.; Sallau, A.; Eigege, A.; Emukah, E.; Patterson, A. E.; Ajiji, J.; Okorofor, I.; Oji, O. U.; Umar, M.; Alphonsus, K.; Damen, J.; Ngondi, J.; Ozaki, M.; Cromwell, E.; Obiezu, J.; Eneiramo, S.; Okoro, C.; McClintic-Doyle, R.; Oresanya, O.; Miri, E.; Emerson, P. M.; Richards Jr, F. O.	2014	Malaria prevalence, anemia and baseline intervention coverage prior to mass net distributions in Abia and Plateau States, Nigeria	BMC Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
64 7	Noor, A. M.; Alegana, V. A.; Kamwi, R. N.; Hansford, C. F.; Ntomwa, B.; Katokele, S.; Snow, R. W.	2013	Malaria Control and the Intensity of Plasmodium falciparum Transmission in Namibia 1969-1992	PloS one	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
64 8	Ntshalintshali, N. E.; Zulu, Z.; Novotny, J. M.; Kunene, S. P.; Msibi, P.; Sturrock, H.; Gonzalez, I.; Bell, D.; Dorsey, G.; Gosling, R.; Greenhouse, B.; Hsiang, M. S.	2013	Use of passive and active surveillance to assess the role of housing as a potential risk factor for local transmission of plasmodium falciparum infection in Swaziland	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
64 9	Nwaneri, D. U.; Oladipo, O. A.; Sadoh, A. E.; Ibadin, M. O.	2016	Caregivers' vector control methods and their impact on malaria outcome in under-five presenting in tertiary health institution in Nigeria	Journal of Preventive Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
65 0	Nwe, T. W.; Oo, T.; Wai, K. T.; Zhou, S.; van Griensven, J.; Chinnakali, P.; Shah, S.; Thi, A.	2017	Malaria profiles and challenges in artemisinin resistance containment in Myanmar	Infectious diseases of poverty	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
65 1	Nyarango, P. M.; Gebremeske, T.; Mebrahtu, G.; Mufunda, J.; Abdulmumini, U.; Ogbamariam, A.; Kosia, A.; Gebremichael, A.; Gunawardena, D.;	2006	A steep decline of malaria morbidity and mortality trends in Eritrea between 2000 and 2004: The effect of combination of control methods	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	Ghebrat, Y.; Okbaldet, Y.				
65 2	Nze, L. O.; Donfack, O. T.; Motobe, L.; Smith, J.; Fuseini, G.; Phiri, W. P.; Perry, M.; Falla, C. C.; Garcia, G.	2018	Community engagement and the use of household mapping to target sensitization and improve IRS coverage on Bioko Island	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
65 3	Odugbemi, B. A.; Wright, K. O.; Onajole, A. T.; Kuyinu, Y. A.; Goodman, O. O.; Odugbemi, T. O.; Odusanya, O. O.	2016	A malariometric survey of under-fives residing in indoor residual spraying- implementing and non- implementing communities of Lagos, Nigeria	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
65 4	Oguttu, D. W.; Matovu, J. K. B.; Okumu, D. C.; Ario, A. R.; Okullo, A. E.; Opigo, J.; Nankabirwa, V.	2017	Rapid reduction of malaria following introduction of vector control interventions in Tororo District, Uganda: a descriptive study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
65 5	Okullo, A. E.; Matovu, J. K. B.; Ario, A. R.; Opigo, J.; Wanzira, H.; Oguttu, D. W.; Kalyango, J. N.	2017	Malaria incidence among children less than 5 years during and after cessation of indoor residual spraying in Northern Uganda	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
65 6	Okumu, F. O.; Killeen, G. F.; Moore, S. J.	2012	Simulated community- level effects of combining long lasting insecticidal nets with indoor residual spraying for malaria control in Africa	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
65 7	Okumu, F. O.; Kiware, S. S.; Moore, S. J.; Killeen, G. F.	2013	Mathematical evaluation of community level impact of combining bed nets and indoor residual spraying upon malaria transmission in areas where the main vectors are Anopheles arabiensis mosquitoes	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
65 8	Okumu, F.; Moore, S.	2011	Combining indoor residual spraying and insecticide-treated nets for malaria control in Africa: A review of possible outcomes and an	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

			outline of suggestions for the future		
659	Oladoyinbo, T. O.; Adeogun, A. O.; Babalola, A. S.; Babatunde, M.; Ladipo, O. T.; Olarinde, T. I.; Oyedemi, I. D.	2021	Factors Affecting Willingness to Use Indoor Residual Spraying Among Pregnant Women Attending Antenatal Care in Hyperendemic State of West Africa: A Random Survey	Journal of medical entomology	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
660	Olotu, O.; Ipadeola, O.	2016	Knowledge, acceptance and willingness to pay for indoor residual spray in rural and urban communities in niger state, Nigeria	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
661	O'Meara, W. P.; Mangeni, J. N.; Steketee, R.; Greenwood, B.	2010	Changes in the burden of malaria in sub-Saharan Africa	The Lancet Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
662	Omondi, C. J.; Atieli, H.; Odongo, D.; Githeko, A. K.; Kazura, J. W.; Yan, G.	2019	Impact of indoor residual spray program on the prevalence of plasmodium infections and anemia in western Kenya: an open cohort study	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
663	Omotayo, A. I.; Ande, A. T.; Oduola, A. O.; Olakiigbe, A. K.; Ghazali, A. K.; Adeneye, A.; Awolola, S. T.	2021	Community Knowledge, Attitude and Practices on Malaria Vector Control Strategies in Lagos State, South-West Nigeria	Journal of medical entomology	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
664	Opiyo, M.; Sacoor, C.; Maquina, M.; Alafo, C.; Aide, P.; Nhacolo, A.; Fernandez-Montonya, L.; Marti, H.; Saute, F.; Paaijmans, K.	2019	The protective gap of indoor residual spraying: Wall modifications after spraying affects actual coverage and hampers malaria elimination efforts	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
665	Opiyo, P.; Mukabana, W. R.; Kiche, I.; Mathenge, E.; Killeen, G. F.; Fillinger, U.	2007	An exploratory study of community factors relevant for participatory malaria control on Rusinga Island, western Kenya	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

66 6	Otieno, G.; Koske, J. K.; Mutiso, J. M.	2016	Cost effectiveness analysis of optimal malaria control strategies in Kenya	Mathematics	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
66 7	Ototo, E. N.; Mbugi, J. P.; Wanjala, C. L.; Zhou, G.; Githeko, A. K.; Yan, G.	2015	Surveillance of malaria vector population density and biting behaviour in western Kenya	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
66 8	Owoeye, Deborah O.; Akinyemi, Joshua O.; Yusuf, Oyindamola B.	2018	Decomposition of changes in malaria prevalence amongst under-five children in Nigeria	MalariaWorld journal	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
66 9	Oyekale, Abayomi Samuel	2014	Assessment of Pregnancy Status, Malaria Knowledge and Malaria Fever Morbidity among Women of Reproductive Ages in Nigeria	Iranian Journal of Public Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
67 0	PACTR201411000882128	2021	Maltrials.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
67 1	PACTR201807166695568	2021	IMPACT OF POPULATION BASED INDOOR RESIDUAL SPRAYING IN COMBINATION WITH CHEMOTHERAPY ON KEY MALARIA INDICATORS IN A HIGH TRANSMISSION SETTING IN NORTH EASTERN UGANDA.	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
67 2	Pampana, E. J.	1948	Malaria Control by Residual Indoor Spraying with Dichloro-diphenyl-trichloroethane (DDT): Survey of Methods for testing Residual Toxicity and of Results	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
67 3	Pardo, G.; Descalzo, M. A.; Molina, L.; Custodio, E.; Lwanga, M.; Mangué, C.; Obono, J.; Nchama, A.; Roche, J.; Benito, A.; Cano, J.	2006	Impact of different strategies to control Plasmodium infection and anaemia on the island of Bioko (Equatorial Guinea)	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
67 4	Parham, P. E.; Hughes, D. A.	2015	Climate influences on the cost-effectiveness of vector-based interventions against	Philosophical transactions of the Royal Society of London.	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

			malaria in elimination scenarios	Series B, Biological sciences	
67 5	Pattanasin, S.; Satitvipawee, P.; Wongklang, W.; Viwatwongkasem, C.; Bhumiratana, A.; Soontornpipit, P.; Jareinpituk, S.	2012	Risk factors of malaria infection among rubber tappers living in the area of malaria control program in Prachuab Khiri Khan province in Southern Thailand	International journal of infectious diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
67 6	Paul, N. I.	2019	Malaria preventive practices among under-fives in delta state, Nigeria	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
67 7	Paul, N. I.; Maduka, O.; Nwauche, C. A.; Oboro, I. L.; Kasso, T.; Yaguo-Ide, L. E.; Awopeju, A. T.; Otto, G.; Chijioke-Nwauche, I. N.; Iyalla, C.	2019	Malaria preventive practices among under-fives in Rivers State, Nigeria	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
67 8	Paul, N. I.; O, Maduka; I, Chijioke-Nwauche; A. T. O, Awopeju; T, Kasso; I. L, Oboro; G, Otto; M, Ogoro; L. E, Yaguo-Ide; C. A, Nwauche	2019	Malaria Preventive Practices among Under-five Children in Rivers State, Nigeria	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
67 9	Peak, C. M.; Thuan, P. D.; Britton, A.; Nguyen, T. D.; Wolbers, M.; Thanh, N. V.; Buckee, C. O.; Boni, M. F.	2015	Measuring the association between artemisinin-based case management and malaria incidence in southern Vietnam, 1991-2010	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
68 0	Peprah, S.; Dhudha, H.; Ally, H.; Masalu, N.; Kawira, E.; Chao, C. N.; Genga, I. O.; Mumia, M.; Were, P. A.; Kinyera, T.; Otim, I.; Legason, I. D.; Biggar, R. J.; Bhatia, K.; Goedert, J. J.; Pfeiffer, R. M.; Mbulaiteye, S. M.	2019	A population-based study of the prevalence and risk factors of low-grade Plasmodium falciparum malaria infection in children aged 0-15 years old in northern Tanzania	Tropical Medicine & International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

68 1	Peprah, S.; Tenge, C.; Genga, I. O.; Mumia, M.; Were, P. A.; Kuremu, R. T.; Wekesa, W. N.; Sumba, P. O.; Kinyera, T.; Otim, I.; Legason, I. D.; Biddle, J.; Reynolds, S. J.; Talisuna, A. O.; Biggar, R. J.; Bhatia, K.; Goedert, J. J.; Pfeiffer, R. M.; Mbulaiteye, S. M.	2019	A cross-sectional population study of geographic, age-specific, and household risk factors for asymptomatic plasmodium falciparum malaria infection in western Kenya	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
68 2	Perera, W. D.; Gunathilaka, P. A. D. H.; Taylor-Robinson, A.	2019	Malaria in Sri Lanka: Investigating causes of the recent elimination and making plans to prevent reintroduction	Journal of Vector Borne Diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
68 3	Perry, M.; De Carvalho, J. N.; Garcia, G.; Schwabe, C.; Hergott, D. E. B.; Cook, J.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2017	Understanding the environment of malaria related behaviors on Bioko Island, equatorial Guinea	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
68 4	Pietra, V.; Sahondra Harisoa, L.; Tombo, M.; et al.,	2001	Systeme de surveillance epidemiologique et d'alerte du paludisme sur les Hautes Terres Centrales de Madagascar : resultats 1999 - 2000	Arch. inst. pasteur Madag	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
68 5	Pinder	2014	Efficacy of indoor residual spraying with dichlorodiphenyltrichloro ethane against malaria in Gambian communities with high usage of long-lasting insecticidal mosquito nets: a cluster-randomised controlled trial	Lancet	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
68 6	Pinder, M.; Bradley, J.; Jawara, M.; Affara, M.; Conteh, L.; Correa, S.; Jeffries, D.; Jones, C.; Kandeh, B.; Knudsen, J.; et al.,	2021	Improved housing versus usual practice for additional protection against clinical malaria in The Gambia (RooPfs): a household-randomised controlled trial	The lancet planetary health	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray

68 7	Pinder, M.; Jawara, M. S.; Jarju, L. B.; Kandeh, B.; Jeffries, D.; Bojang, K. A.; D'Alessandro, U.; Conway, D. J.; Lindsay, S. W.	2012	To assess whether indoor residual spraying can provide additional protection against clinical malaria over current best practice of long-lasting insecticidal mosquito nets in the gambia: a twoarmed cluster-randomized study	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
68 8	Pinder, M.; Jawara, M.; Jarju, L. B.; Kandeh, B.; Jeffries, D.; Lluberas, M. F.; Mueller, J.; Parker, D.; Bojang, K.; Conway, D. J.; et al.,	2011	To assess whether indoor residual spraying can provide additional protection against clinical malaria over current best practice of long-lasting insecticidal mosquito nets in The Gambia: study protocol for a two-armed cluster-randomised trial	Trials	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
68 9	Pinder, M.; Jawara, M.; Jarju, L. B.; Salami, K.; Jeffries, D.; Adiamoh, M.	2014	Efficacy of indoor residual spraying with dichlorodiphenyltrichloro ethane against malaria in Gambian communities with high usage of long-lasting insecticidal mosquito nets: a cluster-randomised controlled trial	Lancet	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
69 0	Pluess, B.; Tanser, F. C.; Lengeler, C.; Sharp, B. L.	2010	Indoor residual spraying for preventing malaria	Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
69 1	Pollard, D.; Winters, A.; Hamainza, B.; Larsen, D.	2017	Results from a baseline survey to evaluate different indoor residual spray implementation strategies for malaria control	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
69 2	Pongvongsa, T.; Ha, H.; Thanh, L.; Marchand, R. P.; Nonaka, D.; Tojo, B.; Phongmany, P.; Moji, K.; Kobayashi, J.	2012	Joint malaria surveys lead towards improved cross-border cooperation between Savannakhet province, Laos and Quang Tri province, Vietnam	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
69 3	Pothin, E.; BriÅ«t, O.; Kesteman, T.; Randrianarivojosia, M.; Rogier, C.; Smith, T.	2014	The importance of historical data in simulating malaria epidemiology and control interventions: Application	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

			to multiple sites in Madagascar		
69 4	Pothin, E.; Briet, O.; Solomon, H.; Basaye, S.; Smith, T.	2015	Impact of IRS on malaria burden when combined with Ilin in Ethiopia: Modelling the 2015-2017 malaria national strategy	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
69 5	Pothin, E.; Cohen, J. M.; Smith, D. L.; Gething, P. W.; Battle, K.; Tatem, A. J.; Ruktanonchai, N.; Eisele, T. P.; Lemoine, J. F.; Menach, A. L.	2016	Malaria stratification for elimination activities	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
69 6	Pradhan, M. M.; Sahu, P. K.; Ranjit, M.; Datta, A.; Pati, S.	2021	Malaria elimination in high transmission Hard-to-reach areas in the state of Odisha India	BMC Proceedings	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
69 7	Prakash, Anil; Bhattacharyya, D. R.; Mohapatra, P. K.; Goswami, B. K.; Mahanta, J.	2008	Community practices of using bed nets & acceptance & prospects of scaling up insecticide treated nets in north-east India	The Indian journal of medical research	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
69 8	Prasad, H.	2009	Evaluation of malaria control programme in three selected districts of Assam, India	Journal of Vector Borne Diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
69 9	Pringle, J.; Das, S.; Kobayashi, T.; Searle, K.; Siame, M.; Katowa, B.; Chaponda, M.; Muleba, M.; Mulenga, M.; Norris, D.; Moss, W. J.	2015	Plasmodium falciparum multiplicity of infection pre-and post-vector control campaigns in Nchelenge District, Zambia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
70 0	Protopopoff	2018	Effectiveness of a long-lasting piperonyl butoxide-treated insecticidal net and indoor residual spray interventions, separately and together, against malaria transmitted by pyrethroid-resistant mosquitoes: a cluster, randomised controlled, two-by-two fact	Lancet (london, england)	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

70 1	Protopopoff, N.; Charlwood, D.; Mosh, J.; Wright, A.; Kisnza, W.; Mosh, F.	2017	Evaluation of a novel long lasting insecticidal net to indoor residual spray product, separately to together, against malaria transmitted by pyrethroid resistant mosquitoes in northwest Tanzania: a cluster randomized controlled trial	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: duplicate
70 2	Protopopoff, N.; Charlwood, D.; Mosh, J.; Wright, A.; Kisnza, W.; Mosh, F.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Rowland, M.	2015	Evaluation of a novel long lasting insecticidal net to indoor residual spray product, separately to together, against malaria transmitted by pyrethroid resistant mosquitoes in northwest Tanzania: a cluster randomized controlled trial	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
70 3	Protopopoff, N.; Mosh, J. F.; Lukole, E.; Charlwood, J. D.; Wright, A.; Mwalimu, C. D.; Manjurano, A.; Mosh, F. W.; Kisnza, W.; Kleinschmidt, I.; et al.,	2018	Effectiveness of a long-lasting piperonyl butoxide-treated insecticidal net and indoor residual spray interventions, separately and together, against malaria transmitted by pyrethroid-resistant mosquitoes: a cluster, randomised controlled, two-by-two fact	Lancet (london, england)	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
70 4	Protopopoff, N.; Van Bortel, W.; Marcotty, T.; Van Herp, M.; Maes, P.; Baza, D.; D'Alessandro, U.; Coosemans, M.	2008	Spatial targeted vector control is able to reduce malaria prevalence in the highlands of Burundi	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
70 5	Protopopoff, N.; Van Herp, M.; Maes, P.; Reid, T.; Baza, D.; D'Alessandro, U.; Van Bortel, W.; Coosemans, M.	2007	Vector control in a malaria epidemic occurring within a complex emergency situation in Burundi: A case study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
70 6	Protopopoff, N.; Wright, A.; West, P. A.; Tigererwa, R.; Mosh, F. W.; Kisnza, W.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Rowland, M.	2015	Combination of Insecticide Treated Nets and Indoor Residual Spraying in Northern Tanzania Provides Additional Reduction in Vector Population	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only

			Density and Malaria Transmission Rates Compared to Insecticide Treated Nets Alone: a Randomised Control Trial		
707	Protopopoff, N.; Wright, A.; West, P. A.; Tigererwa, R.; Wmosha, F.; Kisinza, W.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Rowland, M.	2016	Erratum: combination of insecticide treated nets and indoor residual spraying in northern Tanzania provides additional reduction in vector population density and malaria transmission rates compared to insecticide treated nets alone: a randomised control t	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
708	Protopopoff, Natacha; Wright, Alexandra; West, Philippa A.; Tigererwa, Robinson; Mosha, Franklin W.; Kisinza, William; Kleinschmidt, Immo; Rowland, Mark	2016	Correction: Combination of Insecticide Treated Nets and Indoor Residual Spraying in Northern Tanzania Provides Additional Reduction in Vector Population Density and Malaria Transmission Rates Compared to Insecticide Treated Nets Alone: A Randomised Contro	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
709	Psychas, P. J.; Eckman, B.; Abuaku, B.; Ahorlu, C.; Koram, K.	2014	Determinants of risk of malaria parasitemia in bunkpurugu-yunyoo district, Northern Ghana, incorporating remote sensing and survey data	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
710	Raghavendra, K.; Ghosh, S. K.; Eapen, A.; Tiwari, S. N.; Satyanarayan, T. S.; Ravindran, J.; Sreehari, U.; Dash, A. P.	2011	Field evaluation of lambda-cyhalothrin (ICON 10 CS) indoor residual spraying against Anopheles culicifacies in India	Journal of Vector Borne Diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
711	Raghavendra, K.; Ghosh, S. K.; Eapen, A.; Tiwari, S. N.; Satyanarayan, T. S.; Ravindran, J.; Sreehari, U.; Dash, A. P.	2011	Field evaluation of lambda-cyhalothrin (ICON 10 CS) indoor residual spraying against Anopheles culicifacies in India	Journal of Vector Borne Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

71 2	Rajvanshi, H.; Bharti, P. K.; Nisar, S.; Jain, Y.; Jayswar, H.; Mishra, A. K.; Sharma, R. K.; Saha, K. B.; Shukla, M. M.; Das, A.; Kaur, H.; Wattal, S. L.; Singh, N.; Lal, A. A.	2020	Study design and operational framework for a community-based Malaria Elimination Demonstration Project (MEDP) in 1233 villages of district Mandla, Madhya Pradesh	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
71 3	Rakotoarison, A. H.; Rasamimalala, M.; Rakotondramanga, J. M.; Ramiranirina, B.; Franchard, T.; Kapesa, L.; Razafindrakoto, J.; Baril, L.; Piola, P.; Rakotomanana, F.	2017	Using multi criteria evaluation to identify priority area for indoor residual spraying, Madagascar	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
71 4	Rakotomanana, F.; Rakotoarison, A. H.; Girond, F.; Piola, P.	2016	Malaria risk assessment using multi-criteria evaluation to identify priority areas for indoor residual spraying in the central highlands of madagascar	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
71 5	Ramachandra, T.	1951	Malaria control using indoor residual sprays in the Eastern Province of Afghanistan	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
71 6	Raman, Jaishree; Gast, Laura; Balawanth, Ryleen; Tessema, Sofonias; Brooke, Basil; Maharaj, Rajendra; Munhenga, Givemore; Tshikae, Power; Lakan, Vishan; Mwamba, Tshياما; Makowa, Hazel; Sangweni, Lindi; Mkhabela, Moses; Zondo, Nompumelelo; Mohulatsi, Ernest; Nyawo, Zuziwe; Ngxongo, Sifiso; Msimang, Siphon; Dagata, Nicole; Greenhouse, Bryan; Birkholtz, Lyn-Marie;	2020	High levels of imported asymptomatic malaria but limited local transmission in KwaZulu-Natal, a South African malaria-endemic province nearing malaria elimination	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

	Shirreff, George; Graffy, Rebecca; Qwabe, Bheki; Moonasar, Devanand				
71 7	Raouf, S.; Mpimbaza, A.; Kigozi, R.; Sserwanga, A.; Dorsey, G.	2016	Resurgence of malaria after discontinuation of indoor residual spraying of insecticide in a previously high transmission intensity area of Uganda	The Lancet Global Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
71 8	Raouf, S.; Mpimbaza, A.; Kigozi, R.; Sserwanga, A.; Rubahika, D.; Katamba, H.; Lindsay, S. W.; Kapella, B. K.; Belay, K. A.; Kanya, M. R.; Staedke, S. G.; Dorsey, G.	2017	Resurgence of Malaria Following Discontinuation of Indoor Residual Spraying of Insecticide in an Area of Uganda With Previously High-Transmission Intensity	Clinical Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
71 9	Ratovonjato, J.; Randrianariveolosia, M.; Rakotondrainibe, M. E.; Raharimanga, V.; Andrianaivolambo, L.; Le Goff, G.; Rogier, C.; Ariey, F.; Boyer, S.; Robert, V.	2014	Entomological and parasitological impacts of indoor residual spraying with DDT, alphacypermethrin and deltamethrin in the western foothill area of Madagascar	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
72 0	Reducing the Burden of Malaria by Targeting Hotspots of Malaria Transmission	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
72 1	Reducing the Burden of Malaria by Targeting Hotspots of Malaria Transmission	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
72 2	Rehman, A. M.; Coleman, M.; Schwabe, C.; Baltazar, G.; Matias, A.; Gomes, I. R.; Yellott, L.; Aragon, C.; Nchama, G. N.; Mzilahowa, T.; Rowland, M.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2011	How much does malaria vector control quality matter: The epidemiological impact of holed nets and inadequate indoor residual spraying	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

72 3	Rehman, A. M.; Mann, A. G.; Schwabe, C.; Reddy, M. R.; Roncon Gomes, I.; Slotman, M. A.; Yellott, L.; Matias, A.; Caccone, A.; Nseng Nchama, G.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2013	Five years of malaria control in the continental region, Equatorial Guinea	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
72 4	Reisen, W. K.; Pradhan, S. P.; Shrestha, J. P.; Shrestha, S. L.; Vaidya, R. G.; Shrestha, J. D.	1993	Anopheline mosquito (Diptera: Culicidae) ecology in relation to malaria transmission in the inner and outer terai of Nepal, 1987-1989	Journal of medical entomology	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
72 5	Rejeki, D. S. S.; Wijayanti, S. P. M.; Octaviana, D.; Suratman, S.	2019	The effect of climate and intervention methods on malaria incidence: A time series analysis	Annals of Tropical Medicine and Public Health	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
72 6	Rek, J. C.; Alegana, V.; Arinaitwe, E.; Cameron, E.; Kamya, M. R.; Katureebe, A.; Lindsay, S. W.; Kilama, M.; Staedke, S. G.; Todd, J.; Dorsey, G.; Tusting, L. S.	2018	Rapid improvements to rural Ugandan housing and their association with malaria from intense to reduced transmission: a cohort study	The lancet planetary health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
72 7	Rek, J.; Alegana, V.; Arinaitwe, E.; Cameron, E.; Kamya, M.; Katureebe, A.; Lindsay, S. W.; Kilama, M.; Staedke, S. G.; Todd, J.; Dorsey, G.; Tusting, L. S.	2018	Rapid improvements to rural Ugandan housing and their association with malaria from intense to reduced transmission: Findings from a cohort study	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
72 8	Rezaei-Hemami, M.; Akbari-Sari, A.; Raiesi, A.; Vatandoost, H.; Majdzadeh, R.	2013	Cost effectiveness of malaria interventions from preelimination through elimination: A study in Iran	Journal of Arthropod- Borne Diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
72 9	Rezaei-Hemami, Mohsen; Akbari-Sari, Ali; Raiesi, Ahmad; Vatandoost, Hassan; Majdzadeh, Reza	2014	Cost Effectiveness of Malaria Interventions from Preelimination through Elimination: a Study in Iran	Journal of Arthropod- Borne Diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
73 0	Ricotta, E.; Oppong, S.; Yukich, J. O.; BriÅ«t, O. J. T.	2019	Determinants of bed net use conditional on access in population surveys in Ghana	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

73 1	Riedel, N.; Vounatsou, P.; Miller, J. M.; Gosoni, L.; Chizema-Kawesha, E.; Mukonka, V.; Steketee, R. W.	2010	Geographical patterns and predictors of malaria risk in Zambia: Bayesian geostatistical modelling of the 2006 Zambia national malaria indicator survey (ZMIS)	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
73 2	Roberts, D. R.; Manguin, S.; Mouchet, J.	2000	DDT house spraying and re-emerging malaria	Lancet (london, england)	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
73 3	Roberts, D.; Matthews, G.	2016	Risk factors of malaria in children under the age of five years old in Uganda	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
73 4	Roberts, K. W.; Smith Gueye, C.; Baltzell, K.; Ntuku, H.; McCreesh, P.; Maglior, A.; Whittemore, B.; Uusiku, P.; Mumbengegwi, D.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Gosling, R.; Hsiang, M. S.	2021	Community acceptance of reactive focal mass drug administration and reactive focal vector control using indoor residual spraying, a mixed-methods study in Zambezi region, Namibia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
73 5	Robertson, M. L.; Saifodine, A.; Candrinho, B.; Fornadel, C.; McLean, T.; Loch, L.; Carty, C. A.; Wagman, J.; Saute, F.	2016	Cost-effectiveness of malaria control measures: a cluster- randomized control trial of IRS and itns in mozambique	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
73 6	Robertson, M.; Wagman, J.; Zulliger, R.; Saifodine, A.; Candrinho, B.; Richardson, J.; Slutsker, L.; Chaccour, C.; Saute, F.	2019	The cost of measuring impact: randomized control trial (RCT) methodologies for vector control	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
73 7	Roca-Feltrer, A.; Barranco, J.; Chipeta, P.; Phiri, K.; Lalloo, D.; Terlouw, D. J.	2010	Use of 'rolling' malaria indicator surveys (rmis) as a monitoring and evaluation (m&e) tool in malaria endemic settings with marked seasonality	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
73 8	Roca-Feltrer, A.; Barranco, J.; Chipeta, P.; Phiri, K.; Lalloo, D.; Terlouw, D. J.	2010	Use of 'rolling' malaria indicator surveys (rmis) as a monitoring and evaluation (m&e) tool in	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

			malaria endemic settings with marked seasonality		
739	Roca-Feltrer, A.; Phiri, K.; Lalloo, D.; Terlouw, D.	2011	Malaria burden and coverage estimates from the 2010-2011 monthly 'rolling' malaria indicator survey (RMIS) in Chikhwawa District, Malawi: A potential district-level malaria monitoring and evaluation (M&E) tool for program managers	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
740	Roh, M. E.; Shiboski, S.; Natureeba, P.; Kakuru, A.; Muhindo, M.; Ochieng, T.; Plenty, A.; Koss, C. A.; Clark, T. D.; Awori, P.; et al.,	2017	Protective Effect of Indoor Residual Spraying of Insecticide on Preterm Birth Among Pregnant Women With HIV Infection in Uganda: a Secondary Data Analysis	Journal of Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
741	Roh, M.; Koss, C.; Natureeba, P.; Shiboski, S.; Kakuru, A.; Muhindo, M.; Ochieng, T.; Plenty, A.; Clark, T.; Nakalambe, M.; Cohan, D.; Jagannathan, P.; Gosling, R.; Havlir, D.; Kanya, M.; Dorsey, G.	2017	Association between indoor residual spraying of insecticide and improved birth outcomes among HIV-infected pregnant women in Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
742	Rohani, A.; Fakhriy, H. Ahmad; Suzilah, I.; Zurainee, M. N.; Najdah, W. M. A. Wan; Ariffin, M. Mohd; Shakirudin, N. Mohamad; Afiq, M. S. Mohd; Jenarun, J.; Tanrang, Y.; Lee, H. L.	2020	Indoor and outdoor residual spraying of a novel formulation of deltamethrin K-Othrine® (Polyzone) for the control of simian malaria in Sabah, Malaysia	PloS one	Exclusion reason: duplicate
743	Rohani, A.; Fakhriy, H. Ahmad; Suzilah, I.; Zurainee, M. N.; Najdah, W. M. A. Wan; Ariffin, M. Mohd; Shakirudin, N. Mohamad; Afiq, M. S.	2020	Indoor and outdoor residual spraying of a novel formulation of deltamethrin K-Othrine R (Polyzone) for the control of simian malaria in Sabah, Malaysia	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	Mohd; Jenarun, J.; Tanrang, Y.; Lee, H. L.				
74 4	Romero-Leiton, J. P.; Castellanos, J. E.; Ibargen- Mondragn, E.	2019	An optimal control problem and cost- effectiveness analysis of malaria disease with vertical transmission applied to San Andrs de Tumaco (Colombia)	Computational and Applied Mathematics	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
74 5	Romi, R.; Razaiarimanga, M. C.; Raharimanga, R.; Rakotondraibe, E. M.; Ranaivo, L. H.; Pietra, V.; Raveloson, A.; Majori, G.	2002	Impact of the malaria control campaign (1993- 1998) in the highlands of Madagascar: Parasitological and entomological data	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
74 6	Roosiermiatie, B.; Nishiyama, M.; Nakae, K.	2000	The human behavioral and socioeconomic determinants of malaria in Bacan Island, North Maluku, Indonesia	Journal of epidemiology / Japan Epidemiologic al Association	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
74 7	<u>Rowland, M;</u> <u>Hewitt,</u> <u>S;</u> <u>Durrani, N</u>	1994	Prevalence of malaria in Afghan refugee villages in Pakistan sprayed with lambdacyhalothrin or malathion	<i>Transactions of The Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene</i>	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
74 8	<u>Rowland, M;</u> <u>Hewitt,</u> <u>S;</u> <u>Durrani, N</u> <u>Bano, N;</u> <u>Wirtz, R</u>	1997	Transmission and control of vivax malaria in Afghan refugee settlements in Pakistan	<i>Transactions of The Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene</i>	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
74 9	Rowland, M.; Hewitt, S.; Durrani, N.; Bano, N.; Wirtz, R.	1997	Transmission and control of vivax malaria in Afghan refugee settlements in Pakistan	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
75 0	Rowland, M.; Mahmood, P.; Iqbal, J.; Carneiro, I.; Chavasse, D.	2000	Indoor residual spraying with alphacypermethrin controls malaria in Pakistan: a community- randomized trial	Tropical Medicine & International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
75 1	Roy, R. G.; Joy, C. T.; Mohamed Hussain, C.; Mohamed Ismail, K.	1978	Malaria in Lakshadweep islands	Indian journal of medical research	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

75 2	Runge, M.; Pothin, E.; Mandike, R.; Mohamed, A.; Rumisha, S.; Molteni, F.; Smith, T.; Lengeler, C.	2017	Varying impact of malaria interventions at district level-implications of a mathematical model for strategic planning	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
75 3	Russell, J. R.; Gerardin, J.; Ouedraogo, A. L.; Smith, D. L.; Rodriguez-Barraquer, I.; Kamya, M.; Nankabirwa, J.; Dorsey, G.; Rek, J.; Staedke, S.; Ssewanyana, I.; Greenhouse, B.; Wenger, E. A.	2017	Understanding the decline and rebound in immunity to symptomatic malaria due to intervention disruption in malaria transmission	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
75 4	Ryan, S. J.; Martin, A. C.; Walia, B.; Winters, A.; Larsen, D. A.	2020	Comparing prioritization strategies for delivering indoor residual spray (IRS) implementation, using a network approach	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
75 5	Sahondra Harisoa, L. J.; Pietra, V.; Tombo, M. L.; Albonico, M.; Ranaivo, L. H.; De Giorgi, F.; Razanacolona, J.; D'Ancona, F. P.; Sabatinelli, G.; Raveloson, A.; Modiano, D.; Rakotondramarina, D.	2001	Epidemiologic surveillance system and control of malaria in the central highlands of Madagascar: results 1999-2000	Archives de l'Institut Pasteur de Madagascar	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
75 6	Sahu, S. S.; Thankachy, S.; Dash, S.; Nallan, K.; Swaminathan, S.; Kasinathan, G.; Purushothaman, J.	2020	Evaluation of long-lasting indoor residual spraying of deltamethrin 62.5 SC- PE against malaria vectors in India	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
75 7	Saita, S.; Pan-Ngum, W.; Phuanukoonnon, S.; Sriwichai, P.; Silawan, T.; White, L. J.; Parker, D. M.	2019	Human population movement and behavioural patterns in malaria hotspots on the Thai-Myanmar border: Implications for malaria elimination	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

75 8	Salam, R. A.; Das, J. K.; Lassi, Z. S.; Bhutta, Z. A.	2014	Impact of community-based interventions for the prevention and control of malaria on intervention coverage and health outcomes for the prevention and control of malaria	Infectious diseases of poverty	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
75 9	Salawu, M. M.; Akinyemi, O.; Adebisi, A.	2014	Knowledge and use of malaria preventive measures by caregivers of under-fives in rural Southwestern Nigeria	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
76 0	Sama, W.; Killeen, G.; Smith, T.	2004	Estimating the duration of Plasmodium falciparum infection from trials of indoor residual spraying	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
76 1	Samdi, L. M.; Ajayi, J. A.; Oguche, S.; Ayanlade, A.	2012	Seasonal variation of malaria parasite density in paediatric population of Northeastern Nigeria	Global journal of health science	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
76 2	Sande, S.; Zimba, M.; Mberikunashu, J.; Tangwena, A.; Chimusoro, A.	2017	Progress towards malaria elimination in Zimbabwe with special reference to the period 2003-2015	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
76 3	Sarpong, N.; Owusu-Dabo, E.; Kreuels, B.; Fobil, J. N.; Segebaya, S.; Amoyaw, F.; Hahn, A.; Kruppa, T.; May, J.	2015	Prevalence of malaria parasitaemia in school children from two districts of Ghana earmarked for indoor residual spraying: A cross-sectional study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
76 4	Sauboin, Christophe; Van Vlaenderen, Ilse; Van Bellinghen, Laure-Anne; Standaert, Baudouin	2019	Reducing Malaria Mortality at the Lowest Budget: An Optimization Tool for Selecting Malaria Preventative Interventions Applied to Ghana	MDM policy & practice	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
76 5	Schicker, R. S.; Hiruy, N.; Melak, B.; Gelaye, W.; Bezabih, B.; Stephenson, R.; Patterson, A. E.; Tadesse, Z.; Emerson, P. M.; Richards, F. O.; Noland, G. S.	2015	A venue-based survey of malaria, anemia and mobility patterns among migrant farm workers in amhara region, Ethiopia	PloS one	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
76 6	Scholtens, R. G.; Kaiser, R. L.; Langmuir, A. D.	1972	An epidemiologic examination of the	International Journal of Epidemiology	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

			strategy of malaria eradication		
767	Scott, C. A.; Yeshiwondim, A. K.; Serda, B.; Guinovart, C.; Tesfay, B. H.; Agmas, A.; Zeleke, M. T.; Guesses, G. S.; Ayenew, A. L.; Workie, W. M.; Steketee, R. W.; Earle, D.; Bezabih, B.; Getachew, A.	2016	Mass testing and treatment for malaria in low transmission areas in Amhara Region, Ethiopia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
768	Scott, C.; Guinovart, C.; Serda, B.; Tesfay, B.; Yeshiwondim, A.; Agmas, A.; Zeleke, M.; Guesses, G.; Ayenew, A.; Workie, W.; Zegeye, E.; Kalnoky, M.; Conner, R.; Steketee, R.; Bezabih, B.; Getachew, A.	2015	Mass testing and treatment for malaria in moderate transmission areas in Amhara region, Ethiopia	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
769	Selvaraj, Prashanth; Wenger, Edward A.; Gerardin, Jaline	2018	Seasonality and heterogeneity of malaria transmission determine success of interventions in high-endemic settings: a modeling study	BMC Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
770	Senyatso, R. Y.; Berlin, E. P.; Mosweunyane, T.; Molefi, M.	2019	Time series analysis of malaria in Botswana to forecast future cases	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
771	Sezi, C. L.	2014	The phenomenon of diminishing -returns in the use of bed nets and indoor house spraying and the emerging place of antimalarial medicines in the control of malaria in Uganda	African Health Sciences	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
772	Shah, N. K.; Tyagi, P.; Sharma, S. K.	2013	The Impact of Artemisinin Combination Therapy and Long-Lasting Insecticidal Nets on Forest Malaria Incidence in Tribal Villages of India, 2006-2011	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

77 3	Shakely, D.; Ali, A. S.; Abbas, A. K.; Msellem, M.; Bhattarai, A.; Beer, N.; Al-Mafazy, A. W.; Elfving, K.; Cook, J.; Xu, W.; Morris, U.; Rand, A.; Petzold, M.; Omar, R.; McElroy, P.; Drakely, C.; MaËšrtensson, A.; BjÃ¶rkman, A.	2014	Malaria elimination-not yet accomplished in Zanzibar	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
77 4	Sharma, S. K.; Upadhyay, A. K.; Haque, M. A.; Tyagi, P. K.; Kindo, B. K.	2012	Impact of changing over of insecticide from synthetic pyrethroids to DDT for indoor residual spray in a malaria endemic area of Orissa, India	Indian journal of medical research	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
77 5	Sharma, S. K.; Upadhyay, A. K.; Haque, M. A.; Tyagi, P. K.; Kindo, B. K.	2012	Impact of changing over of insecticide from synthetic pyrethroids to DDT for indoor residual spray in a malaria endemic area of Orissa, India	Indian journal of medical research	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
77 6	Sharma, S. N.; Shukla, R. P.; Raghavendra, K.; Subbarao, S. K.	2005	Impact of DDT spraying on malaria transmission in Bareilly District, Uttar Pradesh, India	Journal of Vector Borne Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
77 7	Sharp, B. L.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Streat, E.; Maharaj, R.; Barnes, K. I.; Durrheim, D. N.; Ridl, F. C.; Morris, N.; Seocharan, I.; Kunene, S.; La Grange, J. J. P.; Mthembu, J. D.; Maartens, F.; Martin, C. L.; Barreto, A.	2007	Seven years of regional malaria control collaboration - Mozambique, South Africa, and Swaziland	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
77 8	Shepard, D. S.; Glaser, E.; Kihombo, A.; Khoshi, S.	2013	Cost effectiveness of indoor residual spraying in Nyanza province Kenya	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
77 9	Shepard, D. S.; Halasa, Y. A.; Kihombo, A.; Kihomo, R. M.; Mangesho, P.;	2016	Cost-effectiveness of insecticide-treated wall liner and indoor residual spraying to prevent	American journal of tropical	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	Messenger, L.; Mnzava, R.; Mtove, G.; Mugasa, J.; Seif, M.; et al.,		malaria in Kenya and Tanzania	medicine and hygiene	
78 0	Shepard, D. S.; Mangesho, P.; Kihomo, R. M.; Kihombo, A.; Mugasa, J.; Malongo, A.; Mnzava, R.; Tenu, F.; Rwiyereka, A. K.; Halasa, Y. A.; Samuels, A. M.; Rowland, M.; Masha, F.; Kisinza, W.	2014	Household expenditures for malaria treatment from a population-based survey	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
78 1	Sherlock, M.; Giorgi, E.; Roca-Feltrer, A.; Masesa, C.; Phiri, K.; Laloo, D.; Diggle, P.; Terlouw, D.	2015	A comparison of household survey screening for malaria among older children (5- 14yrs) and adults versus young children to determine fine-scale heterogeneity in an area of high transmission	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
78 2	Shittu-Koiki, E.	2018	How effective are malaria eradication strategies in Africa?	American Journal of Clinical Pathology	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
78 3	Shrivastava, S. R.; Shrivastava, P. S.; Ramasamy, J.	2017	Aiming for Malaria elimination: World Health Organization	Annals of Tropical Medicine and Public Health	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
78 4	Sikalima, Jay; Schue, Jessica L.; Hill, Sarah E.; Mulenga, Modest; Handema, Ray; Daka, Victor; Chileshe, Justin; Kasongo, Webster; Chaponda, Mike; Bukasa Kabuya, Jean-Bertin; Moss, William J.; Ippolito, Matthew M.; Southern,; Central Africa International Centers of Excellence for Malaria, Research	2021	House Structure Is Associated with Malaria among Febrile Patients in a High-Transmission Region of Zambia	The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
78 5	Silal, S. P.; Shretta, R.; Celhay, O. J.; Mercado, C. E. G.; Saralamba, S.;	2019	Malaria elimination transmission and costing in the asia-pacific: A multi-species dynamic	Wellcome open research	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

	Maude, R. J.; White, L. J.		transmission model [version 2; peer review: 2 not approved]		
786	Silal, S. P.; White, L. J.; Kollipara, A.; Moya, M.; Graffy, R.; Mabunda, E.; Malatje, G.; Qwabe, B.; Pillay, Y.; Moonasar, D.	2018	Supporting decision-making for malaria elimination in south Africa: A mathematical modelling approach	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
787	Silumbe, K.; Chanda, J.; Ndhlovu, K.; Rutagwera, M. R.; Hamainza, B.; Yeta, A.; Mudenda-Chilufya, M.; Miller, J. M.	2019	Reductions in malaria burden through the use of a scalable intervention package (SIP) in accordance with the Zambia national malaria elimination strategic plan 2017-2021: The case of Mulobezi district in Western Province	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
788	Simon, C.; Moakofhi, K.; Mosweunyane, T.; Jibril, H. B.; Nkomo, B.; Motlaleng, M.; Ntebela, D. S.; Chanda, E.; Haque, U.	2013	Malaria control in Botswana, 2008-2012: The path towards elimination	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
789	Singh, N.; Chand, S. K.; Bharti, P. K.; Singh, M. P.; Chand, G.; Mishra, A. K.; Shukla, M. M.; Mahulia, M. M.; Sharma, R. K.	2013	Dynamics of forest malaria transmission in Balaghat district, Madhya Pradesh, India	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
790	Singh, N.; Mishra, A. K.; Saha, K. B.; Bharti, P. K.; Sisodia, D. S.; Sonal, G. S.; Dhariwal, A. C.; Sharma, R. K.	2018	Malaria control in a tribal area of central India using existing tools	Acta tropica	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
791	Singh, R. K.; Das, M. K.; Dhiman, R. C.; Mittal, P. K.; Dua, V. K.; Sreehari, U.; Prasad, S.	2012	Evaluation of indoor residual spray and insecticide treated bed nets in a malaria endemic area of santhal pargana, Dumka district (Jharkhand)	Journal of Communicable Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
792	Sinzinkayo, D.; Baza, D.; Gnanguenon, V.; Koepfli, C.	2021	The lead-up to epidemic transmission: malaria trends and control interventions in Burundi 2000 to 2019	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

79 3	Sisya, T. J.; Kamn'gona, R. M.; Vareta, J. A.; Fulakeza, J. M.; Mukaka, M. F.; Laufer, M. K.; Seydel, K. B.; Taylor, T. E.; Nkhoma, S. C.	2014	Subtle changes in plasmodium falciparum infection complexity following enhanced intervention in Malawi	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
79 4	Sisya, T. J.; Kamn'gona, R. M.; Vareta, J. A.; Fulakeza, J. M.; Mukaka, M. F.; Seydel, K. B.; Laufer, M. K.; Taylor, T. E.; Nkhoma, S. C.	2015	Subtle changes in Plasmodium falciparum infection complexity following enhanced intervention in Malawi	Acta tropica	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
79 5	Skarbinski, J.; Mwandama, D.; Luka, M.; Jafali, J.; Wolkon, A.; Townes, D.; Campbell, C.; Zoya, J.; Ali, D.; Mathanga, D. P.	2011	Impact of health facility- based insecticide treated bednet distribution in Malawi: Progress and challenges towards achieving universal coverage	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
79 6	Skarbinski, J.; Mwandama, D.; Wolkon, A.; Luka, M.; Jafali, J.; Smith, A.; Mzilahowa, T.; Gimnig, J.; Campbell, C.; Chiphwanya, J.; Ali, D.; Mathanga, D. P.	2012	Impact of indoor residual spraying with lambda- cyhalothrin on malaria parasitemia and anemia prevalence among children less than five years of age in an area of intense, year-round transmission in Malawi	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
79 7	Skarbinski, J.; Mwandama, D.; Wolkon, A.; Luka, M.; Jafali, J.; Smith, A.; Mzilahowa, T.; Gimnig, J.; Campbell, C.; Chiphwanya, J.; Mathanga, D. P.; Ali, D.	2011	Impact of indoor residual spraying with lambda- cyhalothrin on malaria parasitemia and anemia prevalence among children <5 years in an area of intense, year- round transmission in Malawi	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
79 8	Sleigh, A. C.; Liu, X. L.; Jackson, S.; Li, P.; Shang, L. Y.	1998	Resurgence of vivax malaria in Henan Province, China	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
79 9	Smith Gueye, C.; Newby, G.; Gosling, R. D.; Whittaker, M. A.; Chandramohan, D.; Slutsker, L.; Tanner, M.	2016	Strategies and approaches to vector control in nine malaria- eliminating countries: A cross-case study analysis	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

800	Smith, J. L.; Mumbengegwi, D.; Haindongo, E.; Cueto, C.; Roberts, K. W.; Gosling, R.; Uusiku, P.; Kleinschmidt, I.; Bennett, A.; Sturrock, H. J.	2021	Malaria risk factors in northern Namibia: The importance of occupation, age and mobility in characterizing high-risk populations	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
801	Smith, J. M.; Nfumu, J. O. O.; Vaz, L. M.; Phiri, W. P.; Hergott, D. E. B.; De Carvalho, J. N.; Garcia, G.; Schwabe, C.; Cook, J.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2017	Net migration or non-use? bed net ownership following mass distribution campaigns on Bioko Island, Equatorial Guinea	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
802	Smits, A.; Coosemans, M.; Van Bortel, W.; Barutwanayo, M.; Delacollette, C.	1995	Readjustment of the malaria vector control strategy in the Rusizi Valley, Burundi	Bulletin of Entomological Research	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
803	Solomon, T.; Loha, E.; Deressa, W.; Gari, T.; Lindtjrn, B.	2019	Spatiotemporal clustering of malaria in southern-central Ethiopia: a community-based cohort study	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
804	Soma, D. D.; Kassi, D.; Sanou, S.; Karama, F. B.; Ouari, A.; Mamai, W.; Oudraogo, G. A.; Salem, G.; Dabir, R. K.; Fournet, F.	2018	Uneven malaria transmission in geographically distinct districts of Bobo-Dioulasso, Burkina Faso	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
805	Spjeldns, A. O.; Kitua, A. Y.; Blomberg, B.	2014	Education and knowledge helps combating malaria, but not degedege: A cross-sectional study in Rufiji, Tanzania	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
806	Spraying And Nets Towards malaria Elimination	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
807	Spraying And Nets Towards malaria Elimination	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
808	Sreehari, U.; Mittal, P. K.; Razdan, R. K.; Dash, A. P.; Ansari, M. A.	2009	Impact of etofenprox (Vectron 20 WP) indoor residual spray on malaria transmission	Indian journal of medical research	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

809	Sreehari, U.; Mittal, P. K.; Razdan, R. K.; Dash, A. P.; Ansari, M. A.	2009	Impact of etofenprox (Vectron® 20 WP) indoor residual spray on malaria transmission	Indian journal of medical research	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
810	Srivastava, H. C.; Yadav, R. S.	2000	Malaria outbreak in a tribal area of Gujarat state, India	The Southeast Asian journal of tropical medicine and public health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
811	Ssempiira, J.; Nambuusi, B.; Kissa, J.; Agaba, B.; Makumbi, F.; Kasasa, S.; Vounatsou, P.	2017	The contribution of malaria control interventions on spatio-temporal changes of parasitaemia risk in Uganda during 2009-2014	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
812	Ssewanyana, I.; Rek, J.; Rodriguez, I.; Wu, L.; Arinaitwe, E.; Nankabirwa, J.; Mayanja-Kizza, H.; Rosenthal, P. J.; Dorsey, G.; Kanya, M.; Drakeley, C.; Greenhouse, B.; Tetteh, K.	2018	Predominant loss of low avidity IGG antimalarial antibodies associated with reduction in infection after indoor residual spraying in Nagongera, Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
813	Steen, T. W.; Drage, M.; Solum, J. A.	2009	How to combat HIV, tuberculosis and malaria?	Tidsskrift for den Norske Lægeforening : tidsskrift for praktisk medicin, ny række	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
814	Steinhardt, L. C.; Ravaoarisoa, E.; Wiegand, R.; Harimanana, A.; Hedje, J.; Cotte, A.; Zigirumugabe, S.; Kesteman, T.; Rasoloharimanana, T. L.; Rakotomalala, E.; Butts, J.; Rogier, C.; Piola, P.; Randrianariveojosia, M.; Vigan-Womas, I.	2015	A school-based serology study to validate use of routine data for targeting malaria interventions in the central highlands of madagascar	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
815	Steinhardt, L. C.; Yeka, A.; Nasr, S.; Wiegand, R. E.; Rubahika, D.; Sserwanga, A.; Wanzira, H.; Lavoy,	2013	The effect of indoor residual spraying on malaria and anemia in a high-transmission area of Northern Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	G.; Kanya, M.; Dorsey, G.; Filler, S.				
81 6	Steinhardt, L.; Yeka, A.; Nasr, S.; Rubahika, D.; Sserwanga, A.; Wanzirah, H.; Lavoy, G.; Kanya, M.; Dorsey, G.; Filler, S.	2011	District-based household survey data and associated biomarkers in indoor residual spraying (IRS) and non-irs districts in Northern Uganda	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
81 7	Steketee, R. W.; Campbell, C. C.	2010	Impact of national malaria control scale-up programmes in Africa: Magnitude and attribution of effects	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
81 8	Stelmach, R.; Colaço, R.; Lalji, S.; McFarland, D.; Reithinger, R.	2018	Cost-effectiveness of indoor residual spraying of households with insecticide for malaria prevention and control in Tanzania	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
81 9	Stevenson, J. C.; Stresman, G. H.; Baidjoe, A.; Okoth, A.; Oriango, R.; Owaga, C.; Marube, E.; Bousema, T.; Cox, J.; Drakeley, C.	2015	Use of different transmission metrics to describe malaria epidemiology in the highlands of western Kenya	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
82 0	Stuckey, E. M.; Miller, J. M.; Littrell, M.; Chitnis, N.; Steketee, R.	2016	Operational strategies of anti-malarial drug campaigns for malaria elimination in Zambia's southern province: A simulation study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
82 1	Stuckey, E. M.; Stevenson, J. C.; Cooke, M. K.; Owaga, C.; Marube, E.; Oando, G.; Hardy, D.; Drakeley, C.; Smith, T. A.; Cox, J.; Chitnis, N.	2012	Simulation of malaria epidemiology and control in the highlands of western Kenya	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
82 2	Stuckey, E. M.; Stevenson, J.; Baidjoe, A.; Bousema, T.; Odongo, W.; Kariuki, S.; Smith, T.; Cox, J.; Chitnis, N.	2013	Determining the optimal mix of malaria control interventions in the highlands of western Kenya through simulation models	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
82 3	Stuckey, E. M.; Stevenson, J.; Galaktionova, K.; Baidjoe, A. Y.; Bousema, T.;	2014	Modeling the cost effectiveness of malaria control interventions in the highlands of Western Kenya	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	Odongo, W.; Kariuki, S.; Drakley, C.; Smith, T. A.; Cox, J.; Chitnis, N.				
82 4	Stuckey, Erin M.; Stevenson, Jennifer; Galactionova, Katya; Baidjoe, Amrish Y.; Bousema, Teun; Odongo, Wycliffe; Kariuki, Simon; Drakeley, Chris; Smith, Thomas A.; Cox, Jonathan; Chitnis, Nakul	2014	Modeling the cost effectiveness of malaria control interventions in the highlands of western Kenya	PloS one	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
82 5	Sudarsan, S. P.; Von Mach, T. A.; Shaw, A.	2016	Community experiences with bednet distribution and indoor residual spraying campaigns for malaria prevention in rural ghana: A qualitative investigation	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
82 6	Sudathip, P.; Zwang, J.; Tipmontree, R.; Kitcharkarn, S.; Thongrad, T.; Young, F.; Reithinger, R.; Shah, J. A.; Sintasath, D.; Prempre, P.; Areechokchai, D.; Kajanasuwan, J.; Lertpiriyasuwat, C.	2019	A foci cohort analysis to assess malaria elimination in Thailand	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
82 7	Suresh, J. G.; Galatas, B.; Selvaraj, P.; Nikolov, M.; Bertozzi-Villa, A.; Miller, J.; Hamainza, B.; Guinovart, C.; MartÃ-Soler, H.; Aide, P.; Saute, F.; Wenger, E. A.; Gerardin, J.; Bever, C. A.	2018	Stratification of malaria transmission dynamics and optimal intervention packages in Zambia and Mozambique	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
82 8	Susanna, D.; Ernawati, K.; Achmadi, U. F.	2012	Sustainable planning in a malaria vector control program: A study in Pesawaran, Indonesia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
82 9	Suuron, Vitalis Mwinuri; Mwanri, Lillian; Tsourtos, George; Owusu-Addo, Ebenezer	2020	An exploratory study of the acceptability of indoor residual spraying for malaria control in upper western Ghana	BMC Public Health	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

830	Suwonkerd, W.; Vryheid, R.; Suwannachote, N.	2010	Progress of partial integration of malaria control with other vector borne diseases control in northern Thailand	The Southeast Asian journal of tropical medicine and public health	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
831	Swana, E. K.; Mupemba, B.; Suprianto, S.; Mawaw, P. M.; Yav, T.; Mukeng, C. K.; Hattingh, I.; Luboya, O. N.; Kakoma, J. B. S.; Bangs, M. J.	2017	School-based malaria prevalence survey: Important longitudinal surveillance tool to assess epidemiological impact of malaria control interventions in the Democratic Republic of the Congo	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
832	Swana, Edouard K.; Yav, Thierry I.; Ngwej, Leonard M.; Mupemba, Betty N.; Suprianto,; Mukeng, Clarence K.; Hattingh, Izak; Luboya, Oscar N.; Kakoma, Jean-Baptiste S.; Bangs, Michael J.	2018	School-based malaria prevalence: informative systematic surveillance measure to assess epidemiological impact of malaria control interventions in the Democratic Republic of the Congo	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
833	Sy, O.; Cisse, B.; Tairou, F.; Diallo, A.; Ba, E.; Gomis, J. F.; Ndiaye, J. L.; Konate, L.; Gaye, O.; Milligan, P.; Faye, O.	2015	[Acceptability of indoor residual spraying in the Central-Western of Senegal]	Etude de l'acceptabilite de l'aspersion intradomiciliaire d'insecticide a effet remanent dans le centre-ouest du Senegal.	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
834	Sy, O.; Niang, E. H. A.; Diallo, A.; Ndiaye, A.; KonatÃ©, L.; Ba, E. H. C. C.; Tairou, F.; CissÃ©, B.; Gaye, O.; Milligan, P.; Faye, O.	2019	Evaluation of the effectiveness of a targeted community-based IRS approach for malaria elimination in an area of low malaria transmission of the central-western Senegal	Parasite Epidemiology and Control	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
835	Taffese, Hiwot S.; Hemming-Schroeder, Elizabeth; Koepfli, Cristian; Tesfaye, Gezahegn; Lee, Ming-Chieh; Kazura, James; Yan, Gui-Yun; Zhou, Guo-Fa	2018	Malaria epidemiology and interventions in Ethiopia from 2001 to 2016	Infectious diseases of poverty	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

83 6	Tairou, F.; Circe Ba, E. H. K.; Diallo, A.; Sy, O.; Cisse, B.; Gomis, J. F.; Gaye, O.; Milligan, P.; Pitt, C.	2015	The costs and cost-effectiveness of two spatially targeted, multi-component malaria elimination strategies: results of a large three-arm cluster-randomized trial in rural Senegal	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
83 7	Tangena, Julie-Anne A.; Hendriks, Chantal M. J.; Devine, Maria; Tammamo, Meghan; Trett, Anna E.; Williams, Ignatius; DePina, Adilson Jose; Sisay, Achamylesh; Herizo, Ramandimbiarijaona; Kafy, Hmooda Toto; Chizema, Elizabeth; Were, Allan; Rozier, Jennifer; Coleman, Michael; Moyes, Catherine L.	2020	Indoor residual spraying for malaria control in sub-Saharan Africa 1997 to 2017: an adjusted retrospective analysis	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
83 8	Targeted Indoor Residual Spraying Against Malaria	Year not provided	Title not provided	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
83 9	Taylor, C.; Florey, L.	2016	Association between improved housing characteristics and malaria prevalence in children under five	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
84 0	Teklehaimanot, H. D.; Teklehaimanot, A.; Kiszewski, A.; Rampao, H. S.; Sachs, J. D.	2009	Malaria in São Tomé and Príncipe: On the brink of elimination after three years of effective antimalarial measures	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
84 1	Temu, E. A.; Coleman, M.; Abilio, A. P.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2012	High prevalence of malaria in Zambezia, Mozambique: The protective effect of IRS versus increased risks due to pig-keeping and house construction	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
84 2	Tessema, S. K.; Rek, J.; Chen, A.; Teyssier, N.; Lee, Y.; Arinaitwe, E.; Nankabirwa, J. I.; Staedke, S. G.; Kanya, M. R.;	2018	Repeated indoor residual spraying reduces plasmodium falciparum effective population size and increases inbreeding in a very high	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	Dorsey, G.; Rodriguez-Barraquer, I.; Greenhouse, B.		transmission area of Uganda		
843	Thapar, R.; Srivastava, P.; Singh, S.	2019	A study to assess knowledge, attitude and practices on prevention and control of malaria in two endemic blocks of district Nuh (Mewat region) in Haryana	Journal of Communicable Diseases	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
844	Tilahun, A.; Yimer, M.; Gelaye, W.; Tegegne, B.	2020	Prevalence of asymptomatic Plasmodium species infection and associated factors among pregnant women attending antenatal care at Fendeka town health facilities, Jawi District, North west Ethiopia: A cross-sectional study	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
845	Topazian, Hillary M.; Gumbo, Austin; Brandt, Katerina; Kayange, Michael; Smith, Jennifer S.; Edwards, Jessie K.; Goel, Varun; Mvalo, Tisungane; Emch, Michael; Pettifor, Audrey E.; Juliano, Jonathan J.; Hoffman, Irving	2021	Effectiveness of a national mass distribution campaign of long-lasting insecticide-treated nets and indoor residual spraying on clinical malaria in Malawi, 2018-2020	BMJ global health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
846	Toyama, Y.; Ota, M.; Molla, G.; Beyene, B. B.	2016	Sharp decline of malaria cases in the Burie Zuria, Dembia, and Mecha districts, Amhara Region, Ethiopia, 2012-2014: Descriptive analysis of surveillance data	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
847	Tripathi, R.; Makeen, H. A.; Albarraq, A. A.; Tripathi, P.; Meraya, A. M.; Mubaraki, A. A.; Alfaifi, M. E.	2019	A community-based survey of malaria and its prevention in Jazan, Saudi Arabia	International journal of health promotion and education	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
848	Tripathi, Rina; Makeen, Hafiz A.; Albarraq, Ahmed A.; Tripathi, Pankaj;	2020	A community-based survey of malaria and its prevention in Jazan, Saudi Arabia	International Journal of Health	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

	Meraya, Abdulkarim M.; Mubarak, Amal A.; Alfaifi, Mashael E.			Promotion & Education	
849	Tseng, Lien Fen; Chang, Wen Chun; Ferreira, Maria Conceicao; Wu, Cheng Hua; Rampao, Herodes Sacramento; Lien, Jih Ching	2008	Rapid control of malaria by means of indoor residual spraying of alphacypermethrin in the Democratic Republic of Sao Tome and Principe	The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
850	Tsoka-Gwegweni, J. M.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2013	Malaria control aimed at the entire population in KwaZulu-Natal negates the need for policies to prevent malaria in pregnancy	South African Medical Journal	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
851	Tugume, A.; Muneza, F.; Oporia, F.; Kiconco, A.; Kihembo, C.; Kisakye, A. N.; Nsubuga, P.; Deogratias, S.; Yeka, A.	2019	Effects and factors associated with indoor residual spraying with Actellic 300 CS on malaria morbidity in Lira District, Northern Uganda	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
852	Tukei, B. B.; Beke, A.; Lamadrid-Figueroa, H.	2017	Assessing the effect of indoor residual spraying (IRS) on malaria morbidity in Northern Uganda: a before and after study	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
853	Turnbull, L. B.; Ayodo, G.; Onyango, E.; John, C. C.	2018	Age-related risk clinical malaria over time in a highland area of Kenya during a period of decreasing malaria transmission followed by an epidemic	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
854	Tusting, Lucy S.; Bottomley, Christian; Gibson, Harry; Kleinschmidt, Immo; Tatem, Andrew J.; Lindsay, Steve W.; Gething, Peter W.	2017	Housing Improvements and Malaria Risk in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Multi-Country Analysis of Survey Data	PLoS Medicine	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
855	Uragayala, S.; Kamaraju, R.; Tiwari, S.; Ghosh, S. K.; Valecha, N.	2015	Small-scale evaluation of the efficacy and residual activity of alpha-cypermethrin WG (250 g AI/kg) for indoor spraying in comparison with alpha-cypermethrin WP (50 g AI/kg) in India	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only

856	Valadez, J. J.; Devkota, B.; Pradhan, M. M.; Meherda, P.; Sonal, G. S.; Dhariwal, A.; Davis, R.	2014	Improving malaria treatment and prevention in India by aiding district managers to manage their programmes with local information: A trial assessing the impact of Lot Quality Assurance Sampling on programme outcomes	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
857	van Eijk, A. M.; Choubey, S.; Barla, P.; Haque, M. A.; Nandini, P.; Acharya, S.; Sullivan, S. A.; Mohanty, S.; Satpathi, S.; Carlton, J. M.	2020	Malaria in Sundargarh district, Odisha, India: Epidemiological and behavioral aspects from surveys	Acta tropica	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
858	Villegas, L.; Hiwat, H.; Cairo, H.; Hardjopawiro, L.	2010	Sustained malaria control in Suriname after 3 years of effective interventions	International journal of infectious diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
859	Vo, T. H.; Canavati, S. E.; Quintero, C. E.; Tran, L. K.; Ohrt, C.; Ngo, T. D.; Tran, D. T.; Martin, N. J.	2017	Targeted-reactive case detection at sleeping sites to interrupt malaria transmission in Vietnam II: Reported and observed malaria prevention, treatment and risk behaviors	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: No indoor or outdoor surface spray
860	Vontas, J.; Grigoraki, L.; Morgan, J.; Tsakireli, D.; Fuseini, G.; Segura, L.; de Carvalho, J. N.; Nguema, R.; Weetman, D.; Slotman, M. A.; Hemingway, J.	2018	Rapid selection of a pyrethroid metabolic enzyme CYP9K1 by operational malaria control activities	Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
861	Voorham, J.	1997	The use of wide-mesh gauze impregnated with lambda-cyhalothrin covering wall openings in huts as a vector control method in Suriname	Revista de saude publica	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
862	Wagman, J.; Cissé, I.; Kone, D.; Fomba, S.; Eckert, E.; Mihigo, J.; Bankineza, E.; Bah, M.; Diallo, D.; Gogue, C.; Tynuv, K.; Saibu,	2020	Rapid reduction of malaria transmission following the introduction of indoor residual spraying in previously unsprayed	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	A.; Richardson, J. H.; Fornadel, C.; Slutsker, L.; Robertson, M.		districts: An observational analysis of Mopti Region, Mali, in 2017		
863	Wagman, J.; Gogue, C.; Tynuv, K.; Mihigo, J.; Bankineza, E.; Bah, M.; Diallo, D.; Saibu, A.; Richardson, J. H.; Kone, D.; Fomba, S.; Bernson, J.; Steketee, R.; Slutsker, L.; Robertson, M.	2018	An observational analysis of the impact of indoor residual spraying with non-pyrethroid insecticides on the incidence of malaria in SÃ©gou Region, Mali: 2012-2015	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
864	Wagman, J.; Gogue, C.; Tynuv, K.; Mihigo, J.; Diallo, D.; Bankineza, E.; Bah, M.; Saibu, A.; Richardson, J.; Kone, D.; Fomba, S.; Slutsker, L.; Robertson, M.	2017	An observational analysis of the impact of IRS in the SÃ©gou region of Mali: 2011-2014	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
865	Wagman, J.; Gogue, C.; Tynuv, K.; Mihigo, J.; Diallo, D.; Bankineza, E.; Bah, M.; Saibu, A.; Richardson, J.; Kone, D.; Fomba, S.; Slutsker, L.; Robertson, M.	2017	Observational evidence of a complimentary effect of combining next generation indoor residual spraying and seasonal malaria chemoprevention in the sÃ©gou region of mali, 2014	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
866	Wagman, J.; Gogue, C.; Tynuv, K.; Mihigo, J.; Fomba, S.; Bankineza, E.; Bah, M.; Diallo, D.; Saibu, A.; Richardson, J.; Slutsker, L.; Robertson, M.	2018	Rapid reduction of malaria transmission after introducing a third generation indoor residual spraying product in previously unsprayed districts of MOPTI region, Mali in 2017	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
867	Wagman, J.; Seyoum, A.; Magesa, S.; Varela, K.; Muthoni, R.; Gogue, C.; Tynuv, K.; Chaccour, C.; Saute, F.; Zulliger, R.; et al.,	2019	A good spray: entomological surveillance results from a cluster randomized trial to evaluate the impact of a third generation indoor residual spray product on malaria transmission in mozambique	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

86 8	Walker, P. G. T.; Griffin, J. T.; Ferguson, N. M.; Ghani, A. C.	2016	Estimating the most efficient allocation of interventions to achieve reductions in Plasmodium falciparum malaria burden and transmission in Africa: A modelling study	The Lancet Global Health	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
86 9	Walldorf, J. A.; Cohee, L. M.; Fiore, J.; Bauleni, A.; Coalson, J. E.; Phiri, T.; Mathanga, D.; Valim, C.; Kapito-Tembo, A. P.; Taylor, T. E.; Laufer, M. K.	2013	Reservoirs of asymptomatic malaria in Malawi: Results of two cross-sectional studies	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
87 0	Waltmann, A.; Darcy, A. W.; Harris, I.; Koepfli, C.; Lodo, J.; Vahi, V.; Piziki, D.; Shanks, G. D.; Barry, A. E.; Whittaker, M.; Kazura, J. W.; Mueller, I.	2015	High Rates of Asymptomatic, Sub-microscopic Plasmodium vivax Infection and Disappearing Plasmodium falciparum Malaria in an Area of Low Transmission in Solomon Islands	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
87 1	Wang, X.; Zhou, G.; Yan, G.	2019	Malaria control and elimination in Africa: Why are some countries doing better than others?	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
87 2	Wangdi, K.; Banwell, C.; Gatton, M. L.; Kelly, G. C.; Namgay, R.; Clements, A. C. A.	2016	Malaria burden and costs of intensified control in Bhutan, 2006-14: An observational study and situation analysis	The Lancet Global Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
87 3	Wangdi, K.; Canavati, S. E.; Ngo, T. D.; Nguyen, T. M.; Tran, L. K.; Kelly, G. C.; Martin, N. J.; Clements, A. C. A.	2020	Spatial and temporal patterns of malaria in phu Yen Province, Vietnam, from 2005 to 2016	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
87 4	Wangdi, K.; Canavati, S. E.; Ngo, T. D.; Tran, L. K.; Nguyen, T. M.; Tran, D. T.; Martin, N. J.; Clements, A. C. A.	2018	Analysis of clinical malaria disease patterns and trends in Vietnam 2009-2015 11 Medical and Health Sciences 1117 Public Health and Health Services	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
87 5	Wangdi, K.; Furuya-Kanamori, L.; Clark, J.; Barendregt, J. J.; Gatton, M. L.;	2018	Comparative effectiveness of malaria prevention measures: A	Parasites and Vectors	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

	Banwell, C.; Kelly, G. C.; Doi, S. A. R.; Clements, A. C. A.		systematic review and network meta-analysis		
876	Wangdi, Kinley; Canavati, Sara E.; Ngo, Thang Duc; Tran, Long Khanh; Nguyen, Thu Minh; Tran, Duong Thanh; Martin, Nicholas J.; Clements, Archie C. A.	2018	Analysis of clinical malaria disease patterns and trends in Vietnam 2009-2015	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: duplicate
877	Wanzira, H.; Katamba, H.; Okullo, A. E.; Agaba, B.; Kasule, M.; Rubahika, D.	2017	Factors associated with malaria parasitaemia among children under 5 years in Uganda: a secondary data analysis of the 2014 Malaria Indicator Survey dataset	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
878	Webb, J. L. A., Jr.	2014	Malaria control and eradication projects in tropical africa, 1945-1965	The Global Challenge of Malaria: Past Lessons and Future Prospects	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
879	Webb, James L. A., Jr.	2011	The first large-scale use of synthetic insecticide for malaria control in tropical Africa: lessons from Liberia, 1945-1962	Journal of the History of Medicine and Allied Sciences	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
880	Wen, Shawn; Harvard, Kelly E.; Gueye, Cara Smith; Canavati, Sara E.; Chancellor, Arna; Ahmed, Be-Nazir; Leaburi, John; Lek, Dysoley; Namgay, Rinzin; Surya, Asik; Thakur, Garib D.; Whittaker, Maxine Anne; Gosling, Roly D.	2016	Targeting populations at higher risk for malaria: a survey of national malaria elimination programmes in the Asia Pacific	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
881	West	2014	Indoor residual spraying in combination with insecticide-treated nets compared to insecticide-treated nets alone for protection against malaria: a cluster	PLoS Medicine	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

			randomised trial in Tanzania		
88 2	West, P. A.; Protopopoff, N.; Rowland, M.; Cumming, E.; Rand, A.; Drakeley, C.; Wright, A.; Kivaju, Z.; Kirby, M. J.; Mosha, F. W.; Kisinza, W.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2013	Malaria Risk Factors in North West Tanzania: The Effect of Spraying, Nets and Wealth	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
88 3	West, P. A.; Protopopoff, N.; Rowland, M.; Wright, A.; Kivaju, Z.; Kirby, M.; Mosha, F. W.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2012	Comparison of long-lasting insecticidal nets versus long-lasting insecticidal nets in combination with indoor residual house spraying for malaria vector control: results of a cluster randomized trial	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
88 4	West, P. A.; Protopopoff, N.; Wright, A.; Kivaju, Z.; Tigererwa, R.; Mosha, F. W.; Kisinza, W.; Rowland, M.; Kleinschmidt, I.	2015	Enhanced protection against malaria by indoor residual spraying in addition to insecticide treated nets: is it dependent on transmission intensity or net usage?	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
88 5	West, Philippa A.; Protopopoff, Natacha; Wright, Alexandra; Kivaju, Zuhura; Tigererwa, Robinson; Mosha, Franklin W.; Kisinza, William; Rowland, Mark; Kleinschmidt, Immo	2014	Indoor residual spraying in combination with insecticide-treated nets compared to insecticide-treated nets alone for protection against malaria: a cluster randomised trial in Tanzania	PLoS Medicine	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
88 6	White, M. T.; Conteh, L.; Cibulskis, R.; Ghani, A. C.	2011	Costs and cost-effectiveness of malaria control interventions - A systematic review	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
88 7	Whitworth, Kristina W.; Bornman, Riana M. S.; Archer, Janet I.; Kudumu, Mwenda O.; Travlos, Gregory S.; Wilson, Ralph E.;	2014	Predictors of Plasma DDT and DDE Concentrations among Women Exposed to Indoor Residual Spraying for Malaria Control in the South	Environmental Health Perspectives	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data

	Longnecker, Matthew P.		African Study of Women and Babies (SOWB)		
888	Willis, D. W.	2017	Urban planning to prevent mosquito-borne diseases in the Caribbean	Climate Change Management	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
889	Winskill, P.; Walker, P.; Patouillard, E.; Cibulskis, R.; Ghani, A.	2018	Prioritizing the scale up of interventions for malaria control and elimination	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
890	Winskill, Peter; Slater, Hannah C.; Griffin, Jamie T.; Ghani, Azra C.; Walker, Patrick G. T.	2017	The US President's Malaria Initiative, Plasmodium falciparum transmission and mortality: A modelling study	PLoS Medicine	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
891	Winskill, Peter; Walker, Patrick Gt; Griffin, Jamie T.; Ghani, Azra C.	2017	Modelling the cost-effectiveness of introducing the RTS,S malaria vaccine relative to scaling up other malaria interventions in sub-Saharan Africa	BMJ global health	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
892	Witbooi, P.; Abiodun, G.; Nsuami, M.	2021	A model of malaria population dynamics with migrants	Mathematical Biosciences and Engineering	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
893	Worrall, E.; Connor, S. J.; Thomson, M. C.	2007	A model to simulate the impact of timing, coverage and transmission intensity on the effectiveness of indoor residual spraying (IRS) for malaria control	Tropical Medicine and International Health	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
894	Worrall, Eve; Connor, Stephen J; Thomson, Madeleine C	2008	Improving the cost-effectiveness of IRS with climate informed health surveillance systems	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
895	Wylie, B.; Singh, M. P.; Yeboah-Antwi, K.; Singh, N.; Hamer, D. H.	2015	Reproductive history among women exposed to insecticides through malaria control programs in central east India	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

89 6	Yewhalaw, D.; Kassahun, W.; Woldemichael, K.; Tushune, K.; Sudaker, M.; Kaba, D.; Duchateau, L.; Van Bortel, W.; Speybroeck, N.	2010	The influence of the Gilgel-Gibe hydroelectric dam in Ethiopia on caregivers' knowledge, perceptions and health- seeking behaviour towards childhood malaria	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
89 7	Yibeltal, T.; Abitew, D. B.; Melese, A. B.; Mulu, Y.	2020	Determinants of HIV- malaria co-infection among people living with HIV on anti-retroviral therapy in Northeast Ethiopia: unmatched case control study	Tropical Medicine and Health	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
89 8	Yimer, F.; Animut, A.; Erko, B.; Mamo, H.	2015	Past five-year trend, current prevalence and household knowledge, attitude and practice of malaria in Abeshge, south-central Ethiopia	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - no control data
89 9	Yukich, Joshua O.; Lengeler, Christian; Tediosi, Fabrizio; Brown, Nick; Mulligan, Jo-Ann; Chavasse, Des; Stevens, Warren; Justino, John; Conteh, Lesong; Maharaj, Rajendra; Erskine, Marcy; Mueller, Dirk H.; Wiseman, Virginia; Ghebremeskel, Tewolde; Zerom, Mehari; Goodman, Catherine; McGuire, David; Urrutia, Juan Manuel; Sakho, Fana; Hanson, Kara; Sharp, Brian	2008	Costs and consequences of large-scale vector control for malaria	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
90 0	Yukich, Joshua; Tediosi, Fabrizio; Lengeler, Christian	2007	Operations, costs and cost-effectiveness of five insecticide-treated net programs (Eritrea, Malawi, Tanzania, Togo, Senegal) and two indoor residual spraying programs (Kwa-Zulu- Natal, Mozambique)	USAID report	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

90 1	Zacarias, O. P.; Bostrom, H.	2013	Comparing support vector regression and random forests for predicting malaria incidence in Mozambique	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
90 2	Zgambo, M.; Mbakaya, B. C.; Kalembo, F. W.	2017	Prevalence and factors associated with malaria parasitaemia in children under the age of five years in Malawi: A comparison study of the 2012 and 2014 Malaria Indicator Surveys (MISs)	PloS one	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
90 3	Zhao, Y.; Zeng, J.; Liu, Q.; He, Y.; Zhang, J.; Yang, Z.; Fan, Q.; Wang, Q.; Cui, L.; Cao, Y.	2018	Risk factors for asymptomatic malaria infections from seasonal cross-sectional surveys along the China-Myanmar border	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
90 4	Zhou, G.	2019	Drop-the-loser adaptive interventions: an innovative design for finding the optimal integrated malaria vector control strategies	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
90 5	Zhou, G.; Githeko, A. K.; Minakawa, N.; Yan, G.	2010	Community-wide benefits of targeted indoor residual spray for malaria control in the Western Kenya Highland	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
90 6	Zhou, Guofa; Afrane, Yaw A.; Dixit, Amruta; Atieli, Harrysone E.; Lee, Ming-Chieh; Wanjala, Christine L.; Beilhe, Leila B.; Githeko, Andrew K.; Yan, Guiyun	2013	Modest additive effects of integrated vector control measures on malaria prevalence and transmission in western Kenya	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
90 7	Zhou, Guofa; Afrane, Yaw A.; Dixit, Amruta; Atieli, Harrysone E.; Lee, Ming-Chieh; Wanjala, Christine L.; Beilhe, Leila B.; Githeko, Andrew K.; Yan, Guiyun	2013	Modest additive effects of integrated vector control measures on malaria prevalence and transmission in western Kenya	Malaria journal	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
90 8	Zhou, Guofa; Lee, Ming-chieh; Atieli, Harrysone E.; Githure, John I.; Githeko, Andrew K.;	2020	Adaptive interventions for optimizing malaria control: an implementation study protocol for a block-	Trials	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

	Kazura, James W.; Yan, Guiyun		cluster randomized, sequential multiple assignment trial		
90 9	Zhou, Guofa; Lee, Ming-Chieh; Wang, Xiaoming; Zhong, Daibin; Hemming- Schroeder, Elizabeth; Yan, Guiyun	2021	An Adaptive Intervention Trial Design for Finding the Optimal Integrated Strategies for Malaria Control and Elimination in Africa: A Model Simulation Study	The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
91 0	Zhou, Shui-Sen; Zhang, Shao-Sen; Zhang, Li; Rietveld, Aafje E. C.; Ramsay, Andrew R.; Zachariah, Rony; Bissell, Karen; Van den Bergh, Rafael; Xia, Zhi-Gui; Zhou, Xiao-Nong; Cibulskis, Richard E.	2015	China's 1-3-7 surveillance and response strategy for malaria elimination: Is case reporting, investigation and foci response happening according to plan?	Infectious diseases of poverty	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
91 1	Zingoni, Z. M.; Mudare, N.; Makuwaza, A.; Munyati, S.; Gwanzura, L.; Mutambu, S. L.; Mason, P.; Kobayashi, T.; Moss, W.; Mharakurwa, S. I.	2017	Return of chloroquine sensitive plasmodium falciparum malaria of mutasa district, zimbabwe	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
91 2	Zinszer, K.; Charland, K.; Vahay, S.; Jahagirdar, D.; Rek, J.; Arinaitwe, E.; Kanya, M.; Rodriguez- Barraquer, I.; Greenhouse, B.; Dorsey, G.	2019	The impact of multiple rounds of indoor residual spraying on malaria incidence and haemoglobin levels in children from a high transmission setting	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
91 3	Zinszer, K.; Charland, K.; Vahey, S.; Jahagirdar, D.; Rek, J. C.; Arinaitwe, E.; Nankabirwa, J.; Morrison, K.; Sadoine, M. L.; Tutt- GuÃ©rette, M. A.; Staedke, S. G.; Kanya, M. R.; Greenhouse, B.;	2019	The Impact of Multiple Rounds of Indoor Residual Spraying on Malaria Incidence and Hemoglobin Levels in a High-Transmission Setting	Journal of Nutrition	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

	Rodriguez-Barraquer, I.; Dorsey, G.				
91 4	Zinszer, K.; Jahagirdar, D.; Rek, J.; Arinaitwe, E.; Nankabirwa, J.; Kamya, M.; Rodriguez-Barraquer, I.; Greenhouse, B.; Dorsey, G.	2018	The impact of multiple rounds of indoor residual spraying on malaria incidence and hemoglobin levels in a high transmission setting	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
91 5	Zinszer, K.; Morrison, K.; Rek, J.; Arinaitwe, E.; Nankabirwa, J.; Kamya, M. R.; Dorsey, G.	2017	Increasing the time between incident malaria episodes in Ugandan children: Repeated application of IRS	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
91 6	Zinszer, Kate; Charland, Katia; Vahey, Sarah; Jahagirdar, Deepa; Rek, John C.; Arinaitwe, Emmanuel; Nankabirwa, Joaniter; Morrison, Kathryn; Sadoine, Margaux L.; Tutt-Guette, Marc-Antoine; Staedke, Sarah G.; Kamya, Moses R.; Greenhouse, Bryan; Rodriguez-Barraquer, Isabel; Dorsey, Grant	2020	The Impact of Multiple Rounds of Indoor Residual Spraying on Malaria Incidence and Hemoglobin Levels in a High-Transmission Setting	Journal of Infectious Diseases	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
91 7	Zogo, B.; Tchiekoi, B. N.; Soma, D. D.; Som, A.; Ahoua Alou, L. P.; Koffi, A. A.; Fournet, F.; Dahounto, A.; Coulibaly, B.; Dabir, R. K.; Baba-Moussa, L.; Moiroux, N.; Pennetier, C.	2019	Effectiveness of complementary strategies on malaria burden and transmission: A four-armed randomized controlled trial in Korhogo area, Northern Cte D'ivoire	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
91 8	Zogo, B.; Tchiekoi, B. N.; Soma, D. D.; Some, A.; Ahoua Alou, L. P.; Koffi, A. A.; Fournet, F.; Dahounto, A.	2019	Effectiveness of complementary strategies on malaria burden and transmission: a four-armed randomized controlled trial in	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: duplicate

	Coulibaly, B.; Dabire, R. K.; et al.,		Korhogo area, Northern CÃfÃ'te D'ivoire		
919	Zulliger, R.; Alonso, S.; Chaccour, C.; Candrinho, B.; Wagman, J.; Saifodine, A.; Robertson, M.; Saute, F.	2019	Cost and cost-effectiveness of combining long-lasting insecticidal nets (LLIN) with thirdgeneration indoor residual spraying (IRS) in a hightransmission area of Mozambique	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
920	Author details not provided	Year not provided	Cost-effectiveness evaluation of vector control strategies in Mozambique (COST)	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: duplicate
921	Author details not provided	Year not provided	DHS Website Seaching - Record #11	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: No prevalence data
922	Author details not provided	2021	Insecticide resistance status of malaria vectors Anopheles gambiae (s.l.) of southwest Burkina Faso and residual efficacy of indoor residual spraying with microencapsulated pirimiphos-methyl insecticide	Parasites & vectors	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - entomological data only
923	Author details not provided	2018	Cost-effectiveness of a combined intervention of long lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying compared with each intervention alone for malaria prevention in ethiopia	Cost effectiveness and resource allocation	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
924	Author details not provided	2019	Integrating case detection of visceral leishmaniasis and other febrile illness with vector control in the post-elimination phase in Nepal	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
925	Author details not provided	2017	New mode of action chemistry for indoor residual spraying	International Pest Control	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

926	Author details not provided	1995	Vector control for malaria and other mosquito-borne diseases. Report of a WHO study group	World Health Organization technical report series	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
927	Author details not provided	Year not provided	DHS Website Seaching - Record #1	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
928	Author details not provided	Year not provided	DHS Website Seaching - Record #10	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
929	Author details not provided	Year not provided	DHS Website Seaching - Record #12	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
930	Author details not provided	Year not provided	DHS Website Seaching - Record #13	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
931	Author details not provided	Year not provided	DHS Website Seaching - Record #14	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
932	Author details not provided	Year not provided	DHS Website Seaching - Record #15	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
933	Author details not provided	Year not provided	DHS Website Seaching - Record #16	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
934	Author details not provided	Year not provided	DHS Website Seaching - Record #17	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
935	Author details not provided	Year not provided	DHS Website Seaching - Record #18	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
936	Author details not provided	Year not provided	DHS Website Seaching - Record #19	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
937	Author details not provided	Year not provided	DHS Website Seaching - Record #2	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
938	Author details not provided	Year not	DHS Website Seaching - Record #20	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other

		provi ded			
93 9	Author details not provided	Year not provi ded	DHS Website Seaching - Record #21	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
94 0	Author details not provided	Year not provi ded	DHS Website Seaching - Record #22	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
94 1	Author details not provided	Year not provi ded	DHS Website Seaching - Record #23	Journal not provided	Exclusion reason: wrong study design - other
94 2	Author details not provided	2018	Results from a comparison-control trial examining different targeting strategies for Irs Zambia 2017	American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other
94 3	Abong'o B, Gimnig JE, Torr SJ, Longman B, Omoke D, Muchoki M, Ter Kuile F, Ochomo E, Munga S, Samuels AM, Njagi K, Maas J, Perry RT, Fornadel C, Donnelly MJ, Oxborough RM.	2020	Impact of indoor residual spraying with pirimiphos-methyl (Actellic 300CS) on entomological indicators of transmission and malaria case burden in Migori County, western Kenya.	Scientific reports	Exclusion reason: Wrong study design - other

Supplementary item 6 – Characteristics of included studies

Charlwood et al.

Study: Charlwood JD, Qassim M, Elnsur EI, Donnelly M, Petrarca V, Billingsley PF, Pinto J, Smith T. The impact of indoor residual spraying with malathion on malaria in refugee camps in eastern Sudan. <i>Acta Trop.</i> 2001 Sep 1;80(1):1-8. doi: 10.1016/s0001-706x(01)00152-8. PMID: 11495638.	
DESIGN	
Lead Author	J.D. Charlwood.
Publication year	2001.
Trial name	Not reported.
Other reports of this study (i.e., author, year, title, doi)	Not reported.
Time period study was conducted	Sprayed mid-September. Mariological data was only considered from October-December 1997.
Design	Randomised controlled trial.
Eligibility criteria of participants	The two largest camps, with populations over 20 000 were excluded from the experiment.
Recruitment methods and rate	Not reported.
Unit of allocation	Refugee camps in Eastern Sudan.
Number of units	14 refugee camps were included in the overall study. Intervention arm (n=9). Control arm (n=5).
Method of Randomization/ matching or other	Not reported. “These were treated as single units from the parasitological point of view and were randomly allocated to intervention (spraying all buildings with malathion) or control (unsprayed) groups”.
Number of clusters per arm	Intervention arm n = 9. Control arm n =5.
Adjustment for clustering	Analysis was adjusted for village and month effects.
Cluster details (including buffer sizes between clusters, other indication of dilution effects)	The camps were classified by the Commissioner’s Office for Refugees, (COR), as being riverine—having permanent flowing water within 7 km of the camp; irrigation built close to large irrigation projects; or inland where the water supply was much more limited. Thus, they varied according to their proximity to dry season water suitable for anopheline breeding.
Total trial participants per group/arm (including number of exclusions and reasons)	Intervention arm n = 23452. Control arm n = 25263.
Outcomes assessed	Incidence rate of malaria (all ages and under 5). Deaths (all-cause) (all ages and under 5).
SETTING	
Country	Eastern Sudan.
Site/s (town/settlements/region)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refugee camps of Eastern Sudan. • The area contains a number of large towns, notably Gedaref, population densities are generally very low. There are 23 refugee camps, or groups of camps, situated in the area. • The two largest camps, with populations over 20 000 were excluded from the experiment. Of the remainder most are isolated, but some consist of pairs or groups of three camps, which utilise the same

	<p>clinics. These were treated as single units from the parasitological point of view and were randomly allocated to intervention (spraying all buildings with malathion) or control (unsprayed) groups.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The camps were classified by the Commissioner’s Office for Refugees, (COR), as being riverine—having permanent flowing water within 7 km of the camp; irrigation built close to large irrigation projects; or inland where the water supply was much more limited.
Peak transmission season	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria incidence is highly seasonal and accompanies the single rainy season, which generally occurs in September and lasts for 4 or 5 weeks. • The annual rainfall of close to 500 mm is concentrated in August and September. This results in epidemics of malaria in the latter part of the year. • Much of the annual rainfall fell during the course of the experiment.
Baseline malaria endemicity/ level of transmission	Sporozoite rates were low and prevalence rates of 1.0% from 800 school-aged children were similar to those obtained by Babiker et al. (1997) from a Sudanese village in the same area. Despite the use of residual insecticides, annual epidemics of malaria have occurred in the camps for the last 12 years.
Study site (e.g., rural/ urban/ peri-urban/ level of urbanicity)	Rural (assumed).
Vector species and vector profile details (i.e., behaviours, resistance profile/ susceptibility tests, parity, sporozoite rates and all other reported information)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mosquitoes were sexed, identified to species or species complex. All 22 of the specimens identified cytologically and all 120 identified by PCR were <i>A. arabiensis</i>. • This was the most common mosquito in all collections. One specimen from Wad Helewa had the rare inversion ‘2Rs’ identified from the Kasim el Girba area 20 years previously.
Malaria species	<i>P. falciparum</i> and <i>P. vivax</i> .
PARTICIPANTS (those who received the intervention and on whom impact was measured)	
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants who received the intervention	25263 refugees were in the control camps and 23452 participants were in the intervention camps. No other demographic information.
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants on whom the impact was measured.	The outcome was measured on all suspected malaria patients attending the clinics had blood slides taken. No demographic information reported.
Frequency of travel in the last month	Not reported.
INTERVENTION (Repeat if multiple arms)	
Insecticide brand, type, formulation (including active ingredient), dose, duration (this includes timing and frequency of application)	Malathion wettable power.
Insecticide application method(s) and strategy (e.g., spray, paint, treated materials, wallpaper)	Applied at 2g/m ² over a 5-day period in the second week of September. Applied to the interior walls of all turkels in the intervention camps.
Personnel applying the intervention	Not reported.
Target area (inside/outside)	Interior walls.

How the coverage of the intervention was measured	Not reported.
Coverage of household (full, selective/partial)	Not reported.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	Not reported.
Length of intervention, including number of rounds of spraying/application per year/season	Spraying occurred once, over a 5-day period of September 1997.
Type of dwelling (e.g., fixed or temporary) and construction material of surfaces insecticides applied to (e.g., cement, brick or mud walls, canvas etc)	Turkel (Mud, wattle thatch).
Time to start intervention after index case	Not reported.
Human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, re-plastering of houses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On rainless nights people in this part of the world tend to sleep outside. • In some areas the vector, <i>Anopheles arabiensis</i> Paton, is considered to be largely exophilic and zoophagic. Thus, it is possible that malaria could be exclusively transmitted outside by an outdoor resting mosquito. • This could make control by indoor residual spraying ineffective. In Kenya, however, 37% of indoor resting <i>A. arabiensis</i> had fed outside before entering houses.
COMPARISON	
Details of Comparison	No IRS (Refugee camps that went unsprayed).
How the coverage of the comparison was measured	Not reported.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction for the comparison	Not reported. Number of huts sprayed in each unit were given however, no total to determine percent.
Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period and other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From 1975 to 1980 malathion wettable powder applied at 2 g/m² to the interior walls of the turkels was used to control malaria in the area. • However, nascent resistance resulted in a change to fenitrothion (Hemingway, 1983). • Spraying was resumed in the camps in 1986. This is coupled with treatment of malaria cases by a variety of drugs. In 1996 due to importation difficulties, sufficient insecticide was only available to spray approximately half the camps. • An experiment was conducted in 1997 to determine the effect of malathion.
OUTCOME 1	
Name	Incidence rate of malaria (all ages and under 5).
Definition/ assessment metric	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passive case detection - all suspected malaria patients attending the clinics had blood slides taken. • Finger-prick blood from the first 20 patients attending clinics at each camp after the start of the experiment was stored on filter paper.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A sample of these filter papers were tested for parasites by nested-PCR amplification of the small subunit ribosomal RNA genes.
Events	In the months October–December there were 6517 cases of malaria, 1873 in the under 5 year olds in the control camps and 7842 cases, 1761 in the under 5 year olds, from the intervention camps.
Total (or unit time)	Not reported.
Time of outcome assessment	One time point offered: one to three months post IRS.
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	For being in the intervention camp compared to the control camp <u>All ages</u> IRR = 1.1 (0.8 – 1.14) <u>Under-5</u> IRR = 0.9 (0.7-1.2)
Effect type	IRR.
OUTCOME 2	
Name	Deaths (all-cause) (all ages and under 5).
Definition/ assessment metric	Not reported.
Events	In the period up to September there were 35 child deaths in the camps assigned to be sprayed, and 41 in the control camps. There were no deaths during October–December among children in the sprayed camps, compared with six deaths in control camps.
Total (or unit time)	Not reported.
Time of outcome assessment	Between the period of October to December 1997
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	For being in the intervention camp compared to the control camp. <u>All ages</u> IRR = 0.4 (0.2 – 1.2) <u>Under-5</u> IRR = 0.0 Confidence intervals cannot be estimated because there were no reported deaths among under-5s in the treated camps after the treatment was introduced.
Effect type	IRR.
COSTS	
Event/raw costs	Not reported.
Results	Not reported.
Time of cost assessment	Not reported.
Resources needed/ used	Not reported.
ADDITIONAL DATA	
Unintended benefits	Not reported.
Harms	Not reported.
Other contextual information present/measured/reported) (feasibility, acceptability, preferences/values, impact on equity)	Not reported.
Entomological outcomes measured (list)	Human Blood Index. Sporozoite Rates.
Other	Not reported.
Source of funding	Not reported.

Possible conflicts of interest	We would like to thank UNHCR Geneva and Sudan and the Commissioner's Office for Refugees (COR) for their support for this work.
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Curtis et al.

Study: Curtis CF, Maxwell CA, Finch RJ, Njunwa KJ. A comparison of use of a pyrethroid either for house spraying or for bednet treatment against malaria vectors. Trop Med Int Health. 1998 Aug;3(8):619-31.	
DESIGN	
Lead Author	C. F. Curtis.
Publication year	1998.
Trial name	Pangani Falls Redevelopment Project.
Other reports of this study (i.e., author, year, title, doi)	Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene Meeting at Manson House, London, 21 January 1999: Malaria control: bednets or spraying? Background and trial in Tanzania.
Time period study was conducted	1995 – 1997. The interventions were introduced in 6 of the villages in December 1995 but, owing to logistical problems, spraying and provision of nets was delayed in two until February 1996. Until these villages had been treated, data from them were excluded from the post-intervention data presented.
Design	Cluster randomised controlled trial.
Eligibility criteria of participants	Not reported.
Recruitment methods and rate	The villages have been the site of primary health care activity instigated by the Pangani Falls Redevelopment Project. The village populations were censused and found to range between 971 and 2445, with an average of 17.9% aged less than 6 years. Agreement to the trial was given after consultations with village authorities and mass meetings in each of the 12 villages. The inhabitants of those villages which did not receive nets during the trial were told that they would receive them at the end of it.
Unit of allocation	Villages that were randomised to clusters. The clusters received the intervention.
Number of units	4 villages per intervention. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $n = 4$ villages to receive nets. • $n = 4$ villages to receive IRS. $n = 4$ villages to remain untreated.
Method of Randomization/ matching or other	Consideration was given to stratification of the villages prior to their assignment to nets, spraying or controls. However, no significant differences were found between villages in the baseline data on vector populations and malaria incidence, so it was decided to randomly assign two villages from Muheza and two from Hale to each of the treatments, leaving two villages in each area as controls (i.e. a total of 4:4:4, control:netted:sprayed villages).
Number of clusters per arm	4 villages per cluster.
Adjustment for clustering	Not reported.
Cluster details (including buffer sizes between clusters, other indication of dilution effects)	Not reported.

Total trial participants per group/arm (including number of exclusions and reasons)	Not reported. However, the village populations were censused and found to range between 971 and 2445, with an average of 17.9% aged less than 6 years.
Outcomes assessed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria incidence, children under 6, cross-sectional survey. • Malaria incidence, children under 6, passive case detection. • Malaria incidence, children older than 6, passive case detection. • Anaemia incidence, children under 6, cross-sectional survey.
SETTING	
Country	Tanzania.
Site/s (town/settlements/region)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The trial was carried out in 12 villages, six of which were near Muheza, Tanga Region, on the road to Pangani. • The other six trial villages were 30 km further inland near Hale
Peak transmission season	The main rainy season is from April to June. Populations of <i>An. gambiae s.l.</i> and malaria cases peak at this time.
Baseline malaria endemicity/ level of transmission	The study area is “intensely malarious”.
Study site (e.g., rural/ urban/ peri-urban/ level of urbanicity)	Not reported. Assumed to be rural.
Vector species and vector profile details (i.e., behaviours, resistance profile/ susceptibility tests, parity, sporozoite rates and all other reported information)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The main vectors identified were <i>An. gambiae s.s.</i> and <i>An. Funestus</i> however <i>An. Arabiensis</i> was also present in the six villages in the drier region near Hale. • Major seasonal fluctuations in the populations of <i>An. gambiae s.l.</i> and <i>An. funestus</i> with similar catches in the pre-intervention year in the villages later assigned to control and the interventions (except for a remarkably high catch of <i>An. funestus</i> in the first quarter in one of the groups of villages). • From samples in the months of January and May in the Hale villages about 5% of the <i>An. gambiae</i> complex were identified by PCR as <i>An. arabiensis</i>, the remainder being <i>An. gambiae s.s.</i> • After both interventions there were marked reductions in the vector populations. Analysis of variance of the light trap catches (transformed to log x 1 1) was carried out treating the data from individual villages as replications.
Malaria species	<i>P. falciparum</i> for entomology outcomes (only states malaria for incidence).
PARTICIPANTS (those who received the intervention and on whom impact was measured)	
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants who received the intervention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The authors report that baseline data were collected during 1995. • However, they do not provide this baseline data in their paper. • They do state that the balance of baseline characteristics was sufficient to suggest no concerns with the randomisation procedure. • All individuals in the village received the intervention as prescribed if they were consenting.
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants on whom the impact was measured.	Not reported. Just that cross-sectional surveys were conducted on children between their first and sixth birthdays. Numbers reported below.
Frequency of travel in the last month	Any children who were reported to have stayed away from home or who missed their blood check for more than one week were dropped from the cohort as they may have acquired malaria under different conditions from those in their homes.
INTERVENTION (Repeat if multiple arms)	

Insecticide brand, type, formulation (including active ingredient), dose, duration (this includes timing and frequency of application)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microencapsulated lambdacyhalothrin (10% Icon CS). • The target dose was 30mg a.i./m². • Diluted 50ml of concentrate in 8 litres. • Villages were sprayed in January/February 1996 and re-sprayed in July-August of that year. • It was found that on average spraying 15 houses consumed 1 litre of concentrate. The mean interior wall and roof area per house was found to be 232 m² which implies that the actual dose applied was about 31 mg a.i./m² (The target was 30mg a.i./m²).
Insecticide application method(s) and strategy (e.g., spray, paint, treated materials, wallpaper)	Interior wall and ceiling.
Personnel applying the intervention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spraying was carried out by teams of 10 residents from each of the four villages designated for spraying, equipped with Hudson Xpert sprayers. • The teams had been given two days training and worked in pairs under a supervisor.
Target area (inside/outside)	Indoors.
How the coverage of the intervention was measured	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spraying with microencapsulated lambdacyhalothrin (10% Icon CS) was carried out by teams of 10 residents from each of the four villages designated for spraying, equipped with Hudson Xpert sprayers. • The teams had been given two days training and worked in pairs under a supervisor from our research team. The target dose was 30mg a.i./m². • This was approached by diluting 50ml of the concentrate in a full pump charge of 8l. It was found that on average spraying 15houses consumed 1 litre of concentrate. • The mean interior wall and roof area per house was found to be 232m²whichimplies that the actual dose applied was about 31mg a.i./m² (i.e. very close to the target). • Re-spraying of the four villages was carried out in July–August 1996, i.e. 7–8months after the initial spray
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	Not reported.
Coverage of household (full, selective/partial)	Full.
Length of intervention, including number of rounds of spraying/application per year/season	2 spray rounds over a calendar year. The interventions were introduced in 6 of the villages in December 1995 but, owing to logistical problems, spraying and provision of nets was delayed in two until February 1996. Until these villages had been treated, data from them were excluded from the post-intervention data presented.
Type of dwelling (e.g., fixed or temporary) and construction material of surfaces insecticides applied to (e.g., cement, brick or mud walls, canvas etc)	Mud walls and palm thatched hut used for entomological bioassays.
Time to start intervention after index case	Not reported

Human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, re-plastering of houses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People were asked not to wash their provided nets. This would be done by the research team and re-treated where necessary. • A questionnaire, supported by checking marks made with washable ink, indicated that 70% of people had chosen not to wash their nets until requested to do so just before retreatment was scheduled. 																																
COMPARISON																																	
Details of Comparison	No IRS.																																
How the coverage of the comparison was measured	Not reported.																																
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction for the comparison	Not reported.																																
Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period and other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)	Not reported.																																
OUTCOME 1																																	
Name	Malaria incidence, children under 6, cross-sectional survey.																																
Definition/ assessment metric	<p>Cross-sectional surveys were carried out monthly from the latter part of 1995 until the end of 1996 in each village on samples of children between their first and sixth birthdays. A sample of 50 such children was randomly selected by computer from the census list for each village, after excluding children who had been so selected in the previous month.</p> <p>Blood slide was used to detect <i>P falciparum</i> if found with parasitaemia greater than 4000/ml Malaria was confirmed.</p>																																
Events	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Quarter/Year</th> <th>Group</th> <th><i>n</i></th> <th>Malaria parasites >4000/ul (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="2">1st q.'96</td> <td>C</td> <td>259</td> <td>27.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>S</td> <td>164</td> <td>25.6</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="2">2nd q.'96</td> <td>C</td> <td>339</td> <td>28.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>S</td> <td>291</td> <td>25.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="2">3rd q.'96</td> <td>C</td> <td>300</td> <td>30.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>S</td> <td>282</td> <td>20.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="2">4th q.'96</td> <td>C</td> <td>240</td> <td>26.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>S</td> <td>212</td> <td>19.3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Quarter/Year	Group	<i>n</i>	Malaria parasites >4000/ul (%)	1st q.'96	C	259	27.0	S	164	25.6	2nd q.'96	C	339	28.3	S	291	25.8	3rd q.'96	C	300	30.3	S	282	20.9	4th q.'96	C	240	26.3	S	212	19.3
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Time of outcome assessment	<u>Children under 6 years</u> Time point 1: Q1 1996 Time point 2: Q2 1996 Time point 3: Q3 1996 Time point 4: Q4 1996																																
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary)	Comparing the controls with the two interventions within each quarter of the year, the netted villages did not differ significantly (x2 or t-tests)																																

outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	from the controls for any of the measures of parasitaemia in the preintervention period but, by the 3rd and 4th quarters of 1996, they were highly significantly less than controls in percentage with more than 4000 parasites/ml and in geometric mean parasite density. For the sprayed villages the evidence for this improvement was less convincing since they differed significantly from controls for these two parameters in the pre-intervention period.																															
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Total (or unit time)	See above.																															
Time of outcome assessment	<u>Children under 6 years passive case detection</u> Time point 1: Q3 & Q4 1995 Time point 2: Q1 & Q2 1996 Time point 3: Q3 & Q4 1996																															
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	In almost no cases did the passive surveillance give significant evidence for reductions in malaria or associated fever because of either intervention against the vectors. It is not clear why this was so but it is a warning not to expect to see dramatic effects on malaria morbidity as recorded by village health workers when vector control measures are introduced into holoendemic areas.																															
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OUTCOME 3																																
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	3rd & 4th '96	C	504	35.2	5.1	1.0
		S	457	34.1	6.3	2.2
Total (or unit time)	See above.					
Time of outcome assessment	<u>Children over 6 years – passive surveillance</u> Time point 1: Q1 and Q2 1996 Time point 2: Q3 and Q4 1996					
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	In almost no cases did the passive surveillance give significant evidence for reductions in malaria or associated fever because of either intervention against the vectors. It is not clear why this was so but it is a warning not to expect to see dramatic effects on malaria morbidity as recorded by village health workers when vector control measures are introduced into holoendemic areas.					
Effect type	OR.					
OUTCOME 4						
Name	Anaemia incidence, children under 6, cross-sectional survey.					
Definition/ assessment metric	Cross-sectional surveys were carried out monthly from the latter part of 1995 until the end of 1996 in each village on samples of children between their first and sixth birthdays. A sample of 50 such children was randomly selected by computer from the census list for each village, after excluding children who had been so selected in the previous month. Blood slide was used to detect anaemia. Haemoglobin concentration of < 8g/dl was anaemic.					
Events	<u>Quarter/Year</u>	<u>Group</u>	<u>n</u>	<u>% with Hb <8g/dl</u>		
	1st q.'96	C	259	23.6		
		S	164	15.2		
	2nd q.'96	C	313	12.4		
		S	258	09.7		
	3rd q.'96	C	297	21.0		
		S	282	10.6		
	4th q.'96	C	240	17.5		
		S	212	07.5		
	2nd q.'97	C	268	24.1		
Total (or unit time)	As above.					
Time of outcome assessment	<u>Anaemia</u> Time point 1: Q1 1996 Time point 2: Q2 1996 Time point 3: Q3 1996 Time point 4: Q4 1996					
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	The villages assigned for spraying showed no significant difference (by t or x2 test) from control levels of haemoglobin or percentage with anaemia (which is defined as haemoglobin, 8 g /dl, col.6) in the pre-intervention period, but these differences had become highly significant by the last two quarters of 1996. The netted villages also					

	showed highly significantly greater mean haemoglobin concentrations and lower prevalence of anaemia than the controls in the last two quarters of 1996.
Effect type	OR (but will need to impute data using percentages provided).
COSTS	
Event/raw costs	TREATMENT (\$USD)
	1/yr 2/yr
	<u>Treated nets</u>
Annual replacement cost of nets (700 nets @ \$4 each with life of 4 years)	0700 0700
Cost of insecticide (2.33 l at \$120*/litre: 50 ml of 10% Icon CS treat 15 nets)	0280 0560
Labour cost (6 person days for treatment and house checking @ \$4/person day)	0024 0048
Transport of personnel	0020 0040
Total	1024 1348
	<u>House spraying</u>
Cost of insecticide for 258 houses (1 litre of 10% Icon CS treats 15 houses)	2064 4128
Labour cost (50 person days)	0200 0400
Transport of personnel:	0040 0080
<u>Total</u>	2304 4608
Results	A net treatment programme would be less costly than house spraying.
Time of cost assessment	At the end of year 1 (1995) and year 2 (1996).
Resources needed/ used	Spray equipment and personnel, nets.
ADDITIONAL DATA	
Unintended benefits	Not reported.
Harms	Despite wearing goggles and face masks, the spray teams suffered from paraesthesia in their facial skin and, for the second round of spraying, visors were provided.
Other contextual information present/measured/reported) (feasibility, acceptability, preferences/values, impact on equity)	Questionnaires administered to householders indicated general satisfaction with both methods of vector control and, unlike in countries with long histories of house spraying, there was no problem of refusals of access for spraying. Towards the end of the trial there were repeated demands from the inhabitants of the sprayed villages (as well as the control villages) for the promised nets to be delivered on time. This was the clearest indication of how welcome a gift of nets is in this area of Tanzania. Though house spraying was assented to there was no similar demand for its continuation.

Entomological outcomes measured (list)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total no. anophelines collected through indoor window exit trap. • Knockdown of mosquitos. Mortality at 24h.
Other	Not reported.
Source of funding	Financial support was provided by the British Overseas Development Administration and Medical Research Council and by the Pangani Falls Redevelopment Project.
Possible conflicts of interest	Not reported.

Loha et al.

Study: Loha, E., Deressa, W., Gari, T. <i>et al.</i> Long-lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying may not be sufficient to eliminate malaria in a low malaria incidence area: results from a cluster randomized controlled trial in Ethiopia. <i>Malar J</i> 18 , 141 (2019).	
DESIGN	
Lead Author	Eskindir Loha
Publication year	2019
Trial name	Malaria Trials project (MaTrials); protocol PACTR201411000882128
Other reports of this study (i.e., author, year, title, doi)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deressa, W., Loha, E., Balkew, M. <i>et al.</i> Combining long-lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying for malaria prevention in Ethiopia: study protocol for a cluster randomized controlled trial. <i>Trials</i> 17, 20 (2016). https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-016-1154-2 • Gari, T., Solomon, T. & Lindtjørn, B. Older children are at increased risk of <i>Plasmodium vivax</i> in south-central Ethiopia: a cohort study. <i>Malar J</i> 20, 251 (2021). https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-021-03790-3 • Solomon T, Loha E, Deressa W, Gari T, Lindtjørn B (2019) Spatiotemporal clustering of malaria in southern-central Ethiopia: A community-based cohort study. <i>PLOS ONE</i> 14(9): e0222986. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0222986 • Hailu A, Lindtjørn B, Deressa W, Gari T, Loha E, Robberstad B. Cost-effectiveness of a combined intervention of long lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying compared with each intervention alone for malaria prevention in Ethiopia. <i>Cost Eff Resour Alloc.</i> 2018 Nov 22;16:61. doi: 10.1186/s12962-018-0164-1.
Time period study was conducted	September 2014 to December 2016.
Design	2 x 2 factorial cluster randomised controlled trial.
Eligibility criteria of participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Villages located within 5 km from Lake Zeway or the Bulbula River were included in the study, as preliminary findings indicated that the incidence of malaria was highest in this part of the area. • All consenting residents of households in all clusters were recruited for the study. Residents and household heads who did not provide informed consent were excluded. • Inclusion: Villages with a relatively easy access, relatively higher malaria transmission and located within 5 km from Lake Zeway will be included in the study. • Villages with difficult access, a very low malaria transmission, and located beyond 5 km from Lake Zeway were excluded.
Recruitment methods and rate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From a total of 48 rural kebeles in the Adami Tullu district, 13 kebeles with a relatively higher malaria transmission adjacent to

	<p>Lake Zeway were included in the study following a census carried out in 24 kebeles and pilot studies in four kebeles. Villages with a relatively easy access, relatively higher malaria transmission and located within 5 km from Lake Zeway will be included in the study.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From the total list of the clusters in 13 kebeles, 207 were located within 5km of Lake Zeway, had a relatively higher malaria transmission, and were included in the sampling frame, of which 176 were randomly selected.
Unit of allocation	The village (or cluster) will be the unit of randomization, and an equal number of villages were randomized to one of the four arms: (1) LLINs + IRS, (2) LLINs alone, (3) IRS alone or (4) control (routine practice).
Number of units	44 clusters per trial arm.
Method of Randomization/ matching or other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A researcher not involved in the study randomly allocated a random number that was used as the seed for the computer-generated list of villages using SPSS software. • The randomly selected clusters were numbered and equally randomized into the four arms following a computer-generated list using SPSS software. • While the study is done in Ethiopia, randomization was done in Bergen in Norway. This was done to prevent selection bias by concealing the allocation sequence from the field researchers assigning villages to the four intervention groups until the moment of assignment. • Because of many clusters in each arm, stratification of clusters or restricted randomization was not done.
Number of clusters per arm	44 clusters per trial arm.
Adjustment for clustering	The main outcome variable will also be analysed as a binary variable and will be compared in the intervention and control clusters using multilevel mixed-effects logistic regression models, taking into account the clustering effects. To control for potential confounding factors, the clustering effect of villages, the effect of repeated measurement in the same individual and individual level covariates (such as age, gender, LLINs' use) will be taken into consideration during the analysis.
Cluster details (including buffer sizes between clusters, other indication of dilution effects)	If one or more or all of the household members had left the study area during the study period, the individuals were considered lost to follow-up.
Total trial participants per group/arm (including number of exclusions and reasons)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LLINs+IRS = 1619 households with 8216 people. • LLINs only = 1387 households with 7288 people. • IRS only = 1530 households with 7753 people. • Control = 1544 households with 8038 people. • In the study, 176 of 207 clusters living within a distance of 5 km from Lake Zeway were randomly selected. Some 6,071 households with 34548 people were included the trial.
Outcomes assessed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidence of malaria. • Incidence of anaemia.
SETTING	
Country	Ethiopia.
Site/s (town/settlements/region)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adami Tullu district in the East Shewa Zone of the Oromia Regional State in Ethiopia.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The capital of the district, Zeway (or Batu), has a latitude and longitude of 7°56'N 38°42'E with an elevation of 1640 m above sea level. 																						
Peak transmission season	The peak malaria transmission season in the study area is from September to December, following the rainy season during June to August.																						
Baseline malaria endemicity/ level of transmission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The preliminary findings indicated that the incidence of malaria was 8 cases per 10000 person-weeks. <i>P. falciparum</i> and <i>P. vivax</i> co-exist in the area in varied proportions. A longitudinal community-based study carried out in 1994 revealed a malaria prevalence of 6.8 % (66 % <i>P. falciparum</i>, 31% <i>P. vivax</i> and 3% <i>P. malariae</i>) from July to December, peaking in September at 12.6%. Community-based cross-sectional surveys conducted in October to November 2006 and April 2007 indicated an overall parasite prevalence of 4.8 %, varying between localities from 1.7 % to 10.4 %, with 88 % <i>P. vivax</i> and 12% <i>P. falciparum</i> parasite species composition. 																						
Study site (e.g., rural/ urban/ peri-urban/ level of urbanicity)	Rural.																						
Vector species and vector profile details (i.e., behaviours, resistance profile/ susceptibility tests, parity, sporozoite rates and all other reported information)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Preliminary findings using the WHO susceptibility tube tests in 2013 showed a 100% susceptibility of <i>An. Arabiensis</i> and <i>An. pharoensis</i> to propoxur. <i>Anopheles arabiensis</i> is the major malaria vector in the district and <i>An. pharoensis</i> is considered to have an auxiliary role. A study performed prior to the start of this trial demonstrated that <i>An. arabiensis</i> was susceptible to propoxur (a carbamate), but resistant to the pyrethroid insecticides. However, <i>An. pharoensis</i> was susceptible to all pyrethroids and carbamates tested. <i>An. arabiensis</i> is the major malaria vector in the district and <i>An. pharoensis</i> is considered to have an auxiliary role. An entomological study in the past showed that the former species prevailed from June to October with peak densities from July to September, while the latter species peak months were from September to November. Preliminary insecticide susceptibility tests showed that <i>An. arabiensis</i> was greatly resistant to deltamethrin (mortality 14%), alphacypermethrin (less than 1% mortality), lambdacyhalothrin (4% mortality) and permethrin (17% mortality), but susceptible to bendiocarb and propoxur (mortality 100%). <i>An. pharoensis</i> was fully susceptible to all the aforementioned insecticides with a 100% mortality (MalTrials unpublished pilot data). 																						
Malaria species	<i>P. vivax</i> and <i>P. falciparum</i>																						
PARTICIPANTS (those who received the intervention and on whom impact was measured)																							
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants who received the intervention	<table border="0"> <tr> <td style="vertical-align: top;">IRS arm:</td> <td style="vertical-align: top;">Control arm:</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Number of cluster = 44</td> <td>Number of cluster = 44</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Number of households = 1527</td> <td>Number of households = 1538</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Population = 8567</td> <td>Population = 8839</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Population per cluster = 195</td> <td>Population per cluster = 201</td> </tr> <tr> <td>- Age group (in years)</td> <td>- Age group (in years)</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>< 5 years = 1711 (19.4%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>5 - 14 years = 2758 (31.2%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>15 years and older = 4270 (49.4%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total = 8839</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>- Gender</td> </tr> </table>	IRS arm:	Control arm:	Number of cluster = 44	Number of cluster = 44	Number of households = 1527	Number of households = 1538	Population = 8567	Population = 8839	Population per cluster = 195	Population per cluster = 201	- Age group (in years)	- Age group (in years)		< 5 years = 1711 (19.4%)		5 - 14 years = 2758 (31.2%)		15 years and older = 4270 (49.4%)		Total = 8839		- Gender
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Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants on whom the impact was measured.	<p>Analysed (from flowchart).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IRS = 1520 households, 8521 individuals (excluded 7 households, N=46). • Control = 1538 households. 8839 individuals (excluded 0). 	
Frequency of travel in the last month	<p>If one or more or all of the household members had left the study area during the study period, the individuals were considered lost to follow-up.</p>	
INTERVENTION (Repeat if multiple arms)		
Insecticide brand, type, formulation (including active ingredient), dose, duration (this includes timing and frequency of application)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Propoxur (isopropoxy-phenyl methylcarbamate) is highly effective against mosquito vectors for m2 more than 3 months at a dosage of 2 g/ in the form of a water-dispersible powder (WP), and will be acquired from the state-owned Adami Tullu Pesticide Processing Share Company located in the study district. 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Propoxur 50 % WP contains 2 g of active ingredient and is packaged in 400 g sachets, and two sachets will be mixed with 8 L of water. • Preliminary findings using the WHO susceptibility tube tests in 2013 showed a 100 % susceptibility of An. Arabiensis and An. pharoensis to propoxur (MalTrials unpublished pilot data). • The average surface area measurement m²) per unit structure will be used (110 to be sprayed by a spray man per day to calculate the correct amount of insecticide required for the spraying. 8-liter Hudson X pert(HD Hudson Manufacturing Company, Chicago, IL, USA), spray canisters were used.
Insecticide application method(s) and strategy (e.g., spray, paint, treated materials, wallpaper)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indoor residual spraying with propoxur will be carried out at three times during the study period (September 2014, July 2015 and July 2016). • Spraying will be done once a year prior to the peak transmission season at the beginning, the middle and before the end of the trial, following the national spraying operation guidelines and WHO operation manual guidelines. • Indoor residual spraying with propoxur was carried out three times (September 2014, July 2015, July 2016). • Spraying was done once a year prior to the peak transmission season, following the national spraying operation guidelines. • 12 houses were sprayed by each spray operator per day using an 8-l Hudson X-pert (HD Hudson Manufacturing Co, Chicago, IL, USA). Prior to spraying, community sensitization was performed to inform residents about the safety, purpose and time of spraying. • IRS operation was performed using propoxur (isopropoxyphenyl methylcarbamate) purchased from the stateowned Adami Tullu Pesticide Processing Share Company located in the study district.
Personnel applying the intervention	A 6-day training on spraying operation will also be given for locally recruited spray men and supervisors. The spraying teams will be organized by squads of four spray personnel and a porter, and supervised by a squad leader.
Target area (inside/outside)	Indoors.
How the coverage of the intervention was measured	Not reported.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	IRS - no household had received IRS spraying the year prior to the study. Weeks 1 – 52 IRS = 97%. Weeks 53 – 104 IRS = 92%. Weeks 105 to 121 IRS = 94%.
Coverage of household (full, selective/partial)	Full.
Length of intervention, including number of rounds of spraying/application per year/season	Spraying was done once a year prior to the peak transmission season at the beginning, the middle and before the end of the trial, starting in September 2014, and repeated in August of 2015 and 2016.
Type of dwelling (e.g., fixed or temporary) and construction material of surfaces insecticides applied to (e.g., cement, brick or mud walls, canvas etc)	<u>Main roof material for IRS group</u> Thatch/leaf =4035 (47.7%) Corrugated iron = 4484 (52.3) Cement/concrete = 48 (0.6) Total = 8567

Time to start intervention after index case	Spraying began in September of 2014 and repeated in August 2015 and 2016.
Human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, re-plastering of houses)	Not reported.
COMPARISON	
Details of Comparison	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control is no IRS. • The control arm will receive the routine standard practice of malaria prevention of the Ethiopian Malaria Control Program. The control households would receive new LLINs and IRS spraying when the district health office found it appropriate, but during the study period, no communities in the <i>woreda</i> received such additional interventions. • Main roof material for no IRS group <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thatch/leaf = 3774 (42.7%) - Corrugated iron = 5055 (57.2%) - Cement/concrete = 10 (0.1%) - Total = 8839
How the coverage of the comparison was measured	Not reported.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction for the comparison	No IRS.
Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period and other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All participants received standard practice of malaria prevention of the Ethiopian Malaria Control Program (control group received only this). • In Ethiopia, LLINs and IRS are applied either simultaneously or separately depending on the local setting. • The LLIN use coverage before the intervention was 11%, and no household had received IRS spraying the year prior to the study. • With an average of 2.57 nets per household, a total of 3006 households (1,618 households in LLIN + IRS arm and 1,388 households in LLIN arm) in both arms of the trial received 7,740 LLINs (4,157 nets in LLINs + IRS and 3,583 nets in LLINs only). • Mean LLIN use during the specified period is available in tables.
OUTCOME 1	
Name	Incidence of malaria.
Definition/ assessment metric	The primary outcome measure was malaria incidence determined by the detection of <i>P. falciparum</i> or <i>P. vivax</i> by rapid diagnosis tests in patients with a fever or having a history of fever within the previous 48h.
Events	Episodes IRS = 291 Control = 293
Total (or unit time)	Person years IRS = 17153 Control = 18752
Time of outcome assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Hb concentration was measured in children 6–59 months old in the study households at three time points during the study (December 2014–2016, at end of each year’s main malaria transmission season) – (3-6 months post IRS).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weekly household visits for malaria incidence surveys from Q3 2014 to Q1 2017. Time points offered in weeks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time point 1: 1-26 weeks (up to 6 months). Time point 2: 27-52 weeks (6-12 months post first IRS, second IRS occurs July (not Oct)). Time point 3: 53-79 weeks. Time point 4: 79-121 weeks. Week one is assumed to be immediately after IRS in October. Therefore time-point 1: up to 6 months post IRS.
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	<p>Incidence rates were similar in the four arms with 17.2 per 1000 PYO in the LLIN + IRS arm, 16.1 in the LLIN arm, 17.0 in the IRS arm, and 15.6 in the control arm.</p> <p>Incidence per 10000 years (95%CI) IRS = 17.0 (15.1-19.0) Control = 15.6 (13.9-17.5)</p> <p>The overall malaria incidence was 16.5 per 1000 PYs of observation time (PYO). Incidence rates were similar in the four arms with 17.2 per 1000 PYO in the LLIN + IRS arm, 16.1 in the LLIN arm, 17.0 in the IRS arm, and 15.6 in the control arm. The incidence of <i>P. falciparum</i> infection was 9.1 per 1000 PYO (95% CI 8.4–9.8), for <i>P. vivax</i> 4.2 (3.7–4.6), and for mixed <i>P. falciparum</i> and <i>P. vivax</i> infection 3.3 per 1000 PYO (95% CI 2.8–3.6). There was no difference in malaria incidence among the four arms after adjusting.</p>
Effect type	IRR.
OUTCOME 2	
Name	Incidence of anaemia.
Definition/ assessment metric	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The other main outcome was anaemia and Hb concentration in children under the age of 5 years which was measured using a portable photometer (Hb310 analyser, using a portable photometer (Hb310 analyser HemoCue® AB, Angelholm, Sweden) at the end of each transmission season. The Hb concentration was measured in children 6–59 months old in the study households at three time points during the study (December 2014–2016, at end of each year’s main malaria transmission season) to assess the prevalence of anaemia. Through house-to-house visits, a single finger-prick sample was taken from each child, and height and weight were measured. Children with Hb values less than 11 g/dl were defined as anaemic.
Events	<p>Survey 1 (2014) IRS = 199 Control = 223</p> <p>Survey 2 (2015) IRS = 272 Control = 287</p> <p>Survey 3 (2016)</p>

	IRS = 192 Control = 236																																																				
Total (or unit time)	Total randomised (assumed).																																																				
Time of outcome assessment	Following study.																																																				
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	<p>There was no significant difference in risk of anaemia among the trial arms.</p> <p>Survey 1 (2014) (Anaemia prevalence and OR)</p> <table> <tr> <td>IRS alone = 29.1 (25.8 – 32.6)</td> <td>OR 1.12 (0.89 – 1.41)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Control = 28.3 (25.2 – 31.6)</td> <td>OR 1.08 (0.86 – 1.35)</td> </tr> </table> <p>Survey 2 (2015)</p> <table> <tr> <td>IRS alone = 38.5 (35 – 42.2)</td> <td>OR 1.02 (0.83 – 1.25)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Control = 11.38 (11.27 – 11.50)</td> <td>OR 35.8 (32.5 -39.2)</td> </tr> </table> <p>Survey 3 (2016)</p> <table> <tr> <td>IRS alone = 28.8 (25.4 – 32.2)</td> <td>OR 0.96 (0.77 – 1.20)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Control = 29.2 (26.7 – 33.0)</td> <td>OR 1.01 (0.81 – 1.25)</td> </tr> </table> <p>There was no significant difference in risk of anaemia among the trial arms.</p> <p>The prevalence of anaemia was 28.2% (95% CI 26.6–29.8) in 2014 and increased to 36.8% (95% CI 35.1–38.5) in 2015, and fell to 29.8% (95% CI 28.2–31.4) at the end of the study.</p>	IRS alone = 29.1 (25.8 – 32.6)	OR 1.12 (0.89 – 1.41)	Control = 28.3 (25.2 – 31.6)	OR 1.08 (0.86 – 1.35)	IRS alone = 38.5 (35 – 42.2)	OR 1.02 (0.83 – 1.25)	Control = 11.38 (11.27 – 11.50)	OR 35.8 (32.5 -39.2)	IRS alone = 28.8 (25.4 – 32.2)	OR 0.96 (0.77 – 1.20)	Control = 29.2 (26.7 – 33.0)	OR 1.01 (0.81 – 1.25)																																								
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	Cost per household covered	5.49	15.56	20.51
	Total number of household in the study arms	1388	1527	1618
Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The annualized total cost for LLIN arm per 10000 population was USD 10641. • About 88% of the cost is due to the bed net (LLIN) itself, while only 12% was expenditure for the delivery of the intervention (6% for personnel and 5% for transportation costs). • Therefore, the unit cost of LLIN per person year-protected was USD 1.06. • Similarly, with 95% of households covered with IRS costs a total of USD 30660 per 10000 population. • From the total cost, about 58% (17799) was spent for the purchase of the insecticide, and 26% (7883) was for personnel. • The unit cost of malaria prevention with IRS alone per person-year protected was USD 3.07. In the combined implementation of the interventions (LLIN + IRS), USD 40408 was incurred in order to universally cover about 10000 population with both LLIN and IRS. In the combined implementation, about 48%, 22%, and 17% of the cost was attributed to the cost of the insecticide (Propoxur), the personnel, and the bed nets (LLINs), respectively. The unit cost of combined intervention (LLIN + IRS) per person-year protected was USD 4.04. • In this model, a hypothetical Ethiopian birth cohort was followed over their lifetime (i.e. the time horizon in this evaluation was 80 years). A similar Markov lifecycle cohort model was employed for each intervention group (LLIN alone, IRS alone, LLIN + IRS) and control group (Routine). 			
Time of cost assessment	Following roll-out of the intervention.			
Resources needed/ used	8-liter Hudson X pert(HD Hudson Manufacturing Company, Chicago, IL, USA), spray canisters.			
ADDITIONAL DATA				
Unintended benefits	Not reported.			
Harms	Not reported.			
Other contextual information present/measured/reported (feasibility, acceptability, preferences/values, impact on equity)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local residents primarily depend on farming, livestock rearing, and to a lesser extent, fishing in Lake Zeway, for their subsistence. • In 2014, there was one public and one non-governmental organization hospital, 9 public health centres, and 43 health posts in the district. Each <i>kebele</i> has at least one health post staffed by two health extension workers (HEWs) reporting to the health centre. • After completion of the study, households in the IRS and control groups received LLINs according to the national guidelines for bed net distribution. 			
Entomological outcomes measured (list)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human biting rates, mosquito resting density, longevity, sporozoite rates, and the entomological inoculation rate (EIR) inside houses. • The primary entomological outcome measure is malaria transmission expressed as EIR, estimated as the mean number of sporozoite infective bites/person/year. 			

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The secondary entomological outcome measures are the mean number of <i>An. arabiensis</i>/light trap/night, and mean number of <i>An. arabiensis</i> in spray catches/night inside houses.
Other	To control for potential confounding factors, the clustering effect of villages and the effect of repeated measurement in the same individual and individual-level covariates (such as age, gender, LLIN use) were taken into consideration during the analysis. Building materials (roof type) is another potential confounding factor, and was also adjusted for in the regression analysis, which was estimated by a proportional hazards model. For ease of analysis, corrugated iron was merged with cement/ concrete roof type.
Source of funding	This study has been funded by the Research Council of Norway (project number: 220554).
Possible conflicts of interest	<p>The authors acknowledge the Center for International Health at the University of Bergen in Norway, and Addis Ababa and Hawassa Universities in Ethiopia for their technical and logistical support to the research.</p> <p>The authors declare that they have no competing interests.</p>

Misra et al.

Study: Malaria control: Bed nets or spraying? Spray versus treated nets using deltamethrin—a community randomized trial in India	
DESIGN	
Lead Author	S. P. Misra.
Publication year	1999.
Trial name	Malaria Control and Research Project.
Other reports of this study (i.e., author, year, title, doi)	Bhatia et al. (2004). Cost-effectiveness of malaria control interventions when malaria mortality is low: insecticide-treated nets versus in-house residual spraying in India.
Time period study was conducted	June 1997- May 1998.
Design	Cluster randomised controlled trial.
Eligibility criteria of participants	<p>Surat district was chosen because it had:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) a high malaria risk; (ii) diverse eco- systems; (iii) varied factors which affect the epidemiology of malaria including tribal, urban, coastal, and migrant populations; (v) irrigated and industrial areas; (vi) presence in the district of triple resistant vector species (resistant to DDT, benzene hexa-chloride (BHC) and malathion); (vii) a mix of <i>P.vivax</i> and <i>P. falciparum</i> cases; and (viii) perennially congenial mosquitogenic conditions that produce extended transmission in urban and rural areas.
Recruitment methods and rate	<p>Randomly selected on the basis of high malaria endemicity.</p> <p>All villages received one of the three trial interventions however, follow-up was restricted to 150 households</p>
Unit of allocation	Neighbouring villages (details not specified) were randomised to one of the three groups (Nets, IRS, untreated).

Number of units	42 villages per arm.
Method of Randomization/ matching or other	Each group was randomized between the 2 interventions and control by public drawing of lots.
Number of clusters per arm	42 villages per arm.
Adjustment for clustering	Not reported.
Cluster details (including buffer sizes between clusters, other indication of dilution effects)	All villages included in the study were at least 1km away from a neighbouring village.
Total trial participants per group/arm (including number of exclusions and reasons)	NETS: 30634, 42 villages. IRS: 30503, 42 villages. CONTROL: 30647, 42 villages.
Outcomes assessed	
SETTING	
Country	India.
Site/s (town/settlements/region)	Surat, district of Gujarat state.
Peak transmission season	Not reported.
Baseline malaria endemicity/ level of transmission	High malaria risk in this area.
Study site (e.g., rural/ urban/ peri-urban/ level of urbanicity)	Mixture of both urban and rural areas.
Vector species and vector profile details (i.e., behaviours, resistance profile/ susceptibility tests, parity, sporozoite rates and all other reported information)	Anopheles culicifacies.
Malaria species	P falciparum and P vivax.
PARTICIPANTS (those who received the intervention and on whom impact was measured)	
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants who received the intervention	Not reported.
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants on whom the impact was measured.	Not reported. Outcomes were only reported on individuals who reported having a fever when the field workers visited the study area (twice a week).
Frequency of travel in the last month	Not reported.
INTERVENTION (Repeat if multiple arms)	
Insecticide brand, type, formulation (including active ingredient), dose, duration (this includes timing and frequency of application)	Deltamethrin. The authors then state that the spraying operation in the trial villages was based on the NAMP guidelines.
Insecticide application method(s) and strategy (e.g., spray, paint, treated materials, wallpaper)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spraying of households was undertaken by village and was time consuming from convincing a household to accept spraying to preparation of the house, and the process of spraying. • Each household was required to empty the house prior to spraying, and the community provided water for spraying. • Each spray squad is expected to cover 60–80 houses per day in lowland areas and 50–60 houses per day in the hills/foothills.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A central ‘godown’ was used for storing the insecticide drums and other equipment. Trucks were hired for moving these to local storage areas and for transporting the spray staff. • The project vehicles were mainly used for supervisory visits.
Personnel applying the intervention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The spraying operation in the trial villages was based on the NAMP guidelines. Although attempts have been made to integrate the NAMP with the primary health care system, organization and implementation of IRS is still largely vertical. • The district malaria officer (DMO) is in charge of malaria control activities including spraying and supervises the technical and administrative work of the malaria inspectors. • Each malaria inspector is allocated several primary health centres (PHCs) from which their malaria control activities are based. • A health supervisor assists the malaria inspector to organise and supervise the spray operations in a defined area, including direct supervision of multipurpose workers. • Spray workers are hired on a temporary basis by the DMO office for the whole district for 4–5 months during the spraying season. These workers are organised into spray squads consisting of 5 field workers and one supervisor. • Each multipurpose worker is expected to supervise the work of 2–4 squads.
Target area (inside/outside)	Indoors.
How the coverage of the intervention was measured	Not reported.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	Unlike a state-run spray programme, coverage in this trial was not an issue as the majority of houses were fully sprayed and refusals were minimal.
Coverage of household (full, selective/partial)	Full.
Length of intervention, including number of rounds of spraying/application per year/season	Not reported.
Type of dwelling (e.g., fixed or temporary) and construction material of surfaces insecticides applied to (e.g., cement, brick or mud walls, canvas etc)	Not reported. Mud walls.
Time to start intervention after index case	Not reported.
Human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, re-plastering of houses)	Not reported.
COMPARISON	
Details of Comparison	No IRS.
How the coverage of the comparison was measured	Not reported.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction for the comparison	Not reported.

Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period and other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)	Not reported.				
OUTCOME 1					
Name	Incidence of malaria (symptomatic).				
Definition/ assessment metric	The field workers visited each household twice a week and took blood smears from all who complained of fever. The slides were examined and cross-checked in a central laboratory.				
Events		ITNs	IRS	CONTROL	
	Malaria cases in surveillance population	682	1101	1603	
	Malaria cases in intervention pop	1226	1664	2556	
Total (or unit time)		ITNs	IRS	CONTROL	
	Malaria cases in surveillance population	30634	30503	30647	
Time of outcome assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Households were visited bi-weekly to enquire about fever cases. • Baseline survey September 1996. • Mass blood survey in September 1997. • One time point offered. Assumed within 6 months. 				
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	<p>The impact on incidence of fever with malaria parasitaemia and prevalence of parasitaemia in the 3 arms of the trial was compared. The incidence rates were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control: 61.5 per 1000 person-years. • Spray: 43.4 per 1000 person-years. • Nets: 28.1 per 1000 person years. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Both ITNs and IRS are effective in terms of reducing the number of malaria cases. • Of the total of 2401 estimated cases of malaria averted by the two interventions, 69% could be attributed to ITNs, indicating that ITNs are significantly more effective than IRS. 				
Effect type	IRR.				
COSTS					
Event/raw costs	<u>Cost comparison of ITNs and IRS (Indian Rupees)</u>				
		ITNs	% of total	IRS	% of total
	Recurrent costs				
	Personnel	1024336	33.52	780666	33.49
	Insecticides	307956	10.08	864901	37.10
	Project office operating expenses	46590	1.52	41602	1.78

Vehicle operating expenses	93862	3.07	93684	4.02
Hire of IEC items	67662	2.21	67662	2.90
Building operating expenditure repairs and anti-termite measures	35147	1.15	15063	0.65
Other	2560	0.80	5500	0.24
Total recurrent costs	1578113	51.63	1869078	80.18
Capital costs				
Mosquito nets	989471	32.37	Na	Na
Equipment	157491	5.15	189582	8.13
Space rental (inc. project office)	119586	3.91	66409	2.85
Vehicles	188881	6.18	183372	7.87
Other (development of health education material)	22751	0.74	22750	0.98
Total capital costs	1,478,180	48.37	462,113	19.82
Total costs	3056293	100.00	2331191	100.00

Price and quantity of principal inputs for both intervention groups, Indian Rupees (1997–1998)

	Price	ITN		IRS	
		Total	Total cost(%)	Total	Total cost(%)
Personnel (in man-days)					
Field and office staff	81	2900	2342,900(23)	2478	200718 (26)
Govt supervisors	205	232	47560 (5)	234	47970 (6)
Project supervisors	332	160	53120 (5)	146	48472 (6)
Others (IEC, Management)	nd	nd	688756 (67)	nd	483506 (62)
Sub-total Personnel			1024336 (100)		780666 (100)
 Mosquito nets	 90	 35136	 989471	 Na	 Na
 Insecticides					
Deltametrin flow	840.7	366.3	307956		
Deltamethrin	712.4	Litres		1214.1kg	864901
Total			2321763		1645567

Results

- The recurrent costs, as a percentage of total costs of individual interventions, are higher for IRS (80%) compared with ITNs (52%) mainly due to the higher proportion of insecticide costs for IRS (74%) compared with ITNs (26%).
- There were few other differences in the cost profile of the two interventions for other recurrent cost categories.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The capital costs of ITNs were almost three times those of the IRS due to the mosquito nets and storage. • The total costs of ITNs are greater than those of IRS, which is also reflected in the higher cost per capita.
Time of cost assessment	End of study. Trial ended in 1998.
Resources needed/ used	Manpower, insecticides, storage, equipment, vehicles (all listed above).
ADDITIONAL DATA	
Unintended benefits	Not reported.
Harms	Not reported.
Other contextual information present/measured/reported) (feasibility, acceptability, preferences/values, impact on equity)	Not reported.
Entomological outcomes measured (list)	Vector density. Blood meal preference. Mortality.
Other	Not reported.
Source of funding	Department for International Development and the Health Project Management Office, British Council in India.
Possible conflicts of interest	Not reported.

Rowland et al.

Study: Rowland M, Mahmood P, Iqbal J, Carneiro I, Chavasse D. Indoor residual spraying with alphacypermethrin controls malaria in Pakistan: a community-randomized trial. Trop Med Int Health. 2000 Jul;5(7):472-81.	
DESIGN	
Lead Author	Mark Rowland.
Publication year	2000.
Trial name	Not reported.
Other reports of this study (i.e., author, year, title, doi)	Not reported.
Time period study was conducted	June 1997 – December 1997.
Design	Cluster randomised controlled trial.
Eligibility criteria of participants	Not reported.
Recruitment methods and rate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The area was mapped by NIMRT, divided into nine sectors of approximately equal population size and area. • Then each sector was assigned at random to untreated, WP, or SC spraying in replicates of three. • Village elders attended meetings to learn about the study and to give their consent to the project. • One or two schools were selected from sentinel villages in each sector for outcome assessment using cross sectional surveys. • All 60 villages within the study area were included in the trial.
Unit of allocation	60 villages within the study area were included in the trial.
Number of units	60 villages in total participated. Number of villages belonging to each sector or treatment group was not reported.
Method of Randomization/ matching or other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study area was mapped by NIMRT and divided into nine sectors of approximately equal population size and area.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each sector was assigned at random to untreated, WP, or SC spraying in replicates of three.
Number of clusters per arm	Not reported.
Adjustment for clustering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The point-estimates of treatment effects were calculated using the overall data for each treatment arm. • Confidence intervals are not reported as they assume independence of observations and are therefore incorrect. • As there were only three sampling units (i.e. sectors) in each treatment arm, it was not possible to obtain precise estimates of effect adjusting for the non-independence (intracluster correlation) of individuals within the same sector.
Cluster details (including buffer sizes between clusters, other indication of dilution effects)	Sentinel villages were chosen carefully so that the distance to villages in a different treatment group was at least 1.5 km.
Total trial participants per group/arm (including number of exclusions and reasons)	<p>Sentinel villages were consistent between treatment groups. Number of participants in sentinel villages from each cluster:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two or three sentinel villages totalling 2000 population were selected from each sector for disease and entomological monitoring and enumerated. • WP sector = 6017 (participants) and 1206 (households). • SC sector = 5677 (participants) and 1124 (households). • Control sector = 6567 (participants) and 1328 (households).
Outcomes assessed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidence of malaria (both <i>falciparum</i> and <i>vivax</i>), through active case detection confirmed by RDT. • Incidence of malaria (both <i>falciparum</i> and <i>vivax</i>), through cross-sectional surveys of children aged 5-15, confirmed by RDT.
SETTING	
Country	Pakistan.
Site/s (town/settlements/region)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three Union Councils that covered 180 km² of the Sheikhpura district. • 60km west of Lahore, the provincial capital. • The study area was a flat, irrigated, agricultural plain, with rice as the main crop during the malaria season (June–November). The area appeared environmentally homogeneous. At night, cattle, water buffalo, and other domestic animals were kept in the villages in owners' compounds, and hence almost all sources of blood meals and indoor resting sites were situated in the villages.
Peak transmission season	June-November.
Baseline malaria endemicity/ level of transmission	<p>From the baseline surveys in the preintervention period (May-June 1997):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Falciparum</i> incidence was around 5 episodes per 1000 person years. • <i>Vivax</i> incidence was "10 times higher".
Study site (e.g., rural/ urban/ peri-urban/ level of urbanicity)	Rural (assumed).
Vector species and vector profile details (i.e., behaviours, resistance profile/ susceptibility tests, parity, sporozoite rates and all other reported information)	<p>List of vector species:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Anopheles culicifacies</i> • <i>Anopheles stephensi</i> • <i>Anopheles annularis</i> • <i>Anopheles pulcherrimus</i> • <i>Anopheles subpictus</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Cules spp.</i> <p>Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Anopheles stephensi</i> was by far the most abundant species; geometric mean density in space spray catches was 697 specimens per sector per month. • Next was <i>A. subpictus</i> with 288 per sector per month. • <i>Culicifacies</i> was 137 per sector per month. • Few <i>anophelines</i> were caught in May and June (the rice crop was only planted in June). • <i>Culicines</i>, however, were more abundant in May than in any other month and were presumably breeding in sites other than paddy fields. • The July monsoon marked an increase in abundance of <i>A. culicifacies</i>, <i>A. stephensi</i>, <i>A. annularis</i>, and <i>A. pulcherrimus</i>. • <i>A. subpictus</i> first appeared in October and <i>A. nigerrimus</i> in November. • <i>A. stephensi</i> showed two peaks, first in July–August, then in November. • The densities of all anophelines except <i>A. pulcherrimus</i> and <i>nigerrimus</i> were significantly lower in the sprayed sectors • All surfaces treated with 25 mg/m² alphacypermethrin (mud, brick, cement, wood, and thatch) killed 100% of <i>A. culicifacies</i> and <i>A. stephensi</i> for at least 112 days after treatment. Even after 184 days, when cone bioassay tests were finished, all types of treated surface were still killing around 50%. There was no evidence that the decay rate on cement or mud was any faster than on wood or thatch. • Resistance tests showed 100% mortality of laboratory-reared and wild-caught <i>A. stephensi</i> and <i>A. culicifacies</i> (<i>N</i> =80). Hence there was no evidence for resistance in the study area.
Malaria species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>. • <i>Plasmodium vivax</i>.
PARTICIPANTS (those who received the intervention and on whom impact was measured)	
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants who received the intervention	All households in randomised sectors received the intervention.
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants on whom the impact was measured.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students from one or two schools from each sentinel village in each sector were chosen to have their thick and thin smears taken. • 200 to 300 children aged 5-15 were present on the day the blood smears were taken. • Any other information not reported.
Frequency of travel in the last month	Not reported.
INTERVENTION (Repeat if multiple arms)	
Insecticide brand, type, formulation (including active ingredient), dose, duration (this includes timing and frequency of application)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The wettable powder (5% WP) and suspension concentrate (10% SC) formulations of 'Fendona' were tested. • Target dose was 25 mg alphacypermethrin per m².
Insecticide application method(s) and strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supervised spray operations were completed within 24 days in June 1997.

(e.g., spray, paint, treated materials, wallpaper)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spraymen used Hudson X-pert spray pumps (Hudson, IL, USA). • Sprayed living quarters, storage rooms and animal shelters. • Each sprayman sprayed 9–10 compounds per day.
Personnel applying the intervention	Spraymen.
Target area (inside/outside)	Indoors in living quarters, storage rooms, and animals shelters.
How the coverage of the intervention was measured	Not reported.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 96% of compounds (2665) sprayed in WP sectors. • 97% of compounds (1991) sprayed in SC sectors.
Coverage of household (full, selective/partial)	Full.
Length of intervention, including number of rounds of spraying/application per year/season	One spray round, occurring in June 1997. Spraying occurred for 24 days.
Type of dwelling (e.g., fixed or temporary) and construction material of surfaces insecticides applied to (e.g., cement, brick or mud walls, canvas etc)	House compounds were constructed from mud and brick and separated by high perimeter walls.
Time to start intervention after index case	Not reported.
Human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, re-plastering of houses)	Not reported.
COMPARISON	
Details of Comparison	No treatment control.
How the coverage of the comparison was measured	Not reported.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction for the comparison	No treatment control.
Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period and other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)	Not reported.
OUTCOME 1	
Name	Incidence of malaria (both <i>falciparum</i> and <i>vivax</i>), through active case detection confirmed by RDT.
Definition/ assessment metric	The survey teams visited 400 houses in each sector every fortnight. Any member of a household reporting fever during the previous 3 days had a blood smear taken.
Events	Incidence per 1000 person years (before intervention) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Falciparum</i> malaria (IRR for post intervention scores) Control = 5.4 SC = 5.3 WP = 2.0

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Vivax malaria (IRR for post intervention scores)</u> Control = 56 SC = 70 WP = 44
Total (or unit time)	<p>Incidence per 1000 person years (after intervention)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Falciparum malaria (IRR for pre-intervention scores)</u> Control = 29.5 SC = 2.7 WP = 1.4 • <u>Vivax malaria (IRR for pre-intervention scores)</u> Control = 18.7 SC = 4.2 WP = 3.2
Time of outcome assessment	<p>Cross-sectional surveys were undertaken in April–May (before IRS) and September (after IRS). One time point offered: approx. three months post IRS.</p>
<p>Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)</p>	<p>Incidence per 1000 person years (ppy)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Falciparum malaria (IRR for post-intervention scores)</u> Control = 1 (reference) SC = 0.09 WP = 0.05 • <u>Vivax malaria (IRR for post-intervention scores)</u> Control = 1 (reference) SC = 0.23 WP = 0.20 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the pre-intervention period from May to June there was no significant difference in incidence rate between any of the 3 intervention groups for <i>falciparum</i> (Kruskal–Wallis, $\chi^2 = 0.4$, d.f. = 2, $P = 0.81$) or <i>vivax</i> malaria ($\chi^2 = 2.5$, d.f. = 2, $P = 0.29$). • Overall <i>falciparum</i> incidence was around 5 episodes per 1000 person years (ppy) while <i>vivax</i> incidence was 10 times higher. • In the post-intervention period from July to January, incidence rates in control and insecticide treatment groups diverged significantly. The overall incidence of <i>falciparum</i> malaria rose to 29 ppy in the control group but remained < 3 ppy in the insecticide treatment groups (Kruskal–Wallis, $\chi^2 = 7.2$, d.f. = 2, $P = 0.03$). • Similarly, the overall incidence of <i>vivax</i> malaria was 19 ppy in the control but fell to 4 ppy in the SC and WP groups. The result was not significant using the Kruskal–Wallis test ($\chi^2 = 4.3$, d.f. = 2, $P = 0.11$). • As there was no evidence that one formulation was better than the other against <i>falciparum</i> (signed rank, $P = 0.51$) or <i>vivax</i> malaria (signed rank, $P = 0.83$), the data from both insecticide treatment arms were grouped and compared with the control, giving a significant difference (signed rank test, $P = 0.02$). • The protective efficacy, $100 \times (1 - \text{IRR})$ %, of both insecticide treatments was 90–95% against <i>falciparum</i> malaria and around 80% against <i>vivax</i> malaria.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria was fairly rare and seemed to affect all age groups equally ($P = 0.28$). 																														
Effect type	IRR.																														
OUTCOME 2																															
Name	Incidence of malaria (both <i>falciparum</i> and <i>vivax</i>), through cross-sectional surveys of children aged 5-15, confirmed by RDT.																														
Definition/ assessment metric	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-sectional surveys were undertaken in April–May and September, i.e. before and after spraying. • Cross-sectional surveys were administered to one or two schools from the sentinel villages. • One or two schools were selected from sentinel villages in each sector and thick and thin smears were taken from 200 to 300 children aged 5–15 present on the day. 																														
Events	<table border="0"> <tr> <td colspan="3"><u>Prevalence</u></td> </tr> <tr> <td><u><i>Falciparum</i> malaria</u></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><u>Before</u></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><u>After</u></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Control</td> <td style="text-align: center;">0.7</td> <td style="text-align: center;">3.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SC</td> <td style="text-align: center;">1.1</td> <td style="text-align: center;">0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>WP</td> <td style="text-align: center;">0.05</td> <td style="text-align: center;">0.06</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3"> </td> </tr> <tr> <td><u><i>Vivax</i> malaria</u></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><u>Before</u></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><u>After</u></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Control</td> <td style="text-align: center;">6.4</td> <td style="text-align: center;">7.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SC</td> <td style="text-align: center;">5.3</td> <td style="text-align: center;">2.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>WP</td> <td style="text-align: center;">3.7</td> <td style="text-align: center;">2.7</td> </tr> </table>	<u>Prevalence</u>			<u><i>Falciparum</i> malaria</u>	<u>Before</u>	<u>After</u>	Control	0.7	3.9	SC	1.1	0.0	WP	0.05	0.06	 			<u><i>Vivax</i> malaria</u>	<u>Before</u>	<u>After</u>	Control	6.4	7.5	SC	5.3	2.0	WP	3.7	2.7
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Control	719	831																													
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Time of outcome assessment	Cross-sectional surveys were undertaken in April–May and September, i.e. before and after spraying.																														
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	<p><u>OR post-intervention</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u><i>Falciparum</i> malaria</u> Control = 1 (reference) SC = 0.00 WP = 0.14 • <u><i>Vivax</i> malaria (IRR for post-intervention scores)</u> Control = 1 (reference) SC = 0.26 WP = 0.35 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The prevalence of <i>falciparum</i> malaria was only around 1% in the pre-intervention survey, while that of <i>vivax</i> malaria stood around 5%. • There was no significant difference between any treatment group pre-intervention, either for <i>falciparum</i> (Kruskal–Wallis, $\chi^2 = 0.4$, d.f. = 2, $P = 0.81$) or <i>vivax</i> malaria ($\chi^2 = 2.5$, d.f. = 2, $P = 0.29$). • In the post-intervention survey 3 months after spraying, <i>falciparum</i> malaria prevalence increased to 3.9% in the control group but remained < 1% in the SC and WP groups. 																														

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Similarly, <i>vivax</i> malaria prevalence remained at 7.5% in the control group but fell to < 3% in the SC and WP groups. • Both results were of borderline significance using Kruskal–Wallis ($P = 0.06$), but if the data are regrouped to compare both insecticide treatments ($n = 6$) against the control ($n = 3$), the result is significant for both <i>falciparum</i> (signed rank, $P = 0.02$) and <i>vivax</i> malaria (signed rank, $P = 0.04$). • The protective efficacy, $100*(1- OR)\%$, of the spray intervention indicates that <i>falciparum</i> malaria prevalence was reduced by 100% in the SC and by 86% in the WP groups, while <i>vivax</i> malaria prevalence was reduced by 77% in the SC and by 63% in the WP group. • The protective efficacies for <i>vivax</i> malaria were lower than for <i>falciparum</i> malaria.
Effect type	OR.
COSTS	
Event/raw costs	Not reported.
Results	Not reported.
Time of cost assessment	Not reported.
Resources needed/ used	Not reported.
ADDITIONAL DATA	
Unintended benefits	Since no persistent odour or residue was evident after spraying, and because both nuisance and vector mosquitoes were controlled, many people expressed appreciation for the spray campaign.
Harms	Transitory skin irritation and headache were reported by some sprayers and a few householders shortly after spraying. The effect wore off after a few hours.
Other contextual information present/measured/reported) (feasibility, acceptability, preferences/values, impact on equity)	Not reported.
Entomological outcomes measured (list)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insecticide residual activity. • Mosquito densities. • Mosquito longevity. • Landing catches on water buffalo.
Other	In international tenders it is price competitive against its main rivals deltamethrin, lambda-cyhalothrin and cyfluthin.
Source of funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The field study was funded by Cyanamid, with technical support from WHOPEs. • HealthNet International's Malaria Control Programme is supported by the European Commission (DG1) and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees. • Research costs were partly covered by the Department for International Development of the United Kingdom and by HealthNet International.
Possible conflicts of interest	Not reported.

Study: Gunasekaran K, Sahu SS, Jambulingam P, Das PK. DDT indoor residual spray, still an effective tool to control Anopheles fluviatilis-transmitted Plasmodium falciparum malaria in India. Trop Med Int Health. 2005 Feb;10(2):160-8. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-3156.2004.01369.x. PMID: 15679559.	
DESIGN	
Lead Author	K. Gunasekaran.
Publication year	2005.
Trial name	Vector Control Research Centre (VCRC).
Other reports of this study (i.e., author, year, title, doi)	Not reported.
Time period study was conducted	August 2001 to March 2002.
Design	Controlled before and after study.
Eligibility criteria of participants	Not reported.
Recruitment methods and rate	In each district, six villages from the experimental and three from unsprayed (control) group were randomly selected as index villages to monitor prevalence and incidence of malaria infection and fever.
Unit of allocation	Villages belonging to two districts (Malkangiri and Koraput) of Orissa State.
Number of units	<u>Malkangiri (Khairput)</u> Intervention: n=26 Control: n = 6 <u>Koraput (Boipariguda)</u> Intervention: n = 28 Control: n = 4
Method of Randomization/matching or other	Not reported. Assumed mostly rural.
Number of clusters per arm	Intervention – Malkangiri 26 units, Koraput 28 units. Control – Malkangiri 6 units, Koraput 4 units.
Adjustment for clustering	Not reported.
Cluster details (including buffer sizes between clusters, other indication of dilution effects)	Not reported.
Total trial participants per group/arm (including number of exclusions and reasons)	<u>Malkangiri (Khairput)</u> Intervention: n = 5742 Control: n = 843 <u>Koraput (Boipariguda)</u> Intervention: n = 5886 Control: n = 1268
Outcomes assessed	Malaria prevalence. Malaria incidence.
SETTING	
Country	India.
Site/s (town/settlements/region)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orissa State, Malkangari district and Koraput district. • Situated in the southern part of Orissa State. • The district of Malkangiri with seven Primary Health Centres (PHC) has an area of 6259 km². The population of this district is 507 606.

	Koraput District has an area of 7897 km ² and a population of 1 100 938 (2001 census) served by 14 PHCs.
Peak transmission season	Malaria incidence peaked from July to December.
Baseline malaria endemicity/ level of transmission	During the last three years (1999–2001) the Annual Parasite Incidence (API) ranged from 23.8 to 33.5 in Malkangiri and from 16.8 to 19.5 in Koraput District.
Study site (e.g., rural/ urban/ peri-urban/ level of urbanicity)	Not reported.
Vector species and vector profile details (i.e., behaviours, resistance profile/ susceptibility tests, parity, sporozoite rates and all other reported information)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indoor resting mosquito collections (from both test and control villages prior to and after the spray) yielded a total of 3022 anophelines of 16 species in Malkangiri and 3059 <i>Anopheles</i> mosquitoes of 11 species in Koraput District. • <i>Anopheles culicifacies</i> and <i>A. fluviatilis</i> constituted 27.7% and 26.7%, respectively, of the anophelines collected in the former district. • In the latter district, <i>A. fluviatilis</i> was the predominant species (76.5%) followed by <i>A. culicifacies</i> (9.8%). • Based on the high API values recorded over the years and logistics, the PHCs of Khairput (Malkangiri District) and Boipariguda (Koraput District) were selected. The API from 1999 to 2001 varied between 21.1 and 30.8 in Khairput and between 22.5 and 32.0 in Boipariguda. • <i>Anopheles fluviatilis</i> collected from both districts before spraying showed 100% mortality when exposed to DDT impregnated paper. • In Koraput District, all mosquitoes of this species, collected immediately after DDT spraying in sprayed villages, were dead. • <i>Anopheles culicifacies</i> was resistant to DDT in both Malkangiri and Koraput Districts as the corrected mortality was respectively 21.1% and 21.2%. Testing for its susceptibility at individual sibling species level could not be made, as the number collected was too low.
Malaria species	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> was the predominant species, constituting 97.6% (n = 414) of the total malaria positives recorded in Malkangiri District and 99.2% (n = 619) in Koraput District.
PARTICIPANTS (those who received the intervention and on whom impact was measured)	
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants who received the intervention	Not reported.
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants on whom the impact was measured.	Not reported.
Frequency of travel in the last month	Not reported.
INTERVENTION (Repeat if multiple arms)	
Insecticide brand, type, formulation (including active ingredient), dose, duration (this includes timing and frequency of application)	Dichlorodiphenyl trichlorethane (DDT). The DDT IRS was done with 1 g active ingredient per m ² between 29 October and 4 November 2001.
Insecticide application method(s) and strategy (e.g., spray, paint, treated materials, wallpaper)	Spray directly to mud walls.

Personnel applying the intervention	Spraying was performed by the anti-malaria programme spray-men supervised by both VCRC and district health department staff.
Target area (inside/outside)	Interior walls.
How the coverage of the intervention was measured	Not reported. States that details on coverage of the spray were recorded.
Coverage of household (full, selective/partial)	Spray coverage of individual rooms ranged from 30.6% to 84.6% (overall: 48.6%) for Malkangiri District. Spray coverage of individual rooms ranged from 36.2%-92% (overall: 56.6%) for Koraput District. Coverage of cattle sheds was 100%.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	Spray coverage of households ranged from 44.6% to 100% (overall: 74.2%) for Malkangiri District. Spray coverage of households ranged from 68.6–100% (overall: 86.2%) for Koraput District.
Length of intervention, including number of rounds of spraying/application per year/season	One rounds of DDT spraying between 29 October and 4 November 2001
Type of dwelling (e.g., fixed or temporary) and construction material of surfaces insecticides applied to (e.g., cement, brick or mud walls, canvas etc)	Bioassays done on mud walls.
Time to start intervention after index case	Not reported.
Human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, re-plastering of houses)	In Malkangiri District, nearly 50% of households were found to have re-plastered their walls by day 60 and 100% by day 90. In Koraput District, the corresponding rates were 80% by day 30 and 100% by day 60. Some householders refused to allow spraying of their houses mainly because of a traditional custom of not allowing outsiders to enter their prayer rooms. Villagers do not object to spraying of their cattle sheds.
COMPARISON	
Details of Comparison	No IRS.
How the coverage of the comparison was measured	Not reported. Three control villages were selected from the unsprayed villages to monitor prevalence and incidence of malaria infection and fever.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction for the comparison	Not reported.
Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period and other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The DDT was used for IRS in Malkangiri District from 1958 to 1971. • In 1972, DDT was replaced with HCH for IRS and three rounds of HCH spray was continued till 1997 when it was banned from public health use. Subsequently in 1998, DDT was again brought in for IRS and it is still being used in this district. • In Koraput District DDT is the only insecticide that has been used for two rounds of IRS every year from 1958 to the present time in all villages.
OUTCOME 1	

Name	Malaria prevalence.
Definition/ assessment metric	A blood survey was conducted before and 4 months after the spraying in both experimental and control villages among 25% of the population (all age groups) in each village. Thick blood films, collected from individuals regardless of the presence of symptoms of malaria, were stained with Giemsa and examined in the VCRC laboratory for presence of malaria parasites.
Events	(Slide positivity rate of number of smears collected). <u>BEFORE SPRAYING</u> <u>Malkangiri</u> Intervention: 1509 (smears collected) with SPR of 22.3% = 337 positive Control: 259 (smears collected) with SPR of 30.1% = 78 positive <u>Boipariguda</u> Intervention: 1576 (smears collected) with SPR of 32.7% = 516 positive Control: 386 (smears collected) with SPR of 26.7% = 104 positive <u>AFTER SPRAYING</u> <u>Malkangiri</u> Intervention: 1540 (smears collected) with SPR of 12.5%= 192.5 positive Control: 265 (smears collected) with SPR of 54.7% = 145 positive <u>Boipariguda</u> Intervention: 1525 (smears collected) with SPR of 14.4% = 220 positive Control: 343 (smears collected) with SPR of 35.3% = 122 positive
Total (or unit time)	See above.
Time of outcome assessment	Approx. four months post IRS.
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	Results presented as Mantel-Haenszel chi-squared analysis of prevalence of malaria infection before and after DDT spraying. <u>Malkangiri:</u> Intervention: OR = 0.5 (0.4-0.6) Control: OR = 2.85 (2.04-4.46) <u>Koraput:</u> Intervention: OR = 0.34 (0.28 – 0.4) Control: OR = 1.45 (1.04-2.04)
Effect type	OR.
OUTCOME 2	
Name	Malaria incidence.
Definition/ assessment metric	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidence of malaria was assessed by active surveillance in the index villages at fortnightly intervals. • Blood films were collected from those who complained of fever at the time of each visit and from those who had a history of fever during the period from the last visit to the current one, for confirmation of presence of malaria parasites.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The monthly parasite incidence (MPI) (number of positive malaria fever cases per 1000 population) was calculated for every month for both sprayed and unsprayed villages before and after the spray.
Events	Raw data for malaria incidence not provided.
Total (or unit time)	Raw data for malaria incidence not provided.
Time of outcome assessment	Not reported.
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In Malkangiri, incidence of malaria fever in the control villages increased in November and peaked during December and January. DDT sprayed villages, the MPI was reduced by from 84.1% to 91.7% over 4 months (mean: 85.6%). The reduction of MPI in the sprayed villages of Koraput District ranged from 62.9% to 83% (mean: 77%). <p><u>Malkangiri:</u> Intervention: OR = 0.64 (0.39-1.07) Control: OR = 4.71 (2.47-9.21)</p> <p><u>Koraput:</u> Intervention: OR = 0.69 (0.42-1.12) Control: OR = 3.39 (2.09-5.48)</p>
Effect type	OR (incidence proportion).
COSTS	
Event/raw costs	Not reported.
Results	Not reported.
Time of cost assessment	Not reported.
Resources needed/ used	Not reported.
ADDITIONAL DATA	
Unintended benefits	Not reported.
Harms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wall decolourization. Bad smell. Increase in bed bug nuisance. Contamination of food grains stored above the false ceiling and social caste feelings against the spray-men were also some of the reasons attributed for the refusal.
Other contextual information present/measured/reported) (feasibility, acceptability, preferences/values, impact on equity)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In both the districts, cone bioassays conducted prior to spraying showed zero mortality of <i>A. fluviatilis</i>, indicating absence of any DDT residue on the sprayable surfaces to cause mortality despite the fact that the villages were sprayed in the previous year. After the spray, in Malkangiri district, up to 12 weeks the mortality of <i>A. fluviatilis</i> was 100% on exposure to the sprayed walls, which were either not re-plastered or re-plastered once or twice. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> At the 13th week, the mortality on walls, which had not been re-plastered, was 85% and on re-plastered walls it was relatively low. At week 17, the mortality was 76% on walls, which had not been re-plastered and during this period wall re-plastering once or twice further reduced the mortality to 62% and 57% respectively. In Koraput District, 100% mortality of <i>A. fluviatilis</i> was observed up to 10 weeks on the sprayed walls which had not been re-plastered as well as on walls which had been re-plastered, once.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At the 11th week, the mortality was reduced to 60% even on walls which had not been re-plastered indicating a relatively short residual effect of DDT spraying in this district. - On walls re-plastered once or twice the mortality was 27% and 13% respectively. - At week 16, the mortality was only 19% on walls which had not been re-plastered and, during this period, re-plastering twice brought down the mortality to 5%. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The state health department is responsible for IRS in the districts for malaria control. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In 2001, due to some administrative constraints, the second round of DDT spraying was not carried out in many villages in the districts. - The experiment was conducted in the sprayed villages and controls were selected from the unsprayed ones. <p>DDT spraying was not withdrawn for the sake of experiment in any of the villages.</p>
Entomological outcomes measured (list)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vector susceptibility. • Indoor resting collections. • Parous rate. • Residual effect of DDT.
Other	Not reported.
Source of funding	Not reported.
Possible conflicts of interest	Not reported.

Guyatt et al.

Study: Guyatt HL, Corlett SK, Robinson TP, Ochola SA, Snow RW. Malaria prevention in highland Kenya: indoor residual house-spraying vs. insecticide-treated bednets. <i>Trop Med Int Health</i> . 2002 Apr;7(4):298-303. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-3156.2002.00874.x. PMID: 11952944.	
DESIGN	
Lead Author	Helen Guyatt.
Publication year	2002.
Trial name	Not reported (but mention this was conducted with “Merlin” and “Ministry of Health staff”).
Other reports of this study (i.e., author, year, title, doi)	Guyatt HL, Kinnear J, Burini M & Snow RW (2002) A comparative cost analysis of insecticide treated nets and indoor residual spraying in highland Kenya. <i>Health Policy and Planning</i> 17, 144–153.
Time period study was conducted	November 1999 – May 2000 (However IRS was only provided from February – May 2000).
Design	Non-randomised controlled trial.
Eligibility criteria of participants	Not reported.
Recruitment methods and rate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In February 2000, local health staff identified high-risk communities likely to benefit most from aggressive preventative measures before the seasonal rise in malaria incidence in June. • Priority areas were selected based on a number of criteria including whether communities were near swamps, underwent brick-making activities, had a history of high malaria morbidity and mortality or were remote from health care facilities. • Between February and May 2000, four mobile teams, composed of Merlin and Ministry of Health staff, were trained by staff from the

	local supplier, Zeneca, and subsequently undertook IRS using Icon 10% WP (lambda-cyhalothrin, 100 g/kg ai; Zeneca, Nairobi, Kenya).
Unit of allocation	“Sublocations” of the Nyamache Division and the Gucha District.
Number of units	Approximately 200 homesteads (“family units”) were randomly selected in each of the three study arms (Control, ITN and IRS). Only IRS homesteads that did not have ITNs were selected.
Method of Randomization/matching or other	A strictly randomized study design was not possible because interventions were targeted to communities according to operational rather than experimental priorities.
Number of clusters per arm	A total of 5 clusters. Control = 2 clusters. IRS = 3 clusters.
Adjustment for clustering	Not reported.
Cluster details (including buffer sizes between clusters, other indication of dilution effects)	Not reported.
Total trial participants per group/arm (including number of exclusions and reasons)	9180 participants in 2 clusters in the control arm. 11928 participants in 3 clusters in the IRS arm. Number of households in each arm: IRS n = 200 Control n = 200 ITN n = 190
Outcomes assessed	Malaria prevalence.
SETTING	
Country	Western Kenya.
Site/s (town/settlements/region)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nyamache Division and Gucha District. • The districts of Gucha and Kisii are located in the western highlands at altitudes between 1400 and 2200 m above sea level. • The area is densely populated with a combined population of 957 250 in 1999 occupying 1450 km². • The population predominantly comprises rural farmers growing combinations of subsistence crops for home consumption and tea for cash income. • In July 1999, Kisii and Gucha districts suffered a malaria epidemic, prompting much political concern and nongovernmental, donor-supported investment in improving case management and vector control. • In order to pre-empt a similar epidemic in 2000, one of the emergency relief organizations deployed to the area (Merlin) expanded a programme of vector control throughout the two districts.
Peak transmission season	Transmission is acutely seasonal following the climatic variation in the area. The greatest concentration of clinical disease occurs between June and August with the extent of the burden varying considerably between years
Baseline malaria endemicity/level of transmission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In July 1999, Kisii and Gucha districts suffered a malaria epidemic, prompting much political concern and non-governmental, donor-supported investment in improving case management and vector control.

Study site (e.g., rural/ urban/ peri-urban/ level of urbanicity)	The population predominantly comprises rural farmers.
Vector species and vector profile details (i.e., behaviours, resistance profile/ susceptibility tests, parity, sporozoite rates and all other reported information)	The ecology and climate of the western highlands of Kenya support conditions that favour low intensity, stable transmission of <i>P. falciparum</i> by two principal vectors, <i>Anopheles gambiae</i> ss and <i>An. Funestus</i> .
Malaria species	<i>P. falciparum</i> .
PARTICIPANTS (those who received the intervention and on whom impact was measured)	
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants who received the intervention	All households in the clusters received the interventions (as reported – no details on refusals). <u>Control</u> Median (IQR) households (family units) = 1 (1-2) Median (IQR) residents = 8 (6-11) Farming Land => 2 acres = 70% <u>IRS</u> Median (IQR) households (family units) = 1 (1-2) Median (IQR) residents = 8 (6-11) Farming Land => 2 acres = 75.5% • Almost all residents examined were of the Wakisii ethnic group (99.7%)
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants on whom the impact was measured.	Only one, randomly selected member of the household, from each age group (of 6months-4years; 5-15 years; over 15 years) was selected to have outcomes measured (i.e. 3 members of each household, chosen at random from the 200 households in each cluster).
Frequency of travel in the last month	Almost all residents had not travelled outside the study area in the last 2 months (99.4%).
INTERVENTION (Repeat if multiple arms)	
Insecticide brand, type, formulation (including active ingredient), dose, duration (this includes timing and frequency of application)	Between February and May 2000, four mobile teams, composed of Merlin and Ministry of Health staff, were trained by staff from the local supplier, Zeneca, and subsequently undertook IRS using Icon 10% WP (lambda-cyhalothrin, 100 g/kg).
Insecticide application method(s) and strategy (e.g., spray, paint, treated materials, wallpaper)	Not reported.
Personnel applying the intervention	Four mobile teams, composed of Merlin and Ministry of Health staff who were trained by staff from the local supplier.
Target area (inside/outside)	Indoors.
How the coverage of the intervention was measured	Information on a series of basic demographic, travel, social and wealth indicators was collected from the selected homesteads, together with details on the use of ITNs and the coverage with IRS by each member of the homestead.
Coverage of household (full, selective/partial)	Full (assumed).
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	Not reported.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the 200 homesteads receiving IRS, 94% of the 600 individuals examined slept in a sprayed room. • Sleeping in a sprayed room reduced the risk of infection by 75% (95% CI: 73–76%). 															
Length of intervention, including number of rounds of spraying/application per year/season	Spraying was conducted between February and May of 2000 (assumed to be 1 round).															
Type of dwelling (e.g., fixed or temporary) and construction material of surfaces insecticides applied to (e.g., cement, brick or mud walls, canvas etc)	Not reported – only state homesteads.															
Time to start intervention after index case	Not reported.															
Human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, re-plastering of houses)	Not reported.															
COMPARISON																
Details of Comparison	No IRS.															
How the coverage of the comparison was measured	Information on a series of basic demographic, travel, social and wealth indicators was collected from the selected homesteads, together with details on the use of ITNs and the coverage with IRS by each member of the homestead.															
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction for the comparison	No IRS (or ITN) usage in control clusters.															
Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period and other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)	Not reported.															
OUTCOME 1																
Name	Malaria prevalence.															
Definition/ assessment metric	A finger prick blood sample was taken for the determination of P. falciparum antigen (Pf HRP-2) using the rapid whole blood immunochromatographic test (ICT Diagnostics, Amrad, Australia).															
Events	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Control</th> <th>IRS</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Overall</td> <td>76/600 (12.7%)</td> <td>18/561 (3.2%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Age <5</td> <td>17/172 (9.9%)</td> <td>4/147 (2.7%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Age 5-15</td> <td>30/205 (14.6%)</td> <td>9/193 (4.7%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Age >15</td> <td>29/223 (13%)</td> <td>5/221 (2.3%)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Control	IRS	Overall	76/600 (12.7%)	18/561 (3.2%)	Age <5	17/172 (9.9%)	4/147 (2.7%)	Age 5-15	30/205 (14.6%)	9/193 (4.7%)	Age >15	29/223 (13%)	5/221 (2.3%)
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Total (or unit time)	See above.															
Time of outcome assessment	One time point only: approx. two months post IRS.															
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The prevalence of P. falciparum infection in the 600 individuals in the 200 homesteads not covered by ITNs or IRS was 12.7%. • In the 200 homesteads receiving IRS, 94% of the 600 individuals examined slept in a sprayed room. 															

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sleeping in a sprayed room reduced the risk of infection by 75% (95% CI: 73–76%). <p>Stratification by age-group demonstrated that the effects were consistent across all ages.</p>																								
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COSTS																									
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Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Taking the best-case cost scenario for ITNs (economic analysis), the annual cost per person protected with ITNs remains more than twice the amount for IRS (US\$ 2.34 compared with US\$ 0.88). For ITNs, nearly two-thirds of the costs were attributed to the OCGs (62%), with the remaining 38% distributed equally between nets and insecticide. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In contrast, three quarters of the costs for IRS were consumed by the price of the insecticide. Opportunity costs for using existing personnel constituted < 5% of the total costs. Incorporating the estimated reductions in prevalence of infection from sleeping under an ITN (8%) or sleeping in a sprayed room (9.5%), the cost per infection case prevented in this population in July 2000 was estimated as US\$ 29 for ITNs and US\$ 9 for IRS. 																								
Time of cost assessment	A retrospective cost analysis of the vector control activities was undertaken in consultation with the Merlin team.																								
Resources needed/ used	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spray equipment and personnel. The economic costs included opportunity costs of using existing personnel and volunteers, and assumed the costs for capital items (bednets, spray pumps and megaphones) and training were annualized over their life expectancy and discounted at 3%. The life-expectancy of a bednet was assumed to be 5 years, and training was assumed to last 2 years before a refresher course would be required 																								
ADDITIONAL DATA																									
Unintended benefits	Not reported.																								
Harms	Not reported.																								
Other contextual information present/measured/reported (feasibility, acceptability, preferences/values, impact on equity)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ITN arm of the study: November 1999, Merlin established 32 organized community groups (OCGs) throughout Kisii and Gucha districts to act as conduits for the distribution of bednets and insecticide net treatments. The first batch of treated nets at the OCGs (160 nets in Kisii and 125 nets in Gucha) were sold at a highly subsidized price of Kshs. 50 (US\$ 0.64) to pregnant women and women with children < 5 years from 																								

	<p>‘poor’ homesteads identified by the local government civil administration.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All subsequent nets and treatments were sold at a combined price of Kshs. 350 (US\$ 4.47). • The ITNs were targeted at communities in the immediate vicinity of the OCGs. • However, the clusters chosen for this study involved no concurrent usage of ITNs in either group (IRS v Control).
Entomological outcomes measured (list)	Not reported.
Other	Not reported.
Source of funding	Financial support was provided by the Wellcome Trust as part of H.L.G.’s Research Career Development Fellowship (#055100).
Possible conflicts of interest	R.W.S. is in receipt of a Wellcome Trust Senior Research Fellowship (#033340).

Mashauri et al.

Study: Mashauri FM, Kinung'hi SM, Kaatano GM, Magesa SM, Kishamawe C, Mwanga JR, Nnko SE, Malima RC, Mero CN, Mboera LE. Impact of indoor residual spraying of lambda-cyhalothrin on malaria prevalence and anemia in an epidemic-prone district of Muleba, north-western Tanzania. <i>Am J Trop Med Hyg.</i> 2013 May;88(5):841-9. doi: 10.4269/ajtmh.12-0412. Epub 2013 Mar 4. PMID: 23458959; PMCID: PMC3752746.	
DESIGN	
Lead Author	Mashauri.
Publication year	2013.
Trial name	Not reported.
Other reports of this study (i.e., author, year, title, doi)	Not reported.
Time period study was conducted	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The first IRS round was carried out in May 2007 and the second round was carried out in January–February 2008. • The parasitological baseline survey was conducted before the start of the IRS intervention in May 2007. • Monitoring of the impact of the first IRS intervention was done in December 2007, 6 months post IRS intervention, and the monitoring of the impact of the second IRS intervention was evaluated in August 2008, 6 months post second IRS intervention.
Design	Controlled before and after study.
Eligibility criteria of participants	Only areas in Muleba district that were considered to be in an ‘epidemic’ were provided the IRS intervention.
Recruitment methods and rate	The IRS intervention in Muleba district was spatially and temporally targeted to villages prone to malaria epidemics to enhance the feasibility and lower cost. No details are provided as to the number of characteristics of the people who received the intervention.
Unit of allocation	Villages received the intervention and were stratified into 2 clusters, however sub-villages were used for outcome assessment.
Number of units	<u>Intervention</u> Villages: n=4 Sub-villages: n=8

	<u>Control</u> Villages: n=2 Sub-villages: n=4
Method of Randomization/matching or other	Not reported.
Number of clusters per arm	8 sub-villages (4 villages) in IRS arm. 4 sub-villages (2 villages) in control arm.
Adjustment for clustering	Not reported.
Cluster details (including buffer sizes between clusters, other indication of dilution effects)	The distance from selected IRS households to the nearest non-IRS households was >10 km.
Total trial participants per group/arm (including number of exclusions and reasons)	<u>Baseline Survey</u> IRS: n=818 Control: n=343 <u>Survey 1</u> IRS: n=754 Control: n=405 <u>Survey 2</u> IRS: n=719 Control: n=316
Outcomes assessed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria prevalence. • Anaemia. • Splenomegaly.
SETTING	
Country	North-Western Tanzania - Muleba district.
Site/s (town/settlements/region)	<u>Intervention</u> Ijumbi (Nshamba division) Nshambya (Nshamba division) Bushemba (Nshamba division) Ikondo ((Muleba division) <u>Control</u> Kibanga (Muleba division) Bunywambebe (Kamachumu division) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Muleba district (1 °45ç N, 31 °40ç E) is north-west of Tanzania with an area of 10739 km², of which 62% consists of Lake Victoria. • Most parts of the district lie at 1200–1500 m above sea level. • Administratively, the district has five divisions, namely Izigo, Kamachumu, Kimwani, Muleba, and Nshamba, 31 wards, and 134 registered villages. • It has a population of 425172 people with 85035 (20%) being children < 5 years of age. • The district has 36 health facilities, 3 of them being hospitals (Rubya, Kagondo, and Ndolage). • Others are health centers (4) and dispensaries (29).

Peak transmission season	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Muleba district experience an equatorial climate with two annual rainy seasons. • The short rains between October and December and the long rains between March and May. • Malaria transmission intensity in Muleba district follows this seasonal cycle with peaks in malaria incidence occurring 1–2 months following the month of highest rainfall.
Baseline malaria endemicity/ level of transmission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Muleba district is characterized by highland villages with unstable malaria transmission prone to malaria epidemics and lowland villages with stable malaria transmission and act as reservoirs for the highland villages. • Recent data indicate a mean prevalence of malaria infection of 49–53.3%, showing a marked increase in prevalence from 40% to 44% recorded 8 years earlier.
Study site (e.g., rural/ urban/ peri-urban/ level of urbanicity)	Not reported but makes mention of rural areas of Tanzania.
Vector species and vector profile details (i.e., behaviours, resistance profile/ susceptibility tests, parity, sporozoite rates and all other reported information)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Female Anopheles funestus mosquitoes were collected using mouth aspirators during the baseline survey. • A total of 320 adult female An. Funestus were tested for susceptibility to four commonly used insecticides, permethrin, deltamethrin, lambda-cyhalothrin, and DDT. • All tested female An. Funestus were fully susceptible to all four insecticides. • Anopheles Gambiai were used for quality control. • After 4 weeks of IRS, five houses were randomly selected from each of the four sprayed villages. • The other five unsprayed houses were randomly selected as control from each of the two unsprayed village. • The percentage KD60 and 24 hours mortality scores were above 95% and 80%, respectively, in all tested treated surfaces using a known susceptible strain of An. gambiae s.s. • These results indicate that IRS was properly done in different treated surfaces in the district.
Malaria species	Plasmodium falciparum was the most dominant malaria species accounting for (99.1%) of malaria infection in the district. Other species were P. malariae (0.6%) and P. ovale (0.3%).
PARTICIPANTS (those who received the intervention and on whom impact was measured)	
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants who received the intervention	No participant characteristics or demographics have been reported. However, the results were stratified into age groups (<5 years, 5-14 years and >15 years).
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants on whom the impact was measured.	Not reported.
Frequency of travel in the last month	Not reported.
INTERVENTION (Repeat if multiple arms)	
Insecticide brand, type, formulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lambda-cyhalothrin capsule suspension (ICON 10 CS). Following the President's Malaria Initiative (PMI), IRS intervention program. • Two rounds of IRS per year were organized, the first IRS round was carried out in May 2007 and the second round was carried out in

(including active ingredient), dose, duration (this includes timing and frequency of application)	January–February 2008, before the season of high transmission, which is May–July and November–January.
Insecticide application method(s) and strategy (e.g., spray, paint, treated materials, wallpaper)	Not reported.
Personnel applying the intervention	Not reported.
Target area (inside/outside)	Indoors.
How the coverage of the intervention was measured	After 4 weeks of IRS, five houses were randomly selected from each of the four sprayed villages.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	Full (assumed).
Coverage of household (full, selective/partial)	Not reported.
Length of intervention, including number of rounds of spraying/application per year/season	2 spray rounds. - The first round was carried out in May 2007. - The second round was carried out in January-February 2008.
Type of dwelling (e.g., fixed or temporary) and construction material of surfaces insecticides applied to (e.g., cement, brick or mud walls, canvas etc)	Cement, Mud, White/Painted and Wood surfaces were used for quality control tests.
Time to start intervention after index case	Not reported.
Human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, re-plastering of houses)	Not reported.
COMPARISON	
Details of Comparison	No IRS.
How the coverage of the comparison was measured	After 4 weeks of IRS, five unsprayed houses were randomly selected as control from each of the two unsprayed village.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction for the comparison	Not reported.
Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period and other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • After the 2006 malaria epidemics there were ITNs/LLINs distribution campaigns in the district. • Furthermore, the Tanzania government introduced ACTs as the first-line treatment of uncomplicated malaria. These two combined interventions might have played important role in malaria reduction in both IRS and non-IRS villages. • The survey on ITNs/LLINs ownership and usage would have provided additional information about whether the effects of IRS and ITNs/LLINs act synergistically in the intervention villages. • Without information on ITNs/LLINs coverage and ACTs access it is not possible to draw a firm conclusion that reduction of parasitological indices in IRS villages was only because of IRS intervention. • However, the results show that individuals living in IRS villages have an additional benefit of IRS intervention because malaria

	parasitological indices in IRS villages remain significantly lower than non-IRS villages.
OUTCOME 1	
Name	Malaria prevalence.
Definition/ assessment metric	In every survey, finger prick blood was collected from all consented selected participants for malaria parasites. A drop of blood was used to prepare thick and thin blood smears. Giemsa-stained blood smears were examined microscopically for malaria parasites by an experienced microscopist.
Events	<p><u>IRS</u> <u>PARASITEMIA PREVALENCE (%)</u></p> <p><u>Overall</u> Baseline = 20.1 (17.3-22.8) (N = 818) 1st follow up = 9.1 (7.0-11.1) (N=754) 2nd follow up = 6.6 (4.8-8.4) (N=719)</p> <p><u>Children <5</u> Baseline = 24.2 (18.2-30.2) (N=194) 1st follow up = 4.6 (0.7-8.5) (N=108) 2nd follow up = 4.3 (0.6-7.9) (N=117)</p> <p><u>Children 5-14</u> Baseline = 27.2 (21.9-32.5) (N=273) 1st follow up = 14.9 (11.1=18.6) (N=343) 2nd follow up = 11.2 (7.7-14.7) (N = 313)</p> <p><u>Adult => 15</u> Baseline = 15.7 (11.9-19.5) (N=351) 1st follow up = 5.9 (3.3-8.6) (N=303) 2nd follow up = 3.1 (1.1-5.1) (N=289)</p> <p><u>CONTROL</u> <u>Overall</u> Baseline = 34.8 (29.8-39.8) (N=348) 1st follow up = 16.3 (12.7-19.9) (N=405) 2nd follow up = 9.3 (6.1-12.3) (N=316)</p> <p><u>Children <5</u> Baseline = 38.5 (27.7-49.2) (N=78) 1st follow up = 24.3 (14.2-34.3) (N=70) 2nd follow up = 9.1 (0.7-18.9) (N=33)</p> <p><u>Children 5-14</u> Baseline = 46.9 (37.7-56.1) (N=113) 1st follow up = 24.7 (18.1-31.3) (N=166) 2nd follow up = 11.2 (6.6-15.8) (N=179)</p> <p><u>Adult => 15</u> Baseline = 24.2 (17.5-30.9) (N=157) 1st follow up = 4.7 (1.5-7.9) (N=169)</p>

	2 nd follow up = 6.7 (1.9-11.5) (N=104)
Total (or unit time)	See above.
Time of outcome assessment	Time point 1 was December 2007 – six months post IRS. Time point 2 was August 2008 – six months post second IRS.
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In IRS villages the overall parasitemia prevalence was 20.1% (95% CI: 17.3–22.8; N=818) at baseline was reduced to 6.6% (95% CI: 4.8–8.4; N=719) at second follow-up survey. • An overall reduction of 67.2% in all ages. • Children < 5 years of age had the highest parasitemia reduction from 24.1% (95% CI: 18.2–30.2; N = 194) at baseline to 4.3% (95% CI: 0.6–7.9; N = 117) at second follow-up survey an overall reduction 82.2%.
Effect type	OR.
OUTCOME 2	
Name	Anaemia.
Definition/ assessment metric	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In every survey, finger prick blood was collected from all consented selected participants for Hb examination. • Hemoglobin levels were examined using a digital hemoglobinometer (Hemo-cue EKF-diagnostic GmbH, Magdeburg, Germany). • Anemia was defined as Hb levels < 8 g/dL.
Events	<p><u>IRS</u></p> <p><u>ANAEMIA PREVALENCE (%)</u></p> <p><u>Overall</u></p> <p>Baseline = 31.7 (28.5-34.9) (N=804)</p> <p>1st follow up = 8.9 (6.9-10.3) (N=753)</p> <p>2nd follow up = 15.7 (13.0-18.3) (N=718)</p> <p><u>Children <5</u></p> <p>Baseline = 59 (52.1-65.9) (N=195)</p> <p>1st follow up = 25 (16.3-33.2) (N=10)</p> <p>2nd follow up = 37.5 (28.7-46.3) (N=117)</p> <p><u>Children 5-14</u></p> <p>Baseline = 28.5 (23.1-33.9) (N=270)</p> <p>1st follow up = 7.9 (5.0-10.7) (N=343)</p> <p>2nd follow up = 12.8 (9.1-16.5) (N=312)</p> <p><u>Adult => 15</u></p> <p>Baseline = 18.5 (14.5-22.6) (N=339)</p> <p>1st follow up = 4.0 (1.8-6.20) (N=302)</p> <p>2nd follow up = 9.7 (6.3-13.1) (N=289)</p> <p><u>CONTROL</u></p> <p><u>Overall</u></p> <p>Baseline = 38.2 (32.7-43.7) (N=303)</p> <p>1st follow up = 19.3 (15.4-23.1) (N=405)</p> <p>2nd follow up = 9.8 (6.5-13.1) (N=316)</p> <p><u>Children <5</u></p> <p>Baseline = 73.1 (63.3-82.9) (N=78)</p> <p>1st follow up = 53.7 (41.9-65.3) (N=70)</p>

	<p>2nd follow up = 30.3 (14.6-46) (N=33)</p> <p><u>Children 5-14</u> Baseline = 40.9 (31.7-50.11) (N=110) 1st follow up = 15.1 (9.6-20.5) (N=166) 2nd follow up = 11.2 (6.6-15.8) (N=179)</p> <p><u>Adult => 15</u> Baseline = 18.7 (11.6-25.8) (N=115) 1st follow up = 8.9 (4.6-13.2) (N=169) 2nd follow up = 1.0 (-0.9-2.9) (N=104)</p>
Total (or unit time)	See above.
Time of outcome assessment	Time point 1 was December 2007 – six months post IRS. Time point 2 was August 2008 – six months post second IRS.
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The overall anemia prevalence at baseline was 31.7% (95% CI: 28.5–34.9; N=804) was reduced to 15.7% (95% CI: 13.0–18.3; N=718) at second follow-up survey an overall reduction of 50.5%. • Furthermore, children 5–14 years of age had the highest reduction of anemia prevalence from 28.5% (95% CI: 23.1–33.9; N = 270) at baseline to 12.8% (95% CI: 9.1–16.5; N = 312) at second follow-up an overall reduction of 55.1%.
Effect type	OR.
COSTS	
Event/raw costs	Not reported.
Results	Not reported.
Time of cost assessment	Not reported.
Resources needed/ used	Spray equipment.
ADDITIONAL DATA	
Unintended benefits	After two rounds of IRS intervention splenomegaly was reduced to 0.8% (95% CI: 0.1–1.4; N = 719) an overall reduction of 75.8%. Children < 5 years of age had an overall splenomegaly reduction of 100% at second follow-up survey.
Harms	Not reported.
Other contextual information present/measured/reported) (feasibility, acceptability, preferences/values, impact on equity)	Not reported.
Entomological outcomes measured (list)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insecticide susceptibility tests. • Resistance status. • Contact cone bioassay.
Other	Not reported.
Source of funding	This study was supported by the U.S. President’s Malaria Initiative through Research Triangle Institute – International and the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare, of the United Republic of Tanzania. The sponsor had no role in the study design, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, or writing the manuscript.
Possible conflicts of interest	Not reported.

Ramachandra

Study: Ramachandra. T. Malaria control using indoor residual sprays in the Eastern Province of Afghanistan. Bull World Health Organ. 1951;3(4):639-61. PMID: 14821772; PMCID: PMC2554025.	
DESIGN	
Lead Author	T. Ramachandra.
Publication year	1951.
Trial name	Not reported.
Other reports of this study (i.e., author, year, title, doi)	Not reported.
Time period study was conducted	Mid-July 1949 and field observations were completed by the end of October 1949.
Design	Controlled Before and After.
Eligibility criteria of participants	All the selected villages were situated between the Alishing and Alingar rivers, just above their junction, in a total area of about 20 square miles (52 km ²).
Recruitment methods and rate	Not reported.
Unit of allocation	Villages in Laghman District.
Number of units	IRS n=11 Control n=13
Method of Randomization/ matching or other	Not reported.
Number of clusters per arm	IRS n=11 Control n=13
Adjustment for clustering	Not reported.
Cluster details (including buffer sizes between clusters, other indication of dilution effects)	Laghman being a well-populated area, it was not possible to select all sprayed villages sufficiently removed from unsprayed ones. In some cases the latter were within the effective flight range of mosquitos. It is not an impossibility that some infiltration could have taken place.
Total trial participants per group/arm (including number of exclusions and reasons)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A small-scale demonstration of malaria control by the use of DDT indoor residual sprays was carried out in Lagham District. • Thirteen villages with a total population of approximately 14,000 were selected. • Number of schoolboys in both sprayed and unsprayed villages. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sprayed villages: n=57 (age 6-9) - Control villages: n=24 (age 6-9)
Outcomes assessed	Malaria Prevalence.
SETTING	
Country	Afghanistan.
Site/s (town/settlements/region)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laghman District of the Eastern Province of Afghanistan. Situated between 34° 30' and 35° 00' N and 70° 00' and 70° 20' E. • All the selected villages were situated between the Alishing and Alingar rivers, just above their junction, in a total area of about 20 square miles (52 km²).
Peak transmission season	Chief malaria season was August, September, and October.
Baseline malaria endemicity/ level of transmission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are no recorded data regarding either the endemicity of malaria or the anopheles species prevalent in the area. • Pre-IRS results suggest a positive-parasite rate of 18.8%. • Malaria is hyperendemic in the entire area with childhood spleen-rates (age 2-9) of over 50% in almost all villages.

Study site (e.g., rural/ urban/ peri-urban/ level of urbanicity)	Not reported.
Vector species and vector profile details (i.e., behaviours, resistance profile/ susceptibility tests, parity, sporozoite rates and all other reported information)	<p>The following species of anopheles have been met during the study period of the survey:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Annularis - Culicifacies - Fluvialilis - Hyrcanus - Maculatus - Moghuliensis - Pulcherrimus - Splendidus - Stephensi - Subpictus - Superpictus - Turkhudi - Vagus <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adults of culicifacies and stephensi were the most abundant, being 42% and 34% of the total of all species collected. • Different villages have widely different proportions of the different vector species.
Malaria species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plasmodium falciparum infections numbered only 10 out of 111, while the bulk of infections (101) were with vivax one smear showing malariae. • In the post-operational survey of October the figures were: total number of smears examined, 482; number positive, 149; average cumulative parasite-rate 30.9%. • The relative prevalence of the species was vivax 50, falciparum 99, and malariae nil.
PARTICIPANTS (those who received the intervention and on whom impact was measured)	
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants who received the intervention	All households in the targeted areas received the IRS intervention (assumed).
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants on whom the impact was measured.	There are no details regarding who the impact was measured on.
Frequency of travel in the last month	Not reported.
INTERVENTION (Repeat if multiple arms)	
Insecticide brand, type, formulation (including active ingredient), dose, duration (this includes timing and frequency of application)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The villages were all sprayed between 1 and 15 August 1949 with DDT. • A small-scale demonstration of malaria control by the use of DDT indoor residual sprays was performed. • Two formulations of DDT,-DDT-Aromex2-soap emulsion and 50% water suspension of wettable powder, were used. • The emulsion was sprayed in two dosages, 200 mg per square foot (2.15 g per m²) and 112m²) mg per square foot (1.21g per and the wettable powder only at the latter dosage.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The intended final concentration was 5%, but in actual practice it was estimated that the strength was about 4.8%. • In Pashai-Demalah and Chalmati, the intended dosage was 112 mg per square foot, but it was estimated that the actual dosages were 61 and 73 mg per square foot (0.66 and 0.79 g per m²) only. • These two villages were given a second spraying on 1 and 2 October.
Insecticide application method(s) and strategy (e.g., spray, paint, treated materials, wallpaper)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stirrup pumps to which were fitted a well-designed nozzle giving a fanshaped spray (made by Galeazzi, Rome) were used. Galeazzi pressure sprayers were used during the second round with satisfactory results. • The usual method of preparing the mother emulsion by adding soap was found to lead to difficulties, including once a complete reversal of phase, so that a slight modification was adopted with extremely satisfactory results. • The modification consisted of taking only the DDT-Aromex solution to the field and adding the requisite quantity of the soap in the field to individual buckets at the time of preparing the final emulsion. The intended final concentration was 5%, but in actual practice it was estimated that the strength was about 4.8%. • Before the labourers visited the villages, they were trained in the requisite speed of spraying to get the intended work done. But it has to be stated that the intended dosages were perhaps slightly exceeded or diminished in actual practice in most of the villages, in all but two the variations being not too great. • In Pashai-Demalah and Chalmati, the intended dosage was 112 mg per square foot, but it was estimated that the actual dosages were 61 and 73 mg per square foot (0.66 and 0.79 g per m²) only. • These two villages were given a second spraying on 1 and 2 October.
Personnel applying the intervention	<p>Before the labourers visited the villages, they were trained in the requisite speed of spraying to get the intended work done.</p> <p>On the average daily labour employed consisted of 8 havildars (squad foremen) and 40 labourers. Each squad foreman had 5 labourers with him, four manning pumps and one for supply of materials.</p>
Target area (inside/outside)	All indoor surfaces, walls, as well roofs, as and all domestic articles, except cooking vessels, etc., were sprayed.
How the coverage of the intervention was measured	Six routine adult collecting stations were established in each village and timed weekly collections for 20 minutes were made in each station, commencing at 10 a.m.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	Full (assumed).
Coverage of household (full, selective/partial)	Not reported.
Length of intervention, including number of rounds of spraying/application per year/season	1 spray round for all villages from 23 rd July to 15 th August. 2 villages received a second round from 1 st -2 nd October.
Type of dwelling (e.g., fixed or temporary) and construction material of surfaces insecticides applied to (e.g., cement, brick or mud walls, canvas etc)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All houses are made of mud or of sundried bricks. Hardly 1% of houses have lime or cement plaster. • The surface of the walls is very rough and extremely absorbent. The roofs are all flat and made of logs of wood covered with twigs and leaves and overlaid with a thick coat of mud. Because of this

	<p>construction the lower side of the roofs presents a very large superficial area with numerous crevices and niches providing ideal resting-places for anophelines.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The plan of most of the houses, however small they may be, is based on an imitation of a fort. • There is a high rectangular mud wall on the outside with a single well-made door which leads into a large courtyard. • All the rooms of the house open into this courtyard, their number depending on the position and wealth of the owner. Often more than one family live in such a house with a common courtyard.
Time to start intervention after index case	Not reported.
Human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, re-plastering of houses)	During the months of March to October, the entire human population sleeps outdoors because of the oppressive heat.
COMPARISON	
Details of Comparison	No IRS.
How the coverage of the comparison was measured	Not reported.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction for the comparison	Not reported.
Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period and other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)	Not reported.
OUTCOME 1	
Name	Malaria prevalence.
Definition/ assessment metric	Not reported. Blood smears were taken (but methods were not reported) and a number of positive smears has been provided.
Events	<p><u>Positive parasite-rate for blood smears taken</u></p> <p><u>Pre-spraying (n=15 villages)</u> 111 / 590 (18.85)</p> <p><u>Post-spraying</u> <u>(IRS) (n=11 villages)</u> 340/548 (62%) <u>(Control) (n=13 villages)</u> 568/638 (89%)</p>
Total (or unit time)	See above.
Time of outcome assessment	Pre-operational survey in July and August of 1949. Post operational survey October 1949. Only one time point offered approx. one month post IRS.
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the pre-operational survey of July-August (table I) the average cumulative parasite-rate in 15 villages was 18.8% (111 positive smears out of 590 examined).

outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the post-operational survey of October the figures were: total number of smears examined, 482; number positive, 149; average cumulative parasite-rate 30.9%. • Of the 70 infants examined in unsprayed villages, 49 were positive giving an extremely high infant parasite-rate of 70.0%. • The average cumulative parasite-rate in the sprayed villages was only 10.6% as against 30.9% in unsprayed villages. While this difference is in itself significant, the childhood parasite-rate of unsprayed villages is only 30.9% when the infant parasite-rate is as high as 70.0%. • 72 infants examined in sprayed villages 6 showed parasites (infant parasite-rate 8.3 %) as against 49 out of 70 (rate 70.0%) in unsprayed villages. This difference is certainly highly significant, but the fact that there were still over 8 % infections.
Effect type	OR.
COSTS	
Event/raw costs	Not reported.
Results	Not reported.
Time of cost assessment	Not reported.
Resources needed/ used	Not reported.
ADDITIONAL DATA	
Unintended benefits	Not reported.
Harms	Not reported.
Other contextual information present/measured/reported) (feasibility, acceptability, preferences/values, impact on equity)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is one public dispensary in the area and the number of malaria cases and all cases treated for each month from Hamal (March-April) 1947. • The diagnosis is entirely on clinical grounds and the variations in the number of patients treated depend on many extraneous factors. • All the adverse factors now well known to influence such figures are exaggerated in Afghanistan and it is a moot question whether these data have any value at all. • There are no other morbidity data at all fit for recording, except the general observation made that in the middle of October every house in the unsprayed villages had at least 2-3 patients.
Entomological outcomes measured (list)	Vector prevalence/ density. Species identification knockdown.
Other	Not reported.
Source of funding	Not reported.
Possible conflicts of interest	Not reported.

Supplementary item 7 – Support for risk of bias judgments

Randomised controlled trials

Unique ID	1	Study ID	Loha 2019	Assessor	JCS
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	IRS	Comparator	No IRS	Source	
Outcome	Incidence of malaria (all ages)	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question		Response	Comments	
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		Y	The randomly selected clusters were numbered and equally randomized into the four arms following a computer-generated list using SPSS software. While the study is done in Ethiopia, randomization was done in Bergen in Norway. This was done to prevent selection bias by concealing the allocation sequence from the field researchers assigning villages to the four intervention groups until the moment of assignment.	
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		Y		
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?		N	House types were imbalanced between groups. This may be due to chance as not a substantial excess of differences between groups and not related to the outcome. Therefore, not necessarily suggestive of a problem with the randomisation process. Some concerns albeit minor.	
	Risk of bias judgement		Low		
Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?		Y	Prior to implementing the intervention and randomizing villages to arms, a baseline survey, mapping- and a pilot study were carried out to estimate an optimum sample size.	
	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?		NA	Not applicable.	

	1.b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?	Y	House types were imbalanced between groups but not individual participant characteristics. This may not be suggestive of differential identification or recruitment of participants.
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	Y	Due to the nature of the interventions, blinding of the study participants was not possible. Participants gave consent to have their houses sprayed.
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	Blinding was not possible
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	N	No deviations reported by authors.
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	Not applicable.
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	Not applicable.
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	ITT performed
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?	NA	Not applicable.
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	Data for all clusters available.
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	Y	Data available for all participants. Loss to follow-up less than 20%.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	Y	Evidence the result was not biased by missing outcome data. Loss to followup balanced across groups and less than 20% of total numbers.
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	Not applicable
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	

	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	The primary outcome measure was malaria incidence determined by the detection of <i>P. falciparum</i> or <i>P. vivax</i> by rapid diagnosis tests, if patients had a history of fever.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Participants were encouraged to attend health facilities for RDT if they had a fever, and their attendance was checked.
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	Yes, active and passive case detection. "Through weekly household visits, study participants with a fever or having a history of fever within the previous 48 h were given numbered identification cards and encouraged to present to the nearest health posts for testing and treatment. All persons with possible malaria were checked if they had actually visited the health post. In addition, the health centres and the hospital were regularly visited to find malaria cases that could have visited these health facilities without reporting to the field workers." It is likely the hospital staff were aware of participation in the study and thus that a trial was taking place if patients presenting with numbered identification cards.
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	Yes, active and passive case detection. "Through weekly household visits, study participants with a fever or having a history of fever within the previous 48 h were given numbered identification cards and encouraged to present to the nearest health posts for testing and treatment. All persons with possible malaria were checked if they had actually visited the health post. In addition, the health centres and the hospital were regularly visited to find malaria cases that could have visited these health facilities without reporting to the field workers." It is likely the hospital staff were aware of participation in the study if patients presenting with numbered identification cards.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	Y	Greater encouragement could be given to those in intervention groups with knowledge of the intervention received however, checks were completed to ensure all those presenting with fever attended the clinics for testing. Patients themselves may present more or less frequently to health facilities for testing with subjective feelings of illness (patients as initial assessors).
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	

	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	Report follows methods as stated in protocol.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	No evidence of multiple outcome assessments.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	Have subgrouped their data based on demographics, which is not unusual. Multiple reports of the same study noted.
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	Low	

Unique ID	2	Study ID	Loha 2019	Assessor	JCS
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	IRS	Comparator	No IRS	Source	
Outcome	Prevalence of anaemia (children under 5 years)	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question		Response	Comments	
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		Y	The randomly selected clusters were numbered and equally randomized into the four arms following a computer-generated list using SPSS software. While the study is done in Ethiopia, randomization was done in Bergen in Norway. This was done to prevent selection bias by concealing the	
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		Y		

			allocation sequence from the field researchers assigning villages to the four intervention groups until the moment of assignment.
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	House types were imbalanced between groups. This may be due to chance as not a substantial excess of differences between groups and not related to the outcome. Therefore, not necessarily suggestive of a problem with the randomisation process. Some concerns albeit minor.
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?	Y	Prior to implementing the intervention and randomizing villages to arms, a baseline survey, mapping- and a pilot study were carried out to estimate an optimum sample size.
	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?	NA	Not applicable.
	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?	Y	House types were imbalanced between groups but not individual participant characteristics. This is not suggestive of differential identification or recruitment of participants.
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Low
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	Y	Due to the nature of the interventions, blinding of the study participants was not possible. Participants gave consent to have their houses sprayed.
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	Blinding was not possible
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	N	No deviations reported by authors.
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	Not applicable.
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	Not applicable.
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	ITT performed

	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?	NA	Not applicable.
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Likely given nature of intervention ITT was used
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	Data for all clusters available.
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	Y	Data available for all participants. Loss to follow-up less than 20%.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	Y	No evidence regarding bias however, loss to followup balanced across groups.
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	Not applicable
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	The primary outcome measure was malaria incidence determined by the detection of P. falciparum or P. vivax by rapid diagnosis tests, if patients had a history of fever.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Participants were encouraged to attend health facilities for RDT if they had a fever, and their attendance was checked.
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	Yes, active and passive case detection. "Through weekly household visits, study participants with a fever or having a history of fever within the previous 48 h were given numbered identification cards and encouraged to present to the nearest health posts for testing and treatment. All persons with possible malaria were checked if they had actually visited the health post. In addition, the health centres and the hospital were regularly visited to find malaria cases that could have visited these health facilities without reporting to the field workers." It is likely the hospital staff were aware of participation in the study and thus that a trial was taking place

			if patients presenting with numbered identification cards.
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	Yes, active and passive case detection. "Through weekly household visits, study participants with a fever or having a history of fever within the previous 48 h were given numbered identification cards and encouraged to present to the nearest health posts for testing and treatment. All persons with possible malaria were checked if they had actually visited the health post. In addition, the health centres and the hospital were regularly visited to find malaria cases that could have visited these health facilities without reporting to the field workers." It is likely the hospital staff were aware of participation in the study if patients presenting with numbered identification cards.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	Y	Greater encouragement could be given to those in intervention groups with knowledge of the intervention received however, checks were completed to ensure all those presenting with fever attended the clinics for testing. Patients themselves may present more or less frequently to health facilities for testing with subjective feelings of illness (patients as initial assessors).
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	Report follows methods as stated in protocol.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	No evidence of multiple outcome assessments.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	Have subgrouped their data based on demographics, which is not unusual. Multiple reports of the same study noted.
	Risk of bias judgement		
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	Low	

Unique ID	3	Study ID	Rowland 2000	Assessor	JCS
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Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	IRS	Comparator	No IRS	Source	
Outcome	Incidence of malaria (all ages)	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question		Response	Comments	
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		Y	"The study area was mapped by NIMRT and divided into nine sectors of approximately equal population size and area. Each sector was assigned at random to untreated, WP, or SC spraying in replicates of three." No information regarding allocation concealment provided by study authors.	
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		NI		
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?		NI	"Two or three sentinel villages totalling 2000 population were selected from each sector for disease and entomological monitoring and enumerated. The population and number of houses in sentinel villages were, respectively, 6017 and 1206 in WP sectors, 5677 and 1124 in SC sectors, and 6567 and 1328 in control sectors; hence sentinel villages were consistent between treatment groups. Sentinel villages were chosen carefully so that the distance to villages in a different treatment group was at least 1.5 km". The sentinel villages were selected from within the randomised villages. No baseline characteristics are presented except for numbers. Numbers are similar between groups however, more information needed.	
	Risk of bias judgement		Some concerns		
Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?		NI	The villages were mapped however, no information is provided about whether participants were recruited or identified prior to allocation. It is unclear whether consent was given by village elders before or after villages were allocated.	

of participants	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?	Unable to determine this information given.	
	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?	NI	No baseline characteristics of participants were provided.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	Some concerns
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	Y	Village elders gave consent for the trial and no report of blinding participants or deception.
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	Based on the nature of the intervention, participants and carers were likely aware they were receiving IRS.
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	No mention of ITT analysis. A cross section of participants were selected for outcome assessment and these were the only participants assessed. There was no mention of how participants were selected (e.g., randomly) other than that they were selected from sentinel villages.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?	NI	Unclear whether this was likely to influence the results or whether there were deviations.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	The authors have only measured the outcome in a cross section of participants within selected sentinel villages within each cluster randomised. All clusters are represented.

	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	The authors have only measured the outcome in a cross section of participants within selected sentinel villages.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	N	No evidence that the results were not biased.
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NI	There is no evidence that missing data was related to its true value however, as cross sections selected for outcome assessment were not selected randomly data may not necessarily be missing at random.
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	The survey teams visited 400 houses in each sector every fortnight. Any member of a household reporting fever during the previous three days had a blood smear taken.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Unlikely to have differed between groups as fever and blood smear are objective measures.
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	Those visiting households and taking smears were aware that the trial was taking place.
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	Given the nature of the intervention and lack of information reported by authors regarding blinding, the outcome assessors were likely aware, or could become aware, of the assigned intervention.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	Given this was a cross-sectional survey and objective measures were used, it is unlikely that knowledge of the assigned intervention would have impacted the outcome assessment.
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No protocol but data was analysed in accordance with methods and objectives of the study
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	No evidence of multiple outcome assessments.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	No evidence of data dredging.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	

Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	
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Unique ID	4	Study ID	Rowland 2000	Assessor	JCS
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	IRS	Comparator	No IRS	Source	
Outcome	Prevalence of malaria (children aged 5-15 years)	Results		Weight	1

Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"The study area was mapped by NIMRT and divided into nine sectors of approximately equal population size and area. Each sector was assigned at random to untreated, WP, or SC spraying in replicates of three." No information regarding allocation concealment provided by study authors.
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	NI	
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	NI	"Two or three sentinel villages totalling 2000 population were selected from each sector for disease and entomological monitoring and enumerated. The population and number of houses in sentinel villages were, respectively, 6017 and 1206 in WP sectors, 5677 and 1124 in SC sectors, and 6567 and 1328 in control sectors; hence sentinel villages were consistent between treatment groups. Sentinel villages were chosen carefully so that the distance to villages in a different treatment group was at least 1.5 km". The sentinel villages were selected from within the randomised villages. No baseline characteristics are presented except for numbers. Numbers are similar between

			groups however, more information needed.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?	NI	The villages were mapped however, no information is provided about whether participants were recruited or identified prior to allocation. It is unclear whether consent was given by village elders before or after villages were allocated.
	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?	NI	Unable to determine this from the information given.
	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?	NI	No baseline characteristics of participants were provided.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	Some concerns
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	Y	Village elders gave consent for the trial and no report of blinding participants or deception.
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	Based on the nature of the intervention, participants and carers were likely aware they were receiving IRS.
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	No mention of ITT analysis. A cross section of children were selected from selected schools within sentinel villages. There was no mention of how participants were selected (e.g., randomly).
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?	NI	Unclear whether this was likely to influence the results or whether there were deviations.

	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	The authors have only measured the outcome in a cross section of participants within selected sentinel villages within each cluster randomised. All clusters are represented.
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	The authors have only measured the outcome in a cross section of participants within selected sentinel villages.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	N	No evidence that the results were not biased.
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NI	There is no evidence that missing data was related to its true value however, as cross sections selected for outcome assessment were not selected randomly data may not necessarily be missing at random.
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	The survey teams visited 400 houses in each sector every fortnight. Any member of a household reporting fever during the previous three days had a blood smear taken.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Unlikely to have differed between groups as fever and blood smear are objective measures.
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	Those visiting households and taking smears were aware that the trial was taking place.
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	Given the nature of the intervention and lack of information reported by authors regarding blinding, the outcome assessors were likely aware, or could become aware, of the assigned intervention.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	Given this was a cross-sectional survey and objective measures were used, it is unlikely that knowledge of the assigned intervention would have impacted the outcome assessment.
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No protocol but data was analysed in accordance with methods and objectives of the study

	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	No evidence of multiple outcome assessments.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	No evidence of data dredging.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	5	Study ID	Curtis 1998	Assessor	JCS
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	IRS	Comparator	No IRS	Source	
Outcome	Prevalence of malaria (children under 6 years, active)	Results		Weight	1

Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	NI	Generation of random allocation sequence was not described. Baseline surveys indicated no difference between villages in baseline data on vector populations or malaria incidence prior to randomisation and as such, stratification of the villages prior to randomisation was not required. No information provided regarding allocation concealment.
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	NI	
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	NI	Authors suggest that there were no differences prior to randomisation but have not reported information following randomisation.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	

Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?	Y	Yes, some baseline data were collected during 1995, with no significant differences found between villages in the baseline data on vector populations and malaria incidence. This suggests identification of participants prior to randomisation of clusters.
	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?	NA	Not applicable.
	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?	NI	No baseline characteristics of participants were provided.
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Low
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	Y	Agreement to the trial was given after consultations with village authorities and mass meetings in each of the 12 villages. The inhabitants of those villages which did not receive nets during the trial were told that they would receive them at the end of it. Clearance, especially for the use of chlorproguanil dapsone, was given by the Ethical Committee of the Tanzanian National Institute for Medical Research. This indicates participants were aware they were in a trial.
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	Based on the nature of the intervention, participants and carers were likely aware they were receiving IRS.
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Modified ITT based on Cochrane's definition. Data missing at random and therefore modified ITT considered.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse	NA	Not applicable.

	participants in the group to which they were randomized ?		
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	N	The interventions were introduced in 6 of the villages in December 1995 but, owing to logistical problems, spraying and provision of nets was delayed in two until February 1996. Until these villages had been treated, data from them were excluded from the postintervention data presented.
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	The authors have only collected this data from 60 randomly selected children from each village.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	Y	Data missing at random and therefore unlikely to influence results.
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	Missingness unlikely to depend on the outcomes true value as missing at random.
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Cross sectional surveys and malaria parastemia confirmed through blood slides.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Randomly selected participants for blood slides.
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	Outcome assessors were taking blood surveys.
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	Outcome assessors were patients encouraged to attend a health assistant and the health assistant measuring temperature and blood. No report of blinding in the trial and due to the nature of the intervention, participants as outcome assessors would be aware.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	Confirmed by blood slide.
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	

Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No protocol but data was analysed in accordance with methods and objectives of the study
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	No evidence of multiple outcome assessments.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	No evidence of data dredging.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	

Unique ID	6	Study ID	Curtis 1998	Assessor	JCS
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	IRS	Comparator	No IRS	Source	
Outcome	Prevalence of malaria (children under 6 years, passive)	Results		Weight	1

Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	NI	Generation of random allocation sequence was not described. Baseline surveys indicated no difference between villages in baseline data or vector populations prior to randomisation and as such, stratification of the villages prior to randomisation was not required. No information provided regarding allocation concealment.
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	NI	
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	NI	Authors suggest that there were no differences prior to randomisation but have not reported information following randomisation.

	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?	Y	Yes, some baseline data were collected during 1995, with no significant differences found between villages in the baseline data on vector populations and malaria incidence. This suggests identification of participants prior to randomisation of clusters.
	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?	NA	Not applicable.
	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?	NI	No baseline characteristics of participants were provided.
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Low
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	Y	Agreement to the trial was given after consultations with village authorities and mass meetings in each of the 12 villages. The inhabitants of those villages which did not receive nets during the trial were told that they would receive them at the end of it. Clearance, especially for the use of chlorproguanil dapsone, was given by the Ethical Committee of the Tanzanian National Institute for Medical Research. This indicates participants were aware they were in a trial.
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	Based on the nature of the intervention, participants and carers were likely aware they were receiving IRS.
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	Passive case detection and therefore analysis of those attending clinics only.

	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?	NI	Unclear whether this was likely to influence the results or whether there were deviations.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	N	The interventions were introduced in 6 of the villages in December 1995 but, owing to logistical problems, spraying and provision of nets was delayed in two until February 1996. Until these villages had been treated, data from them were excluded from the postintervention data presented.
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	The authors have only collected data from those that attended health clinics.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	N	Data not missing at random and may be systematic. Patients visited health assistant if they felt they were unwell.
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NI	Difficult to determine if missingness was related to the outcomes true value in this context.
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Subjective assessment first and then confirmed with blood slide
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Encouragement to attend health check through passive surveillance could systematically impact outcome assessment however, unlikely. Participants required fever and positive blood slide.
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	Outcome assessors were patients encouraged to attend a health assistant and the health assistant measuring temperature and blood.
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	Outcome assessors were patients encouraged to attend a health assistant and the health assistant measuring temperature and blood. No report of blinding in the trial and due to the nature of the intervention, participants as outcome assessors would be aware.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	Y	Confirmed by blood slide. May be more/less likely to attend health check if asymptomatic/ symptomatic depending on knowledge of intervention received.
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	

	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No protocol but data was analysed in accordance with methods and objectives of the study
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	No evidence of multiple outcome assessments.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	No evidence of data dredging.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	7	Study ID	Curtis 1998	Assessor	JCS
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	IRS	Comparator	No IRS	Source	
Outcome	Prevalence of malaria (children older than 6 years, passive)	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response		Comments	
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	NI		Generation of random allocation sequence was not described. Baseline surveys indicated no difference between villages in baseline data or vector populations prior to randomisation and as such, stratification of the villages prior to randomisation was not required. No information provided regarding allocation concealment.	
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	NI			

	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	NI	Authors suggest that there were no differences prior to randomisation but have not reported information following randomisation.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?	Y	Yes, some baseline data were collected during 1995 , with no significant differences found between villages in the baseline data on vector populations and malaria incidence. This suggests identification of participants prior to randomisation of clusters.
	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?	NA	Not applicable
	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?	NI	No baseline characteristics of participants were provided.
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Low
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	Y	Agreement to the trial was given after consultations with village authorities and mass meetings in each of the 12 villages. The inhabitants of those villages which did not receive nets during the trial were told that they would receive them at the end of it. Clearance, especially for the use of chlorproguanil dapsone, was given by the Ethical Committee of the Tanzanian National Institute for Medical Research. This indicates participants were aware they were in a trial.
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	Based on the nature of the intervention, participants and carers were likely aware they were receiving IRS.
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.

	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	Passive case detection and therefore analysis of those attending clinics only.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?	NI	Unclear whether this was likely to influence the results or whether there were deviations.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	N	The interventions were introduced in 6 of the villages in December 1995 but, owing to logistical problems, spraying and provision of nets was delayed in two until February 1996. Until these villages had been treated, data from them were excluded from the postintervention data presented.
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	The authors have only collected data from those that attended health clinics.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	N	Data not missing at random and may be systematic. Patients visited health assistant if they felt they were unwell.
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NI	Difficult to determine if missingness was related to the outcomes true value in this context.
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Subjective assessment first and then confirmed with blood slide
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Encouragement to attend health check through passive surveillance could systematically impact outcome assessment however, unlikely. Participants required fever and positive blood slide.
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	Outcome assessors were patients encouraged to attend a health assistant and the health assistant measuring temperature and blood.
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	Outcome assessors were patients encouraged to attend a health assistant and the health assistant measuring temperature and blood. No report of blinding in the trial and due to the nature of the intervention, participants as outcome assessors would be aware.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	Y	Confirmed by blood slide. May be more/less likely to attend health check if asymptomatic/ symptomatic depending on knowledge of intervention received.

	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No protocol but data was analysed in accordance with methods and objectives of the study
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	No evidence of multiple outcome assessments.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	No evidence of data dredging.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	8	Study ID	Curtis 1998	Assessor	JCS
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	IRS	Comparator	No IRS	Source	
Outcome	Prevalence of anaemia (children under 6 years, active)	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question		Response	Comments	
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		NI	Generation of random allocation sequence was not described. Baseline surveys indicated no difference between villages in baseline data or vector populations prior to randomisation and as such, stratification of	
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were		NI		

	enrolled and assigned to interventions?		the villages prior to randomisation was not required. No information provided regarding allocation concealment.
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	NI	Authors suggest that there were no differences prior to randomisation but have not reported information following randomisation.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?	Y	Yes, some baseline data were collected during 1995 , with no significant differences found between villages in the baseline data on vector populations and malaria incidence. This suggests identification of participants prior to randomisation of clusters.
	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?	NA	Not applicable.
	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?	NI	No baseline characteristics of participants were provided.
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Low
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	Y	Agreement to the trial was given after consultations with village authorities and mass meetings in each of the 12 villages. The inhabitants of those villages which did not receive nets during the trial were told that they would receive them at the end of it. Clearance, especially for the use of chlorproguanil dapsone, was given by the Ethical Committee of the Tanzanian National Institute for Medical Research. This indicates participants were aware they were in a trial.
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	Based on the nature of the intervention, participants and carers were likely aware they were receiving IRS.
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.

	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Modified ITT based on Cochrane's definition. Data missing at random and therefore modified ITT considered.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?	NA	Not applicable.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	N	The interventions were introduced in 6 of the villages in December 1995 but, owing to logistical problems, spraying and provision of nets was delayed in two until February 1996. Until these villages had been treated, data from them were excluded from the postintervention data presented.
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	The authors have only collected this data from 60 randomly selected children from each village.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	Y	Data missing at random and therefore unlikely to influence results.
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	Missingness unlikely to depend on the outcomes true value as missing at random.
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Cross sectional surveys and malaria parastemia confirmed through blood slides.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Randomly selected participants for blood slides.
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	Outcome assessors were taking blood surveys.
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	Outcome assessors were patients encouraged to attend a health assistant and the health assistant measuring temperature and blood. No report of blinding in the trial and due to the nature of the intervention, participants as outcome assessors would be aware.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have	N	Confirmed by blood slide.

	been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No protocol but data was analysed in accordance with methods and objectives of the study
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	No evidence of multiple outcome assessments.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	No evidence of data dredging.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	

Unique ID	9	Study ID	Mirsa 1999	Assessor	JCS
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	IRS	Comparator	No IRS	Source	
Outcome	Incidence of malaria (all ages)	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question		Response	Comments	
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		Y	Each group was randomized between the two interventions and control by public drawing of lots. No report of allocation concealment however, public drawing of	
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were		Y		

	enrolled and assigned to interventions?		lots implies there was no knowledge of the sequence prior to assignment.
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	NI	No baseline characteristics provided
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?	Y	Mass surveys in September 1996 (peak transmission season) in 45 villages showed a mean prevalence of 2.2% malaria parasitaemia. Because of the low prevalence and large variation between villages, 42 villages in each arm were required for the trial to have a power of 80% to detect a minimum difference of 25% between IRS and ITNs.
	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?	NA	Not applicable.
	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?	NI	No baseline characteristics of participants were provided.
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Low
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	Y	Assignment to intervention was public.
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	Likely due to nature of intervention, public lottery and assignment of villages where participants live.
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	NI	In this trial the majority of houses were fully sprayed and refusals were minimal. Deviations/ switches not reported.
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	In large villages only 150-169 households were included for data collection. A local person from each village was recruited to be the field worker. Authors do not report

			how these households were selected. No mention of ITT analysis.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?	NI	Unclear whether this was likely to influence the results or whether there were deviations.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	All clusters included
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	Cross section of participants (from selected households in larger villages) followed up.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	N	No evidence that the results were not biased.
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NI	There is no evidence that missing data was related to its true value however, as cross sections selected for outcome assessment were not selected randomly data may not necessarily be missing at random.
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Cross sectional surveys and malaria parastemia confirmed through blood slides.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Unlikely to have differed between groups as fever and blood smear are objective measures.
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	Those visiting households and taking smears were aware that the trial was taking place.
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	Given the nature of the intervention and lack of information reported by authors regarding blinding, the outcome assessors were likely aware, or could become aware, of the assigned intervention.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	Given this was a cross-sectional survey and objective measures were used, it is unlikely that knowledge of the assigned intervention would have impacted the outcome assessment.
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in selection of the	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was	NI	No protocol but data was analysed in accordance with methods and objectives of the study

reported result	finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?		
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	No evidence of multiple outcome assessments.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	No evidence of data dredging.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	10	Study ID	Charlwood 2001	Assessor	JCS
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	IRS	Comparator	No IRS	Source	
Outcome	incidence malaria (all ages)	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question		Response	Comments	
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		NI	Generation of random allocation sequence was not described. No information provided regarding allocation concealment.	
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		NI		
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?		Y	No characteristics reported outside population and village characteristics. More villages, huts, and participants in the intervention group.	
	Risk of bias judgement		High		
Bias arising from the timing of identification	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?		NI	No report of participants being identified prior to randomisation. Only consideration of camps. "The two largest camps, with populations over 20 000 were excluded	

n or recruitment of participants			from the experiment. Of the remainder most are isolated, but some consist of pairs or groups of three camps, which utilise the same clinics. These were treated as single units from the parasitological point of view and were randomly allocated to intervention (spraying all buildings with malathion) or control (unsprayed) groups".
	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?	NI	Unable to determine this from the information given.
	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?	NI	No baseline characteristics of participants were provided.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	Some concerns
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	NI	Due to the nature of the interventions, blinding of the study participants was not possible. No information regarding consent and IRS was offered in the years previous to the study and therefore it is difficult to determine if participants were aware they were in a trial.
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	Based on the nature of the intervention, participants and carers were likely aware they were receiving IRS.
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	Passive case detection and therefore analysis of those attending clinics only.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?	NI	Unclear whether this was likely to influence the results or whether there were deviations.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	All clusters included
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	The authors have only collected data from those that attended health clinics.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	N	Data not missing at random and may be systematic. Patients visited camp clinic.
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NI	Difficult to determine if missingness was related to the outcomes true value in this context.
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Passive case detection was standardised between camps so that all suspected malaria patients attending the clinics had blood slides taken.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Unlikely to have differed between groups as symptomatic and blood smear are objective measures.
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	Outcome assessors were taking blood samples for all suspected malaria patients. It is likely they were aware of the trial.
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	Given the nature of the intervention and lack of information reported by authors regarding blinding, the outcome assessors were likely aware, or could become aware, of the assigned intervention.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	Y	Confirmed by blood slide. May be more/less likely to attend health check if asymptomatic/ symptomatic depending on knowledge of intervention received.
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No protocol but data was analysed in accordance with methods and objectives of the study
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	No evidence of multiple outcome assessments.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	No evidence of data dredging.

	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	11	Study ID	Charlwood 2001	Assessor	JCS
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	IRS	Comparator	No IRS	Source	
Outcome	incidence malaria (under 5)	Results		Weight	1

Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	NI	Generation of random allocation sequence was not described. No information provided regarding allocation concealment.
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	NI	
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	Y	No characteristics reported outside population and village characteristics. More villages, huts, and participants in the intervention group.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?	NI	No report of participants being identified prior to randomisation. Only consideration of camps. "The two largest camps, with populations over 20 000 were excluded from the experiment. Of the remainder most are isolated, but some consist of pairs or groups of three camps, which utilise the same clinics. These were treated as single units from the parasitological point of view and were randomly allocated to intervention (spraying all buildings with malathion) or control (unsprayed) groups".

	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?	NA	Unable to determine this from the information given.
	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?	NI	No baseline characteristics of participants were provided.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	Some concerns
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	NI	Due to the nature of the interventions, blinding of the study participants was not possible. No information regarding consent and IRS was offered in the years previous to the study and therefore it is difficult to determine if participants were aware they were in a trial.
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	Based on the nature of the intervention, participants and carers were likely aware they were receiving IRS.
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	Passive case detection and therefore analysis of those attending clinics only.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?	NI	Unclear whether this was likely to influence the results or whether there were deviations.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	All clusters included
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	The authors have only collected data from those that attended health clinics.

	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	N	Data not missing at random and may be systematic. Patients visited camp clinic.
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NI	Difficult to determine if missingness was related to the outcomes true value in this context.
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Passive case detection was standardised between camps so that all suspected malaria patients attending the clinics had blood slides taken.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Unlikely to have differed between groups as symptomatic and blood smear are objective measures.
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	Outcome assessors were taking blood samples for all suspected malaria patients. It is likely they were aware of the trial.
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	Given the nature of the intervention and lack of information reported by authors regarding blinding, the outcome assessors were likely aware, or could become aware, of the assigned intervention.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	Y	Confirmed by blood slide. May be more/less likely to attend health check if asymptomatic/ symptomatic depending on knowledge of intervention received.
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No protocol but data was analysed in accordance with methods and objectives of the study
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	No evidence of multiple outcome assessments.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	No evidence of data dredging.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	12	Study ID	Charlwood 2001	Assessor	JCS
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	IRS	Comparator	No IRS	Source	
Outcome	Incidence all-cause mortality (all ages)	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question		Response	Comments	
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		NI	Generation of random allocation sequence was not described. No information provided regarding allocation concealment.	
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		NI		
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?		Y	No characteristics reported outside population and village characteristics. More villages, huts, and participants in the intervention group.	
	Risk of bias judgement		High		
Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?		NI	No report of participants being identified prior to randomisation. Only consideration of camps. "The two largest camps, with populations over 20 000 were excluded from the experiment. Of the remainder most are isolated, but some consist of pairs or groups of three camps, which utilise the same clinics. These were treated as single units from the parasitological point of view and were randomly allocated to intervention (spraying all buildings with malathion) or control (unsprayed) groups".	
	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?		NA	Unable to determine this from the information given.	

	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?	NI	No baseline characteristics of participants were provided.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	Some concerns
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	NI	Due to the nature of the interventions, blinding of the study participants was not possible. No information regarding consent and IRS was offered in the years previous to the study and therefore it is difficult to determine if participants were aware they were in a trial.
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	Based on the nature of the intervention, participants and carers were likely aware they were receiving IRS.
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	Passive case detection and therefore analysis of those attending clinics only.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?	NI	Unclear whether this was likely to influence the results or whether there were deviations.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	All clusters included
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	NI	No information provided by authors regarding how mortality data was collected
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	N	No evidence that the results were not biased.
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	N	

	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Objective outcome - death
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Unlikely to have differed between groups as objective.
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	Unclear who the outcome assessors were or whether they were aware of the trial.
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	Given the nature of the intervention and lack of information reported by authors regarding blinding, the outcome assessors were likely aware, or could become aware, of the assigned intervention.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	Unlikely knowledge of the assigned intervention would impact death but unclear how it was measured.
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No protocol but data was analysed in accordance with methods and objectives of the study
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	No evidence of multiple outcome assessments.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	No evidence of data dredging.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	13	Study ID	Charlwood 2001	Assessor	JCS
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Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	IRS	Comparator	No IRS	Source	
Outcome	Incidence all-cause mortality (under 5)	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question		Response	Comments	
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		NI	Generation of random allocation sequence was not described. No information provided regarding allocation concealment.	
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		NI		
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?		Y	No characteristics reported outside population and village characteristics. More villages, huts, and participants in the intervention group.	
	Risk of bias judgement		High		
Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?		NI	No report of participants being identified prior to randomisation. Only consideration of camps. "The two largest camps, with populations over 20 000 were excluded from the experiment. Of the remainder most are isolated, but some consist of pairs or groups of three camps, which utilise the same clinics. These were treated as single units from the parasitological point of view and were randomly allocated to intervention (spraying all buildings with malathion) or control (unsprayed) groups".	
	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?		NI	Unable to determine this from the information given.	
	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?		NI	No baseline characteristics of participants were provided.	

	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	Some concerns
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	NI	Due to the nature of the interventions, blinding of the study participants was not possible. No information regarding consent and IRS was offered in the years previous to the study and therefore it is difficult to determine if participants were aware they were in a trial.
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	Based on the nature of the intervention, participants and carers were likely aware they were receiving IRS.
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NI	No information was provided by authors about deviations to the intervention.
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	Passive case detection and therefore analysis of those attending clinics only.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?	NI	Unclear whether this was likely to influence the results or whether there were deviations.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	All clusters included
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	NI	No information provided by authors regarding how mortality data was collected
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	N	No evidence that the results were not biased.
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	N	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	

Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Objective outcome - death
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Unlikely to have differed between groups as objective.
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	Unclear who the outcome assessors were or whether they were aware of the trial.
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	Given the nature of the intervention and lack of information reported by authors regarding blinding, the outcome assessors were likely aware, or could become aware, of the assigned intervention.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	Unlikely knowledge of the assigned intervention would impact death but unclear how it was measured.
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No protocol but data was analysed in accordance with methods and objectives of the study
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	No evidence of multiple outcome assessments.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	No evidence of data dredging.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Risk of Bias Non-randomised Studies

Gunasekaran

Signalling questions	Description	Response options
Bias due to confounding		
<p>1.1 Is there potential for confounding of the effect of intervention in this study? If N/PN to 1.1: the study can be considered to be at low risk of bias due to confounding and no further signalling questions need be considered If Y/PY to 1.1: determine whether there is a need to assess time-varying confounding:</p>	<p>Yes, there is potential for confounding and confounders were not considered by authors.</p>	<p>Y</p>
<p>1.2. Was the analysis based on splitting participants' follow up time according to intervention received? If N/PN, answer questions relating to baseline confounding (1.4 to 1.6) If Y/PY, go to question 1.3.</p>	<p>No, the analysis was not based on splitting of follow-up time based on the intervention received.</p>	<p>N</p>
<p>1.3. Were intervention discontinuations or switches likely to be related to factors that are prognostic for the outcome? If N/PN, answer questions relating to baseline confounding (1.4 to 1.6) If Y/PY, answer questions relating to both baseline and time-varying confounding (1.7 and 1.8)</p>	<p>Not applicable.</p>	<p>NA</p>
Questions relating to baseline confounding only		
<p>1.4. Did the authors use an appropriate analysis method that controlled for all the important confounding domains?</p>	<p>No, there were no confounding factors identified, or adjusted for in the analysis of the data by authors. For this systematic review, raw data was extracted from primary studies and not adjusted for confounding.</p>	<p>N</p>

1.5. If Y/PY to 1.4: Were confounding domains that were controlled for measured validly and reliably by the variables available in this study?	Not applicable.	NA
1.6. Did the authors control for any post-intervention variables that could have been affected by the intervention?	No.	N
Questions relating to baseline and time-varying confounding		
1.7. Did the authors use an appropriate analysis method that controlled for all the important confounding domains and for time-varying confounding?	Not applicable.	NA
1.8. If Y/PY to 1.7: Were confounding domains that were controlled for measured validly and reliably by the variables available in this study?	Not applicable.	NA
Risk of bias judgement	Serious.	Serious
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to confounding?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Unpredictable

Bias in selection of participants into the study		
2.1. Was selection of participants into the study (or into the analysis) based on participant characteristics observed after the start of intervention? If N/PN to 2.1: go to 2.4	No. Selection of participants was based on districts receiving IRS and households sprayed. Those that were febrile and reported to one of the specified health clinics had outcomes measured.	N
2.2. If Y/PY to 2.1: Were the post-intervention variables that influenced selection likely to be associated with intervention?	Not applicable.	NA
2.3 If Y/PY to 2.2: Were the post-intervention variables that influenced selection likely to be influenced by the outcome or a cause of the outcome?	Not applicable.	NA

2.4. Do start of follow-up and start of intervention coincide for most participants?	Yes.	Y
2.5. If Y/PY to 2.2 and 2.3, or N/PN to 2.4: Were adjustment techniques used that are likely to correct for the presence of selection biases?	Not applicable.	NA
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to selection of participants into the study?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias in classification of interventions		
3.1 Were intervention groups clearly defined?	Yes. IRS districts received IRS, no-IRS districts did not receive IRS.	Y
3.2 Was the information used to define intervention groups recorded at the start of the intervention?	Yes.	Y
3.3 Could classification of intervention status have been affected by knowledge of the outcome or risk of the outcome?	No.	N
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to classification of interventions?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias due to deviations from intended interventions		
If your aim for this study is to assess the effect of assignment to intervention, answer questions 4.1 and 4.2		
4.1. Were there deviations from the intended intervention beyond what would be expected in usual practice?	Yes, many participants re-plastered their walls following application of IRS.	Y

4.2. If Y/PY to 4.1: Were these deviations from intended intervention unbalanced between groups <i>and</i> likely to have affected the outcome?	Yes, while no information is provided regarding the number of people that re-plastered their homes in each group, the efficacy of the insecticide (mortality of vectors) was impacted, and was not balanced between the groups compared or at the times compared.	Y
If your aim for this study is to assess the effect of starting and adhering to intervention, answer questions 4.3 to 4.6		
4.3. Were important co-interventions balanced across intervention groups?	Not applicable.	NA
4.4. Was the intervention implemented successfully for most participants?	Not applicable.	NA
4.5. Did study participants adhere to the assigned intervention regimen?	Not applicable.	NA
4.6. If N/PN to 4.3, 4.4 or 4.5: Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of starting and adhering to the intervention?	Not applicable.	NA
Risk of bias judgement	Serious.	Serious
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to deviations from the intended interventions?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias due to missing data		
5.1 Were outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants?	No, only six (intervention) and three (control) villages from both districts were chosen to serve as index villages to monitor epidemiological outcomes. From these villages, only approximately (25-30%) of people had their outcomes measured.	N
5.2 Were participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status?	No.	N
5.3 Were participants excluded due to missing data on other variables needed for the analysis?	No.	N

5.4 If PN/N to 5.1, or Y/PY to 5.2 or 5.3: Are the proportion of participants and reasons for missing data similar across interventions?	No information provided by the authors.	NI
5.5 If PN/N to 5.1, or Y/PY to 5.2 or 5.3: Is there evidence that results were robust to the presence of missing data?	No evidence of data robustness.	N
Risk of bias judgement	Serious.	Serious
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to missing data?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias in measurement of outcomes		
6.1 Could the outcome measure have been influenced by knowledge of the intervention received?	No, a blood survey was conducted four months after the spraying in both experimental and control villages among 25% of the population in each village.	PN
6.2 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Yes. No information provided however, it is reasonable to assume that health staff would have been aware.	PY
6.3 Were the methods of outcome assessment comparable across intervention groups?	Yes.	Y
6.4 Were any systematic errors in measurement of the outcome related to intervention received?	No information provided by the authors.	NI
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to measurement of outcomes?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias in selection of the reported result		
Is the reported effect estimate likely to be selected, on the basis of the results, from...		

7.1. ... multiple outcome <i>measurements</i> within the outcome domain?	No, not for malaria prevalence.	N
7.2 ... multiple <i>analyses</i> of the intervention-outcome relationship?	No.	N
7.3 ... different <i>subgroups</i> ?	No.	N
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to selection of the reported result?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Overall bias		
Risk of bias judgement	Serious.	Serious
Optional: What is the overall predicted direction of bias for this outcome?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

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Signalling questions	Description	Response options
Bias due to confounding		
<p>1.1 Is there potential for confounding of the effect of intervention in this study? If N/PN to 1.1: the study can be considered to be at low risk of bias due to confounding and no further signalling questions need be considered If Y/PY to 1.1: determine whether there is a need to assess time-varying confounding:</p>	<p>Yes, there is potential for confounding and confounders were not considered by authors.</p>	<p>Y</p>
<p>1.2. Was the analysis based on splitting participants' follow up time according to intervention received? If N/PN, answer questions relating to baseline confounding (1.4 to 1.6) If Y/PY, go to question 1.3.</p>	<p>No, the analysis was not based on splitting of follow-up time based on the intervention received.</p>	<p>N</p>
<p>1.3. Were intervention discontinuations or switches likely to be related to factors that are prognostic for the outcome? If N/PN, answer questions relating to baseline confounding (1.4 to 1.6) If Y/PY, answer questions relating to both baseline and time-varying confounding (1.7 and 1.8)</p>	<p>Not applicable.</p>	<p>NA</p>
Questions relating to baseline confounding only		
<p>1.4. Did the authors use an appropriate analysis method that controlled for all the important confounding domains?</p>	<p>No, the authors reported age-adjusted results however, have not included any other important confounders (e.g., including village/ cluster) in their analysis. For this systematic review, raw data was extracted from primary studies and not adjusted for confounding.</p>	<p>N</p>

1.5. If Y/PY to 1.4: Were confounding domains that were controlled for measured validly and reliably by the variables available in this study?	Not applicable.	NA
1.6. Did the authors control for any post-intervention variables that could have been affected by the intervention?	No.	N
Questions relating to baseline and time-varying confounding		
1.7. Did the authors use an appropriate analysis method that controlled for all the important confounding domains and for time-varying confounding?	Not applicable.	NA
1.8. If Y/PY to 1.7: Were confounding domains that were controlled for measured validly and reliably by the variables available in this study?	Not applicable.	NA
Risk of bias judgement	Serious.	Serious
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to confounding?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Unpredictable

Bias in selection of participants into the study		
2.1. Was selection of participants into the study (or into the analysis) based on participant characteristics observed after the start of intervention? If N/PN to 2.1: go to 2.4	Yes, participants were excluded if they did not fit to the age categories of interest if another member of the household also met that category and was selected first.	Y
2.2. If Y/PY to 2.1: Were the post-intervention variables that influenced selection likely to be associated with intervention?	No.	N
2.3 If Y/PY to 2.2: Were the post-intervention variables that influenced selection likely to be influenced by the outcome or a cause of the outcome?	Not applicable.	NA

2.4. Do start of follow-up and start of intervention coincide for most participants?	Yes.	Y
2.5. If Y/PY to 2.2 and 2.3, or N/PN to 2.4: Were adjustment techniques used that are likely to correct for the presence of selection biases?	Not applicable.	NA
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to selection of participants into the study?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias in classification of interventions		
3.1 Were intervention groups clearly defined?	Yes. IRS districts received IRS, no-IRS districts did not receive IRS.	Y
3.2 Was the information used to define intervention groups recorded at the start of the intervention?	Yes.	Y
3.3 Could classification of intervention status have been affected by knowledge of the outcome or risk of the outcome?	No.	N
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to classification of interventions?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias due to deviations from intended interventions		
If your aim for this study is to assess the effect of assignment to intervention, answer questions 4.1 and 4.2		
4.1. Were there deviations from the intended intervention beyond what would be expected in usual practice?	None reported.	N

4.2. If Y/PY to 4.1: Were these deviations from intended intervention unbalanced between groups <i>and</i> likely to have affected the outcome?	Not applicable.	NA
If your aim for this study is to assess the effect of starting and adhering to intervention, answer questions 4.3 to 4.6		
4.3. Were important co-interventions balanced across intervention groups?	Not applicable.	NA
4.4. Was the intervention implemented successfully for most participants?	Not applicable.	NA
4.5. Did study participants adhere to the assigned intervention regimen?	Not applicable.	NA
4.6. If N/PN to 4.3, 4.4 or 4.5: Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of starting and adhering to the intervention?	Not applicable.	NA
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to deviations from the intended interventions?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias due to missing data		
5.1 Were outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants?	No, all households in the clusters received the interventions (as reported – no details on refusals). However only one, randomly selected member of the household, from each age group (of 6 months- 4 years; 5-15 years; over 15 years) was selected to have outcomes measured (i.e. 3 members of each household, chosen at random from the 200 households in each cluster	N
5.2 Were participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status?	No.	N

5.3 Were participants excluded due to missing data on other variables needed for the analysis?	No.	N
5.4 If PN/N to 5.1, or Y/PY to 5.2 or 5.3 : Are the proportion of participants and reasons for missing data similar across interventions?	No information provided by the authors.	NI
5.5 If PN/N to 5.1, or Y/PY to 5.2 or 5.3 : Is there evidence that results were robust to the presence of missing data?	Yes, participants were randomly selected for outcome assessment and therefore data was missing at random.	Y
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to missing data?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias in measurement of outcomes		
6.1 Could the outcome measure have been influenced by knowledge of the intervention received?	No, a random selection of homesteads were measured with finger prick blood test.	N
6.2 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Yes. No information provided however, it is reasonable to assume that health staff would have been aware.	PY
6.3 Were the methods of outcome assessment comparable across intervention groups?	Yes.	Y
6.4 Were any systematic errors in measurement of the outcome related to intervention received?	No information provided by the authors.	NI
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to measurement of outcomes?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias in selection of the reported result		
Is the reported effect estimate likely to be selected, on the basis of the results, from... 7.1. ... multiple outcome <i>measurements</i> within the outcome domain?	No.	N
7.2 ... multiple <i>analyses</i> of the intervention-outcome relationship?	No.	N
7.3 ... different <i>subgroups</i> ?	No.	N
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to selection of the reported result?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null / Away from null / Unpredictable

Overall bias		
Risk of bias judgement	Serious.	Serious
Optional: What is the overall predicted direction of bias for this outcome?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null / Away from null / Unpredictable

Mashauri

Signalling questions	Description	Response options
Bias due to confounding		
<p>1.1 Is there potential for confounding of the effect of intervention in this study? If N/PN to 1.1: the study can be considered to be at low risk of bias due to confounding and no further signalling questions need be considered If Y/PY to 1.1: determine whether there is a need to assess time-varying confounding:</p>	<p>Yes, there is potential for confounding and confounders were not considered by authors.</p>	<p>Y</p>
<p>1.2. Was the analysis based on splitting participants' follow up time according to intervention received? If N/PN, answer questions relating to baseline confounding (1.4 to 1.6) If Y/PY, go to question 1.3.</p>	<p>No, the analysis was not based on splitting of follow-up time based on the intervention received.</p>	<p>N</p>
<p>1.3. Were intervention discontinuations or switches likely to be related to factors that are prognostic for the outcome? If N/PN, answer questions relating to baseline confounding (1.4 to 1.6) If Y/PY, answer questions relating to both baseline and time-varying confounding (1.7 and 1.8)</p>	<p>Not applicable.</p>	<p>NA</p>
Questions relating to baseline confounding only		
<p>1.4. Did the authors use an appropriate analysis method that controlled for all the important confounding domains?</p>	<p>No, the authors stratified by age however, have not included any other important confounders (e.g., including village/ cluster) in their analysis. For this systematic review, raw data was extracted from primary studies and not adjusted for confounding.</p>	<p>N</p>

1.5. If Y/PY to 1.4: Were confounding domains that were controlled for measured validly and reliably by the variables available in this study?	Not applicable.	NA
1.6. Did the authors control for any post-intervention variables that could have been affected by the intervention?	No.	N
Questions relating to baseline and time-varying confounding		
1.7. Did the authors use an appropriate analysis method that controlled for all the important confounding domains and for time-varying confounding?	Not applicable.	NA
1.8. If Y/PY to 1.7: Were confounding domains that were controlled for measured validly and reliably by the variables available in this study?	Not applicable.	NA
Risk of bias judgement	Serious.	Serious
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to confounding?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Unpredictable

Bias in selection of participants into the study		
2.1. Was selection of participants into the study (or into the analysis) based on participant characteristics observed after the start of intervention? If N/PN to 2.1: go to 2.4	Yes, IRS villages selected from a malaria epidemic area while no IRS villages selected from an area not affected by the epidemic.	Y
2.2. If Y/PY to 2.1: Were the post-intervention variables that influenced selection likely to be associated with intervention?	Yes, epidemic associated with need for intervention.	Y
2.3. If Y/PY to 2.2: Were the post-intervention variables that influenced selection likely to be influenced by the outcome or a cause of the outcome?	Yes.	Y

2.4. Do start of follow-up and start of intervention coincide for most participants?	Yes.	Y
2.5. If Y/PY to 2.2 and 2.3, or N/PN to 2.4: Were adjustment techniques used that are likely to correct for the presence of selection biases?	Not applicable.	NA
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to selection of participants into the study?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias in classification of interventions		
3.1 Were intervention groups clearly defined?	Yes. IRS districts received IRS, no-IRS districts did not receive IRS.	Y
3.2 Was the information used to define intervention groups recorded at the start of the intervention?	Yes.	Y
3.3 Could classification of intervention status have been affected by knowledge of the outcome or risk of the outcome?	No.	N
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to classification of interventions?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias due to deviations from intended interventions		
If your aim for this study is to assess the effect of assignment to intervention, answer questions 4.1 and 4.2		
4.1. Were there deviations from the intended intervention beyond what would be expected in usual practice?	None reported.	N

4.2. If Y/PY to 4.1: Were these deviations from intended intervention unbalanced between groups <i>and</i> likely to have affected the outcome?	Not applicable.	NA
If your aim for this study is to assess the effect of starting and adhering to intervention, answer questions 4.3 to 4.6		
4.3. Were important co-interventions balanced across intervention groups?	Not applicable.	NA
4.4. Was the intervention implemented successfully for most participants?	Not applicable.	NA
4.5. Did study participants adhere to the assigned intervention regimen?	Not applicable.	NA
4.6. If N/PN to 4.3, 4.4 or 4.5: Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of starting and adhering to the intervention?	Not applicable.	NA
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to deviations from the intended interventions?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias due to missing data		
5.1 Were outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants?	No, the outcome was only recorded on participants residing in two randomly selected “sub-villages” in each village selected for outcome assessment. IN every survey, individuals were randomly selected.	N
5.2 Were participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status?	No.	N
5.3 Were participants excluded due to missing data on other variables needed for the analysis?	No.	N

5.4 If PN/N to 5.1, or Y/PY to 5.2 or 5.3: Are the proportion of participants and reasons for missing data similar across interventions?	No information provided by the authors.	NI
5.5 If PN/N to 5.1, or Y/PY to 5.2 or 5.3: Is there evidence that results were robust to the presence of missing data?	Yes, participants were selected randomly for cross-sectional surveys and therefore data is missing at random.	Y
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to missing data?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias in measurement of outcomes		
6.1 Could the outcome measure have been influenced by knowledge of the intervention received?	No, in every survey, finger prick blood was collected from all consented selected participants for malaria parasites and Hb levels examination.	N
6.2 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Yes. No information provided however, it is reasonable to assume that health staff would have been aware.	PY
6.3 Were the methods of outcome assessment comparable across intervention groups?	Yes.	Y
6.4 Were any systematic errors in measurement of the outcome related to intervention received?	No information provided by the authors.	NI
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to measurement of outcomes?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias in selection of the reported result		
Is the reported effect estimate likely to be selected, on the basis of the results, from...		

7.1. ... multiple outcome <i>measurements</i> within the outcome domain?	No.	N
7.2 ... multiple <i>analyses</i> of the intervention-outcome relationship?	No.	N
7.3 ... different <i>subgroups</i> ?	No.	N
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to selection of the reported result?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Overall bias		
Risk of bias judgement	Serious.	Serious
Optional: What is the overall predicted direction of bias for this outcome?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Ramachandra

Signalling questions	Description	Response options
Bias due to confounding		
<p>1.1 Is there potential for confounding of the effect of intervention in this study? If N/PN to 1.1: the study can be considered to be at low risk of bias due to confounding and no further signalling questions need be considered If Y/PY to 1.1: determine whether there is a need to assess time-varying confounding:</p>	<p>Yes, there is potential for confounding and confounders were not considered by authors.</p>	<p>Y</p>
<p>1.2. Was the analysis based on splitting participants' follow up time according to intervention received? If N/PN, answer questions relating to baseline confounding (1.4 to 1.6) If Y/PY, go to question 1.3.</p>	<p>No, the analysis was not based on splitting of follow-up time based on the intervention received.</p>	<p>N</p>
<p>1.3. Were intervention discontinuations or switches likely to be related to factors that are prognostic for the outcome? If N/PN, answer questions relating to baseline confounding (1.4 to 1.6) If Y/PY, answer questions relating to both baseline and time-varying confounding (1.7 and 1.8)</p>	<p>Not applicable.</p>	<p>NA</p>
Questions relating to baseline confounding only		
<p>1.4. Did the authors use an appropriate analysis method that controlled for all the important confounding domains?</p>	<p>No, authors did not consider confounders in their analysis. For this systematic review, raw data was extracted from primary studies and not adjusted for confounding.</p>	<p>N</p>
<p>1.5. If Y/PY to 1.4: Were confounding domains that were controlled for measured validly and reliably by the variables available in this study?</p>	<p>Not applicable.</p>	<p>NA</p>

1.6. Did the authors control for any post-intervention variables that could have been affected by the intervention?	No.	N
Questions relating to baseline and time-varying confounding		
1.7. Did the authors use an appropriate analysis method that controlled for all the important confounding domains and for time-varying confounding?	Not applicable.	NA
1.8. If <u>Y/PY</u> to 1.7: Were confounding domains that were controlled for measured validly and reliably by the variables available in this study?	Not applicable.	NA
Risk of bias judgement	Serious.	Serious
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to confounding?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Unpredictable

Bias in selection of participants into the study		
2.1. Was selection of participants into the study (or into the analysis) based on participant characteristics observed after the start of intervention? If <u>N/PN</u> to 2.1: go to 2.4	No.	N
2.2. If <u>Y/PY</u> to 2.1: Were the post-intervention variables that influenced selection likely to be associated with intervention?	Not applicable	NA
2.3 If <u>Y/PY</u> to 2.2: Were the post-intervention variables that influenced selection likely to be influenced by the outcome or a cause of the outcome?	Not applicable.	NA
2.4. Do start of follow-up and start of intervention coincide for most participants?	Yes.	Y

2.5. If Y/PY to 2.2 and 2.3, or N/PN to 2.4: Were adjustment techniques used that are likely to correct for the presence of selection biases?	Not applicable.	NA
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to selection of participants into the study?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias in classification of interventions		
3.1 Were intervention groups clearly defined?	Yes. IRS districts received IRS, no-IRS districts did not receive IRS.	Y
3.2 Was the information used to define intervention groups recorded at the start of the intervention?	Yes.	Y
3.3 Could classification of intervention status have been affected by knowledge of the outcome or risk of the outcome?	No.	N
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to classification of interventions?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias due to deviations from intended interventions		
If your aim for this study is to assess the effect of assignment to intervention, answer questions 4.1 and 4.2		
4.1. Were there deviations from the intended intervention beyond what would be expected in usual practice?	Yes, two villages received a second round of IRS between 1 and 2 of October after the first round was insufficient.	Y
4.2. If Y/PY to 4.1: Were these deviations from intended intervention unbalanced between groups <i>and</i> likely to have affected the outcome?	Not different between groups but inconsistent between participants.	N

If your aim for this study is to assess the effect of starting and adhering to intervention, answer questions 4.3 to 4.6		
4.3. Were important co-interventions balanced across intervention groups?	Not applicable.	NA
4.4. Was the intervention implemented successfully for most participants?	Not applicable.	NA
4.5. Did study participants adhere to the assigned intervention regimen?	Not applicable.	NA
4.6. If N/PN to 4.3, 4.4 or 4.5: Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of starting and adhering to the intervention?	Not applicable.	NA
Risk of bias judgement	Moderate.	Moderate
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to deviations from the intended interventions?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias due to missing data		
5.1 Were outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants?	No, the outcome was only recorded on a proportion of participants because number of smears is different to number of participants sprayed.	N
5.2 Were participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status?	No.	N
5.3 Were participants excluded due to missing data on other variables needed for the analysis?	No.	N
5.4 If PN/N to 5.1, or Y/PY to 5.2 or 5.3: Are the proportion of participants and reasons for missing data similar across interventions?	No information provided by the authors.	NI

5.5 If PN/N to 5.1, or Y/PY to 5.2 or 5.3: Is there evidence that results were robust to the presence of missing data?	No evidence the results were robust.	N
Risk of bias judgement	Serious.	Serious.
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to missing data?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias in measurement of outcomes		
6.1 Could the outcome measure have been influenced by knowledge of the intervention received?	No, in every survey, smears were collected from all selected participants for malaria parasites.	N
6.2 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Yes. No information provided however, it is reasonable to assume that health staff would have been aware.	PY
6.3 Were the methods of outcome assessment comparable across intervention groups?	Yes.	Y
6.4 Were any systematic errors in measurement of the outcome related to intervention received?	No information provided by the authors.	NI
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to measurement of outcomes?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null /Away from null / Unpredictable

Bias in selection of the reported result		
Is the reported effect estimate likely to be selected, on the basis of the results, from... 7.1. ... multiple outcome <i>measurements</i> within the outcome domain?	No.	N

7.2 ... multiple <i>analyses</i> of the intervention-outcome relationship?	No.	N
7.3 ... different <i>subgroups</i> ?	No.	N
Risk of bias judgement	Low.	Low
Optional: What is the predicted direction of bias due to selection of the reported result?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null / Away from null / Unpredictable

Overall bias		
Risk of bias judgement	Serious.	Serious
Optional: What is the overall predicted direction of bias for this outcome?	Not possible to judge.	Favours experimental / Favours comparator / Towards null / Away from null / Unpredictable

Supplementary item 8 – Subgroup analyses

Incidence of malaria (all ages; RCTs) – subgrouped by background nets (low coverage)

Figure A7.1 Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (RCTs); subgrouped by background nets.

Incidence of malaria (all ages; RCTs) – subgrouped by susceptibility to IRS compound

Figure A7.2. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (RCTs); subgrouped by susceptibility to IRS compound – susceptible.

Incidence of malaria (all ages; RCTs) – subgrouped by setting

Figure A7.3. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (RCTs); subgrouped by setting.

Incidence of malaria (all ages; RCTs) – subgrouped by insecticide class

Figure A7.4. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (RCTs); subgrouped by insecticide class.

Incidence of malaria (all ages; RCTs) – subgrouped by transmission setting

Figure A7.5. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (RCTs); subgrouped by transmission setting.

Prevalence of malaria (all ages; non-randomised studies) – subgrouped by susceptibility to IRS compound

Figure A7.6. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (non-randomised studies); subgrouped by susceptibility to IRS compound.

Prevalence of malaria (all ages; non-randomised studies) – subgrouped by transmission setting

Risk of bias legend
 (A) Bias due to confounding
 (B) Bias in selection of participants into the study
 (C) Bias in classification of interventions
 (D) Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
 (E) Bias due to missing data
 (F) Bias in measurement of outcomes
 (G) Bias in selection of the reported result

Figure A7.7. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (non-randomised studies); subgrouped by transmission setting.

Prevalence of malaria (all ages; non-randomised studies) – subgrouped by insecticide class

Risk of bias legend
 (A) Bias due to confounding
 (B) Bias in selection of participants into the study
 (C) Bias in classification of interventions
 (D) Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
 (E) Bias due to missing data
 (F) Bias in measurement of outcomes
 (G) Bias in selection of the reported result

Figure A7.8. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (non-randomised studies); subgrouped by insecticide class.

Supplementary item 9 – ICEMAN assessments for subgroup analyses

Randomised controlled trials

ICEMAN: Insecticide class

Instrument for assessing the Credibility of Effect Modification Analyses (ICEMAN)
in meta-analyses of randomized controlled trials *Version 1.0*

Quick instructions

Synonyms for effect modification include subgroup effect, interaction, and moderation

The instrument applies to a single proposed effect modification at a time; complete one form per each outcome, time-point, effect measure, and effect modifier

Response options on the left indicate definitely or probably reduced, response options on the right probably or definitely increased credibility

Completely unclear goes under probably reduced credibility

It is helpful to provide a supporting comment or quotation under each question

Whether an effect modification is patient-important is not part of the credibility assessment

The manual provides more detailed instructions and examples

Preliminary considerations

Study reference(s):

If available, protocol reference(s):

State a single outcome and, if applicable, time-point of interest (e.g., mortality at 1 year follow-up):

State a single effect measure of interest (e.g., relative or absolute risk difference):

State a single potential effect modifier of interest (e.g., age or comorbidity):

Was the potential effect modifier measured before or at randomization? yes, continue no, stop here and refer to manual for further instructions

Credibility assessment

1: Is the analysis of effect modification based on comparison within rather than between trials?

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Completely between	<input type="checkbox"/> Mostly between or unclear	<input type="checkbox"/> Mostly within	<input type="checkbox"/> Completely within
<i>Subgroup analysis or meta-regression comparing overall effects of each individual trial. This is typical for aggregate data meta-analysis.</i>	<i>Subgroup analysis or meta-regression with most information coming from overall effects, but some trials providing within-trial subgroup information</i>	<i>Most trials providing within-trial subgroup information; or individual participant data analysis that combines within and between trial information</i>	<i>All trials providing within-trial subgroup information or individual participant data; and the analysis separates within from between trial information, e.g., meta-analysis of interactions</i>

Comment:

2: For within-trial comparisons, is the effect modification similar from trial to trial? Not applicable: no or one within-RCT comparison

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely not similar	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably not similar or unclear	<input type="checkbox"/> Mostly similar	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely similar
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<i>Effect modification reported for two or more trials and clearly different directions</i>	<i>Effect modification not reported for individual trials or too imprecise to tell</i>	<i>Effect modification reported for two or more trials, mostly similar in direction, but considerable differences in magnitude</i>	<i>Effect modification reported for two or more trials, similar in direction, only some differences in magnitude</i>
---	--	--	--

Comment:

3: For between-trial comparisons, is the number of trials large? [] Not applicable: no between RCT comparison

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Very small <i>1 or 2 or in smallest subgroup; 5 or less in continuous meta-regression Two studies in each subgroup.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather small or unclear <i>3-4 in smallest subgroup; 6-10 in continuous meta-regression</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather large <i>5-9 in smallest subgroup; 11 to 15 in continuous meta-regression</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Large <i>10 or more in smallest subgroup; more than 15 in continuous meta-regression</i>
--	---	--	--

Comment:

4: Was the direction of effect modification correctly hypothesized a priori?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Clearly post-hoc or results inconsistent with hypothesized direction or biologically very implausible</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>Vague hypothesis or hypothesized direction unclear Unclear within studies and not hypothesized for this meta-analysis.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>No prior protocol available but unequivocal statement of a priori hypothesis with correct direction of effect modification</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Prior protocol available and includes correct specification of direction of effect modification, e.g., based on a biologic rationale</i>
--	---	--	--

Comment:

5: Does a test for interaction suggest that chance is an unlikely explanation of the apparent effect modification? (consider irrespective of number of effect modifiers)

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Chance a very likely explanation <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value >0.05 Test for differences between subgroups p=0.54 (no differences).</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance a likely explanation or unclear <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.05 and >0.01, or no test of interaction reported and not computable</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance may not explain <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.01 and >0.005</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance an unlikely explanation <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.005</i>
--	--	--	---

Comment:

6: Did the authors test only a small number of effect modifiers or consider the number in their statistical analysis?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Explicitly exploratory analysis or large number of effect modifiers tested (e.g., greater than 10) and multiplicity not considered in analysis</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>No mention of number or 4-10 effect modifiers tested and number not considered in analysis</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>No protocol available but unequivocal statement of 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Protocol available and 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested or number considered in analysis</i>
---	--	---	--

Comment:

7: Did the authors use a random effects model?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Fixed (or common) effect or fixed effects model explicitly stated</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>Probably fixed effect(s) model</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>Probably random (or mixed) effects</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Random (or mixed) effects explicitly stated Authors of this meta-analysis used a random-effects model.</i>
--	--	--	---

Comment:

8: If the effect modifier is a continuous variable, were arbitrary cut points avoided? [] not applicable: not continuous

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Analysis based on exploratory cut point(s), e.g., picking cut point associated with highest interaction p-value</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>Analysis based on cut point(s) of unclear origin</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>Analysis based on pre-specified cut point(s), e.g., suggested by prior RCT Yes, based on class.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Analysis based on the full continuum, e.g., assuming a linear or logarithmic relationship</i>
--	--	--	---

Comment:

9 Optional: Are there any additional considerations that may increase or decrease credibility? (manual section 3.9) [] not applicable

[] Yes, probably decrease [X] Yes, probably increase

*Studies at serious risk of bias based on RoB 2.0 clusters.
No sensitivity analysis conducted in individual studies.*

Comment:

10: How would you rate the overall credibility of the proposed effect modification?

The overall rating should be driven by the items that decrease credibility. The following provides a sensible strategy:

All responses definitely or probably decrease credibility or unclear → very low

Two or more responses definitely decrease credibility → maximum usually low even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria

One response definitely decreases credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria

Two responses probably decrease credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria

No response options definitely or probably decrease credibility → high very likely

Place a mark on the continuous line (or type "x" in editable version)

Comment: *Likely no effect modification. Subgroups small and further research needed to determine credible effect modification.*

ICEMAN: Background nets

Instrument for assessing the Credibility of Effect Modification Analyses (ICEMAN)

in meta-analyses of randomized controlled trials

Version 1.0

Quick instructions

Synonyms for effect modification include subgroup effect, interaction, and moderation

The instrument applies to a single proposed effect modification at a time; complete one form per each outcome, time-point, effect measure, and effect modifier

Response options on the left indicate definitely or probably reduced, response options on the right probably or definitely increased credibility

Completely unclear goes under probably reduced credibility

It is helpful to provide a supporting comment or quotation under each question

Whether an effect modification is patient-important is not part of the credibility assessment

The manual provides more detailed instructions and examples

Preliminary considerations

Study reference(s):

If available, protocol reference(s):

State a single outcome and, if applicable, time-point of interest (e.g., mortality at 1 year follow-up):

State a single effect measure of interest (e.g., relative or absolute risk difference):

State a single potential effect modifier of interest (e.g., age or comorbidity):

Was the potential effect modifier measured before or at randomization? yes, continue no, stop here and refer to manual for further instructions

Credibility assessment

1: Is the analysis of effect modification based on comparison within rather than between trials?

Completely between Mostly between or unclear Mostly within Completely within

Subgroup analysis or meta-regression comparing overall effects of each individual trial. This is typical for aggregate data meta-analysis.

Subgroup analysis or meta-regression with most information coming from overall effects, but some trials providing within-trial subgroup information

Most trials providing within-trial subgroup information; or individual participant data analysis that combines within and between trial information

All trials providing within-trial subgroup information or individual participant data; and the analysis separates within from between trial information, e.g., meta-analysis of interactions

Comment:

2: For within-trial comparisons, is the effect modification similar from trial to trial? Not applicable: no or one within-RCT comparison

Definitely not similar Probably not similar or unclear Mostly similar Definitely similar

Effect modification reported for two or more trials and clearly different directions

Effect modification not reported for individual trials or too imprecise to tell

Effect modification reported for two or more trials, mostly similar in direction, but considerable differences in magnitude

Effect modification reported for two or more trials, similar in direction, only some differences in magnitude

Comment:

3: For between-trial comparisons, is the number of trials large? [] Not applicable: no between RCT comparison

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Very small	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather small or unclear	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather large	<input type="checkbox"/> Large
<i>1 or 2 or in smallest subgroup; 5 or less in continuous meta-regression</i>	<i>3-4 in smallest subgroup; 6-10 in continuous meta-regression</i>	<i>5-9 in smallest subgroup; 11 to 15 in continuous meta-regression</i>	<i>10 or more in smallest subgroup; more than 15 in continuous meta-regression</i>

One study in smallest group.

Comment:

4: Was the direction of effect modification correctly hypothesized a priori?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes
<i>Clearly post-hoc or results inconsistent with hypothesized direction or biologically very implausible</i>	<i>Vague hypothesis or hypothesized direction unclear</i> <i>Not hypothesized for this meta-analysis but expected that nets would decrease effect seen for IRS.</i>	<i>No prior protocol available but unequivocal statement of a priori hypothesis with correct direction of effect modification</i>	<i>Prior protocol available and includes correct specification of direction of effect modification, e.g., based on a biologic rationale</i>

Comment:

5: Does a test for interaction suggest that chance is an unlikely explanation of the apparent effect modification? (consider irrespective of number of effect modifiers)

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Chance a very likely explanation	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance a likely explanation or unclear	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance may not explain	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance an unlikely explanation
<i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value >0.05</i> <i>Test for differences between subgroups p=0.44 (no differences).</i>	<i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.05 and >0.01, or no test of interaction reported and not computable</i>	<i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.01 and >0.005</i>	<i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.005</i>

Comment:

6: Did the authors test only a small number of effect modifiers or consider the number in their statistical analysis?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes
<i>Explicitly exploratory analysis or large number of effect modifiers tested (e.g., greater than 10) and multiplicity not considered in analysis</i>	<i>No mention of number or 4-10 effect modifiers tested and number not considered in analysis</i>	<i>No protocol available but unequivocal statement of 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested.</i>	<i>Protocol available and 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested or number considered in analysis</i>

Comment:

7: Did the authors use a random effects model?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes
<i>Fixed (or common) effect or fixed effects model explicitly stated</i>	<i>Probably fixed effect(s) model</i>	<i>Probably random (or mixed) effects</i>	<i>Random (or mixed) effects explicitly stated</i> <i>Authors of this meta-analysis used a random-effects model.</i>

Comment:

8: If the effect modifier is a continuous variable, were arbitrary cut points avoided? [] not applicable: not continuous

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes
<i>Analysis based on exploratory cut point(s), e.g., picking cut point associated with highest interaction p-value</i>	<i>Analysis based on cut point(s) of unclear origin</i>	<i>Analysis based on pre-specified cut point(s), e.g., suggested by prior RCT</i> <i>Yes, based on nets present/absent. Sometimes unreported.</i>	<i>Analysis based on the full continuum, e.g., assuming a linear or logarithmic relationship</i>

Comment:

9 Optional: Are there any additional considerations that may increase or decrease credibility? (manual section 3.9) [] not applicable

[] Yes, probably decrease [X] Yes, probably increase

*Studies at serious risk of bias based on RoB 2.0 clusters.
No sensitivity analysis conducted in individual studies.*

Comment:

10: How would you rate the overall credibility of the proposed effect modification?

The overall rating should be driven by the items that decrease credibility. The following provides a sensible strategy:

All responses definitely or probably decrease credibility or unclear → very low

Two or more responses definitely decrease credibility → maximum usually low even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria

One response definitely decreases credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria

Two responses probably decrease credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria

No response options definitely or probably decrease credibility → high very likely

Place a mark on the continuous line (or type "x" in editable version)

Comment: *Likely no effect modification. Subgroups small and further research needed to determine credible effect modification.*

ICEMAN: Susceptibility

Instrument for assessing the Credibility of Effect Modification Analyses (ICEMAN)

in meta-analyses of randomized controlled trials

Version 1.0

Quick instructions

Synonyms for effect modification include subgroup effect, interaction, and moderation

The instrument applies to a single proposed effect modification at a time; complete one form per each outcome, time-point, effect measure, and effect modifier

Response options on the left indicate definitely or probably reduced, response options on the right probably or definitely increased credibility

Completely unclear goes under probably reduced credibility

It is helpful to provide a supporting comment or quotation under each question

Whether an effect modification is patient-important is not part of the credibility assessment

The manual provides more detailed instructions and examples

Preliminary considerations

Study reference(s):

If available, protocol reference(s):

State a single outcome and, if applicable, time-point of interest (e.g., mortality at 1 year follow-up):

State a single effect measure of interest (e.g., relative or absolute risk difference):

State a single potential effect modifier of interest (e.g., age or comorbidity):

Was the potential effect modifier measured before or at randomization? yes, continue no, stop here and refer to manual for further instructions

Credibility assessment

1: Is the analysis of effect modification based on comparison within rather than between trials?

Completely between Mostly between or unclear Mostly within Completely within

Subgroup analysis or meta-regression comparing overall effects of each individual trial. This is typical for aggregate data meta-analysis.

Subgroup analysis or meta-regression with most information coming from overall effects, but some trials providing within-trial subgroup information

Most trials providing within-trial subgroup information; or individual participant data analysis that combines within and between trial information

All trials providing within-trial subgroup information or individual participant data; and the analysis separates within from between trial information, e.g., meta-analysis of interactions

Comment:

2: For within-trial comparisons, is the effect modification similar from trial to trial? Not applicable: no or one within-RCT comparison

Definitely not similar Probably not similar or unclear Mostly similar Definitely similar

Effect modification reported for two or more trials and clearly different directions

Effect modification not reported for individual trials or too imprecise to tell

Effect modification reported for two or more trials, mostly similar in direction, but considerable differences in magnitude

Effect modification reported for two or more trials, similar in direction, only some differences in magnitude

Comment:

3: For between-trial comparisons, is the number of trials large? [] Not applicable: no between RCT comparison

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Very small	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather small or unclear	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather large	<input type="checkbox"/> Large
<i>1 or 2 or in smallest subgroup; 5 or less in continuous meta-regression</i>	<i>3-4 in smallest subgroup; 6-10 in continuous meta-regression</i>	<i>5-9 in smallest subgroup; 11 to 15 in continuous meta-regression</i>	<i>10 or more in smallest subgroup; more than 15 in continuous meta-regression</i>

Two studies in each subgroup.

Comment:

4: Was the direction of effect modification correctly hypothesized a priori?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes
<i>Clearly post-hoc or results inconsistent with hypothesized direction or biologically very implausible</i>	<i>Vague hypothesis or hypothesized direction unclear</i> <i>Unclear within studies and not formally hypothesized for this meta-analysis.</i> <i>Expected greater effect for susceptible group.</i>	<i>No prior protocol available but unequivocal statement of a priori hypothesis with correct direction of effect modification</i>	<i>Prior protocol available and includes correct specification of direction of effect modification, e.g., based on a biologic rationale</i>

Comment:

5: Does a test for interaction suggest that chance is an unlikely explanation of the apparent effect modification? (consider irrespective of number of effect modifiers)

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Chance a very likely explanation	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance a likely explanation or unclear	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance may not explain	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance an unlikely explanation
<i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value >0.05</i> <i>Test for differences between subgroups p=0.48 (no differences).</i>	<i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.05 and >0.01, or no test of interaction reported and not computable</i>	<i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.01 and >0.005</i>	<i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.005</i>

Comment:

6: Did the authors test only a small number of effect modifiers or consider the number in their statistical analysis?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes
<i>Explicitly exploratory analysis or large number of effect modifiers tested (e.g., greater than 10) and multiplicity not considered in analysis</i>	<i>No mention of number or 4-10 effect modifiers tested and number not considered in analysis</i>	<i>No protocol available but unequivocal statement of 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested.</i>	<i>Protocol available and 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested or number considered in analysis</i>

Comment:

7: Did the authors use a random effects model?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes
<i>Fixed (or common) effect or fixed effects model explicitly stated</i>	<i>Probably fixed effect(s) model</i>	<i>Probably random (or mixed) effects</i>	<i>Random (or mixed) effects explicitly stated</i> <i>Authors of this meta-analysis used a random-effects model.</i>

Comment:

8: If the effect modifier is a continuous variable, were arbitrary cut points avoided? [] not applicable: not continuous

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes
<i>Analysis based on exploratory cut point(s), e.g., picking cut point associated with highest interaction p-value</i>	<i>Analysis based on cut point(s) of unclear origin</i>	<i>Analysis based on pre-specified cut point(s), e.g., suggested by prior RCT</i> <i>Yes, based on resistance vs susceptible as reported by study authors.</i>	<i>Analysis based on the full continuum, e.g., assuming a linear or logarithmic relationship</i>

Comment:

9 Optional: Are there any additional considerations that may increase or decrease credibility? (manual section 3.9) [] not applicable

[] Yes, probably decrease [X] Yes, probably increase

*Studies at serious risk of bias based on RoB 2.0 clusters.
No sensitivity analysis conducted in individual studies.*

Comment:

10: How would you rate the overall credibility of the proposed effect modification?
The overall rating should be driven by the items that decrease credibility. The following provides a sensible strategy:
All responses definitely or probably decrease credibility or unclear → very low
Two or more responses definitely decrease credibility → maximum usually low even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
One response definitely decreases credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
Two responses probably decrease credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
No response options definitely or probably decrease credibility → high very likely

Place a mark on the continuous line (or type "x" in editable version)

Comment: *Likely no effect modification. Subgroups small and further research needed to determine credible effect modification.*

ICEMAN: Setting

Instrument for assessing the Credibility of Effect Modification Analyses (ICEMAN)

in meta-analyses of randomized controlled trials

Version 1.0

Quick instructions

Synonyms for effect modification include subgroup effect, interaction, and moderation

The instrument applies to a single proposed effect modification at a time; complete one form per each outcome, time-point, effect measure, and effect modifier

Response options on the left indicate definitely or probably reduced, response options on the right probably or definitely increased credibility

Completely unclear goes under probably reduced credibility

It is helpful to provide a supporting comment or quotation under each question

Whether an effect modification is patient-important is not part of the credibility assessment

The manual provides more detailed instructions and examples

Preliminary considerations

Study reference(s):

If available, protocol reference(s):

State a single outcome and, if applicable, time-point of interest (e.g., mortality at 1 year follow-up):

State a single effect measure of interest (e.g., relative or absolute risk difference):

State a single potential effect modifier of interest (e.g., age or comorbidity):

Was the potential effect modifier measured before or at randomization? yes, continue no, stop here and refer to manual for further instructions

Credibility assessment

1: Is the analysis of effect modification based on comparison within rather than between trials?

Completely between Mostly between or unclear Mostly within Completely within

Subgroup analysis or meta-regression comparing overall effects of each individual trial. This is typical for aggregate data meta-analysis.

Subgroup analysis or meta-regression with most information coming from overall effects, but some trials providing within-trial subgroup information

Most trials providing within-trial subgroup information; or individual participant data analysis that combines within and between trial information

All trials providing within-trial subgroup information or individual participant data; and the analysis separates within from between trial information, e.g., meta-analysis of interactions

Comment:

2: For within-trial comparisons, is the effect modification similar from trial to trial? Not applicable: no or one within-RCT comparison

Definitely not similar Probably not similar or unclear Mostly similar Definitely similar

Effect modification reported for two or more trials and clearly different directions

Effect modification not reported for individual trials or too imprecise to tell

Effect modification reported for two or more trials, mostly similar in direction, but considerable differences in magnitude

Effect modification reported for two or more trials, similar in direction, only some differences in magnitude

Comment:

3: For between-trial comparisons, is the number of trials large? [] Not applicable: no between RCT comparison

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Very small <i>1 or 2 or in smallest subgroup; 5 or less in continuous meta-regression</i> <i>One study in smallest subgroup.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather small or unclear <i>3-4 in smallest subgroup; 6-10 in continuous meta-regression</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather large <i>5-9 in smallest subgroup; 11 to 15 in continuous meta-regression</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Large <i>10 or more in smallest subgroup; more than 15 in continuous meta-regression</i>
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Comment:

4: Was the direction of effect modification correctly hypothesized a priori?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Clearly post-hoc or results inconsistent with hypothesized direction or biologically very implausible</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>Vague hypothesis or hypothesized direction unclear</i> <i>Unclear within studies and not formally hypothesized for this meta-analysis.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>No prior protocol available but unequivocal statement of a priori hypothesis with correct direction of effect modification</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Prior protocol available and includes correct specification of direction of effect modification, e.g., based on a biologic rationale</i>
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Comment:

5: Does a test for interaction suggest that chance is an unlikely explanation of the apparent effect modification? (consider irrespective of number of effect modifiers)

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Chance a very likely explanation <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value >0.05</i> <i>Test for differences between subgroups p=0.27 (no differences).</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance a likely explanation or unclear <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.05 and >0.01, or no test of interaction reported and not computable</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance may not explain <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.01 and >0.005</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance an unlikely explanation <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.005</i>
--	--	--	---

Comment:

6: Did the authors test only a small number of effect modifiers or consider the number in their statistical analysis?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Explicitly exploratory analysis or large number of effect modifiers tested (e.g., greater than 10) and multiplicity not considered in analysis</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>No mention of number or 4-10 effect modifiers tested and number not considered in analysis</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>No protocol available but unequivocal statement of 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Protocol available and 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested or number considered in analysis</i>
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Comment:

7: Did the authors use a random effects model?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Fixed (or common) effect or fixed effects model explicitly stated</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>Probably fixed effect(s) model</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>Probably random (or mixed) effects</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Random (or mixed) effects explicitly stated</i> <i>Authors of this meta-analysis used a random-effects model.</i>
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Comment:

8: If the effect modifier is a continuous variable, were arbitrary cut points avoided? [] not applicable: not continuous

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Analysis based on exploratory cut point(s), e.g., picking cut point associated with highest interaction p-value</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>Analysis based on cut point(s) of unclear origin</i> <i>Study authors did not always state the setting directly as urban or rural and so this was inferred from the description of the study site.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>Analysis based on pre-specified cut point(s), e.g., suggested by prior RCT</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Analysis based on the full continuum, e.g., assuming a linear or logarithmic relationship</i>
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Comment:

9 Optional: Are there any additional considerations that may increase or decrease credibility? (manual section 3.9) [] not applicable

[] Yes, probably decrease [X] Yes, probably increase

*Studies at serious risk of bias based on RoB 2.0 clusters.
No sensitivity analysis conducted in individual studies.*

Comment:

10: How would you rate the overall credibility of the proposed effect modification?
The overall rating should be driven by the items that decrease credibility. The following provides a sensible strategy:
All responses definitely or probably decrease credibility or unclear → very low
Two or more responses definitely decrease credibility → maximum usually low even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
One response definitely decreases credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
Two responses probably decrease credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
No response options definitely or probably decrease credibility → high very likely

Place a mark on the continuous line (or type "x" in editable version)

Comment: *Likely no effect modification. Subgroups small and further research needed to determine credible effect modification.*

ICEMAN: Transmission setting

Instrument for assessing the Credibility of Effect Modification Analyses (ICEMAN)

in meta-analyses of randomized controlled trials

Version 1.0

Quick instructions

Synonyms for effect modification include subgroup effect, interaction, and moderation

The instrument applies to a single proposed effect modification at a time; complete one form per each outcome, time-point, effect measure, and effect modifier

Response options on the left indicate definitely or probably reduced, response options on the right probably or definitely increased credibility

Completely unclear goes under probably reduced credibility

It is helpful to provide a supporting comment or quotation under each question

Whether an effect modification is patient-important is not part of the credibility assessment

The manual provides more detailed instructions and examples

Preliminary considerations

Study reference(s):

If available, protocol reference(s):

State a single outcome and, if applicable, time-point of interest (e.g., mortality at 1 year follow-up):

State a single effect measure of interest (e.g., relative or absolute risk difference):

State a single potential effect modifier of interest (e.g., age or comorbidity):

Was the potential effect modifier measured before or at randomization? yes, continue no, stop here and refer to manual for further instructions

Credibility assessment

1: Is the analysis of effect modification based on comparison within rather than between trials?

Completely between Mostly between or unclear Mostly within Completely within

Subgroup analysis or meta-regression comparing overall effects of each individual trial. This is typical for aggregate data meta-analysis.

Subgroup analysis or meta-regression with most information coming from overall effects, but some trials providing within-trial subgroup information

Most trials providing within-trial subgroup information; or individual participant data analysis that combines within and between trial information

All trials providing within-trial subgroup information or individual participant data; and the analysis separates within from between trial information, e.g., meta-analysis of interactions

Comment:

2: For within-trial comparisons, is the effect modification similar from trial to trial? Not applicable: no or one within-RCT comparison

Definitely not similar Probably not similar or unclear Mostly similar Definitely similar

Effect modification reported for two or more trials and clearly different directions

Effect modification not reported for individual trials or too imprecise to tell

Effect modification reported for two or more trials, mostly similar in direction, but considerable differences in magnitude

Effect modification reported for two or more trials, similar in direction, only some differences in magnitude

Comment:

3: For between-trial comparisons, is the number of trials large? [] Not applicable: no between RCT comparison

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Very small <i>1 or 2 or in smallest subgroup; 5 or less in continuous meta-regression</i> <i>One study in smallest subgroup.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather small or unclear <i>3-4 in smallest subgroup; 6-10 in continuous meta-regression</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather large <i>5-9 in smallest subgroup; 11 to 15 in continuous meta-regression</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Large <i>10 or more in smallest subgroup; more than 15 in continuous meta-regression</i>
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Comment:

4: Was the direction of effect modification correctly hypothesized a priori?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Clearly post-hoc or results inconsistent with hypothesized direction or biologically very implausible</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>Vague hypothesis or hypothesized direction unclear</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>No prior protocol available but unequivocal statement of a priori hypothesis with correct direction of effect modification</i> <i>Cut-offs for transmission prespecified in the protocol for this meta-analysis. Not by primary authors. No direction specified.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Prior protocol available and includes correct specification of direction of effect modification, e.g., based on a biologic rationale</i>
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Comment:

5: Does a test for interaction suggest that chance is an unlikely explanation of the apparent effect modification? (consider irrespective of number of effect modifiers)

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Chance a very likely explanation <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value >0.05</i> <i>Test for differences between subgroups p=0.19 (no differences).</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance a likely explanation or unclear <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.05 and >0.01, or no test of interaction reported and not computable</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance may not explain <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.01 and >0.005</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chance an unlikely explanation <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.005</i>
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Comment:

6: Did the authors test only a small number of effect modifiers or consider the number in their statistical analysis?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Explicitly exploratory analysis or large number of effect modifiers tested (e.g., greater than 10) and multiplicity not considered in analysis</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>No mention of number or 4-10 effect modifiers tested and number not considered in analysis</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>No protocol available but unequivocal statement of 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Protocol available and 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested or number considered in analysis</i>
---	--	---	--

Comment:

7: Did the authors use a random effects model?

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Fixed (or common) effect or fixed effects model explicitly stated</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>Probably fixed effect(s) model</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>Probably random (or mixed) effects</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Random (or mixed) effects explicitly stated</i> <i>Authors of this meta-analysis used a random-effects model.</i>
--	--	--	---

Comment:

8: If the effect modifier is a continuous variable, were arbitrary cut points avoided? [] not applicable: not continuous

<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Analysis based on exploratory cut point(s), e.g., picking cut point associated with highest interaction p-value</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>Analysis based on cut point(s) of unclear origin</i> <i>Cut-offs prespecified.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>Analysis based on pre-specified cut point(s), e.g., suggested by prior RCT</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Analysis based on the full continuum, e.g., assuming a linear or logarithmic relationship</i>
--	--	--	---

Comment:

9 Optional: Are there any additional considerations that may increase or decrease credibility? (manual section 3.9) [] not applicable

[] Yes, probably decrease [X] Yes, probably increase

*Studies at serious risk of bias based on RoB 2.0 clusters.
No sensitivity analysis conducted in individual studies.*

Comment:

10: How would you rate the overall credibility of the proposed effect modification?
The overall rating should be driven by the items that decrease credibility. The following provides a sensible strategy:
All responses definitely or probably decrease credibility or unclear → very low
Two or more responses definitely decrease credibility → maximum usually low even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
One response definitely decreases credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
Two responses probably decrease credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
No response options definitely or probably decrease credibility → high very likely

Place a mark on the continuous line (or type "x" in editable version)

Comment: *Likely no effect modification. Subgroups small and further research needed to determine credible effect modification.*

Non-randomised studies

ICEMAN: Insecticide class

Instrument for assessing the Credibility of Effect Modification Analyses (ICEMAN)
in meta-analyses of randomized controlled trials *Version 1.0*

Quick instructions

Synonyms for effect modification include subgroup effect, interaction, and moderation

The instrument applies to a single proposed effect modification at a time; complete one form per each outcome, time-point, effect measure, and effect modifier

Response options on the left indicate definitely or probably reduced, response options on the right probably or definitely increased credibility

Completely unclear goes under probably reduced credibility

It is helpful to provide a supporting comment or quotation under each question

Whether an effect modification is patient-important is not part of the credibility assessment

The manual provides more detailed instructions and examples

Preliminary considerations

Study reference(s):

If available, protocol reference(s):

State a single outcome and, if applicable, time-point of interest (e.g., mortality at 1 year follow-up):

State a single effect measure of interest (e.g., relative or absolute risk difference):

State a single potential effect modifier of interest (e.g., age or comorbidity):

Was the potential effect modifier measured before or at randomization? yes, continue no, stop here
and refer to manual for further instructions

Credibility assessment

1: Is the analysis of effect modification based on comparison within rather than between trials?

Completely between Mostly between or unclear Mostly within Completely within

<i>Subgroup analysis or meta-regression comparing overall effects of each individual trial. This is typical for aggregate data meta-analysis.</i>	<i>Subgroup analysis or meta-regression with most information coming from overall effects, but some trials providing within-trial subgroup information</i>	<i>Most trials providing within-trial subgroup information; or individual participant data analysis that combines within and between trial information</i>	<i>All trials providing within-trial subgroup information or individual participant data; and the analysis separates within from between trial information, e.g., meta-analysis of interactions</i>
---	--	--	---

Comment:

2: For within-trial comparisons, is the effect modification similar from trial to trial? Not applicable: no or one within-RCT comparison

Definitely not similar Probably not similar or unclear Mostly similar Definitely similar

<i>Effect modification reported for two or more trials and clearly different directions</i>	<i>Effect modification not reported for individual trials or too imprecise to tell</i>	<i>Effect modification reported for two or more trials, mostly similar in direction, but considerable differences in magnitude</i>	<i>Effect modification reported for two or more trials, similar in direction, only some differences in magnitude</i>
---	--	--	--

Comment:

3: For between-trial comparisons, is the number of trials large? Not applicable: no between RCT comparison
 Very small Rather small or unclear Rather large Large
1 or 2 or in smallest subgroup; 5 or less in continuous meta-regression *3-4 in smallest subgroup; 6-10 in continuous meta-regression* *5-9 in smallest subgroup; 11 to 15 in continuous meta-regression* *10 or more in smallest subgroup; more than 15 in continuous meta-regression*
Two studies in each subgroup.

Comment:

4: Was the direction of effect modification correctly hypothesized a priori?
 Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes
Clearly post-hoc or results inconsistent with hypothesized direction or biologically very implausible *Vague hypothesis or hypothesized direction unclear* *No prior protocol available but unequivocal statement of a priori hypothesis with correct direction of effect modification* *Prior protocol available and includes correct specification of direction of effect modification, e.g., based on a biologic rationale*
Unclear within studies and not hypothesized for this meta-analysis.

Comment:

5: Does a test for interaction suggest that chance is an unlikely explanation of the apparent effect modification? (consider irrespective of number of effect modifiers)
 Chance a very likely explanation Chance a likely explanation or unclear Chance may not explain Chance an unlikely explanation
Interaction or meta-regression p-value >0.05 *Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.05 and >0.01, or no test of interaction reported and not computable* *Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.01 and >0.005* *Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.005*
Test for differences between subgroups p=0.74 (no differences).

Comment:

6: Did the authors test only a small number of effect modifiers or consider the number in their statistical analysis?
 Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes
Explicitly exploratory analysis or large number of effect modifiers tested (e.g., greater than 10) and multiplicity not considered in analysis *No mention of number or 4-10 effect modifiers tested and number not considered in analysis* *No protocol available but unequivocal statement of 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested.* *Protocol available and 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested or number considered in analysis*

Comment:

7: Did the authors use a random effects model?
 Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes
Fixed (or common) effect or fixed effects model explicitly stated *Probably fixed effect(s) model* *Probably random (or mixed) effects* *Random (or mixed) effects explicitly stated*
Authors of this meta-analysis used a random-effects model.

Comment:

8: If the effect modifier is a continuous variable, were arbitrary cut points avoided? not applicable: not continuous
 Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

Analysis based on exploratory cut point(s), e.g., picking cut point associated with highest interaction p-value

Analysis based on cut point(s) of unclear origin

Analysis based on pre-specified cut point(s), e.g., suggested by prior RCT
Yes, based on class.

Analysis based on the full continuum, e.g., assuming a linear or logarithmic relationship

Comment:

9 Optional: Are there any additional considerations that may increase or decrease credibility? (manual section 3.9) not applicable

Yes, probably decrease Yes, probably increase

*Studies at serious risk of bias based on RoB 2.0 clusters.
No sensitivity analysis conducted in individual studies.*

Comment:

10: How would you rate the overall credibility of the proposed effect modification?

The overall rating should be driven by the items that decrease credibility. The following provides a sensible strategy:

All responses definitely or probably decrease credibility or unclear → very low

Two or more responses definitely decrease credibility → maximum usually low even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria

One response definitely decreases credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria

Two responses probably decrease credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria

No response options definitely or probably decrease credibility → high very likely

Place a mark on the continuous line (or type "x" in editable version)

Very low credibility

Low credibility

Moderate credibility

High credibility

Very likely no effect modification

Likely no effect modification

Likely effect modification

Very likely effect modification

Use overall effect for each subgroup

Use overall effect for each subgroup but note remaining uncertainty

Use separate effects for each subgroup but note remaining uncertainty

Use separate effects for each subgroup

Comment: *Likely no effect modification. Subgroups small and further research needed to determine credible effect modification.*

ICEMAN: Susceptibility to IRS

Preliminary considerations

Study reference(s):

If available, protocol reference(s):

State a single outcome and, if applicable, time-point of interest (e.g., mortality at 1 year follow-up):

State a single effect measure of interest (e.g., relative or absolute risk difference):

State a single potential effect modifier of interest (e.g., age or comorbidity):

Was the potential effect modifier measured before or at randomization? yes, continue no, stop here and refer to manual for further instructions

Credibility assessment

1: Is the analysis of effect modification based on comparison within rather than between trials?

Completely between Mostly between or unclear Mostly within Completely within

<i>Subgroup analysis or meta-regression comparing overall effects of each individual trial. This is typical for aggregate data meta-analysis.</i>	<i>Subgroup analysis or meta-regression with most information coming from overall effects, but some trials providing within-trial subgroup information</i>	<i>Most trials providing within-trial subgroup information; or individual participant data analysis that combines within and between trial information</i>	<i>All trials providing within-trial subgroup information or individual participant data; and the analysis separates within from between trial information, e.g., meta-analysis of interactions</i>
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Comment:

2: For within-trial comparisons, is the effect modification similar from trial to trial? Not applicable: no or one within-RCT comparison

Definitely not similar Probably not similar or unclear Mostly similar Definitely similar

<i>Effect modification reported for two or more trials and clearly different directions</i>	<i>Effect modification not reported for individual trials or too imprecise to tell</i>	<i>Effect modification reported for two or more trials, mostly similar in direction, but considerable differences in magnitude</i>	<i>Effect modification reported for two or more trials, similar in direction, only some differences in magnitude</i>
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Comment:

3: For between-trial comparisons, is the number of trials large? Not applicable: no between RCT comparison

Very small Rather small or unclear Rather large Large

<i>1 or 2 or in smallest subgroup; 5 or less in continuous meta-regression</i>	<i>3-4 in smallest subgroup; 6-10 in continuous meta-regression</i>	<i>5-9 in smallest subgroup; 11 to 15 in continuous meta-regression</i>	<i>10 or more in smallest subgroup; more than 15 in continuous meta-regression</i>
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One study in smallest subgroup.

Comment:

4: Was the direction of effect modification correctly hypothesized a priori?

Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

<p>Clearly post-hoc or results inconsistent with hypothesized direction or biologically very implausible</p>	<p>Vague hypothesis or hypothesized direction unclear <i>Unclear within studies and not formally hypothesised for this meta-analysis.</i> <i>Expected greater effect for susceptible group.</i></p>	<p>No prior protocol available but unequivocal statement of a priori hypothesis with correct direction of effect modification</p>	<p>Prior protocol available and includes correct specification of direction of effect modification, e.g., based on a biologic rationale</p>
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Comment:

5: Does a test for interaction suggest that chance is an unlikely explanation of the apparent effect modification? (consider irrespective of number of effect modifiers)

<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Chance a very likely explanation <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value >0.05</i> <i>Test for differences between subgroups p=0.002 (including not reported category).</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Chance a likely explanation or unclear <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.05 and >0.01, or no test of interaction reported and not computable</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Chance may not explain <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.01 and >0.005</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Chance an unlikely explanation <i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.005</i></p>
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Comment:

6: Did the authors test only a small number of effect modifiers or consider the number in their statistical analysis?

<p><input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Explicitly exploratory analysis or large number of effect modifiers tested (e.g., greater than 10) and multiplicity not considered in analysis</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>No mention of number or 4-10 effect modifiers tested and number not considered in analysis</i></p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>No protocol available but unequivocal statement of 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested.</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Protocol available and 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested or number considered in analysis</i></p>
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Comment:

7: Did the authors use a random effects model?

<p><input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Fixed (or common) effect or fixed effects model explicitly stated</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>Probably fixed effect(s) model</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>Probably random (or mixed) effects</i></p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Random (or mixed) effects explicitly stated</i> <i>Authors of this meta-analysis used a random-effects model.</i></p>
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Comment:

8: If the effect modifier is a continuous variable, were arbitrary cut points avoided? not applicable: not continuous

<p><input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no <i>Analysis based on exploratory cut point(s), e.g., picking cut point associated with highest interaction p-value</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear <i>Analysis based on cut point(s) of unclear origin</i></p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably yes <i>Analysis based on pre-specified cut point(s), e.g., suggested by prior RCT</i> <i>Yes, based on resistance vs susceptible as reported by study authors.</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes <i>Analysis based on the full continuum, e.g., assuming a linear or logarithmic relationship</i></p>
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Comment:

9 Optional: Are there any additional considerations that may increase or decrease credibility? (manual section 3.9) not applicable

[] Yes, probably decrease [**X**] Yes, probably increase

*Studies at serious risk of bias based on RoB 2.0 clusters.
No sensitivity analysis conducted in individual studies.*

Comment:

10: How would you rate the overall credibility of the proposed effect modification?

The overall rating should be driven by the items that decrease credibility. The following provides a sensible strategy:

- All responses definitely or probably decrease credibility or unclear → very low
- Two or more responses definitely decrease credibility → maximum usually low even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- One response definitely decreases credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- Two responses probably decrease credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- No response options definitely or probably decrease credibility → high very likely

Place a mark on the continuous line (or type "x" in editable version)

Comment: *Likely no effect modification. Subgroups small and further research needed to determine credible effect modification.*

ICEMAN: Transmission level

Preliminary considerations

Study reference(s):

If available, protocol reference(s):

State a single outcome and, if applicable, time-point of interest (e.g., mortality at 1 year follow-up):

State a single effect measure of interest (e.g., relative or absolute risk difference):

State a single potential effect modifier of interest (e.g., age or comorbidity):

Was the potential effect modifier measured before or at randomization? yes, continue no, stop here and refer to manual for further instructions

Credibility assessment

1: Is the analysis of effect modification based on comparison within rather than between trials?

Completely between Mostly between or unclear Mostly within Completely within

<i>Subgroup analysis or meta-regression comparing overall effects of each individual trial. This is typical for aggregate data meta-analysis.</i>	<i>Subgroup analysis or meta-regression with most information coming from overall effects, but some trials providing within-trial subgroup information</i>	<i>Most trials providing within-trial subgroup information; or individual participant data analysis that combines within and between trial information</i>	<i>All trials providing within-trial subgroup information or individual participant data; and the analysis separates within from between trial information, e.g., meta-analysis of interactions</i>
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Comment:

2: For within-trial comparisons, is the effect modification similar from trial to trial? Not applicable: no or one within-RCT comparison

Definitely not similar Probably not similar or unclear Mostly similar Definitely similar

<i>Effect modification reported for two or more trials and clearly different directions</i>	<i>Effect modification not reported for individual trials or too imprecise to tell</i>	<i>Effect modification reported for two or more trials, mostly similar in direction, but considerable differences in magnitude</i>	<i>Effect modification reported for two or more trials, similar in direction, only some differences in magnitude</i>
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Comment:

3: For between-trial comparisons, is the number of trials large? Not applicable: no between RCT comparison

Very small Rather small or unclear Rather large Large

<i>1 or 2 or in smallest subgroup; 5 or less in continuous meta-regression</i>	<i>3-4 in smallest subgroup; 6-10 in continuous meta-regression</i>	<i>5-9 in smallest subgroup; 11 to 15 in continuous meta-regression</i>	<i>10 or more in smallest subgroup; more than 15 in continuous meta-regression</i>
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One study in smallest subgroup.

Comment:

4: Was the direction of effect modification correctly hypothesized a priori?

Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

<p><i>Clearly post-hoc or results inconsistent with hypothesized direction or biologically very implausible</i></p>	<p><i>Vague hypothesis or hypothesized direction unclear</i></p>	<p><i>No prior protocol available but unequivocal statement of a priori hypothesis with correct direction of effect modification</i> <i>Cut-offs for transmission prespecified in the protocol for this meta-analysis. Not by primary authors. No direction specified.</i></p>	<p><i>Prior protocol available and includes correct specification of direction of effect modification, e.g., based on a biologic rationale</i></p>
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Comment:

5: Does a test for interaction suggest that chance is an unlikely explanation of the apparent effect modification? (consider irrespective of number of effect modifiers)

<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Chance a very likely explanation</p> <p><i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value >0.05</i> <i>Test for differences between subgroups p=0.03 (including not reported category).</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Chance a likely explanation or unclear</p> <p><i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.05 and >0.01, or no test of interaction reported and not computable</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Chance may not explain</p> <p><i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.01 and >0.005</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Chance an unlikely explanation</p> <p><i>Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.005</i></p>
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Comment:

6: Did the authors test only a small number of effect modifiers or consider the number in their statistical analysis?

<p><input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no</p> <p><i>Explicitly exploratory analysis or large number of effect modifiers tested (e.g., greater than 10) and multiplicity not considered in analysis</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear</p> <p><i>No mention of number or 4-10 effect modifiers tested and number not considered in analysis</i></p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably yes</p> <p><i>No protocol available but unequivocal statement of 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested.</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes</p> <p><i>Protocol available and 3 or fewer effect modifiers tested or number considered in analysis</i></p>
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Comment:

7: Did the authors use a random effects model?

<p><input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no</p> <p><i>Fixed (or common) effect or fixed effects model explicitly stated</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear</p> <p><i>Probably fixed effect(s) model</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Probably yes</p> <p><i>Probably random (or mixed) effects</i></p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes</p> <p><i>Random (or mixed) effects explicitly stated</i> <i>Authors of this meta-analysis used a random-effects model.</i></p>
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Comment:

8: If the effect modifier is a continuous variable, were arbitrary cut points avoided? not applicable: not continuous

<p><input type="checkbox"/> Definitely no</p> <p><i>Analysis based on exploratory cut point(s), e.g., picking cut point associated with highest interaction p-value</i></p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Probably no or unclear</p> <p><i>Analysis based on cut point(s) of unclear origin</i> <i>Cut-offs prespecified.</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Probably yes</p> <p><i>Analysis based on pre-specified cut point(s), e.g., suggested by prior RCT</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Definitely yes</p> <p><i>Analysis based on the full continuum, e.g., assuming a linear or logarithmic relationship</i></p>
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Comment:

9 Optional: Are there any additional considerations that may increase or decrease credibility? (manual section 3.9) not applicable

[] Yes, probably decrease [**X**] Yes, probably increase

*Studies at serious risk of bias based on RoB 2.0 clusters.
No sensitivity analysis conducted in individual studies.*

Comment:

10: How would you rate the overall credibility of the proposed effect modification?

The overall rating should be driven by the items that decrease credibility. The following provides a sensible strategy:

- All responses definitely or probably decrease credibility or unclear → very low
- Two or more responses definitely decrease credibility → maximum usually low even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- One response definitely decreases credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- Two responses probably decrease credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- No response options definitely or probably decrease credibility → high very likely

Place a mark on the continuous line (or type "x" in editable version)

Comment: *Likely no effect modification. Subgroups small and further research needed to determine credible effect modification.*

Supplementary item 10 – Sensitivity analyses

Inflated standard error

Incidence of malaria (all ages)

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomisation process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants in a cluster-randomized trial
- (C) Deviations from intended intervention
- (D) Missing outcome data: Incidence of malaria
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Incidence of malaria
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Incidence of malaria

Figure A9.1. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (RCTs); sensitivity analysis

Footnote: ICC was estimated from Loha et al. at 0.03. Not all studies reported initial sample and thus sensitivity analysis was restricted to studies with the data available to inflate the standard error.

Incidence of malaria (all ages) – subgrouped by background nets

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomisation process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants in a cluster-randomized trial
- (C) Deviations from intended intervention
- (D) Missing outcome data: Incidence of malaria
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Incidence of malaria
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Incidence of malaria

Figure A9.2. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (RCTs); sensitivity analysis of subgroups (nets as background intervention – low coverage).

Footnote: ICC was estimated from Loha et al. at 0.03. Not all studies reported initial sample and thus sensitivity analysis was restricted to studies with the data available to inflate the standard error.

Incidence of malaria (all ages) – subgrouped by susceptibility to IRS compound

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomisation process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants in a cluster-randomized trial
- (C) Deviations from intended intervention
- (D) Missing outcome data: Incidence of malaria
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Incidence of malaria
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Incidence of malaria

Figure A9.3. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (RCTs); sensitivity analysis of subgroups (susceptibility to IRS compound – susceptible).

Footnote: ICC was estimated from Loha et al. at 0.03. Not all studies reported initial sample and thus sensitivity analysis was restricted to studies with the data available to inflate the standard error.

Incidence of malaria (all ages) – subgrouped by setting

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomisation process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants in a cluster-randomized trial
- (C) Deviations from intended intervention
- (D) Missing outcome data: Incidence of malaria
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Incidence of malaria
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Incidence of malaria

Figure A9.4. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (RCTs); sensitivity analysis of subgroups (setting).

Footnote: ICC was estimated from Loha et al. at 0.03. Not all studies reported initial sample and thus sensitivity analysis was restricted to studies with the data available to inflate the standard error.

Incidence of malaria (all ages) – subgrouped by insecticide class

Figure A9.5. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (RCTs); sensitivity analysis of subgroups (insecticide class).

Footnote: ICC was estimated from Loha et al. at 0.03. Not all studies reported initial sample and thus sensitivity analysis was restricted to studies with the data available to inflate the standard error.

Incidence of malaria (all ages) – subgrouped by transmission setting

Figure A9.6. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (RCTs); sensitivity analysis of subgroups (transmission setting).

Footnote: ICC was estimated from Loha et al. at 0.03. Not all studies reported initial sample and thus sensitivity analysis was restricted to studies with the data available to inflate the standard error.

Prevalence of malaria (all ages)

Figure A9.7. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on prevalence of malaria in all ages (non-randomised); sensitivity analysis.

Footnote: ICC was estimated from Loha et al. at 0.03. Not all studies reported initial sample and thus sensitivity analysis was restricted to studies with the data available to inflate the standard error.

Prevalence of anaemia (children under 5 years)

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomisation process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants in a cluster-randomized trial
- (C) Deviations from intended intervention
- (D) Missing outcome data: Incidence of malaria
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Incidence of malaria
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Incidence of malaria

Figure A9.14. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on prevalence of anaemia in children aged under five years (RCTs); sensitivity analysis.

Footnote: ICC was estimated from Loha et al. at 0.03. Not all studies reported initial sample and thus sensitivity analysis was restricted to studies with the data available to inflate the standard error.

Risk of bias

Incidence of malaria (all ages)

Figure A9.15. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on incidence of malaria in all ages (RCTs); sensitivity analysis (stratified by risk of bias).

Footnote: ICC was estimated from Loha et al. at 0.03. Not all studies reported initial sample and thus sensitivity analysis was restricted to studies with the data available to inflate the standard error.

Prevalence of anaemia (children under 5 years)

Figure A9.14. Forest plot of comparison: IRS versus no IRS on prevalence of anaemia in children aged under five years (RCTs); sensitivity analysis (stratified by risk of bias).

Footnote: ICC was estimated from Loha et al. at 0.03. Not all studies reported initial sample and thus sensitivity analysis was restricted to studies with the data available to inflate the standard error.